

Abstract of “From Measurement to Structure: Annotation-Free Acquisition of Symbolic Geometry,” by Aditya Ganeshan, Ph.D., Brown University, May 2026.

Measurement-centric representations such as images, point clouds, meshes, voxels, neural fields, and splats are powerful for reconstruction and rendering, but rarely expose constraints, design intent, or editable structure. Symbolic geometry makes this structure explicit through programs, parametric models, primitives, constraints, and fabrication operations. The difficulty is acquisition: manual authoring is slow, specialized, and tied to each representation. Supervised learning can automate acquisition when paired observations and authored symbolic targets are available. However, new symbolic geometry representations are often introduced before such datasets exist. This dissertation therefore studies annotation-free acquisition: recovering symbolic structure without relying on a large corpus in the target representation.

The dissertation develops a toolkit for annotation-free acquisition based on three strategies: leveraging foundation-model priors, generating in-domain synthetic supervision, and directly optimizing symbolic structures with co-designed parameterizations, objectives, and initialization. These strategies are realized in systems that acquire parameterized 3D editing programs from language, improve unsupervised visual program inference with code rewrites, learn programmatic pattern edits by analogy, adapt integral-joint programs for CNC milling, and fit compact primitive assemblies to measured shapes. Together, these systems show that useful symbolic structure can be recovered before large annotated corpora exist for a target representation. By lowering the cost of acquisition, this toolkit makes it easier to invent and evaluate new symbolic representations, opening more kinds of geometry to structured modeling, exploration, and analysis.

From Measurement to Structure: Annotation-Free Acquisition of Symbolic Geometry

by

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Int. M. Sc. in Applied Mathematics, Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee, 2017

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This dissertation by Aditya Ganeshan is accepted in its present form by
the Department of Computer Science as satisfying the dissertation requirement
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VITA

Aditya Ganeshan grew up in Bhopal, India, the City of Lakes. Drawn early to computer games and mathematics, he studied Applied Mathematics at the Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, earning an Integrated B.Sc. and M.Sc. in 2017. There, his interests moved from real analysis toward computer vision, culminating in a master's dissertation completed in collaboration with the Video Analytics Lab at the Indian Institute of Science.

After graduation, Aditya worked as a researcher in visual computing, first at the Video Analytics Lab and then at Preferred Networks in Japan. His projects moved across semantic segmentation, adversarial attacks, and object pose estimation. During this time, a long-standing fascination with procedural modeling and geometry drew him toward broader questions about how machines should represent visual structure. In 2021, he began his Ph.D. in Computer Science at Brown University, advised by Daniel Ritchie.

His dissertation studies the acquisition of symbolic geometry: structured, often programmatic representations that expose the parts, constraints, parameters, and construction logic behind visual data, especially when examples in the desired symbolic form are scarce or unavailable. During his Ph.D., Aditya spent two summers as a Research Scientist Intern at Adobe Research and was a Visiting Researcher in Takeo Igarashi's lab at the University of Tokyo. His work has been published at leading venues including CVPR, NeurIPS, ICCV, ACM SIGGRAPH Asia, and ACM Transactions on Graphics.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Figure 1.1: Measurement-centric representations such as meshes, point clouds, voxels, and neural fields describe observed geometry directly. **Symbolic geometry** makes task-aligned structure explicit: parts, operations, dependencies, constraints, and executable construction logic. This thesis studies how to acquire such structure when large paired symbolic annotation corpora are unavailable.

Consider a scan of a mechanical bracket. The scan may be accurate enough to reproduce the surface, but it does not say which holes must remain coaxial, which faces are intended to be planar, or which dimensions can change without breaking the part. A mesh of a chair has a similar gap: its triangles may show legs, a seat, and a back, but not that the legs are symmetric, that the seat should stay attached when the chair is resized, or that the back slats should remain evenly spaced. For fabrication, editing, simulation, and design reuse, these unnamed relationships often matter as much as the visible shape.

Many common representations are **measurement-centric**: they record what is present where. Images record color at pixels, point clouds record sampled locations, meshes record surfaces through vertices and faces, voxel grids record occupancy in cells, and neural fields and 3D Gaussian splats encode scenes for rendering and reconstruction through continuous functions or spatial kernels [6]. These representations are powerful because they are general, measurable, and easy to compare against observations. Their limitation

for many downstream tasks is that task-relevant structure often remains implicit.

A representation can instead organize geometry around task-aligned abstractions, such as editing, fabrication, physical action, or compositional reuse of sub-parts. In this dissertation, we use **symbolic geometry** broadly to describe structured, interpretable representations of visual artifacts that combine discrete symbols with continuous parameters. The symbols may name parts, primitives, operations, relations, constraints, deformations, or rules, while the parameters give those symbols metric content. Evaluating the representation can produce geometry in various forms such as a 2D image rendering, a point cloud, a mesh, or even edit to existing geometry.

Symbolic geometry does not replace meshes, splats, images, or other measured forms. Instead, it often sits above them: it may execute to a measured form, render through one, or constrain how one changes. A CAD model [149] can preserve sketches, extrusions, dimensions, and constraints, so an edit to a hole or face can preserve design intent rather than only move surface samples. A CGA-style procedural model [128, 138] can use rules for floors, windows, and facades, making it natural to explore meaningful shape variations without redrawing each instance. An SVG asset [39] can use paths, groups, transforms, and draw order, so the drawing remains selectable, rearrangeable, recolorable, and composable. Different symbolic geometry languages choose different task-aligned abstractions, and those choices determine what is easy to author, manipulate, acquire, and analyze.

1.1 From Measurement to Structure

In practice, instances of symbolic geometry often begin as human-authored objects. Engineers build CAD construction histories through sketches, extrusions, dimensions, constraints, and revisions; artists organize vector drawings into paths, groups, layers, and transforms; domain experts write programs or fabrication specifications that encode operations and validity checks. These skills take years to develop, and even expert authoring requires time, iteration, and representation-specific judgment. Automatic acquisition asks whether a system can start from inputs that are easier to obtain, such as pixels, point samples, scans, meshes, existing assets, or language requests, and recover the symbolic structure a task needs.

When the target representation is executable, this inverse problem is often framed as inferring a symbolic description Y whose execution reconstructs or explains an input X . A point cloud or shape sample may be mapped to a CSG tree [30, 161], primitive assembly [215, 191], CAD construction sequence [198, 202, 205, 204], or ShapeAssembly program [68]. A raster drawing or icon may be mapped to layered vector geometry [31] or SVG code [223]. More generally, X may be an intent specification rather than a measurement. Text requests can describe desired objects, relations, constraints, or edits, and systems can acquire executable

scene or vector-graphics programs that satisfy those requests [28, 64]. These cases are still part of the same acquisition problem: the system recovers symbolic structure from an easy-to-provide input, even when that input is not a scan, image, or shape sample.

In established domains, this inverse map is often learned with **paired supervision**. In this setting, each training example contains both an observation X and the corresponding symbolic description Y that the system should predict. For example, a CAD construction history can be rendered or sampled to produce a point cloud, image, or mesh X , while the original CAD program serves as the target output Y . Training then reduces acquisition to a supervised prediction problem: given X , learn to recover the authored symbolic object Y .

This recipe has been effective when large corpora of authored symbolic assets are available. Renders or measurements from these assets can be paired with the original symbolic descriptions to train models for CAD construction histories [198, 202, 205, 204], ShapeAssembly programs [68], CSG trees [161], and vector graphics [164]. Its limitation is that the target symbolic description must already exist for each training instance. When a domain lacks a large, consistent, and sufficiently diverse dataset of authored symbolic assets, automatic acquisition remains difficult.

1.2 Why Annotation-Free Acquisition?

The paired-supervision recipe depends on observations X paired with target symbolic descriptions Y . This assumption is most feasible in mature domains, where many examples have already been authored in a stable representation. It is however, not feasible when the representation itself is novel. Symbolic geometry is continually revised in response to new tasks, materials, manufacturing processes, scientific models, and interaction needs. Additionally, researchers often introduce new representations when existing ones do not expose the variables, constraints, or operations a task requires. As a result, while novel symbolic representations may have a clear specification, an executor, validity checks, and perhaps a few examples, they often lack a large paired dataset of symbolic assets, which are essential for supervised learning.

Recent examples illustrate this pattern. Solid Knitting [61] defines dense knit objects through interlocked stitch volumes and fabrication constraints. GAPartNet [55] defines action-aligned part abstractions through part semantics and poses for robotic manipulation. PolyGrammar [46] represents polymer families with hypergraphs and grammar rules. Each case changes the symbolic objects that must be acquired, beyond simply adding new labels to an existing output space.

As a result, the same novelty that makes these representations useful also makes them hard to acquire with paired supervision. This dissertation studies **annotation-free acquisition**: recovering, constructing, or

fitting symbolic geometry without assuming per-instance target-language symbolic annotations. Annotation-free methods may still rely on observations or task specifications X , executors, constraints, synthetic data, optimization objectives, foundation-model priors, or partial target specifications. What they do not assume is a large dataset of manually authored symbolic target specifications Y in the target language paired with observations X .

Thesis statement. New symbolic geometry representations expose useful structure for reasoning, editing, fabrication, and action, but rarely come with the paired data needed for supervised acquisition. This thesis shows how to recover that structure anyway, using three reusable strategies: **foundation-model priors**, **in-domain synthetic supervision**, and **co-designed direct optimization**.

A critical reason annotation-dependent techniques have been effective is their relative ease of adaptation: once a domain supplies paired (X, Y) examples, the same learning recipe can often be reused with modest representation-specific machinery. The strategies introduced in this dissertation aim for similar adaptability in the annotation-free setting. Rather than depending on a fixed dataset of target symbolic labels, they use sources of signal that many symbolic representations already expose: pretrained priors, executors, samplers, rewriters, constraints, objectives, or optimizable parameters. As a result, these strategies can be adapted to new symbolic geometry domains before a large paired dataset of symbolic assets can be collected.

1.3 Annotation-Free Acquisition Strategies

This thesis studies three reusable strategies for acquiring symbolic geometry without paired symbolic annotations. The first leverages broad priors learned by foundation models; the second creates in-domain synthetic supervision from operations exposed by the target representation; and the third performs direct continuous optimization against proxy objectives, relying on meaningful parameterizations and suitable initialization to make the search effective.

Foundation-model priors. Foundation models are trained on large collections of text, images, code, 3D assets, and other observations of the real world. Although they are not trained for a new symbolic representation in particular, they can encode broad priors about language, objects, actions, visual structure, and code. Such priors are useful when labels are absent because they can propose decompositions, operations, constraints, or candidate programs before a paired symbolic dataset has been collected.

Chapter 3 studies this strategy in PARSEL. A large language model interprets a natural-language 3D shape-editing request and proposes seed edit operations; Analytical Edit Propagation then uses part relations

and geometric reasoning to complete those seeds into parameterized editing programs. This approach shows that foundation-model priors become most effective when grounded by representation-specific executors, constraints, and geometric checks. Foundation models often excel at suggesting useful structure, but a symbolic system must often validate and/or complete the proposed structure to succeed.

In-domain synthetic supervision. When per-input symbolic labels are unavailable, the symbolic representation itself can sometimes create synthetic supervision. An executor, rewriter, sampler, or set of invariants can generate examples without asking a human to provide the target symbolic object for every input. This is useful because a new representation may not have an authored dataset, but it can still expose relations between symbolic programs, such as rewrites from one program to another or edits that transform one design into a related design.

Chapters 4 and 5 study this strategy in two settings. In SIRI, program rewrites convert imperfectly acquired programs to more compact and accurate alternatives; the converted programs improve the synthetic targets used for training a network to acquire programs. In Pattern Analogies, sampled before/after edit pairs define structured changes in a 2D pattern language. Rather than recovering a full hidden program for each real pattern, a model learns the effect of those symbolic transformations and applies analogous edits to real-world artist-sourced pattern images.

Direct optimization. Some symbolic structures can be acquired by fitting them directly to measured geometry or task constraints. Instead of learning from paired examples, the system treats the parameters of the symbolic representation as variables and optimizes them against an objective.

Chapters 6 and 7 study direct optimization for fabrication-aware design and primitive fitting. MiGumi starts from idealized joint programs and optimizes them into fabrication-valid designs for CNC milling using surface and milling-path coupling losses. SuperFit introduces an expressive primitive representation and residual fitting procedure for acquiring compact primitive assemblies from meshes. Both systems use gradient-based optimization, and show that this strategy works when the representation, objective, and initialization are designed together: the representation exposes variables to adjust, the objective measures the desired structure, and the initialization starts from parameters where gradient descent can improve the fit.

Across these chapters, the acquisition target is not fixed to a single output type. PARSEL and SIRI acquire explicit symbolic programs; Pattern Analogies learns transferable effects of symbolic transformations on raw pattern images; MiGumi optimizes idealized symbolic programs into fabrication-valid ones; and SuperFit fits primitive assemblies to measured meshes. This variation is intentional: the shared bottleneck is not

a particular representation, but the absence of a large paired annotation dataset in the target symbolic language.

1.4 Contributions

This dissertation makes the following contributions:

1. It formulates **annotation-free acquisition** as a central bottleneck for *novel* symbolic geometry representations. New representations expose useful task structure, but often appear before paired target-language corpora exist. The dissertation demonstrates acquisition under this constraint across 3D shape editing, visual program inference, 2D pattern editing, CNC-millable joint design, and primitive assembly fitting.
2. It demonstrates **foundation-model priors** as a strategy for acquiring symbolic editing structure. In PARSEL, a large language model helps infer parameterized 3D editing programs from natural-language requests, while Analytical Edit Propagation grounds those proposals in geometric relations, executors, and constraints.
3. It demonstrates **in-domain synthetic supervision** as a strategy for learning without per-input symbolic labels. In SIRI, code rewrites improve the synthetic targets used for visual program inference. In Pattern Analogies, sampled symbolic edit pairs train a model to transfer programmatic edit effects to real pattern images without inferring their hidden programs.
4. It demonstrates **direct optimization** as a strategy for acquiring symbolic structure from geometry and task constraints. In MiGumi, differentiable coupling losses convert idealized integral-joint programs into CNC-millable, tightly coupled designs. In SuperFit, SuperFrusta and ResFit acquire compact primitive assemblies from meshes by jointly designing the primitive family, initialization procedure, and fitting objective.

Together, these contributions show that automatic acquisition can be made practical across several novel symbolic geometry domains even when large annotated datasets are unavailable. The chapters identify different conditions that make each strategy effective: foundation-model priors must be grounded by executors and geometric checks, synthetic supervision can be enhanced when relations exposed by the target representation are exploited, and direct optimization benefits from co-designing parameterizations, objectives, and initialization. By showing how to leverage these strategies, this dissertation extends automatic acquisition beyond the symbolic geometry domains where experts have already authored large datasets.

1.5 Dissertation Overview

Chapter 2 reviews the related research that motivates this dissertation and positions its contributions within work on symbolic geometric representations, program acquisition, structured editing, and acquisition with and without paired supervision.

The remaining chapters are organized around the three annotation-free acquisition strategies introduced above. Chapter 3 presents PARSEL, which uses foundation-model priors to turn natural-language shape-editing requests into parameterized 3D editing programs. Chapters 4 and 5 then study in-domain synthetic supervision: SIRI uses program rewrites to improve symbolic program acquisition, while Pattern Analogies uses sampled edit pairs to support structured pattern editing without recovering full hidden programs. Chapters 6 and 7 study direct optimization, first for converting idealized joinery into CNC-millable integral joints and then for acquiring compact primitive assemblies from meshes. Chapter 8 concludes by comparing these strategies and discussing how they may be combined for future symbolic geometry representations.

CHAPTER 2

BACKGROUND

In the previous chapter, we introduced symbolic geometry and motivated the central acquisition problem: recovering symbolic structure without large paired annotations. This chapter presents the shared vocabulary used by the following chapters and organizes prior work by acquisition strategy: paired data, foundation-model priors, in-domain synthetic supervision, and direct optimization.

2.1 Symbolic Geometry Representations

This section surveys symbolic representations used across different tasks and domains. The examples vary in syntax and purpose, but they share a practical property: they expose handles that a system can inspect, execute, validate, or modify.

Many symbolic geometry representations make construction history and procedural structure explicit. CSGNet [161] uses constructive solid geometry (CSG) programs; Fusion 360 Gallery [198] and DeepCAD [202] model CAD construction histories; ShapeAssembly [68] represents 3D shape structures as assembly programs; Match [164] captures procedural material graphs; and DeepSVG [19] and image-vectorization systems [31] recover vector programs. Classical procedural modeling exposes related structure through rules: L-systems [144] represent plants with rewriting rules, interactive and guided procedural modeling use rules for buildings, cities, and facades [131, 11], and graph-grammar methods synthesize shapes from graph rewrite rules [116]. Newer domain-specific languages extend this view to interpretable shape programs [142], tangle patterns [156], semi-procedural textures [53], and programmable element textures [105].

Other symbolic representations do not try to reproduce a full authoring history. Instead, they partition and organize geometry into meaningful units. GRASS [91] and GRAINS [92] organize shapes and scenes through recursive part hierarchies. Primitive-based methods describe geometry with compact analytic components whose parameters can be inspected, optimized, or edited, including volumetric primitive abstractions [186], superquadric shape parsing [139], local deep implicit functions [47], adaptive primitive assemblies [215], and explicit CAD primitives [191]. These representations are less concerned with the original modeling

sequence than with recovering useful structure for manipulation, synthesis, or analysis.

Symbolic representations can also be organized around a domain’s physical or semantic structure. Machine-knitting systems expose fabrication through explicit stitch and instruction structure: a compiler for 3D machine knitting [113] translates high-level knit primitives into machine instructions, Solid Knitting [61] represents dense objects through interlocked stitch volumes, and GarmentCode [83] uses programs for parametric sewing patterns. Other domain-specific representations expose semantic or physical organization in different forms: PolyGrammar [55] uses polymer grammar rules, and GAPartNet [46] uses action-aligned parts for manipulation.

2.2 Early Acquisition: Structure, Priors, and Search

Long before contemporary neural acquisition systems, visual computing and AI researchers have studied how observations could be explained by latent objects, parts, relations, and transformations. Roberts’s blocks-world work [151] recovered 3D solid structure from line drawings; Evans’s ANALOGY system [37] solved geometric IQ-test analogies by extracting relations among simple figures; and Binford’s work on visual perception [14] established part- and volume-based interpretations of shape. These systems did not learn from large paired datasets, but they framed a lasting acquisition problem: how can a measured input be explained by a structured symbolic description?

Before deep recognition models became dominant, much of this problem was addressed through explicit priors, search, and probabilistic inference. Probabilistic programming languages such as Church [50] and Picture [84] treated scene perception as inference in a generative model, while approximate Bayesian image interpretation inverted graphics programs to explain images [109]. Related work on probabilistic program induction learned visual concepts as programs [86], inferred programs from examples [32, 33], and learned procedural structure through grammar or model induction [177, 112, 150]. The representation was often hand-designed, and inference could be expensive, but the central idea was clear: a structured prior could make observations explainable.

Search-based reverse-engineering systems made this executable-checking view concrete for geometry. InverseCSG [30] and ReIncarnate [129] recover construction trees or modeling operations by searching over symbolic candidates and comparing their executions against target geometry.

2.3 Acquisition with Paired Data

Supervised neural recognition models changed the balance between search and prediction. When a dataset provides observations paired with target structured descriptions, a model can learn to predict that structure directly, amortizing part of the inverse search. One line of work uses this recipe to recover geometric abstractions that are more structured than meshes or fields, even when they are not full authoring programs. ParSeNet [162] recovers parametric surface patches from point clouds, while Point2Primitive [191] infers explicit primitive structure. These methods show that neural networks can acquire useful part-level or parametric structure from measurements, provided that suitable target abstractions are available during training.

A related but more explicitly symbolic line of supervised work learns from authored design and graphics corpora, where the target representation records how an asset was constructed. In this setting, a CAD model, ShapeAssembly program, material graph, or vector program can be rendered, sampled, or otherwise observed to form pairs (X, Y) between measurements and symbolic targets. ShapeAssembly [68] learns assembly programs for 3D shape structure. Fusion 360 Gallery [198] provides human CAD design sequences, enabling models such as DeepCAD [202], zone graphs [205], SkexGen [204], and Sketch2CAD [88] to learn over sketches, extrusions, constraints, and construction operations. Related supervised formulations learn structured graphics programs outside CAD, including procedural material graphs in Match [164] and vector programs in systems such as DeepSVG [19].

CSG inference provides an important bridge between these categories. Early systems such as CSGNet [161] helped establish neural acquisition of CSG trees from visual input, but because such methods often rely on synthetic program generation rather than human-authored paired corpora, we discuss them with annotation-free and synthetic-supervision approaches in Section 2.5.

Recent supervised CAD systems increasingly cast symbolic CAD acquisition as sequence prediction. Computer-Aided Design as Language [44] serializes CAD sketches for sequence modeling, and Vitruvion [158] trains a transformer to generate sketch primitives and constraints from SketchGraphs. CAD-LLM [203] and CAD-Llama [89] extend this pattern by adapting pretrained language models to CAD sketch or parametric command sequences. These systems differ in architecture and CAD vocabulary, but share the same acquisition signal: paired supervision over tokenized symbolic representations.

Paired supervision remains the cleanest acquisition signal when the target corpus exists: each training input is paired with the symbolic object the model should recover. The rest of the chapter turns to settings where that assumption is relaxed. In those settings, acquisition must instead draw signal from pretrained priors, synthetic structure inside the domain, or objectives that can score candidate symbolic objects directly.

2.4 Acquisition via Foundation-Model Priors

Foundation models change where prior knowledge can enter the acquisition pipeline. Instead of learning every regularity from a target symbolic dataset, a system can draw on models pretrained on broad mixtures of language, code, images, and other visual data. We focus on methods that use the models as a training-free prior, proposal mechanism, or source of weak signal for a symbolic domain that does not yet have many annotations.

Visual programming systems showed an early version of this idea. VisProg and ViperGPT translate questions or instructions into Python-like programs that call detectors, segmenters, classifiers, VQA systems, or other vision modules, then execute those programs to answer visual queries [57, 175]. The programs are usually transient reasoning traces, not reusable geometry assets, but they demonstrate that language models can plan over typed visual operations.

For symbolic geometry, foundation models are often most useful as proposal engines. Chat2SVG [201] uses an LLM to produce SVG templates from geometric primitives, then refines vector paths with image-diffusion guidance and coordinate optimization. ShapeLib [73] uses LLMs to propose procedural 3D abstraction functions from text descriptions and seed exemplars, validates proposed functions against geometry, and trains recognition models over the resulting library. ReparamCAD [81] uses pretrained language and image models to infer meaningful variation spaces for CAD programs, and Real2Code [228] predicts articulation code from visual object structure. In each case, the model supplies semantic or coding hypotheses that still need grounding by an executor, optimizer, or validator.

Recent systems increasingly put that grounding inside an executable loop. A model writes code, observes failures or renders, and revises the result. FunSearch [153] is a broad program-discovery version of this pattern, pairing a language-model proposer with an evaluator that selects high-scoring programs. In geometry domains, BlenderMCP [2] exposes Blender to language-model agents through tool calls; SceneCraft [64] and L3GO [207] generate Blender code for 3D scenes or objects; and VIGA [213] reconstructs or edits scenes through a write-run-render-compare-revise loop over Blender programs. Articraft [230] applies this agentic coding pattern to articulated assets through a domain-specific SDK for parts, geometry, joints, and validation tests. Query2CAD [5] and Zero-to-CAD [4] use similar feedback loops for editable CAD programs. At the technique level, the recurring pattern is clear: foundation models provide flexible symbolic hypotheses, while execution, optimization, and representation-specific checks turn those hypotheses into valid geometry.

2.5 Acquisition via In-Domain Synthetic Supervision

Synthetic supervision uses a domain’s own machinery to create learning signal. Generators propose tasks, executors score candidate solutions, and successful or informative attempts become data for later learning. The general recipe appears in self-play for AlphaZero [166], generated geometry problems in AlphaGeometry [184], and wake-sleep library learning in DreamCoder [36]. A common formulation in visual program inference treats the symbolic language as the environment: actions construct or edit a program, execution produces a visual result, and reconstruction quality or validity supplies feedback.

One way to extract more signal from each execution is to make the language differentiable, or approximately differentiable. UCSG-Net [75] relaxes CSG operations to learn CSG trees without target programs; CSG-Stump [148] uses a learning-friendly CSG-like representation whose softened operations simplify shape parsing; and fuzzy Boolean operators [99] provide differentiable approximations of constructive operations for CSG-style geometry. The visual loss then becomes a training signal through the executor or a softened version of it.

Another route learns surrogates, searches for pseudo-labels, or rewrites programs into better forms. Learning to Infer and Execute 3D Shape Programs [182] trains neural components to predict and execute shape programs. Differentiable proxy models for procedural material graphs [63] optimize otherwise non-differentiable node graphs through learned approximations. Bootstrapped methods alternate between proposing programs, executing or searching for better candidates, and retraining on the best discovered pseudo-labels; PLAD [70] is a representative example for shape programs. Recent CAD systems use a similar generated-data route at larger scale: CAD-Recode [155] trains on procedurally generated CAD code and point-cloud pairs, while GIFT [49] turns geometric feedback and near-miss predictions into bootstrapped image-program training examples.

A related use of program behavior appears in abstraction discovery and rewriting. Equality saturation [199] and CAD rewriting [130] make large sets of equivalent programs searchable. ShapeCoder [71] interleaves a recognition model with e-graph and conditional rewriting machinery to discover abstractions and programs that explain primitive-based shape datasets. Here, the executor and rewrite system do more than post-process programs: they define behavior-preserving alternatives that the learning loop can compare, compress, and reuse.

The same idea extends beyond recovering one program for one observation. If a domain can sample programs and controlled transformations, it can teach models relations between instances: how a program should be edited, repaired, simplified, or analogically transformed. Diffusion on Syntax Trees [76] learns to denoise corrupted abstract syntax trees, turning program synthesis into iterative syntax-preserving edits.

Learning to Edit Visual Programs [72] uses self-supervised edit examples to train models that modify programs rather than infer them from scratch. The shared technique-level lesson is that a symbolic representation is not only an output space. Its executor, sampler, rewrite system, and valid edit operators can become sources of supervision when per-instance labels are absent.

2.6 Acquisition via Direct Optimization

Direct optimization became a central tool for inverse graphics as rendering and geometric operators became more differentiable. Useful gradients are now available for vector graphics through DiffVG [93], triangle meshes through nvdiffrast [85], signed-distance fields through differentiable SDF rendering [187], and neural fields through stochastic preconditioning [97]. This progress is not only making more operations differentiable, but also includes strategies that make difficult fitting objectives more stable in optimization, such as stochastic preconditioning and periodic surface resampling.

Measurement-centric representations often benefit most directly from these tools. A mesh, neural field, or set of 3D Gaussians can be fit to images, point clouds, or other observations because its parameters are continuous, dense, and redundant enough for local improvement to be meaningful. NeRF [120] and 3D Gaussian Splatting [78] are canonical examples. Symbolic representations, in contrast, mix continuous parameters with discrete choices. Small parameter changes may preserve semantic structure, do nothing useful, or break validity, so optimization usually needs a restricted search space, a good initialization, or a representation designed for descent.

Primitive assembly methods provide an early form of this restriction. They do not usually recover a full authoring history, but they replace an unconstrained surface fit with a compact collection of interpretable elements. Local deep implicit functions [47], BSP-Net [23], Neural Parts [140], Marching-Primitives [104], and unsupervised extruded profile primitives [173] all impose structure on the fitting problem so optimization can trade fidelity against compactness and editability.

More explicitly symbolic systems improve direct optimization by constraining the search space. D²CSG [217] uses a CSG-specific architecture, complement modeling, and dropout so per-shape optimization produces compact CSG trees rather than arbitrary dense fits. Img2CAD [214] uses a vision-language model to predict a discrete semantic CAD structure before estimating continuous attributes. Differentiable CAD systems use gradients to keep program parameters and edited geometry in sync [21], while Design for Descent [82] makes the representation-design point explicit: a grammar is easier to optimize when its rewrite structure, continuous parameters, and objectives are chosen with gradient-based search in mind.

2.7 Positioning Our Contributions

The works in this dissertation were developed during a period of rapid growth in symbolic geometry acquisition. Some of the systems surveyed above preceded these chapters, while others appeared later and reflect related trends. We therefore position the dissertation contributions as concrete realizations of several emerging directions in annotation-free acquisition: grounding foundation-model proposals, using symbolic transformations as supervision, and optimizing structured geometric representations directly.

Within acquisition from foundation-model priors, PARSEL is one of the earliest systems to use large language models for geometric shape editing by coupling them with explicit symbolic-geometric reasoning. Rather than asking an LLM to produce a complete valid edit program, PARSEL uses the model to interpret a natural-language request and propose seed edits. Analytical Edit Propagation then completes those seeds into parameterized editing programs that preserve part relations across a continuous range of edit magnitudes. In this sense, PARSEL anticipates a now-common pattern in LLM-based geometry systems: foundation models provide flexible semantic proposals, while execution, constraints, and domain-specific reasoning turn those proposals into valid symbolic geometry.

Within acquisition from in-domain synthetic supervision, SIRI and Pattern Analogies show two ways that symbolic transformations can provide learning signal when paired labels are unavailable. SIRI introduces, to our knowledge, the first bootstrapped visual program inference system that integrates a family of code rewriters into the learning loop. Its rewriters do not merely improve programs at test time; they improve the pseudo-labels on which the inference model is trained, thereby accelerating bootstrapped learning. Pattern Analogies takes a complementary direction: it is one of the first systems to perform programmatic image edits without inferring the underlying program of the target image. Instead, a pattern language supplies synthetic before/after transformations, allowing a model to learn the effect of structured edits and transfer them to real pattern images. Together, these works show that in-domain symbolic transformations, such as rewrites and edits, can be turned into learning signal when paired symbolic labels are unavailable.

Within acquisition by direct optimization, MiGumi and SuperFit show how representation design can make structured fitting feasible. MiGumi introduces Millable Extrusion Geometry to create geometry that is by-construction CNC-millable and uses it to make traditional Kigumi joints CNC-millable while preserving tight coupling between parts. SuperFit introduces SuperFrusta, a compact analytic primitive family, and ResFit, an iterative residual fitting procedure that interleaves shape decomposition with primitive optimization. These systems contribute to a broader line of work on fitting structured symbolic objects directly to geometry or task constraints. Their specific contribution is to show that high-quality direct optimization depends not only on better objectives, but also on representations whose parameters, constraints, and initializations are

well matched to the structure being recovered.

CHAPTER 3

ACQUISITION VIA FOUNDATION-MODEL PRIORS

ParSEL: Parameterized Shape Editing with Language

Figure 3.1: We introduce PARSEL, a system that enables *controllable* editing of 3D assets with natural language. (a) Each subplot shows an input 3D asset (left), edit request (top) and the parametric editing capability provided by PARSEL (right). (b) The parametric edits produced by PARSEL are composable, allowing users to explore shape variations of *non-parametric* models as seamlessly as they would with parametric models.

This chapter begins the dissertation’s acquisition strategies with foundation-model priors. The target representation is a parameterized editing program for 3D shapes: a symbolic object that is useful for editing, but hard to infer from examples because large paired datasets of edit requests, shapes, and programs are not readily available. PARSEL asks how much of this acquisition problem can be handled by the broad language and code priors of an LLM, and what must still be supplied by geometry-specific machinery.

The concrete setting is text-driven shape manipulation. Given a segmented 3D asset and a natural-language edit request, the system must infer an analytical editing program that specifies the primary edit, the geometric relationships to preserve or relax, the secondary edits needed to keep the shape coherent, and the parameterization that lets a user control edit magnitude. This makes language-based editing an acquisition problem: an underspecified human request must be converted into an executable symbolic representation.

PARSEL uses the LLM as a semantic proposal mechanism. The model interprets the request, proposes a seed edit, and supplies high-level hints about relation validity and secondary edit types. These proposals are useful, but direct LLM-authored programs are not reliable enough because exact reasoning about distances, symmetries, attachments, and parameterized part relationships is fundamentally geometric.

The chapter’s main lesson is therefore about coupling. Foundation models can provide flexible priors for intent interpretation and candidate generation, but they need to be grounded in domain-aware symbolic machinery. In PARSEL, that grounding comes from a structured shape abstraction, a domain-specific editing language, and a computer algebra system that completes the LLM’s proposal by searching for constraint-consistent secondary edits.

3.1 Introduction

Creating high-quality 3D assets is a labor-intensive task, requiring years of training and experience. The ability to edit existing high-quality 3D assets to create new assets greatly lowers this barrier. However, the process of manually modifying a 3D object, e.g. by adjusting individual vertices and/or faces, is often tedious. To address this challenge, a number of efforts have explored how to design more user-friendly and intuitive shape editing tools [165, 219].

Following rapid advancements in the field of Natural Language Processing, a wealth of recent methods have explored techniques for editing 3D assets from natural language [168, 1, 45, 119]. This paradigm is alluring from the perspective of accessibility; specifying edit intent through natural language requires minimal tool-specific training. So far, such natural-language-based editing systems have shown promising results for retexturing 3D assets [65], stylizing 3D shapes [119], and even modifying shape geometry [1].

However, editing shapes in a controlled manner with language is challenging, particularly when performing *geometric edits*, i.e. edits involving sub-part manipulation and spatial rearrangement. For instance, consider a scenario where a user intends to widen a chair. Natural language can be used to effectively communicate *how* to edit: “scale the seat, reposition the legs and add more back slats”. Yet, it is difficult to convey *how much* to edit with natural language. Terms such as “moderately widen” and “greatly widen” are inherently subjective, and numerical specifications (“0.2 units”) may not align with the object’s scale. This leads us to a critical insight: *while natural language can effectively convey the edit intent, it is poorly suited for conveying the edit magnitude*. As a result, systems that depend exclusively on language for shape editing are often challenging to use in practice.

To facilitate *controllable* editing of 3D assets using natural language, we introduce PARSEL: PARAMETERIZED SHAPE EDITING WITH LANGUAGE, a system in which users define “how” to edit with language and “how

much” with adjustable parameters. Drawing inspiration from parametric modeling systems, our approach merges the intuitiveness of language with the precision of parametric control. Under this paradigm, users can seamlessly explore a family of shape variations by adjusting parameters until they find an edit that matches their intended magnitude. In Figure 3.1 (a), we showcase qualitative examples of editing various 3D shapes using our system.

PARSEL takes as input a semantically labeled 3D mesh and a user edit request. As output, it exposes an adjustable parameter that the user can interact with to flexibly explore shape variations. We geometrically realize these edits by propagating part-level bounding proxy deformations to the underlying mesh geometry with cage-based deformation methods [74], while simultaneously adapting part-level symmetry groups. Critically, to ensure that the geometry remains consistent under a range of parameter variations, we represent all edit operations as closed-form analytical functions of the adjustable control parameters. In order to create such parameterized editing functions, we introduce a custom domain-specific language. Programs in our DSL specify *how* to edit the shape with numerical parameters, and *how much* to edit with algebraic expressions of the control parameters. Our DSL offers multiple benefits, including the ability to provide a fluid, solver-free edit exploration experience to users, even on consumer laptops.

PARSEL converts language-based edit requests into editing programs with a module that integrates large language models (LLMs) with the algebraic reasoning capabilities of computer algebra systems (CAS). We found that this coupled neuro-symbolic approach is necessary because current state-of-the-art LLMs struggle to directly infer editing programs from input edit requests. Due to their poor geometric reasoning capabilities, LLMs often fail to infer the appropriate adjustments required for multiple input shape parts, resulting in editing programs that produce inconsistent outputs (we explore this phenomenon further in Section 3.4.3).

To overcome this limitation, we present an algorithm that extends partial editing programs with additional operators from our DSL by considering the geometric relations between object parts. We term this technique ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP). While similar in spirit to prior edit-propagation methods [229], previous techniques explicitly optimize part modifications in response to a user edit. In contrast, we *search* for analytical editing functions compatible with a range of possible user edits using a sophisticated CAS solver [117]. Furthermore, by integrating LLMs with AEP, we address a key limitation of all edit-propagation-based editing methods [41, 229]: the requirement to manually adjust the shape’s structure to support different editing intents. By leveraging LLMs, we dynamically modify the shape’s structure based on the edit requests, thus alleviating the need for manual adjustments.

We evaluate PARSEL’s ability to edit 3D objects from language by sourcing (*shape, edit request*) pairs from assets in CoMPaT3D++ [169] and PartNet [126]. On pairs from CoMPaT3D++, we compare PARSEL’s

Figure 3.2: While prior language-based 3D shape editing methods [1] support a broader range of operations on unsegmented shapes, PARSEL delivers *controllable, disentangled* editing of high-quality textured 3D assets. Each approach is tailored to suit different needs.

hybrid approach for producing an editing program against two alternative formulations: (i) asking an LLM to directly author the program, and (ii) using the LLM and AEP to infer a full program without dynamically altering the shape structure. We design a perceptual study to assess how well these variants accomplish the intended task and find that participants greatly prefer the edits produced by PARSEL. To provide further analysis of the design decisions behind PARSEL, we create expert-designed editing programs for PartNet pairs. Treating these manual annotations as ‘ground-truth’, we perform isolated ablation experiments on the LLM prompting workflow and the CAS solver. We also investigate two extensions of our method. First, we demonstrate how PARSEL can aid in creating (approximate) parametric models of non-parametric assets by composing a series of edit requests (Figure 3.1, (b)). Then, we explore how PARSEL can produce a multitude of shape variations from a single user’s edit request.

In summary, we make the following contributions:

1. We introduce PARSEL: PARAMETERIZED SHAPE EDITING WITH LANGUAGE, a novel shape editing system that combines the intuitiveness of natural language with the precision of parametric control.
2. We design a neurosymbolic module that couples an LLM prompting workflow with CAS solvers to translate edits expressed in natural language into shape editing programs.
3. To successfully solve the above inference task, we introduce ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION, an algorithm to search for *analytical* editing functions that extend partial editing programs by considering inter-part geometric relationships.

3.2 Task-Specific Positioning

This chapter sits at the intersection of structure-aware shape editing, language-based editing, and parameterized control. Classical deformation tools use cages or other control objects to manipulate mesh geometry [157, 27], while analyze-and-edit systems infer or maintain part relations, symmetries, and other structural constraints during editing [167, 172, 41, 229, 123]. These methods show the value of symbolic structure for

Figure 3.3: **Overview:** Given a segmented 3D chair and an edit request to “widen the chair,” we first convert the shape into a structured representation: hexahedrons and inter-part relations. This abstraction is illustrated on the left, with symmetry relations annotated on the left and attachment relations depicted with red points on the shape. Our neuro-symbolic approach (center) uses an LLM to interpret the natural language input and ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION to perform geometric reasoning, in order to infer a *parameterized* editing program (right) that aligns with the edit request.

editing, but they typically require a manual initial manipulation and often solve an optimization problem each time the edit magnitude changes.

Language-based editing makes intent easier to specify, but prior image and shape editing systems often emphasize appearance, texture, or stylization rather than precise geometric manipulation [65, 119, 45, 168, 1]. Parameterized editing systems and inverse parametric modeling instead provide editable controls [12, 69, 71, 81, 21, 118], but those controls are usually inferred from geometric variation or from an existing parametric model rather than from a user’s language request. ParSEL uses foundation-model priors to connect language intent to symbolic edit programs, then relies on analytical geometric reasoning to make those programs coherent and adjustable.

3.3 Overview

PARSEL takes 3D assets and natural language edit requests as input, exposing adjustable parameters to control the magnitude of the edit. Specifically, it processes an instance-level segmented 3D mesh paired with a natural language editing request to infer an *editing program* parameterized by user-controlled parameters. Users can then interactively adjust the parameters to explore a wide array of shape variations reflecting different editing magnitudes.

Figure 3.3 provides a schematic overview of our system. In Section 3.4, we detail our approach for parameterized shape editing, outlining the shape representation and our custom domain-specific language (DSL). Our goal is to translate natural language edit requests into editing programs within our DSL that accurately reflect the user’s intent. While large language models (LLMs) offer a promising solution for this translation, they struggle with the complexity of composing editing programs, as these often involve multiple interdependent editing operations. Consequently, although LLMs can correctly identify the initial

operation, known as the *seed-edit*, they often fail to infer complete editing programs.

To address this limitation, in Section 3.5, we introduce ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP), which takes the *seed-edit* inferred by an LLM and introduces additional editing operations to complete the editing program. This approach simplifies the task for the LLM, requiring it to infer only the initial seed edit. Additionally, by employing computer algebra systems for geometric reasoning, AEP ensures that the resulting editing programs have high geometric fidelity and respect essential shape features such as connectivity and symmetry. Integrating LLMs with AEP significantly enhances our system’s capability to meet user expectations by effectively bridging the gap between interpreting the primary edit and performing comprehensive shape adjustments.

Finally, Section 3.6 discusses our LLM-augmented inference approach. A key limitation of all edit-propagation methods [229, 41] is the need for manual adjustments to the shape’s structure to support different editing intents. This section introduces our solution to this challenge: leveraging LLMs to dynamically modify the shape’s structure based on the edit requests. We end this section by briefly discussing our prompting workflow and the techniques we employ to boost the robustness and accuracy of LLM responses, ensuring reliable edits across diverse inputs.

3.4 Parameterized Shape Editing

In this section, we present our framework for enabling *parameterized* editing of 3D shapes. First, we detail the shape representation employed in our system in Section 3.4.1. Next, we describe our domain-specific language (DSL) for creating programs that facilitate parameterized shape editing in Section 3.4.2. Finally, in Section 3.4.3, we discuss the limitations of directly inferring complete editing programs in this DSL using LLMs, highlighting the need for ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP).

3.4.1 Structured Shape Abstraction

Our system processes 3D meshes that are annotated at the instance level. We first transform these meshes into a structured representation to facilitate parametric editing. This representation is inspired by shape representations such as *3D part graphs* [125] and *Sym-Hierarchy* [193].

Specifically, we model the input shape S as an undirected graph $G(N, E)$, where each node $n_i \in N$ corresponds to a semantically labeled mesh subpart, and edges $e_i \in E$ denote inter-part geometric relations such as connectivity or symmetry. To preserve the detailed geometric features of the input mesh while simplifying the complexity of edits, each part P_i is abstracted into a hexahedron H_i . This hexahedron, initialized with the part’s oriented bounding box, acts as the control cage for the underlying part mesh.

Figure 3.4: **Edit Propagation**: Starting with a *seed-edit*, scaling the seat, new edits are incrementally introduced to rectify the broken relations. (left) Initially, the seat-leg and seat-back attachments are broken. (middle) New edits, shifting the legs and scaling the back, are introduced to restore these broken relations. Consequently, the leg-bar and back-bar attachments are broken. This process continues until no relation remains broken or all parts are edited.

Edits made to the hexahedrons are then propagated to deform the vertices of the part mesh using harmonic coordinates [74].

Our system supports two types of inter-part relations, namely *Symmetry Relation*, which models inter-part symmetry groups commonly found in man-made objects, and *Attachment Relation*, which constrains the relative movement between parts, ensuring that edits do not violate the physical connections of the object. Additionally, we automatically extend each part’s label with verbal directional phrases such as “front” and “back” to capture its relative positioning among other instances with the same label. Figure 3.3 illustrates the conversion of a chair model into this structured shape abstraction. Appendix A provides a more detailed overview.

3.4.2 A Language for Parameterized Shape Editing

In the preceding section, we introduced our structured shape representation, which comprises individual parts (abstracted as hexahedrons) and inter-part geometric relations. Building upon this, we now present a domain-specific language (DSL) crafted to facilitate parametric editing of these components using user-controlled parameters.

Our DSL enables common transformations on individual parts, including translation, rotation, scaling, and shearing. These can also be targeted at specific part features such as a face, edge, or corner. Additionally, the DSL supports modifications to symmetry group parameters, like the number of elements and their spacing. A key feature of our DSL is the parameterization of editing operations via user-controlled parameters. This functionality is encapsulated with multiple atomic editing operators, collectively referred to as EDITOP, and defined as follows:

EDITOP(OPERAND, AMOUNT, **PARAMS),

where `EDITOP` signifies the operation, `OPERAND` the target (part, feature, or symmetry relation), and `PARAMS` additional numerical parameters specific to each operation (e.g., a \mathbb{R}^3 vector for a scaling operation’s origin). Central to these operators is `AMOUNT`, the parameter dictating the magnitude of the edit. Unlike the other static parameters, `AMOUNT` is specified as a symbolic mathematical expression of the user-controlled parameters and dynamically evaluated as the user alters these parameters. As a result, adjusting the user-controlled parameter alters the edit magnitude and helps explore shape variations. We denote a sequence of these operations as a *parameterized editing program*. In Figure 3.3 (c), we display a program designed to increase the width of a chair while proportionally adjusting other parts of the chair.

We design our DSL to achieve our goal of enabling *controllable* shape editing. We highlight a few pivotal aspects of our DSL: (i) Unlike prior editing systems, our DSL handles a comprehensive range of operations. For example, [15] only supports coupling of translation symmetries with part deformations, [229] does not edit symmetry hierarchies, and [193] only supports editing of symmetry hierarchies. (ii) The `AMOUNT` expression supports arbitrarily complex mathematical expressions, as demonstrated in the translation symmetry group edit in Figure 3.3 (c). (iii) The ability to apply transforms to part features facilitates non-affine transformations, such as tapering, which is useful in many edits (see Figure 3.6 (c)), (iv) Each part’s edits are independent of the state of other parts. Consequently, these edits can be executed in parallel across all parts, enabling real-time parametric shape editing even on consumer-grade laptops. (v) The edits are composable; parts modified by one operation can seamlessly serve as inputs to subsequent operations. This capability is explored further in Section 3.8.1, where we demonstrate an exciting application of our system. For a more comprehensive discussion of the design and execution model of our DSL, see Appendix A.

3.4.3 Limitations of Direct LLM Inference

As we briefly discussed in Section 3.3, inferring complete editing programs directly with LLMs often fails to produce results that align with the intended edits. LLMs typically succeed at interpreting primary edits explicitly requested; for example, when asked to ‘widen the chair’s seat,’ they correctly infer the edit operators to scale the seat. However, they often neglect necessary secondary edits crucial for maintaining geometric coherence, such as modifying related components like the chair’s legs and back to accommodate the scaled seat. Additionally, even when LLMs identify the need for these secondary adjustments, they struggle to accurately infer the appropriate edit types and their magnitudes. As illustrated in Figure 3.3 (right), editing programs can contain many operations that require careful adjustment of parameters to edit the shape cohesively. Consequently, the `AMOUNT` parameter of different edit operations often involves complex mathematical expressions, making accurate inference challenging. As a result, we find that typically

only the initial *seed-edit* operation inferred by the LLM is reliable.

This limitation is overcome by ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP), which performs the geometric analysis that LLMs cannot. Since the geometric relations driving these secondary edits are compatible with algebraic reasoning, AEP employs Computer Algebra System (CAS) solvers to identify the necessary secondary edits, thereby extending the editing program to better align with the user’s overall intent.

3.5 Analytical Edit Propagation

We now present our approach to extending a *seed-edit* inferred by the LLM using CAS solvers for geometric reasoning. In Section 3.5.1, we explain how edit propagation works and why parameterized editing operations require a different strategy. Section 3.5.2 details our representation of edits, parts, and relations using algebraic expressions, resulting in parameterized constraints that the shape must satisfy. Finally, Section 3.5.3 describes how analytical solvers are employed to solve these parameterized constraints, thereby discovering appropriate new parameterized edits to extend the seed editing program.

3.5.1 Edit Propagation

When designing shape variations, maintaining the shape’s functional and structural attributes is paramount. We delineate these attributes through inter-part relations, as introduced in Section 3.4.1. Thus, an adept editing program strives to *preserve* these relations. Isolated part modification, a tendency of the naive strategy discussed in Section 3.4.3, generally results in the disruption of these inter-part relations. We now introduce an edit propagation algorithm that, starting with one or more seed edits, introduces additional edits to rectify the compromised relations.

As detailed in Section 3.4.1, we model the input shape as an undirected graph $G(N, E)$, where each node $n \in N$ represents a subpart, and each edge $e \in E$ denotes an inter-part relation. Editing a node, such as widening a chair’s seat, can break the edges connected to this node; for example, it might break the attachment relation between the seat and the legs. Edit propagation is then initiated to restore the broken edges by applying corrective edits to other, previously unaltered, nodes within the graph. Importantly, these corrective edits are derived by considering broken relations with *edited* parts only. Consequently, newly introduced edits may subsequently break additional edges, necessitating further edits. This iterative process continues, introducing necessary edits until no edges remain broken or until all nodes have been edited. In Figure 3.4, we demonstrate edit propagation in action, incrementally introducing new edits that eventually result in a cohesive edit of the input shape.

As our seed edits are *parameterized* with user-controlled parameters, they model a range of potential

instantiated seed edits. While traditional edit propagation techniques [229] can be applied to the dynamically evaluated instances of these seed edits, such application results in a laggy user experience. This lag arises because these techniques involve multiple computationally intensive numerical optimization iterations, dependent on the graph’s size. Instead, we propose to search for new parameterized edits that restore and preserve inter-part relations across the range of control parameters. Although this approach requires a computationally intensive search initially, it ensures a smooth, real-time user experience when the control parameters are later adjusted.

To search for parameterized edits, we employ sophisticated Computer Algebra System (CAS) solvers [117]. By representing parts, relations, and edits as algebraic expressions, we enable the use of CAS solvers to efficiently discover analytical solutions to the algebraic constraints dictated by the inter-part relations. As we will see later, this plays a critical role in finding edit parameterizations that preserve relations across the control parameter’s range.

3.5.2 Expressing the Shape Algebraically

For simplicity, we assume that there is a single control parameter x and refer to its range as the input range. First, we present the algebraic form of the part hexahedrons H_i . Then, we present how all inter-part relations are expressed as algebraic constraints on the hexahedrons.

Each part hexahedron consists of 8 3D points, and is represented as a matrix of size $(8, 3)$. A hexahedron under no edit is expressed as a constant function $H_i(x) = H_i^0 \in \mathbb{R}^{\{8,3\}}$, where H_i^0 contains real-valued entries. When a parameterized edit is applied on H_i , its functional form can be derived based on the type of edit. For instance, under an edit $\text{TRANSLATE}(H_i, x, \hat{v})$, H_i can be expressed as $H_i(x) = H_i^0 + x \cdot \hat{v}$, where \hat{v} represents the direction of translation. Similar algebraic expressions can be prescribed for all the atomic editing operators in our DSL, allowing us to express all the hexahedrons as algebraic functions of the control parameter x . For reference, Appendix A tabulates the algebraic form of all the operators.

For modeling the relations algebraically, we separately handle the symmetry and attachment relations. Given hexahedrons H_i and H_j under a symmetry group $G(T)$, where T is the transformation under which the symmetry is held, each symmetry relation can be expressed as a constraint $\|H_i - T(H_j)\|_\infty < \delta$. Similarly, attachment relations are expressed as $\|a - b\|_\infty < \delta$, where a and b are points in H_i and H_j , respectively, that form the attachment. By modeling a and b with harmonic coordinates, we can rewrite this constraint in terms of the hexahedron: $\|M_a H_i - M_b H_j\|_\infty < \delta$, where M_a and M_b are the harmonic coordinates of points a and b , respectively. Since the hexahedrons H_i are parameterized by x , these constraints are also parameterized by x and can be expressed as $C_i(x)$. Now, we can identify whether a relation will be broken

under the parameterized edits by checking whether the corresponding constraints are maintained across the input range. More formally, we denote that a constraint is held by $SAT(C)$, and

$$SAT(C) \implies \|C_i(x)\|_\infty < \delta \forall x \in [0, \tau], \quad (3.1)$$

where $[0, \tau]$ is the input range. Ideally, $SAT(C)$ should be checked analytically, considering the functional form of $C(x)$. However, this can be computationally expensive. Therefore, we instead numerically check whether a constraint is held by evaluating it over random values of x sampled uniformly across the input range.

3.5.3 Analytical Edit Solver

Now, given a set of broken relations, we are tasked with introducing new parameterized edits that restore and preserve these relations across the input range. For a single part P_i , this problem can be written as finding an edit E^* for P_i such that all the constraints on the part are held:

$$\text{Find } E^* \text{ s.t. } SAT(E, \mathbb{C}) \quad (3.2)$$

$$SAT(E, \mathbb{C}) \implies \{\|C_i(x)\|_\infty < \delta \mid \forall C_i \in \mathbb{C}, \forall x \in (0, \tau)\}, \quad (3.3)$$

where \mathbb{C} is the set of all constraints derived from the broken relations of the part.

Restoring symmetry group relations is quite simple, as it has a well-defined analytical solution. Given H_i and H_j under a symmetry group $G(T)$, where H_i has an edit E , we can introduce a new edit $E^* = T(E)$ on H_j such that the symmetry group is preserved. For example, to restore reflection symmetry between two parts with one of them under a parameterized translation, we can introduce a similarly parameterized translation on the other part with its translation direction reflected about the reflection plane. Following [229], we prioritize symmetry relations over attachment relations, and restore them before searching for attachment-preserving edits.

In contrast, restoring attachment relations is uniquely challenging. The set of constraints derived from attachment relations can be of arbitrary size (depending on the number of attachment relations of the part), without well-defined analytical solutions. Therefore, we need to *search* for edits that can satisfy all the constraints. This entails searching for (i) the correct type of edit, with (ii) the correct edit-specific parameters `PARAMS` that are defined over \mathbb{R}^n , and (iii) the correct parameterization `AMOUNT`, which can be an arbitrary algebraic expression of the control parameter x . Naively performing this search is infeasible. We therefore employ two techniques to address this challenge. As we detail below, our solution relies on carefully sampling

Figure 3.5: **Searching for edits:** Which edit operations could we use for the chair leg part? (a) First, broken constraints \mathbb{C} (highlighted with a red line) are detected, denoting the relations to be fixed. (b) We then sample parameterizations of the edit operators in our DSL to create candidate edits \mathbb{E}_R . (c) Using CAS solvers, we search for a `AMOUNT` expression for each edit candidate that satisfies the constraints \mathbb{C} , resulting in the set of valid edits \mathbb{E} .

assignments of `PARAMS` and using CAS solvers to infer feasible `AMOUNT` expressions. To aid exposition, we continue with the example of widening a chair seat, with an accompanying illustration in Figure 3.5. As shown in Figure 3.5 (a), as the seat is widened, the attachment relation between the legs and the seat is broken. We are now tasked with finding a suitable edit for the leg to restore this attachment relation.

Each edit has numeric parameters `PARAMS` that can take arbitrary values in \mathbb{R}^n . Instead of searching across all possible `PARAMS`, we search over a smaller subset of feasible `PARAMS` assignments. The feasible `PARAMS` assignments are created using hexahedron features, such as face centers, vertices, and local axis directions. We enumerate over the applicable DSL edit operators and exhaustively sample feasible assignments of `PARAMS` to create \mathbb{E}_R , a set of feasible edit candidates. In Figure 3.5 (b), we depict the candidate edits from \mathbb{E}_R . Our goal is to now enumerate the edit candidates and ascertain whether they can satisfy the constraints.

To check whether an edit candidate can satisfy the constraints, we must specify its `AMOUNT`. Note that `AMOUNT` is an algebraic expression and needs to be set such that it satisfies the constraints for all values of x in the input range. Therefore, we set `AMOUNT` to be an arbitrary function $f(x)$ and state this task more formally as:

$$\text{Find } f(x) \text{ s.t. } \text{SAT}(E_{\text{AMOUNT}=f(x)}, \mathbb{C}), E \in \mathbb{E}_R \quad (3.4)$$

Here, we leverage the CAS solvers to search for *analytical* solutions for $f(x)$. Note that since we can have multiple constraints on a given part, the constraint set \mathbb{C} can be a mixed set of equations for which CAS solvers may fail to find solutions. Therefore, we instead create a set of feasible analytical solutions \mathbb{F} by solving each constraint independently (i.e. by solving $f(x)$ such that $\|C_i(x)\| = 0$). *Analytical* solutions

in \mathbb{F} that satisfy all constraints (by numerical check) are then accepted as solutions to equation 3.4. We additionally note that solving equation 3.4 for a given edit E is “embarrassingly” parallel, allowing us to search for solutions for different edits $E \in \mathbb{E}_R$ in parallel.

With the *analytical* solutions, we form a set \mathbb{E} containing edits that restore all the constraints, $\mathbb{E} = \{E \in \mathbb{E}_R \mid \text{SAT}(E, \mathbb{C})\}$. This set is depicted in Figure 3.5 (c). Though all the edit candidates in \mathbb{E} restore the *currently* broken relations, each may cause a different set of relations to be broken. Therefore, we must carefully select the edit candidate. Taking inspiration from prior work [41], we design a simple selection criterion for selecting the most suitable edit from \mathbb{E} , which considers the ARAP deformation energy [170] (lower is better) and the number of intrinsic symmetry planes of the edit (higher is better). Appendix A provides additional details.

Improving Solver Robustness

Though the technique presented above succeeds in a majority of analytical edit propagation steps, we found that it can sometimes fail to find good edits. We now detail two features that improve the quality of solutions found by the solver. As we experimentally verify later in Section 3.7.3, these features noticeably improve the program quality.

Extending the Candidate Set The set \mathbb{E}_R of edit candidates can sometimes fail to contain `PARAMS` assignments that can successfully satisfy all the constraints. When none of the edits in \mathbb{E}_R satisfy all the constraints, we introduce additional edits with `PARAMS` assignments based on the features of other *edited* hexahedrons. For example, if a cabinet door is rotated about its hinge, its handle must also be rotated about the same axis. By introducing edits with `PARAMS` assignments based on the door’s features, we can discover such an edit. For simplicity, such edits are later referred to in our experiments as *nhbd-edits*.

Handling UNSAT Despite the extensive search, sometimes the constraints in \mathbb{C} may not be mutually satisfiable. Under such circumstances, we select the *minimally constraint-breaking* edit, i.e. the edit that breaks the smallest number of constraints. This is done by recording, for each solution in \mathbb{F} , the number of constraints it breaks and selecting the one that breaks the fewest constraints. We simply refer to edits introduced in this way as *breaking-edits*.

3.6 LLM-Augmented Inference

In the previous section, we introduced ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP), which utilizes a *seed-edit* inferred by the LLM to discover necessary secondary edits. We now explore how we deploy LLMs in tandem with AEP to infer parameterized editing programs. First, we address a limitation of naive edit propagation,

Figure 3.6: We compare parametric editing of 3D assets across three system variants. The *One Shot LLM* produces unrealistic part intersections (b, c) and fails to propagate corrective edits (a, d). The *Ours Seed Only* variant with ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP) produces consistent variations, but can fail to align with the input edit intent. Our full system (*Ours*), which includes edit *type-hints* and *relation-validity*, produces edits that closely match user requests.

also present in traditional techniques [229, 41], and propose our solution to overcome it.

3.6.1 A Limitation of Naive Edit Propagation

Edit propagation relies on two key assumptions about the user’s intent: (i) The user wishes to preserve inter-part relationships as much as possible, and (ii) The user prefers the simplest possible secondary modification. However, these assumptions do not always hold.

During edit propagation, we attempt to restore all inter-part geometric relationships. However, achieving certain edits may require allowing some relationships to remain broken. For example, even if the front legs of a chair are symmetric to the back legs, the user may desire to edit only the back legs in a symmetry-breaking fashion. Similarly, using the simplest possible secondary modifications, from an ARAP [170] perspective, might not always match user intent. For instance, when widening a chair’s seat, the simplest modification to the legs is to shift them. However, the user might instead prefer to tilt the legs (cf. Figure 3.8).

Performing these edits with traditional methods requires significant manual effort. Users must remove the reflection relationship between the front and back legs to support the first edit and add an attachment relationship between the legs and the floor for the second edit. This underscores a key limitation of traditional edit propagation: *the structure invoked in the shape must be modified to support different edits*. Consequently, with prior methods, users have to manually adjust the shape’s structure to ensure the edits generated align with their intent.

3.6.2 Dynamic Structure Modification Using LLMs

While manually performing these actions is laborious, verbally specifying them in an edit request is straightforward. As our system supports unstructured natural-language input, we use LLMs to interpret these requirements from the edit request and automatically update the shape’s structure to facilitate the edit. This approach eliminates the need for users to manually adjust the shape’s structure, leveraging LLMs to perform these tasks instead. Based on the edit request, the LLM infers (i) the *seed-edit*, (ii) the *relation-validity* for each symmetry relationship in the shape, and (iii) the edit *type-hints* for the different parts.

When a relation is deemed invalid, we delete the corresponding constraints. When a part has a specified *type-hint*, we use it to filter the edit candidates generated during edit propagation (i.e. we filter them out from \mathbb{E}_R). This enables us to directly target the specific edits the user desires, unlike prior approaches that require additional constraints to achieve such complex modifications. With this approach, we can accommodate edit requests that conflict with symmetry relationships in the shape or require specific editing operations for secondary parts.

Prompting Workflows

We infer the three quantities with three separate prompting workflows. For each task, the LLM is provided with a verbal description of the parts in the shape, the user’s edit request, and a set of task-specific instructions. The LLM returns an executable Python snippet, which is parsed and executed to obtain the LLM’s response. For the *seed-edit* inference, the LLM is also given an API to create the edit operators. To avoid confusion between different relations, *relation-validity* is inferred for each symmetry relation independently with a separate prompt. For inferring explicit *type-hints*, we found the LLM to be most reliable when limited to three abstract types: ‘translate’, ‘rotate’, and ‘scale’.

We improve the quality of the LLM response by using prompting techniques such as Chain of Thought (CoT) [196], in-context examples [17], and reminders [107]. Additionally, we perform majority-voting [192] by aggregating results from multiple independent LLM calls and using the modal response. Voting improves our system significantly, even with only five samples (refer to Table 3.3). Since there is no interdependence between the prompts, we prompt the LLM for all tasks in parallel, maintaining response times comparable to a single API call.

3.7 Experiments

We now present experiments that evaluate the editing programs inferred by our system. We additionally perform ablation experiments on the different components of our system to provide more insight. Note that

	Preference Rate
<i>Ours</i> vs. <i>One Shot LLM</i>	79.9%
<i>Ours</i> vs. <i>Ours Seed Only</i>	76.5%

Table 3.1: **Our system is preferred:** Results of a two-alternative forced-choice perceptual study comparing our system against two alternate realizations. Our system (denoted *Ours*) is preferred in an overwhelming majority of the judgments.

we utilize OpenAI’s (text-only) GPT-4 [51] as the LLM for all of our experiments.

3.7.1 Datasets

We evaluate our method over 3D models sourced from two datasets. A *dev-set* is curated using 3D mesh models from the PartNet [126] dataset, while the *test-set* is composed of 3D models from the CoMPaT3D++ dataset [169]. The *dev-set* includes 51 part-segmented meshes sampled from five categories of man-made objects: *Chair*, *Table*, *Couch*, *Storage Furniture*, and *Bed*. We used the *dev-set* as a benchmark while developing the system, and models in this set contain 5 to 81 parts (median 17), and 4 to 318 relations (median 40), covering simple to complex geometries. The *test-set* contains 50 models sourced from 21 different categories within the CoMPaT3D++ dataset. This set is used to verify the efficacy of our system beyond the object categories present in the *dev-set*. Thus, the *test-set* also includes objects from uncommon categories such as *Gazebos*, *Bird Houses*, and *Fans*.

All models are paired with manually written natural language edit requests to create (*shape*, *edit request*) pairs used as input to our system. As we show in the qualitative examples, the edit requests encompass a wide variety of modifications. Additionally, we annotate each pair in the *dev-set* with a ‘ground-truth’ (GT) editing program derived through a *Human-Solver* inference process, where the LLM is replaced by an expert user. Note that both the GT programs and the programs inferred by each variant we consider are written in the DSL introduced in Section 3.4.2.

3.7.2 Language-based Parameterized Editing of 3D Assets

First, we evaluate our system’s efficacy in enabling natural-language-based parametric editing of 3D assets. As described earlier, our system achieves this by inferring parameterized editing programs that align with natural language edit requests. Notably, prior works are not well-suited for this task. Neural approaches [168, 1], although powerful, do not support high-resolution 3D assets, and prior edit-propagation approaches [41, 229] cannot be controlled via natural language. Beyond this, neither of these paradigms support *parametric* editing. Since no prior work adequately addresses this problem, we introduce alternative realizations of our system for comparison:

	$\mathcal{J}(Prog)(\uparrow)$	$\mathcal{D}(Geo)(\downarrow)$	%REL(\uparrow)
<i>One Shot LLM</i>	0.31	8.30	61.71%
<i>Ours Seed Only</i>	0.53	8.62	83.47%
<i>Ours</i>	0.70	4.01	91.57%

Table 3.2: **Our method is closer to GT:** We compare the different system realizations against ‘GT’ annotations. Our system (*Ours*) obtains the best performance over metrics that measure the proximity to the ‘GT’ annotations across *Programmatic*, *Geometric* and *Structural* aspects.

1. *One Shot LLM*: As detailed in Section 3.4.3, this approach involves providing the LLM with all necessary information to infer the entire editing program in a single step.
2. *Ours Seed Only*: This baseline uses an LLM to infer the *seed-edit* and employs *Analytical Edit Propagation (AEP)* to generate the entire editing program.
3. *Ours*: Our full system, which utilizes the LLM to specify the *seed-edit*, *relation-validity*, and edit *type-hints*. These components are then used during AEP to produce edits that closely align with the user’s intent.

Analysis of Human Preference

Using the *test-set*, we conducted a two-alternative forced-choice perceptual study to compare these method variants. We recruited 56 participants for the task. Each participant was shown a series of comparisons, resulting in a total of 1642 judgments. Each comparison included a natural language edit request and two videos showing a 3D shape being edited with the inferred editing programs, with the control parameter smoothly varying across its range (from 0 to an automatically set upper bound, τ). Participants were instructed to “select the method that better satisfies the input editing prompt and results in a better edited shape.” Note that we elide comparisons where the programs inferred by the compared methods match (18% of the comparisons in total).

Table 3.1 presents the results of our experiment. Our method is preferred over *One Shot LLM* in 79.9% of the judgments. *One Shot LLM* often fails to construct meaningful editing programs, demonstrating the failure cases discussed in Section 3.4.3. In contrast, by leveraging *AEP*, our method produces cohesive editing programs that respect the inter-part relationships. Compared to *Ours Seed Only*, our method is preferred in 76.5% of comparisons. Without the ability to provide type hints or disable symmetry relations, *Ours Seed Only* often infers programs that respect inter-part relations but fail to align with the user’s edit intent. Note that *Ours Seed Only* represents a *purely* analytical variant of the prior edit propagation method [229]. This indicates that when editing with prior *analyze-and-edit* methods, users often need to manually adjust multiple settings, such as enabling/disabling relations, to perform their desired edits. In contrast, our system allows users to simply state their edit intent in natural language, and we task the LLM with automatically

Figure 3.7: **Proxydural Modeling**: Leveraging the open-world knowledge of LLMs, we synthesize edit requests for a given shape to enable *automatic* procedural models, termed *Proxydural* due to the use of bounding proxy deformations. Our system allows multiple proxydural models for the same shape, a capability not possible with prior approaches [15].

	$Acc(SE) \uparrow$	$Acc(R) \uparrow$	$\mathcal{J}(T) \uparrow$	$Match \uparrow$
<i>Ours</i>	76.47	88.91	73.92	35.29
- <i>Voting</i>	68.62	88.91	68.02	25.49
- <i>CoT</i>	72.54	88.17	71.69	27.45
- <i>In-Context</i>	66.66	87.68	65.75	23.52
<i>Naive</i>	68.62	86.99	65.36	19.60

Table 3.3: **Prompting Ablation**: We report the LLM’s accuracy at inferring the *seed-edit* ($Acc(SE)$), *relation-validity* ($Acc(R)$), and edit *type-hints* ($\mathcal{J}(T)$), along with the fraction of inputs where the LLM infers everything correctly ($Match$). Voting and in-context examples significantly enhance accuracy, while the naive approach shows a marked decrease.

adjusting these settings. The videos from the perceptual study are included in the materials associated with Appendix A, allowing for independent verification of our results.

Analysis of Inferred Programs

Next, we compare the programs generated by these methods against the manually annotated ground-truth (GT) editing programs on the *dev-set*. We evaluate the quality of the editing programs using three criteria: 1) *Programmatic* ($\mathcal{J}(prog)$): This metric assesses how closely the inferred programs match the GT programs. 2) *Geometric* ($\mathcal{D}(geo)$): This metric measures the geometric distance between the shape edited with the inferred programs and the shape edited with the GT programs. 3) *Structural* ($\%Rel$): This metric quantifies the percentage of inter-part relations whose state (broken vs. maintained) matches the relation’s state under the ground truth (GT) program. Further details are provided in Appendix A.

We present the results of this experiment in Table 3.2. First, we note that the *One Shot LLM* approach fails drastically across the three criteria, which aligns with the preference rates observed in the human study. Secondly, we observe that omitting the *type-hints* and *relation-validity* steps adversely affects the *Ours Seed*

	$\mathcal{J}(\text{Prog})(\uparrow)$	$\mathcal{D}(\text{Geo})(\downarrow)$	%REL(\uparrow)
<i>Ours</i>	0.70	4.01	91.57%
- <i>nhbd</i>	0.70	4.21	91.35%
- <i>breaking</i>	0.68	3.46	86.41%
<i>Naive</i>	0.67	4.31	85.4%

Table 3.4: **Quality of programs inferred by the Solver:** Removing *nhbd-edits* results in higher geometric distance ($\mathcal{D}(\text{Geo})$), while removing *breaking-edits* leads to more structural distance (%REL). The naive approach that removes both of these options is the least effective.

Only approach as well. Specifically, *Ours Seed Only* results in a very high $\mathcal{D}(\text{geo})$ measure, indicating that although AEP restores the inter-part relations, the edits inferred without *type-hints* cause the edited shape to geometrically deviate from the intended shape. Finally, we highlight that our system outperforms the others across all three metrics.

We also present qualitative examples of editing programs inferred from different baselines in Figure 3.6. The improvement in the quantitative metrics is evident in these qualitative examples. The baselines produce visible artifacts, such as intersections between parts, and often violate the intent of the requested edits.

3.7.3 Analyzing the System Design

In this section, we present an ablative analysis of the LLM prompting workflow and the AEP solver to elucidate the impact of various design decisions.

Analysis of the Prompting Workflow

Our system employs separate prompts to infer the *seed edit*, *relation validity*, and edit *type hints*. We measure the LLM’s accuracy at inferring these three terms by comparing its output to that of a human annotator. Additionally, we perform a subtractive ablation by individually removing majority voting [192], Chain-of-Thought (CoT) [196], and in-context examples [17] to measure their impact on the LLM’s accuracy. We report four metrics: 1) $Acc(SE)$, for seed edit accuracy; 2) $Acc(R)$, for relation validity accuracy; 3) $\mathcal{J}(T)$, for type hint accuracy; and 4) $Match$, for the fraction of input pairs where all LLM-inferred quantities match human annotations.

The results are presented in Table 3.3. As demonstrated, there is a significant gap in accuracy between our prompting workflow and the *Naive* approach, which does not include voting, chain-of-thought (CoT) reasoning, or in-context examples. Among these techniques, voting and in-context examples have a more pronounced effect on performance, whereas the absence of CoT results in a relatively smaller decline in accuracy. Although not directly comparable, we find that all models struggle most with correctly setting the seed edit and the type hints. This difficulty likely arises from the need to construct the seed edit using a

complex API and the necessity of inferring type hints for many parts of the shape. Finally, this experiment underscores the task and dataset complexity, as even our best approach fully matches the human annotation for only approximately 35% of the input pairs. Note that due to redundancies in the shape structure and the presence of multiple ways to satisfy an edit request, effective editing programs can be inferred even when not all inferred quantities match the ground truth. Consequently, annotator evaluations indicate that programs produced with our method (*Ours*) matched the intended edits in 72.5% of the inputs.

Analysis of the AEP Solver

Next, we perform an ablative analysis of our *AEP* solver, focusing on the features introduced in Section 3.5.3: (i) *nhbd-edits*, which creates edit candidates with parameters specified using features of other edited parts, and (ii) *breaking-edits*, which use the *minimally constraint-breaking* edit when no edit satisfies all constraints. We compare the inferred programs to the ground truth (GT) programs using the metrics from Section 3.7.2, and provide results in Table 3.4. Removing *nhbd-edits* increases *geometric* distance, while removing *breaking-edits* increases *structural* distance. This aligns with our intuition: *nhbd-edits* improve parameterization, affecting geometric distance, while *breaking-edits* reduce the number of broken relations, affecting structural distance when elided.

3.8 Applications

Our editing system acts as a translator, converting natural language prompts into editing programs. With this system in hand, we can further explore how to employ the creative capabilities of LLMs to enable new applications. We demonstrate two such applications: *Automatic Proxydural Modeling* and creating *Shape Variation Families*. Note that we utilize OpenAI’s (Vision) GPT-4 [133] as the LLM for these applications; Appendix A describes the prompts used for the applications.

3.8.1 Automatic Proxydural Modeling

Our editing programs incorporate analytical edits, representing modified parts as parameterized functions of control parameters exposed to the user. By leveraging function composition, these programs can be automatically stacked, allowing a part edited by one program to serve as the input for another. This capability enables the creation of (approximately) procedural models of any given shape through the following steps: (i) gather multiple independent editing requests, (ii) infer an editing program for each request, each with a single independent control parameter, and (iii) stack these edits using function composition. This approach

allows users to explore shape variations through a set of sliders, akin to interacting with procedural models. Since the shapes are edited using their bounding proxies, we term this approach *Proxydural Modeling*.

In cases where users wish to automatically explore variations of a given shape, our system can still be effectively utilized. The key is to identify interesting modes of variation and automatically craft corresponding editing requests. Once these editing requests are defined, our system can use them to generate the *Proxydural Model*. To achieve this, we leverage the impressive world knowledge and natural language capabilities of LLMs. Given a segmented shape, we prompt the LLM to generate edit requests that capture interesting variations. By providing in-context examples and task-specific instructions, we ensure that the LLM produces requests compatible with our system. These requests are then used to automatically create the PROXYDURAL MODEL. In Figure 3.7, we present multiple PROXYDURAL MODELS automatically crafted by the LLM. Unlike prior inverse procedural modeling approaches [15], our system enables the creation of multiple *Proxydural Models* for a single input geometry, each facilitating the exploration of different shape variations.

3.8.2 Creating a Shape Variation Family

Natural language edit requests can often be underspecified, particularly when it comes to detailing secondary edits. Consequently, edit requests typically support multiple possible realizations. The *minimal-deformation*, *maximally-relation-preserving* edits produced by edit propagation approaches represent only a single interpretation of the request. However, different users may prefer different secondary edits. Therefore, producing editing programs that each model a different interpretation of the request is desirable. We refer to these sets of related but distinct editing programs as *Shape Variation Families*.

To enable this exploration, we create multiple variations of the initial editing request, retaining the user-specified primary edit while exploring different secondary effects. These varied requests are then used to generate distinct editing programs, each resulting in a unique shape variation. We leverage the general world knowledge about object categories contained in LLMs to accomplish this task. Given the user’s primary edit request, we prompt the LLM to generate variations of the request, specifically targeting different secondary effects. As with the previous application, we provide in-context examples and task-specific instructions to ensure that the LLM produces requests compatible with our system. Once the editing programs are generated for all the varied prompts, they are presented to the user. The user can then explore different interpretations of the edit request and select the one most aligned with their intent. In Figure 3.8, we show an example of a *Shape Variation Family* generated with this approach.

Figure 3.8: **Shape Variation Family**: Given a 3D asset and an underspecified edit request, we leverage LLMs to synthesize potential extensions of the request. By inferring programs for both the extended and original requests, we create a set of related but distinct parametric models, each adhering to the initial edit request while supporting different shape variations.

3.9 Limitations and Future Work

While PARSEL is the first system capable of supporting controllable shape edits from natural language, it does have a few limitations:

(i) *Search Efficiency*: A downside of our approach is the computational expense of the analytical edit search. While the median time it takes to search for editing programs is approximately 30 seconds, in certain conditions it can take more than 500 seconds for very complex shapes. This is due to our simple and generous edit sampling process, where the solver may evaluate an extensive array of potential edit candidates under certain conditions. This could likely be mitigated to a large extent with the addition of a ‘smarter’ edit sampling strategy. For instance, analyzing the parametric form of attachment points can help identify suitable editing operations and prune the search space. Alternatively, employing an early exit model, where search stops once a satisfying edit is found, may also improve the runtime of the system (though integration with parallelization may be non-trivial).

(ii) *Limited Edits*: Our system currently supports a limited range of part deformations: only those expressible as affine transforms of the bounding proxy or its features. We contrast this with the prior neural approaches [1] in Figure 3.2, which, despite other drawbacks, support a wider range of shape edits. To accommodate a wider range of edit requests, our system needs to support additional deformation functions, such as making parts spherical or cylindrical. A key challenge in supporting novel deformations is the ability to analytically specify the state of inter-part relations under these deformation functions. This makes iterative non-analytic deformation functions, such as ARAP-energy-based deformation [170], incompatible with our system.

(iii) *Limited Shape Structures*: While our shape representation is effective for many man-made 3D objects,

it has its limitations. Bounding boxes may not be the best control cage for all parts, and other control cages may be required. Although our system can support arbitrary control cages, as we use harmonic coordinates to parameterize the attachment relations, their effect on the solver’s success is unclear. Additionally, we currently model a limited set of symmetry relations. Two common forms observed in 3D assets that we identify are (i) parts formed by joining points on two different curves, often seen in the design of back supports in chairs and beds, and (ii) wallpaper symmetry groups, which involve translation symmetry along two axes, commonly seen in building facades. Extending our system to support these additional structures would greatly enhance its applicability. Finally, we note that relying solely on language-based input can be limiting, particularly for 3D parts without well-defined names or for edits that are better expressed through other modalities, such as sketch-based guidance [41].

We believe that our system makes 3D asset editing more controllable and intuitive for artists. With the rise of text-to-3D approaches, creating new models has become easier, yet editing them remains a challenge. By integrating our system with auto-segmentation techniques [231], we can enable intuitive and precise editing of models generated from text-to-3D approaches. Finally, we emphasize that our system was most effective with careful and directed LLM integration; we task the LLM with performing only high-level translation tasks, and rely on symbolic solvers to perform the necessary geometric analysis. Looking ahead, we hope this work provides a useful framework for the reliable integration of LLMs with symbolic reasoning to support shape analysis.

3.10 Conclusion

In this chapter, we introduced PARSEL: PARAMETERIZED SHAPE EDITING WITH LANGUAGE, a shape editing system that combines the accessibility of natural language with the precision of parametric control. Given a semantically segmented 3D mesh and an edit request, PARSEL compiles language into a *parameterized editing program* whose exposed parameter(s) let users control the magnitude of the edit while preserving part structure and semantics. This is enabled by a neuro-symbolic inference module that couples LLM-based interpretation with domain reasoning. Central to this module is ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION (AEP), which extends an LLM-proposed seed edit into a complete, coherent program by adding additional operations consistent with inter-part geometric relationships, using geometric analysis via computer algebra.

Beyond the specific setting of segmented mesh editing, this chapter establishes one of the dissertation’s central acquisition patterns: when paired training data for a new symbolic representation is scarce, foundation models can supply useful semantic priors, but those priors must be grounded in domain-specific structure. Here, natural language serves as a flexible way to specify edit intent, while LLMs act as general-purpose

interpreters that propose candidate operations. The role of the domain-specific machinery—PARSELLANG and AEP—is to turn those proposals into valid symbolic geometry by enforcing semantic and geometric constraints.

The next chapter turns to a complementary acquisition strategy. Rather than drawing on broad foundation-model priors, it asks how a symbolic representation can help generate its own supervision. In the setting of visual program inference, SIRI uses program rewrites to repair and recombine inferred programs, converting the structure of the target language itself into in-domain synthetic training signal.

CHAPTER 4

ACQUISITION VIA IN-DOMAIN SYNTHETIC SUPERVISION: SIRI

Improving Unsupervised Visual Program Inference with Code Rewriting Families

Figure 4.1: Our method SIRI generates highly compact yet accurate programs, in contrast to CSG-Stump [148], which generates programs with numerous primitives. We show shapes rendered with colored primitives.

The dissertation problem is annotation-free acquisition of symbolic geometry: given an unstructured measurement, generated asset, raw 3D observation, or other weak geometric signal, recover a symbolic representation whose parts, parameters, operations, and constraints make the geometry editable and reusable. The previous chapter approached this problem through foundation-model priors, using broad language and code knowledge to propose symbolic edit structure. This chapter turns to the second acquisition strategy in the thesis: in-domain synthetic supervision.

The setting here is classic visual program inference. We are given a target geometry x and a visual domain-specific language with an executor E ; the goal is to infer a program z such that $E(z)$ reconstructs x . The target may be an image, voxel grid, or shape sample, but the desired output is not another measurement. It is an executable program in a chosen language, such as 2D CSG, 3D CSG, or ShapeAssembly. In supervised settings, paired examples (x, z) can teach this inverse map directly. In the annotation-free setting of this

thesis, those ground-truth programs are unavailable.

SIRI addresses this gap by using the symbolic language itself as a source of training signal. A bootstrapped visual program inference model first proposes imperfect programs for the target shapes. Program rewriters then repair, simplify, and recombine those inferred programs, producing improved examples that can be injected back into training. The supervision is synthetic because no human supplies the target program, but it is in-domain because it is generated by operations that act directly on the symbolic representation and are judged by the same executor-based reconstruction objective.

This matters beyond the original paper because it shows that symbolic representations can participate in their own acquisition. The language is not only the output space of the model; its executor, algebra, and rewrite operators provide structure that helps the model learn without paired annotations. Within the thesis taxonomy, SIRI is therefore the first example of in-domain synthetic supervision: it turns representation-specific operations into a reusable source of acquisition signal for symbolic geometry.

4.1 Introduction

Visual data is often highly structured: manufactured shapes are produced by assembling parts; vector graphics images are built from layers of primitives; detailed textures can be created via intricate compositions of noise functions. *Visual programs*, i.e. programs that produce visual outputs when executed, are a natural approach to capturing this complexity in a structure-aware fashion. Access to well-written visual programs supports downstream applications across visual computing domains, including editing, generative modeling, and structural analysis. But how can we obtain a program which generates a given visual datum?

Visual Program Inference (VPI) methods aim to solve this problem by automatically inferring programs that represent visual inputs. Solving this search problem is very difficult: the space of possible programs is often vast, even when constrained by a domain-specific language (DSL). To overcome this challenge, recent works have investigated learning-based solutions, where a neural network is employed to guide the search. When a dataset of visual programs exists, such networks can be trained in a supervised fashion [202, 198, 205, 204, 68]. Unfortunately, most domains lack such data, so recent works have investigated how to train VPI networks in an *unsupervised* fashion.

Learning to infer visual programs without supervision is challenging: programs usually contain discrete and continuous elements, which complicates end-to-end learning. Various solutions have been proposed to work around this issue: end-to-end learning is possible with neural architectures that act as a smooth relaxation of program executors [148], while policy gradient reinforcement learning [161] and bootstrapped

Project page: <https://bardofcodes.github.io/coref/>

learning methods [70] are able to treat program executors as (potentially non-differentiable) ‘black boxes.’ These solutions come with downsides: designing differentiable relaxations is challenging (or even impossible) for some domains; reinforcement learning suffers from noisy gradients and slow convergence; bootstrapped learning methods are prone to getting stuck in local minima.

Moreover, a seldom acknowledged limitation of these latter methods is that they treat programs as *just* sequences of tokens. We argue that this view is suboptimal: programs are structured objects that support domain-specific reasoning to meaningfully constrain and guide the VPI search process. One example of such reasoning is the use of domain-specific operations that modify programs toward optimizing an objective—we call such operations *rewrites*. Rewrites have been explored in the context of VPI tasks, but primarily as a test-time optimization, e.g. finding better continuous parameters for a fixed program structure. While such optimization is useful, our claim is that other rewrite operations are similarly useful, especially when used in tandem, and that they can be employed to benefit VPI network learning, not only as test-time optimization schemes.

In this chapter, we investigate how to use code rewriting to improve visual program inference. Unlike prior work, we focus on *families* of code rewriters, each of which makes improvements to a program with some goal in mind. We propose *Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection* (SIRI), a bootstrapped learning algorithm that sparsely applies rewriters and injects rewritten programs into a search-train loop at intermittent intervals. To realize SIRI, we design a family of rewrites applicable to multiple visual programming DSLs: gradient-based parameter optimization (*Parameter Optimization*), removing spurious sub-programs (*Code Pruning*), and sub-program substitutions from a cache (*Code Grafting*). We also propose a test-time rewriting scheme that searches for improved programs through interleaved rewrites and is well-suited to the types of programs inferred by SIRI-trained networks.

We evaluate SIRI and our family of rewriters (*PO*, *CP*, *CG*) on three shape-program DSLs: 2D Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG), 3D CSG, and ShapeAssembly [68]. We compare VPI networks trained with SIRI to VPI networks trained by PLAD, a recently proposed bootstrapped learning method [70], and find that SIRI both increases reconstruction performance and converges significantly faster. We further show that naively combining our rewrite families with PLAD performs much worse than SIRI, and in some domains even worsens performance compared with PLAD. Finally, we demonstrate that combining SIRI with our test-time rewriting scheme infers visual programs that can match (3D CSG [148]) or surpass (2D CSG [75]) reconstruction performance of domain-specific neural architectures while producing significantly more parsimonious programs (see number of primitives, Figure 4.1).

In summary, we make the following contributions:

1. *Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection*, a framework for unsupervised visual program inference that

Figure 4.2: Bootstrapped learning methods [70] store a record of the objective-maximizing program for each shape in a Best Program (BP) data structure. Naive rewrite integration applies a family of rewriters to each entry in BP and overwrites an entry when a rewrite is successful. Our method, SIRI, instead applies the rewriters to a subset of BP entries and overwrites entries only when their sources S_i match.

leverages a family of code rewriters.

2. A family of code rewriters applicable to multiple DSLs that benefit VPI learning methods and can be used in a test-time rewriting scheme.

4.2 Task-Specific Positioning

Visual program inference is one instance of annotation-free symbolic acquisition. This chapter focuses on the regime where the target representation is a visual DSL and the system must improve its own inferred programs without ground-truth labels. Prior VPI methods have used differentiable relaxations, reinforcement learning, and bootstrapped search-train loops [161, 75, 148, 215, 218, 70]. These approaches provide useful learning signals, but they often treat programs as flat token sequences rather than structured objects that can be repaired, simplified, or recombined.

Program rewriting supplies that missing structure. CAD reverse-engineering, CSG optimization, equality saturation, and fabrication-aware rewriting all show that local program transformations can improve symbolic artifacts [30, 129, 199, 130, 227, 200]. SIRI adapts this idea to learning: rewriters are not only a test-time optimization tool, but a source of in-domain synthetic supervision for a bootstrapped VPI model.

4.3 Method

In this section, we explore how families of code rewriters can be employed to improve visual program inference. In Section 4.3.1, we formalize our task specification, objective function, and rewriter assumptions. We then present *Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection* (SIRI), an unsupervised learning paradigm for visual program inference (VPI) in Section 4.3.2. SIRI employs a family of rewriters to improve reconstruction

performance for VPI tasks while maintaining a parsimonious program representation. Finally, we describe how these operations can also be used in a test-time rewriting scheme that is especially well-suited to the outputs of SIRI (Section 4.3.3). We describe the family of rewriters we employ for shape-program domains in Section 4.4.

4.3.1 Task Specification

We define the visual program inference task as follows: given a target distribution S of visual inputs (e.g. shapes), we want to learn a model $p_\theta(z|x)$, where $x \in S$, which infers a program z whose execution $E(z)$ reconstructs the input shape x . Following Occam’s razor, we seek programs that are parsimonious. More formally, we seek a p_{θ^*} that maximizes our objective function \mathcal{O} :

$$\theta^* = \arg \max_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{x \in S} \left[\sum_z \mathcal{O}(x, z) p_\theta(z|x) \right], \quad (4.1)$$

$$\mathcal{O}(x, z) = \mathcal{R}(x, E(z)) - \alpha|z|, \quad (4.2)$$

where \mathcal{R} measures the reconstruction accuracy between x and $E(z)$, $|z|$ measures the length of the program, and α modulates the strength of these two terms. Our method takes in a family of rewriters, RWS , to help with this task. Though each rewriter may leverage different domain properties, they are all tied to the same objective \mathcal{O} . Formally, they aim to perform rewrites $RW(x, z) \rightarrow z_i^R$ s.t. $z_i^R \sim \arg \max_{z \in \Omega^i(z)} \mathcal{O}(x, z)$, where $\Omega^i(z)$ represents the set of all programs rewriter i can create from z .

4.3.2 Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection

One way to use rewriters to improve VPI models is to incorporate them into bootstrapped learning schemes. One such recent bootstrapped learning paradigm is proposed by PLAD [70]. PLAD alternates between search and train phases, where a best-program (BP) data structure modulates how these phases communicate (Figure 4.2, left). In the search step, a VPI network $p(z|x)$ is fed visual inputs from S and aims to predict programs that optimize \mathcal{O} (e.g., through beam search). The results of this neurally-guided search (NS) are used to populate the fields of BP, where each key corresponds to a unique shape x , and each value corresponds to the best program (in terms of \mathcal{O} , for x) seen so far. In the train step, the entries of BP are used to construct paired training sets (X, Z) which are then used to optimize $p_\theta(z|x)$ with maximum likelihood loss.

How can rewrites be integrated into such a framework? We demonstrate a naive approach, termed *Naive Rewrite Integration* (NRI), in Figure 4.2, middle. In this naive version, a *Rewrite* step takes place between

each search and train step and modifies the entries of BP. Specifically, for every (x, z) entry in BP, each rewriter is applied to z , and if z^R improves the \mathcal{O} , then (x, z^R) is entered into BP, overwriting the (x, z) entry. Empirically, we find that this approach can in fact be worse than PLAD. While the rewriters perform a local search to optimize \mathcal{O} for the given (x, z) pair, there is no guarantee that a discovered z^R will make a better training target for $p_\theta(z|x)$ as well. NRI has a deleterious effect on the entries of BP, as only one program value is maintained for each shape key, so indiscriminate applications of rewriters can get easily stuck in local minima with respect to $p(z|x)$. Prior works which incorporate program rewriting strategies [33, 36] update training programs in this way.

Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection (SIRI) also employs a *Rewrite* step, but avoids this issue with a more judicious application of rewriters from *RWS* (Figure 4.2, right). Instead of applying rewriters to each shape, rewrites are only applied to a subset of BP entries. SIRI also adds a source field to each BP key that indicates what produced a given program: either neurally-guided search (NS) or some $RW \in RWS$. Critically, this allows SIRI to add programs into BP in a way that can only ‘forget’ (shape, program) pairs from the same source: NS programs replace NS programs, and each *RW* can only bump out *RW* sourced entries.

During the search step, each (x, z) pair produced by the neurally-guided search populates the (x, S_{NS}, z) entry of BP. Then for each $RW \in RWS$, SIRI samples a percentage of BP entries, (x, src, z) , and adds (x, RW, z^R) if the rewriter successfully improves the objective. Note that rewrites can sample inputs from any source, not just S_{NS} . Not only does this scheme ensure that rewriters only overwrite their own previous predictions, but it is also more efficient versus NRI: some rewriters have high computational costs, and excessively applying them can slow down training. Instead, we find that training $p(z|x)$ on BP entries with sparsely rewritten programs both converges faster and reaches better final states, as useful rewriting strategies get amortized by the network weights.

As only a subset of entries are updated in each *Rewrite* phase, some rewrite entries in BP (potentially from previous *Rewrite* phases) may store programs which are worse than the program inferred by $p_\theta(z|x)$ during *Search*. Therefore, before each train step, SIRI purges all stale (x, RW, z^*) entries from BP whenever $\mathcal{O}(x, z^*) < \mathcal{O}(x, z)$, where z is the program inferred for x during the *Search* phase.

4.3.3 Test-time Rewriting

Our family of rewriters, *RWS*, can also be employed at inference time to find better programs for a particular visual target. With a slight abuse of notation, given an (x, z) pair, our test-time rewrite (TTR) approach aims to find a sequence seq^* of at most k rewrite operations from *RWS*, such that $seq^* \sim \arg \max_{seq \in RWS^k} \mathcal{O}(x^*, seq(x, z))$, where $z^{ttr} = seq^*(x, z)$ would be the result of applying each rewrite

Figure 4.3: SIRI uses *rewrites* to improve VPI networks. We depict three rewrites in action that: optimize continuous parameter values (*Parameter Optimization*), remove extraneous code (*Code Pruning*), and substitute sub-expressions from a cache (*Code Grafting*).

in seq^* to z iteratively.

We realize this formulation with a greedy search. We initialize z^{tr} as z , and then for k steps, we iterate through each $RW \in RWS$, compare $\mathcal{O}(x, z^{tr})$ to $\mathcal{O}(x, RW(z^{tr}))$, and replace z^{tr} with $RW(z^{tr})$ if \mathcal{O} improves. To avoid redundant work, if a RW has already tried to improve a particular z , and failed to do so, we instead pass in the next best observed z (in terms of \mathcal{O}) that the RW has not operated over. The final z^{tr} is then returned as the output.

This procedure can in theory be applied to programs produced by any source (e.g. networks that act as differentiable language executors [148]). However, we find that there are unique benefits to applying this procedure to the predictions made by a $p_\theta(z|x)$ network trained with SIRI. Some rewrites build a cache of partial results during bootstrapped learning that can be quickly and effectively applied at inference time (*CG*, Section 4.4.3). Furthermore, some rewrites are too expensive to run on very complex programs, consuming massive amounts of memory, but are well-suited to the parsimonious programs produced by SIRI. For instance, one rewriter (*PO*, Section 4.4.1) was not able to operate on the highly complex programs output by CSG-Stump [148] (see Appendix B).

4.4 Rewriting Visual Programs

As our method relies on an input family of rewriters, RWS , we identify three rewrite operators that generalize across multiple shape-program domains. Figure 4.3 depicts these rewriters in action. In the rest of this section, we provide a high-level description and motivation for the different rewriters we use during SIRI and test-time rewriting: *Parameter Optimization* (Section 4.4.1), *Code Pruning* (Section 4.4.2), and *Code Grafting* (Section 4.4.3). Implementation details are provided in Appendix B.

4.4.1 Parameter Optimization

Visual languages often contain continuous (and differentiable) parameters such as the scale and position of primitives, and discrete parameters such as control flow (e.g. how to combine primitives). While keeping the discrete parameters fixed, the *Parameter Optimization (PO)* rewriter aims to improve the continuous parameters of a given program using gradient-based optimization. Given a program z_ϕ with continuous parameters ϕ inferred for a shape $x \in S$, *PO* adjusts ϕ to maximize the reconstruction accuracy \mathcal{R} between x and the program execution $E(z_\phi)$: $\phi^* \sim \arg \max_\phi \mathcal{R}(x, E(z_\phi))$.

To propagate gradients back from a reconstruction metric to the continuous parameters of z_ϕ , *PO* requires that the program executor E is partially differentiable: one or more continuous parameters should have well-defined derivatives for a given program structure (though the program execution may itself be only piecewise continuous). We highlight that *PO* is useful *even* under such constraints, precisely because *PO* is not the only rewriter we consider: other rewriters in *RWS* can influence structural changes, along with *SIRI*'s *Search* phase. *PO*'s requirements on E differ significantly from the differentiable executors employed by neural relaxation architectures. These works [75, 148] often attempt to differentiate through both discrete and continuous decisions, which leads to noisy gradients and poor program quality.

Although the design of executors is domain-dependent, we outline our procedure for converting the outputs of E into an equivalent signed-distance field representation compatible with our reconstruction metric \mathcal{R} . For each language we consider, we map outputs from E into a tree-like representation, where each leaf represents a primitive (spheres, etc.) and each intermediate node represents a transformation (position, etc.) or a combinator (union, etc.). For CSG-like languages, we can directly map from program parameters ϕ to this representation. It is also possible to convert the output of more complex program executors that produce collections of primitives into this format [68]. Then, we perform boolean combinations of the parameterized primitives and apply the transformation operators to obtain the program's implicit equivalent. With the program's implicit equivalent, we now uniformly sample points $t \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and convert the signed distance at the points into soft-occupancy to yield a differentiable execution of the program. This framing should be extensible to other visual-programming domains of interest when this mapping can be explicitly extracted from the input program (SVG) or parsed from primitives created by a more complex executor [142].

4.4.2 Code Pruning

One drawback of bootstrapping techniques is their tendency to reinforce spurious patterns [95]. The *Code Pruning (CP)* rewriter mitigates this problem by identifying and removing program fragments that negatively contribute to our objective \mathcal{O} . Given a shape x and input z , *CP* rewrites z s.t. $z^R \sim \arg \max_{\Omega_{CP}} \mathcal{O}(x, z)$,

Figure 4.4: Given a target T , we derive the *desired execution*, A^* , for sub-expression A through operator inversion. Our *CG* rewriter leverages *desired executions* to search for replacement candidates.

where $\Omega^{CP}(z) = \{z * |z* \subseteq z\}$ represents the set of all valid sub-programs of z . A naive *CP* rewriter that considers every valid sub-expression would be prohibitively slow. We instead implement a greedy version of *CP* designed for declarative, functional languages. We describe our general approach below; further details are provided in Appendix B.

Our implementation of *CP* employs two greedy searches, a top-down pass and a bottom-up pass, to approximate z^R . At each pass, we identify and prune nodes that decrease the overall objective score \mathcal{O} . The top-down traversal relabels the highest objective-scoring node as the root, pruning all but the tree starting at that node. The bottom-up traversal then checks each node’s contribution to the final execution and prunes branches with negligible contribution.

4.4.3 Code Grafting

A key feature of symbolic representations is the ability to perform part-based reasoning, e.g. compose parts from different instances. The *Code Grafting (CG)* rewriter exploits this feature to improve programs. Specifically, the *CG* rewriter replaces sub-expressions of a particular program with a better sub-expression (in terms of \mathcal{O}). The primary challenge is specifying *what* to replace a sub-expression with, as the space of potential replacements is enormous. To make the search tractable, *CG* builds a program cache populated by sub-expressions discovered while running SIRI, and searches for replacement candidates within the cache.

When the cache is large, searching for good replacement expressions can become expensive. Our *CG* implementation makes this search tractable by focusing on *execution equivalence*, i.e. equivalence is measured by comparing executions stored as n -dimensional occupancy grids. But finding cache entries that would improve reconstruction performance requires some notion of the *desired execution*, i.e. what sub-expression execution would make the program better match the target shape x ?

We develop a procedure for calculating such desired execution through masked function inversion;

	Chamfer Distance (\downarrow)			IoU (\uparrow)		
	2D CSG	3D CSG	ShapeAssembly	2D CSG	3D CSG	ShapeAssembly
PLAD [70]	0.24	1.75	1.98	90.8	74.65	63.1
NRI	0.36	1.25	1.53	88.4	74.43	66.89
SIRI	0.22	1.10	1.44	91.7	76.77	67.8

Table 4.1: We report test-set performance across three VPI domains. Naively integrating the rewriters into PLAD (NRI) can deteriorate the model’s performance (IoU on 2D & 3D CSG). In contrast, SIRI consistently improves over PLAD on all three VPI domains.

an example is depicted in Figure 4.4. We provide the high-level insight by walking through this figure; further details are provided in Appendix B. In this example, T denotes the target shape (the desired final execution), which is a union of two sub-expressions. Suppose we wish to replace sub-expression A . Given the current state of its sibling sub-expressions (B , in this case), we can invert the Union to produce the *desired execution* A^* . A^* can be broken into sub-regions: (black and white) areas where the optimal execution behavior is known and (gray) areas where the optimal execution behavior is unknown (for example, due to the non-invertibility of some operators). CG uses such ternary *desired executions* to search for cache entries that are likely to improve reconstruction accuracy and substitutes the most suitable candidate.

4.5 Results

We evaluate the efficacy of our rewriters over a collection of VPI domains for two tasks: improving bootstrapped learning (Section 4.5.2) and improving VPI with test-time rewrites (Section 4.5.3). We first provide the details concerning our experiments in Section 4.5.1.

4.5.1 Experimental Design

Domain-Specific Languages: We consider three VPI domains: 2D Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG), 3D CSG, and ShapeAssembly [68]. Shapes are formed in CSG by declaring primitives such as cylinders, applying transformations, and composing them via boolean operations. ShapeAssembly produces hierarchies of cuboid part proxies (which can themselves contain sub-programs) assembled through attachment operations. See Appendix B for the complete DSL grammars.

To ease learning, past approaches have used simplified versions of these languages, e.g. restricting CSG to contain only primitive-level transformations or removing hierarchical sub-programs from ShapeAssembly [75, 70, 161]. For fair comparison, we match our DSLs to prior work.

Shape Datasets: We evaluate 2D CSG on the CAD dataset introduced in CSGNet [161]. It contains front

Figure 4.5: We plot the objective O (Y-axis) as a function of training time (X-axis), measured by iterations (left) and wall-clock time (including time taken for rewriting) (right) on the 3D CSG domain. By amortizing the rewrite cost and keeping the training data diverse, SIRI achieves higher performance and does so faster.

and side views of chairs, desks and lamps from the Trimble 3D warehouse. This dataset is divided into 10K training, 3K validation and 3K testing shapes. We evaluate 3D CSG and ShapeAssembly on the 3D CAD dataset released in [70] containing shapes from chair, table, couch, and bench categories of ShapeNet dataset [22] in a voxel grid format. This dataset is split into 10k training, 1k validation and 1k testing shapes.

Model Architecture: Our model $p(z|x)$ synthesizes programs as a sequence of tokens, where each token specifies a command type or its parameters. Numeric parameters are normalized and discretized into 33 bins. Each $p(z|x)$ uses a domain-specific feature extractor (e.g. a 2D or 3D CNN), and a decoder-only transformer module. For 2D languages, the feature extractor takes a 64^2 image as input; for 3D languages, it takes a 32^3 voxel grid. We use the same transformer architecture for all experiments, varying only the last layer output size to model the different number of commands in each language.

Metrics: We measure reconstruction accuracy with two metrics: Intersection Over Union (IoU) and point cloud Chamfer Distance (CD). We use 64^2 and 32^3 resolution occupancy grids for calculating 2D and 3D IoU, respectively. We follow the same methodology as CSGNet [161] for measuring 2D CD; 3D CD is measured between 2048 points sampled on the ground-truth ShapeNet meshes and the meshes produced by executing the inferred programs.

Training details: Following [161, 70, 35], we pretrain our models on a large corpus of synthetically generated programs until it converges. We generate the synthetic programs via the sampling procedure proposed in PLAD [70]. After pretraining, the model is finetuned on the target distribution S , following the procedure outlined in Section 4.3.2. During each *Rewrite* phase, we apply *PO*, *CP* and *CG* to 50%, 50%, 15% of programs respectively. *CG* is applied to only 15% of data due to its higher computational cost. For our training objective O (c.f. equation 4.2), we fix α to 0.015. For 3D we set \mathcal{R} to IoU, and for 2D we set \mathcal{R} to CD. For test-time rewriting (TTR), we interleave *each* rewriter three times, unless specified otherwise (i.e. for Table 4.4).

Figure 4.6: Due to data-independent rewriters, SIRI remains effective at training the network even with a fraction of the data. In comparison, since PLAD’s *Search* phase is tied to the inference network’s performance, data scarcity deteriorates its performance.

4.5.2 Training with SIRI

We first evaluate the benefit of intermittent rewriting for bootstrapped learning. We compare our method SIRI against two baselines: PLAD [70], and *Naive Rewrite Integration* (NRI), which naively integrates the rewriters into PLAD (cf. Section 4.5.2). Note that prior work on integrating code rewriting [33, 36] follows this strategy.

As shown in Table 4.1, SIRI outperforms both the baselines on all domains. While PLAD performs well on simple domains such as 2D CSG, it is less effective on harder domains such as ShapeAssembly. Naively integrating the rewriters (NRI) can in fact even be detrimental to bootstrapped learning, as can be seen for 2D & 3D CSG (w.r.t. IoU). Excessive use of the rewriters and the lack of training data diversity leads the model trained with NRI to overfit to a local minimum, i.e. the *Search* and *Rewrite* phases become ineffective at generating better programs to learn from. SIRI resolves this issue by its frugal usage of the rewriters and by training p_θ on a diverse set of programs obtained from both the *Search* and *Rewrite* phases. We see a similar trend on other visual languages, which we discuss in Appendix B. Finally, we note that with 0.22 CD on the 2D CSG domain, SIRI outperforms UCSG-Net [75] (0.32 CD), the previous state-of-the-art method for 2D CSG.

We also evaluate how SIRI impacts the training convergence in Figure 4.5, plotting the Objective O against iterations (left) and wall-clock time (right). Wall-clock time includes the time required to execute the rewriters. Though NRI starts with high performance, it eventually converges to a lower value of O despite expending a lot of time on rewriting. In contrast, SIRI achieves higher performance while also amortizing the cost of rewriting all the programs as the model generalizes the useful patterns present in the rewritten training programs.

Data Scarcity: Often, large datasets of example shapes are not easily available. Thus, we probe the efficacy of SIRI and PLAD under data scarcity. We present our experiment in Figure 4.6, plotting the validation set CD for PLAD and SIRI. With 100% data, SIRI surpasses PLAD by 0.29 CD, whereas at 10% data, SIRI

	CD (↓)	N. Prim. (↓)	N. ops. (↓)
CSG-Stump 32	1.90	19.03	5.95
CSG-Stump 256	1.22	154.47	52.85
CSG-Stump 256 (cs)	0.78	191.38	72.52
SIRI	1.101	3.90	2.90
SIRI + TTR	0.83	8.47	7.42

Table 4.2: SIRI outperforms CSG-Stump 256 with far fewer primitives. Applying test-time rewrites to SIRI makes its performance comparable to that of class-specific (cs) CSG-Stump while remaining relatively parsimonious.

outperforms PLAD by a margin of 1.33 CD. Since PLAD relies solely on neurally-guided search to discover good programs, which is dependent on the dataset size, reducing the dataset size hurts its performance. In contrast, as SIRI employs rewriters such as *PO* and *CP* that are invariant to the training dataset size, it outperforms PLAD in low-data regimes.

4.5.3 Test-Time Rewriting

We now show how combining SIRI with additional rewriting at test-time allows performance that matches state-of-the-art methods specialized for 3D CSG reconstruction, while producing much more parsimonious programs. Specifically, we now compare SIRI against CSG-Stump [148], a state-of-the-art method with a neural architecture designed specifically for CSG reconstruction.

We train CSG-StumpNet with the author-released code on our dataset. We compare against two versions: CSG-Stump 32 with 32 intersection and union nodes and CSG-Stump 256 with 256 intersection and union nodes. Since the authors originally trained their model independently for each class, we also compare against a class-specific (cs) version of CSG-Stump 256, where we use pretrained class-specific models released by the authors.

We show our results in Table 4.2. We see that SIRI achieves 0.1 lower CD than CSG-Stump 256, despite being domain agnostic. More importantly, it achieves this with a fraction of the primitives and operations. Secondly, when accompanied by test-time rewrites, SIRI achieves similar CD to CSG-Stump 256 (cs), which has models trained *individually* for each class. SIRI achieves this while having an order of magnitude fewer primitives and operators (yielding more interpretable and editable programs). In Figure 4.1, we visualize the difference in inferred program size by rendering their executed shapes with colored primitives.

As the programs inferred by SIRI are parsimonious, applying TTR to the inferred programs takes only 14.6 seconds per shape on average. In contrast, the over-parameterized programs inferred by CSG-Stump are not amenable to fast test-time optimization (see Appendix B). Instead, prior work [215, 218] fine-tunes

Figure 4.7: We present qualitative examples of our method and PLAD [70]. SIRI outperforms PLAD and test-time rewriting improves it further.

the network itself for each test shape, which, for CSG-Stump, requires ~ 30 minutes per shape [218]. Moreover, while network fine-tuning can increase reconstruction accuracy, the inferred programs remain incomprehensibly large.

Test-time rewrites are beneficial for PLAD inferred programs as well. However, we find it best to both (i) train with rewriters and (ii) use them at inference time. We compare test-time rewrites on models trained with PLAD and SIRI and report the results in Table 4.3. For both 3D CSG and ShapeAssembly, using test-time rewrites on SIRI is more beneficial than using them on PLAD. Apart from yielding better initialization for the inferred programs, training with SIRI also equips the *CG* rewriter with a program cache filled with useful sub-expressions; this cache bolsters *CG*'s efficacy at test-time rewriting. Note that SIRI + TTR programs have only a marginal increase in length over PLAD + TTR.

As described in Section 4.3.3, we interleave the application of our three rewriters for test-time rewriting, allowing changes to both the structure and continuous parameters of the program. In Table 4.4, we evaluate the impact of each individual rewriter. Both *PO* and *CG* improve upon the program inferred by beam search while taking only a few seconds. Combining them further improves performance while keeping the programs relatively parsimonious.

	3D CSG		ShapeAssembly	
	CD	Length	CD	Length
PLAD + TTR	1.13	15.80	1.66	8.78
SIRI + TTR	0.83	15.96	1.46	8.80

Table 4.3: Using test-time rewrites with SIRI is superior to using it with PLAD across domains.

	Search	only <i>PO</i>	only <i>CP</i>	only <i>CG</i>	1-TTR	3-TTR
IoU	76.8	81.6	76.8	81.98	87.7	90.5
Length	6.81	6.81	6.62	14.6	13.52	15.95
Time (s)	1.44	1.54	0.12	2.81	4.6	14.6

Table 4.4: Applying only a single rewriter during test time, though beneficial, has limited value. Interleaving the rewriters produces a larger improvement. Here, n -TTR denotes interleaved application of each rewriter n times.

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter addressed the *acquisition* challenge for symbolic geometry: inferring structured, executable programs from visual observations without paired (input, program) supervision. We introduced *Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection* (SIRI, a framework that improves unsupervised visual program inference by intermittently rewriting predicted programs and reinjecting the improved results into training. We also developed a small family of rewrite operators—parameter optimization, code pruning, and code grafting—that capture domain knowledge as local program transformations.

A key outcome is that the *tooling* is largely domain-agnostic. The same rewrite family can be instantiated across multiple 2D and 3D shape-program DSLs, and consistently improves over bootstrapped learning baselines that either ignore rewriting or apply it naively. In addition, we showed that rewriting remains useful after training: a simple test-time rewriting (TTR) procedure further refines predicted programs. Together, SIRI + TTR matches or exceeds the reconstruction quality of specialized neural VPI architectures for 2D/3D CSG, while producing substantially more parsimonious programs.

These results suggest a practical recipe for acquisition: combine a general learning loop with lightweight, domain-informed rewriting that repairs, simplifies, and recombines predicted structure. At the thesis level, SIRI is the first example of *in-domain synthetic supervision*: the symbolic language is not only the output space, but also a source of training signal through its executor and rewrite operations. The next chapter keeps this source of supervision but changes the acquisition target. Rather than inferring a full executable program for every input, Pattern Analogies uses a pattern DSL to synthesize edit demonstrations for raw pattern images, showing that in-domain synthetic supervision can also support structure-aware manipulation when full program recovery is unnecessary or impractical.

CHAPTER 5

ACQUISITION VIA IN-DOMAIN SYNTHETIC SUPERVISION: PATTERN ANALOGIES

Pattern Analogies: Learning to Perform Programmatic Image Edits by Analogy

Figure 5.1: We introduce a system for making *programmatic* edits on pattern images without inferring their underlying programs.

5.1 In-Domain Synthetic Supervision for Pattern Interaction

This chapter returns to the dissertation’s central problem: acquiring symbolic geometry without paired symbolic annotations. The thesis begins from settings where the available input is an unstructured measurement, a generated or raw 3D asset, an image, a language request, or another weak signal, while the desired output is structure that exposes meaningful parts, operations, parameters, or constraints. In earlier chapters, this meant acquiring an editing program from language or an executable visual program from a target shape. Here, the input is a raw pattern image whose organization is visible but not explicitly named: repetition, layout, color variation, and motif placement are present in the pixels, but the programmatic handles that would make them easy to edit are not.

Within the thesis taxonomy, Pattern Analogies is the second example of in-domain synthetic supervision. Chapter 3 used foundation-model priors to propose symbolic edit structure, and Chapter 4 used SIRI / Code

Rewriting Families to improve inferred symbolic programs without ground-truth labels. This chapter uses a different source of in-domain supervision: sampled edits inside a symbolic pattern language. By editing pairs of synthetic SPLITWEAVE programs in the same way, we obtain analogical quartets (A, A', B, B') that demonstrate how a structural transformation should transfer from one pattern instance to another.

The acquisition target is correspondingly different from classic visual program inference. We do not ask the system to recover the full hidden program for a real pattern B . For real-world artist-authored patterns, that program may be ill-defined, partly non-parametric, or far more detailed than is needed for the edit. Instead, the goal is to acquire a structurally edited artifact: B' , an image that applies the programmatic change demonstrated by (A, A') to the target pattern B while preserving the rest of B 's organization. The system therefore learns to acquire the effect of a symbolic transformation on an unstructured input, rather than to acquire a complete symbolic reconstruction of that input.

This distinction is important for the thesis because it broadens what annotation-free acquisition can support. Symbolic structure is useful not only when it is recovered as an explicit program, but also when it provides the training signal and interaction vocabulary for manipulating non-symbolic artifacts. By leveraging how instances in a domain map to one another under valid programmatic edits, the system turns analogy into a flexible form of interaction: users specify intent through a simple before/after example, and the learned model carries that structural relationship to a more complex real pattern. The chapter therefore shows how domain structure can enable new interfaces even when full symbolic reconstruction is unnecessary or impractical.

5.2 Introduction

Visual pattern designs enhance digital media such as presentations, website themes, and user interfaces, and they are woven into the physical world through textiles, wallpapers, and product designs like hardware covers. Given the ubiquity of patterns, methods for editing them are essential: designers should be able to quickly experiment with variations, customize designs to meet specific needs, and adapt existing patterns to align with evolving trends.

Editing pattern images is not straightforward, as patterns are inherently structured, defined by rules that govern their layout and composition: tiling patterns adhere to principles of alignment and repetition (see Figure 5.1: top left), while retro-style designs rely on spatial divisions and fills (see Figure 5.1: bottom center). The edits that designers desire often aim to adjust these underlying organizational rules rather than make superficial, pixel-level changes. We refer to such edits as *programmatic* edits, requiring manipulation of the underlying program that defines a pattern's structure.

One strategy for enabling such programmatic edits is visual program inference (VPI) [110, 34, 164], where a program that replicates an image is automatically inferred, allowing users to modify the image by adjusting program parameters. However, applying VPI to patterns presents two obstacles. First, VPI attempts to infer a program that fully replicates a pattern, which can be challenging as patterns are often *semi-parametric*, blending rule-based logic with non-parametric components. For instance, the layout of elements in a tiling pattern may be rule-based, but the elements themselves may not be. Second, editing with an inferred program can be cumbersome, as inferred programs are often poorly structured, with many unlabeled parameters, making them difficult to interpret. Consequently, VPI not only solves a more complex problem than necessary but also makes editing more challenging.

Can we perform programmatic edits without inferring the underlying program? Doing so requires the ability to *express* and *execute* the edit—both without direct access to the program’s parameters. To express a programmatic edit, it’s crucial to specify both *which* underlying parameter(s) to change and *how* to modify them. We draw inspiration from how humans communicate transformations: through analogies. By providing a pair of simple example patterns (A, A') that illustrate the desired change, users can intuitively convey both aspects of the edit. To execute these edits, we employ a learning-based conditional generative model. Given a pair of simple patterns (A, A') and a complex target pattern B , our system generates B' , an edited version of B which performs the transformation demonstrated between A and A' while preserving B ’s other structural features. Crucially, A does not need to replicate or even be similar to B —it only needs to demonstrate *which* property to edit and how. Thus, specifying A is a much easier task than solving VPI. While prior works [174, 188, 7] have applied analogical editing to image manipulation, they focus primarily on appearance modifications. In contrast, our approach is the first to use analogies for *programmatic*, structure-aware edits. Figure 5.1 (left) shows examples of analogical editing on complex, real-world patterns.

To make our approach possible, we introduce SPLITWEAVE: a domain-specific language (DSL) for crafting visual patterns. SPLITWEAVE serves two purposes in our method. First, it enables parametric definition of input pairs (A, A'), allowing users to guide transformations in (B, B') as if the underlying program for B were accessible. In Figure 5.1 (right), modifying the SPLITWEAVE program for A' produces corresponding changes in B' . Second, SPLITWEAVE supports the creation of large-scale synthetic training data. We develop program samplers that generate high-quality patterns in two common styles: tiling-based designs with repeating elements and color field patterns characterized by splitting the canvas into intricate colored regions. Training a model for analogical editing requires a dataset of quartets (A, A', B, B'). By applying identical programmatic edits to the SPLITWEAVE programs for both A and B to produce A' and B' , we ensure that the transformation from A to A' mirrors that from B to B' . This approach allows us to generate a diverse dataset of analogical quartets. Models trained on this dataset generalize effectively to real-world patterns within

these styles and even extend to related styles.

We use this synthetic dataset to train a novel diffusion-based conditional generative model for executing analogical edits. Our model directly generates edited patterns B' by conditioning on visual features extracted from input patterns (A, A', B) . Existing image-conditioned diffusion models [206, 152] prove ineffective, as they fail to interpret the input analogies accurately and neglect fine details. To address these issues, we incorporate architectural enhancements that enable our model, `TriFUSER`, to effectively perform analogical edits. With these improvements, `TriFUSER` surpasses prior architectures for analogical editing when applied to pattern images.

To evaluate our method, we curated a test set of 50 patterns from Adobe Stock spanning 7 distinct styles. A perceptual study on this dataset reveals that participants consistently prefer edits by `TriFUSER` over those produced by recent training-free and training-based analogical editing methods. Despite training only on two of these styles, our model successfully generalizes to the remaining five, which were unseen during training. On a synthetic validation set with ground-truth analogical edits, our model achieves higher structural and perceptual similarity to the ground truth than prior methods. Finally, we showcase two compelling applications of our approach: mixing attributes of different patterns and transferring pattern animations.

In summary, our contributions are as follows:

1. A novel framework for performing *programmatic* edits to pattern images without requiring program inference, leveraging analogies to specify and apply edits.
2. `SPLITWEAVE`, a DSL for crafting a diverse range of visual patterns, designed to support both parametric control and synthetic dataset generation.
3. A procedure for generating synthetic analogical quartets, enabling editing of *in-the-wild* patterns.
4. `TriFUSER`, a diffusion-based conditional generative model that achieves high fidelity in analogical edits, surpassing prior techniques in both analogical fidelity and generation quality.

5.3 Task-Specific Positioning

Pattern Analogies is related to visual program inference, but it deliberately does not try to infer a full program for every real pattern. Prior VPI work can enable programmatic editing when a faithful and interpretable program is available [34, 164, 70], and recent systems have explored edit-specific or semantically meaningful controls [43, 54, 24, 69, 71]. For real pattern images, however, full program inference is often harder than the edit itself because patterns may mix rule-based layout with non-parametric motifs, textures, or

Figure 5.2: **Overview:** To create high-quality visual patterns, we introduce a custom DSL called SPLITWEAVE. Pairs of SPLITWEAVE programs (A, B) are then jointly edited to create analogical quartets. This synthetic dataset is then used to train TRIFUSER, a neural network for analogical pattern editing.

artist-authored details.

The chapter therefore uses a DSL as a source of edit demonstrations rather than as a required reconstruction target. Pattern and texture DSLs show how compact programs can generate rich visual structure [156, 53, 105, 142]. Here, the DSL is designed to sample analogical quartets that teach programmatic transformations. This connects to a long line of analogy-based visual editing [60, 188, 52, 174, 7], while shifting the emphasis from appearance transfer to structure-aware edits.

5.4 Method

Our objective is to enable programmatic edits of 2D visual patterns without inferring their underlying programs. Instead, we propose an alternative that uses analogies to *express* desired edits and a conditional generative model to *execute* them. Formally, given two source patterns A and A' that demonstrate a desired edit, along with a target pattern B , our goal is to generate an edited target pattern B' that applies this edit to B . This task is defined as learning a mapping $f(A, A', B) \rightarrow B'$, where A, A', B , and B' are 2D RGB images ($\in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3}$). To learn this mapping, we generate a large synthetic dataset of analogical pattern quartets (A, A', B, B') .

Figure 5.2 provides a schematic overview of our approach. First, in Section 5.4.1 we introduce SPLITWEAVE, a Domain-Specific Language (DSL) that enables the creation and manipulation of various kinds of patterns. Section 5.4.2 describes our approach for sampling analogical quartets in SPLITWEAVE to create the synthetic training data. Finally, in Section 5.4.3, we present TRIFUSER, a conditional generative model that learns to

Figure 5.3: (left) Custom program samplers for two pattern styles. Our samplers produce diverse and high-quality patterns, enabling generalization to real-world patterns. (right) We create synthetic analogical quartets (A, A', B, B') with consistent edits between A and B pairs, providing data for training an analogical editing model.

execute analogical edits.

5.4.1 A Language for Visual Patterns

To enable programmatic edits without program inference, our approach requires two core capabilities: (a) generating a large, high-quality synthetic dataset essential for training models to reliably *execute* analogical edits, and (b) the ability to create and parametrically control analogy inputs at test time to effectively *express* desired edits. Existing pattern generation tools are insufficient for these needs, as they are either limited to narrow pattern domains [156] or demand intense coding effort to produce diverse, high-quality patterns [105, 114]. To address these limitations, we introduce `SPLITWEAVE`, a DSL designed specifically to support analogical transformations in visual patterns. `SPLITWEAVE` combines abstractions for pattern synthesis with a node-based visual programming interface (see Appendix C), enabling efficient generation of high-quality synthetic patterns for training while allowing flexible, precise pattern manipulation to define analogy inputs at test time.

`SPLITWEAVE` uses three types of operations for structured pattern creation: (1) *Canvas Fragmentation*, which allows structured divisions of the canvas, such as brick-like or voronoi splits; (2) *Fragment ID-Aware Operations*, enabling transformations that vary across fragments (e.g., scaling alternating rows or columns) to support spatial variability in non-stationary pattern designs; and (3) various *SVG Operators* for outlining, coloring, and compositing. Together, these operations enable efficient creation of patterns with complex structure and visual variety. Figure 5.2 (left) illustrates these capabilities in a `SPLITWEAVE` program for generating a tiling pattern design.

Our goal is to generate high-quality synthetic patterns using `SPLITWEAVE` that enable trained editing

Figure 5.4: (Left) TRIFUSER is a latent diffusion model conditioned on patch-wise tokens of the input images (A, A', B) to generate the analogically edited pattern B' . (Right) To achieve high-quality edits, we enrich these tokens by fusing multi-level features from multiple encoders, followed by a 3D positional encoding: 2D to specify spatial locations and 1D to specify the token’s source (A, A' or B).

models to generalize well to real-world patterns. Naive sampling from the DSL grammar often leads to overly complex or incoherent patterns, limiting their effectiveness in model training. Instead, we draw inspiration from recent advances in fields such as geometric problem solving [185] and abstract reasoning [94], where tailored data generators have proven essential for tackling complex tasks. Following a similar approach, we design custom program samplers for two versatile and widely-used pattern styles. The first, *Motif Tiling Patterns (MTP)*, consists of compositions based on repeated *Tile* elements. These patterns exhibit controlled variations in tile properties across the canvas (e.g. orientation, color, and scale), creating visually cohesive yet richly diverse structures. The second, *Split-Filling Patterns (SFP)*, is generated by dividing the canvas into ordered fragments, applying region-specific coloring and transformations based on fragment IDs. Both pattern styles are common in digital design and support a wide range of programmatic variations, making them particularly suited for analogical editing tasks. Example patterns generated by our program samplers are shown in Figure 5.3; additional implementation details are in Appendix C.

5.4.2 Sampling Analogical Quartets

With the ability to generate diverse synthetic patterns using SPLITWEAVE (Section 5.4.1), our goal is now to construct analogical pattern quartets (A, A', B, B') . Each pattern image in a quartet is generated by a SPLITWEAVE program z . These quartets serve as structured training data for editing models, allowing them to learn consistent transformations that can generalize across different pattern domains.

Analogies in our framework are grounded in Structure Mapping Theory [48], which defines analogies as mappings of relational structure from a base to a target domain. We designate (A, A') as the base and (B, B') as the target, with the requirement that the relationship R between program pairs $(z_A, z_{A'})$ and $(z_B, z_{B'})$ remains consistent:

$$R(z_A, z_{A'}) = R(z_B, z_{B'}). \quad (5.1)$$

Rather than focusing on visual similarity between the patterns (A, A') themselves, this program-level analogy allows us to generate quartets with transformations that affect the underlying program, facilitating *programmatically* edits.

To construct these analogical quartets, we use a program sampler along with a predefined set of editing operators E . For each quartet, we begin by sampling an edit $e \in E$, followed by sampling initial programs z_A and z_B that are compatible with e . Applying e to both z_A and z_B yields transformed programs $z_{A'}$ and $z_{B'}$. By using identical transformations across domains, we ensure a consistent “edit relation” across the quartet, satisfying Equation 5.1 by construction. In Figure 5.3, we illustrate examples of synthetic analogical quartets generated using this method, demonstrating consistent transformations between (A, A') and (B, B') .

Edit Operators E . We focus on edits targeting specific sub-parts of the program. Specifically, we consider three types of edits: *insertion*, *removal*, and *replacement* of sub-programs. For example, an edit operator might *replace* the sub-program responsible for splitting the canvas, while other edits may *insert* or *remove* tiles within the pattern. Appendix C provides additional details.

5.4.3 Learning an Analogical Editor

Our goal is to train a model on the synthetic data that is capable of performing analogical edits on real, *in-the-wild* patterns. Specifically, we aim to generate the target pattern B' from an input triplet (A, A', B) . This approach allows users to demonstrate desired edits with a simple pattern pair (A, A') , which the model then applies to a complex pattern B to produce B' . Given the success of Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) in various generative modeling tasks [152], we chose to adapt an LDM for our task as well. We propose **TRIFUSER**, a latent diffusion model (LDM) for analogical editing (Figure 5.4). We provide a brief overview of LDMs to provide context before detailing **TRIFUSER**’s modifications for analogical editing.

Preliminaries: Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPMs) [62] transform random noise into structured data via reverse diffusion steps guided with a conditioning embedding $c(y)$ (often derived from text). Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) extend DDPMs by mapping data to a lower-dimensional latent space via an encoder. During training, a UNet model [154] learns to remove noise introduced into the latents. During inference, a latent sampled from a normal distribution is iteratively denoised by the model to yield a clean latent. Finally, the clean latent is decoded to generate the output image. Please refer to [208] for a more thorough overview. For analogical editing we adapt an Image Variation (IM) model [206], which uses patch-wise image tokens extracted using a text-image encoder [146] as the conditioning embedding $c(y)$.

The simplest adaptation of an IM model to our task is to generate B' conditioned on image tokens from all three input images, concatenated as $C = c(A) \parallel c(A') \parallel c(B)$, where \parallel denotes token-wise concatenation.

This approach, however, suffers from three drawbacks: *Token Entanglement*, *Semantic Bias*, and *Detail Erosion*. We discuss each of these issues briefly, along with our solutions.

Detail Erosion: Despite using patch-wise tokens, the extracted features lack the fine-grained information needed to retain key aspects of B in the generated pattern B' . Consequently, the model often struggles to preserve elements like tile textures. To address this problem, we combine features from both the first and last layers of the feature encoder:

$$C_{hl}(P) = \text{Linear}(\text{LN}(c_{high}(P)) \cdot \text{LN}(c_{low}(P))), \quad (5.2)$$

where LN is layer normalization, \cdot denotes channel-wise concatenation, P is an input pattern, and Linear is a linear projection layer that fuses low- and high-level features.

Semantic Bias: Image variation models typically use feature extractors such as CLIP [146], which are trained to align image embeddings with corresponding text embeddings. Such embeddings emphasize high-level semantics but lack spatial and fine-grained visual details. Combining these embeddings with features from text-free, self-supervised extractors, such as DiNO [20], has been shown to improve performance in downstream tasks [183, 66]. For our task, a similar approach—combining features from both text-image (m_1) and self-supervised (m_2) feature extractors—significantly enhances generation quality. The extracted features are fused as follows:

$$C_{mix}(P) = \text{Mixer}(C_{hl}^{m_1}(P) \cdot C_{hl}^{m_2}(P)), \quad (5.3)$$

where Mixer is a two-layer MLP that integrates features from the two extractors.

Token Entanglement: To successfully perform an analogical edit, for each patch-level feature token, the model must be able to identify to which source image (A , A' , or B) that patch belongs as well as the 2D position of the patch within that image. Without these distinctions, the model often fails to identify the pattern to edit (i.e., B) and to recognize the desired edit from (A, A'). To address this problem, we introduce 3D positional encodings: two dimensions for spatial location within each pattern and one dimension for the source image. These encodings are applied to the extracted embeddings, yielding:

$$C^\Omega = C_{PE}(A) \parallel C_{PE}(A') \parallel C_{PE}(B), \quad (5.4)$$

$$C_{PE}(P)^{xy} = C_{mix}(P)^{xy} + PE(t_P, x, y), \quad (5.5)$$

where t_P is a one-hot vector encoding which input image a token comes from and $PE(t_P, x, y)$ positionally encodes both spatial and source information for each token.

As we demonstrate in Section 7.5.2, conditioning on C^Ω instead of C significantly enhances the quality of

Figure 5.5: (left) Qualitative comparison between patterns generated by our model, `TRIFUSER`, and the baselines. `TRIFUSER` generates higher quality patterns with greater fidelity to the input analogy. (right) `TRIFUSER` effectively edits patterns from novel pattern styles not present in the training dataset, showing a noteworthy ability to generalize beyond its training distribution.

patterns generated by `TRIFUSER`. Our adapted architecture, shown in Figure 5.4, integrates the modifications described above to effectively address the described drawbacks. Note that this architecture is designed for general analogical editing, not just pattern editing. To enhance generalizability to real-world patterns, we initialize `TRIFUSER` with an existing pretrained IM model [206], and fine-tune only the denoising UNet and the projection layers in our feature extractor.

5.5 Experiments

In this section, we evaluate our approach along three directions: (1) the effectiveness of `TRIFUSER` at performing analogical edits on complex, real-world patterns, emphasizing how our synthetic data enables editing of in-the-wild pattern images; (2) the ability of `TRIFUSER` to support *programmatic*, structure-preserving edits without explicit program inference; and (3) the impact of architectural modifications introduced in `TRIFUSER` on the quality of generated patterns. We conduct a human perceptual study, quantitative assessments, and qualitative comparisons to demonstrate our system’s ability to perform high-quality analogical edits across a range of pattern types.

5.5.1 Experiment Design

Datasets: We generate a large synthetic dataset of analogical quartets, i.e., pairs of analogical patterns (A, A', B, B') , using the `SPLITWEAVE` program samplers introduced in Section 5.4.1. This synthetic dataset

contains approximately 1 million samples covering two pattern styles, namely Split-Filling Patterns (SFP) and Motif Tiling Patterns (MTP) (cf. Section 5.4.1). For MTP patterns, we synthesize 100k distinct tiles using the LayerDiffuse [221] model, guided by text prompts derived from WordNet [121] noun synsets. Additionally, we construct a synthetic test set with 1000 analogical quartets to evaluate model performance on unseen synthetic data. Further details on dataset construction are provided in Appendix C.

To assess TRIFUSER on real-world patterns, we curate a test dataset of 50 patterns created by professional artists and sourced from Adobe Stock. This dataset spans seven distinct sub-domains of 2D patterns, representing a range of pattern styles. These styles include MTP and SFP patterns as well as previously unseen pattern styles such as Memphis-style, geometric, and digital textile patterns. Each pattern is annotated with a desired edit, and we use SPLITWEAVE to generate a pair of simpler patterns (A, A') demonstrating this edit. This test set provides a challenging benchmark to evaluate TRIFUSER’s generalization to diverse, real-world editing tasks.

Training details: We fine-tune a pre-trained diffusion model using our synthetic dataset of analogical quartets, as described in the previous section. We initialize our model with Versatile-Diffusion’s Image Variation model [206]. We use SigLIP [220] as our text-image feature encoder and DiNOv2 [134] for self-supervised features. We fine-tune the model on 8 A100 GPUs using a batch size of 224 for ~ 65 epochs over 7 days. During inference, we generate each edited pattern B' with typical diffusion parameter settings such as a classifier-free guidance weight of 7.5 and 50 denoising steps.

5.5.2 Analogical Editing Baselines

To evaluate the analogical editing capability of TRIFUSER, we compare it to three baseline methods, each representing a leading approach for analogical image editing.

First, we consider *training-free editors* and *latent arithmetic editors*. Training-free editors repurpose pre-trained diffusion models to perform analogical edits without additional training [188, 52], leveraging the rich representations learned by diffusion models for editing. In this category, we compare against *Analogist* [52], the current state-of-the-art method. Latent arithmetic editors, on the other hand, rely on transformations in a learned latent space to infer analogical modifications [147, 180]. Note that these approaches only require samples from the target domain, not analogical training pairs. We implement a baseline for this method by fine-tuning a naive Image Variation model [206] on our synthetic dataset to learn a generative latent embedding space of patterns. At inference, analogical edits are generated using latent arithmetic: given patterns A, A' , and B , we condition the generation of B' on $E(B) + E(A') - E(A)$. We refer to this baseline as *LatentMod*.

	Preference Rate
TRIFUSER vs. <i>Analogist</i>	89.24%
TRIFUSER vs. <i>LatentMod</i>	80.59%
TRIFUSER vs. <i>Inpainter</i>	72.05%

Table 5.1: Results of a two-alternative forced-choice perceptual study comparing our model (TRIFUSER) against three baselines. Ours is preferred in the overwhelming majority of judgments.

Finally, we consider *analogy-conditioned generative editors*, where models are explicitly trained on analogical data to learn analogical transformations [174]. This category includes our proposed TRIFUSER as well. Image Brush, the state-of-the-art method, fine-tunes a diffusion inpainting model for analogical editing with multi-modal conditioning. Since code for Image Brush is unavailable, we implement a similar baseline by fine-tuning a Stable Diffusion inpainting model. This model, which we term *Inpainter*, performs analogical editing by inpainting the lower-left quadrant of a 2×2 analogy grid containing (A, A', B) and conditioned on a fixed text template.

5.5.3 Editing Real-World Patterns

To evaluate TRIFUSER’s real-world analogical editing capabilities, we conducted a human preference study on the curated test set of Adobe Stock patterns.

We performed a two-alternative forced-choice perceptual study comparing TRIFUSER with baseline methods on all 50 entries in the test set. Each method generates $k = 9$ outputs for each input tuple, and we select the best one based on visual inspection. Participants were shown edited patterns generated by two different methods along with the input patterns (A, A', B) and instructed to select the edit that best preserved the analogical relationship and exhibited higher image quality. We recruited 42 participants for the study, resulting in a total of 1720 judgments.

Table 5.1 presents the results, showing that TRIFUSER was preferred over both *Analogist* and *LatentMod*. Due to the domain gap between the training data of the underlying model [152] and pattern images, *Analogist* fails to interpret and edit pattern images. Meanwhile, *LatentMod* fails to perform reasonable edits as the embedding space lacks the low-level details necessary for *grammatical* edits. While these baselines perform adequately on stylistic edits, they are unsuitable for *grammatical* editing. When compared to *Inpainter*, TRIFUSER was favored in 72.05% of comparisons. Both methods benefit from training on analogical quartets, yet *Inpainter* sacrifices pattern quality as it generates the edited pattern in only a quarter of the full canvas resolution.

Figure 5.5 shows examples of pattern edits generated by TRIFUSER and the baselines, with our model consistently delivering superior results. In Figure 5.5, we show examples of TRIFUSER’s edits on out-of-

	DSIM (↓)	DISTS (↓)	LPIPS (↓)	SSIM (↑)
<i>Analogist</i>	0.496	0.432	0.697	0.494
<i>LatentMod</i>	0.242	0.320	0.613	0.502
<i>Inpainter</i>	0.092	0.256	0.371	0.713
TRIFUSER	0.074	0.184	0.304	0.704

Table 5.2: Quantitative evaluation on the synthetic validation set shows that TRIFUSER generates patterns with higher perceptual similarity to the ground truth than the baselines.

distribution pattern styles not present in the training set. These results suggest that our synthetic training data enables manipulation of real-world patterns, even extending to certain untrained pattern styles.

5.5.4 Editing Synthetic Patterns

Next, we evaluate TRIFUSER’s ability to perform *programmatic* edits on the synthetic validation set, which contains ground truth patterns B' . Ideally, this would involve verifying that the underlying program $z_{\hat{B}'}$ of the generated pattern reflects the same transformation from z_B as that between z_A and z'_A . However, this would require visual program inference on \hat{B}' , which is infeasible. Instead, we approximate this criterion by comparing the program outputs \hat{B}' and B' to see if the visual results align with the intended transformation. To quantify this alignment, we use perceptual metrics—DSim [40], DIST [29] and LPIPS [222]—along with SSIM to capture pixel-level structural similarity.

Note that analogies can have multiple valid interpretations, and even a single interpretation may yield several visually related variations. To account for this multiplicity, we generate $k = 5$ output patterns for each input set (A, A', B) and select the one that maximizes each metric. In other words, we evaluate whether at least one generated output aligns with the intended target.

Table 5.2 shows the results of this experiment. First, we note that TRIFUSER outperforms all baselines across all perceptual metrics. These metrics capture different aspects of perceptual similarity [40], and superior performance across all of them suggests a comprehensive improvement. Second, we observe that the analogy-conditioned generative editors (*Inpainter* & TRIFUSER) surpass both the training-free and latent modification editors. Interestingly, *Inpainter* achieves slightly higher SSIM scores than TRIFUSER, suggesting that future methods combining elements of both models might be fruitful.

5.5.5 TRIFUSER Ablation

To evaluate the contributions of each model component introduced in Section 5.4.3, we conduct a subtractive analysis on the synthetic validation set, using the same perceptual and structural metrics as above. For this

	DSIM (↓)	DISTS (↓)	LPIPS (↓)	SSIM (↑)
TRIFUSER	0.074	0.184	0.304	0.704
- Pos. Enc.	0.147	0.239	0.383	0.659
- Lower	0.087	0.196	0.335	0.652
- Mix	0.098	0.210	0.345	0.682
Base [206]	0.585	0.460	0.815	0.435

Table 5.3: Subtractive ablation study on TRIFUSER shows that removing any component (see Section 5.4.3) degrades performance, and that removing all components (Base) results in a sharp decline.

ablation study, we remove each component one at a time and measure the resulting performance, as reported in Table 5.3. The results demonstrate that removing any single modification leads to a performance drop, with the removal of 3D positional encoding causing the most severe degradation. This is understandable: without 3D positional encoding, the network often fails to accurately identify which pattern to edit. For comparison, we also include results from the original Image Variation model [206] trained without any modifications (Base). As expected, this model performs poorly, underscoring the importance of our modifications in achieving high-quality analogical edits.

5.6 Application

The ability to edit patterns without requiring program inference unlocks new creative possibilities. We demonstrate two practical applications of analogical pattern editing:

Pattern Mixing: Figure 5.6 shows an example of using our method to *mix* elements of two real-world patterns X and Y , allowing the user to create unique, hybrid designs. The *Mix* operator is implemented by using a synthetic pair (A, A') to create a variant X' of X and then using the pair (X, X') to specify an edit to Y : $Mix(X, Y) = f(X, X', Y)$, where $X' = f(A, A', X)$. Appendix C provides additional details.

Animation Transfer: TRIFUSER can also be used to create animated sequences of edited patterns. By leveraging parametric SPLITWEAVE programs, users can generate animations for simple patterns and then apply these animations to complex patterns with no additional effort. Appendix C describes the accompanying video examples.

5.7 Conclusion

This chapter addressed the *manipulation* challenge for symbolic geometry through the lens of visual patterns: enabling users to perform *programmatic*, structure-aware edits without writing or even recovering the underlying program. Our central idea is analogy-based editing: users *express* intent by providing a

Figure 5.6: Our model helps users mix elements of different real-world patterns together, accelerating design exploration.

simple before/after demonstration, and a learned conditional generative model *executes* the corresponding structural transformation on a target pattern. Empirically, this interface supports edits that modify repetition, arrangement, and motif-level structure—not just appearance or style.

Technically, our system couples a symbolic generator with a learned executor. We introduced `SPLITWEAVE`, a pattern DSL that represents common structural motifs and enables scalable synthesis of diverse training data. Together with our procedure for sampling analogical quartets, `SPLITWEAVE` enables a large, high-quality dataset without manual annotation. On top of this data, we presented `TRIFUSER`, an LDM architecture and training design tailored to analogy-driven edits, mitigating failure modes that arise when naively deploying diffusion models for structured transformations. Across real, artist-sourced patterns, `TRIFUSER` produces higher-fidelity edits than baselines and generalizes to novel pattern styles beyond its training distribution.

Two broader lessons connect this chapter to the thesis themes. First, symbolic structure can support acquisition even when the final output is not an explicit recovered program: here, `SPLITWEAVE` provides the edit relations used to train a model that acquires structurally edited artifacts from raw pattern images. Second, the chapter demonstrates a practical form of in-domain synthetic supervision: when real symbolic annotations are scarce, a DSL can supply controllable, scalable demonstrations of how instances in the domain map to one another under valid transformations.

This concludes the thesis’s two examples of in-domain synthetic supervision. The next chapter turns to a different source of acquisition signal: direct optimization. Rather than learning from synthetic edit or rewrite examples, `MiGumi` fits fabrication-aware symbolic geometry by optimizing program parameters against millability and coupling objectives.

CHAPTER 6

ACQUISITION VIA DIRECT OPTIMIZATION: MiGUMI

MiGUMI: Making Tightly Coupled Integral Joints Millable

Figure 6.1: We present a method for fabricating integral joints using standard CNC machines. Nonzero-radius milling tools cannot produce sharp internal corners, and naively milling traditional designs leads to geometric deviations that make joints unassemblable. We introduce an optimization that adjusts geometry to yield millable, tightly coupled joints, and validate our approach on a dataset of 30 traditional designs.

6.1 Direct Optimization for Millable Kigumi

This chapter returns to the dissertation’s central problem: acquiring symbolic geometry without paired symbolic annotations. Across the thesis, the input is often an unstructured measurement or weak geometric signal, such as a mesh, point cloud, generated or raw 3D asset, language request, or other non-symbolic description. The goal is not merely to reconstruct the observed surface, but to recover a symbolic form whose parts, parameters, operations, and constraints make the geometry useful for editing, fabrication, or reuse.

The previous chapters developed two sources of acquisition signal. Chapter 3 used foundation-model priors to propose symbolic structure when paired labels were unavailable, while Chapters 4 and 5 used

in-domain synthetic supervision generated from the symbolic representation itself. This chapter begins the thesis’s third route: direct optimization. Rather than training a predictor from examples, direct optimization fits symbolic parameters directly against geometric, physical, or task-specific objectives.

MiGumi is the first direct-optimization example. Its acquisition target is specific: given hand-authored UNMILLABLE KIGUMI designs, authored under an idealized zero-radius milling tool, acquire MILLABLE KIGUMI joint designs that can be fabricated with a real nonzero-radius CNC tool while preserving tight surface coupling. The input already has some symbolic structure, but it is not yet the symbolic structure needed by the fabrication task. The optimization therefore converts an idealized, unmillable design into a fabrication-aware symbolic program whose geometry remains functional after milling artifacts are accounted for.

This chapter matters beyond the original paper because it shows that direct optimization is not just an optimization trick applied after a representation has been chosen. It is a co-design problem between representation and acquisition procedure. MILLABLE EXTRUSION GEOMETRY exposes the parameters that milling changes; the surface and milling-path losses measure the functional structure that must be preserved; and the staged optimization procedure uses both to acquire a usable symbolic object. MiGumi therefore illustrates a broader thesis theme: symbolic representations should be designed not only for expression, but also for how their structure can be recovered.

The source material for this chapter is staged in `papers/migumi/`.

6.2 Introduction

Integral joints (referred to as *Kigumi* in Japanese) are assembled without glue, nails, or screws. Such joints have long been valued for their strength, reusability, and elegance. Developed across diverse woodworking traditions [233], they achieve mechanical function through tightly mating surfaces that constrain motion and transfer load. This property enables a rich design vocabulary, from sliding locks to hidden seams and stress-distributing features. Yet despite their utility, integral joints remain rare in modern manufacturing workflows. Producing them by hand requires high precision, specialized tools, and years of training, making them impractical in most contemporary workflows.

Three-axis CNC milling offers a compelling alternative. It is accessible, programmable, and widely used in modern woodworking. However, traditional integral joint designs contain sharp internal corners: features easily produced with hand tools but incompatible with cylindrical mill bits, which inevitably round internal corners. While such tool-induced artifacts are acceptable in many fabrication settings, integral joints are an exception. Their function depends entirely on tight surface contact between mating parts. Even small rounding errors can introduce gaps or overlaps that disrupt alignment, compromise fit, and in many cases,

make assembly physically impossible.

Adapting integral-joint designs for CNC fabrication requires more than simply translating shapes into toolpaths: the geometry must be modified to anticipate milling artifacts and preserve precise contact between parts. Figure 6.2 shows this issue on a simple dovetail joint: starting from a traditional design, naive milling introduces artifacts that break tight coupling, whereas our method produces geometry that is both millable and tightly coupled. Most joints, however, are far more intricate: surfaces are often shaped by multiple milling passes from different directions, may interact with others cut on orthogonal faces, and many joints involve more than two parts (see Figure 6.1). Adapting such designs requires careful reasoning about how machining errors accumulate across interacting surfaces. We propose a tailored geometric representation and optimization procedure that accounts for these interactions and yields millable, tightly coupled joints across a broad range of joint designs.

Our first contribution is Millable Extrusion Geometry (MXG), a geometric language for parts that can be fabricated by a flat-end cylindrical milling bit. MXG models each part as a sequence of subtractions from an initial material stock (e.g., a wood block). Each subtraction operation removes a perpendicular 3D extrusion of a planar 2D shape expressed using a simple constructive solid geometry (CSG) language, and successive subtractions remove material along different extrusion directions. The representation is millable by design and parameterized by the tool radius, making it natural for analysis and mitigation of tool radius-related artifacts such as the unavoidable rounding of interior corners (cf. Figure 6.2). While MXG only covers a subset of geometry producible by CNC milling, we designed it to be expressive enough to handle large classes of integral wood joints. Its constrained structure enables key algorithmic simplifications that make our method computationally efficient.

Our second contribution is an optimization procedure based on two measures of tight coupling. The first, `SURFACE GAP`, penalizes separation between opposing surfaces to maintain contact after milling. The second, `MILLING PATH DISTANCE`, analyzes the milling path on both sides of a contact surface and constrains their closest-point distance to twice the tool radius, which complements the surface-based measure and stabilizes the optimization. Together, they provide a continuous and differentiable assessment of coupling under milling constraints, enabling robust gradient-based optimization of multi-part assemblies.

We begin with MXG programs authored in an idealized setting with zero tool radius and progressively increase this radius, adjusting the part geometry through optimization to maintain tight coupling. Because contact depends on the interaction of all parts, the optimization must be performed jointly. As we will show later, the structure of MXG and the design of our coupling metrics can be exploited to collapse the full 3D problem domain to a sparse set of planar 1D curves, which makes such an approach computationally feasible. The result is `MILLABLE KIGUMI` or `MiGUMI` joints—*millable* reinterpretations of traditional *tightly coupled*

Figure 6.2: The path toward a millable and usable dovetail joint. (a) The original joint geometry contains features that cannot be milled because they are incompatible with the CNC machine’s finite tool radius. (b) Individually adapting each part to be millable introduces overlaps that prevent successful assembly. (c) Our method jointly optimizes all contact surfaces to produce geometry that is both millable and tightly coupled.

MiGUMI integral joints.

We evaluate our method on a dataset of 30 traditional joint designs, modeled in MXG under an idealized zero-radius setting. Since no existing method directly addresses the problem of restoring tight coupling under milling constraints, we compare against two non-optimization-based variants. We show that these alternatives compromise either millability or coupling, while our approach consistently preserves both. Beyond quantitative analysis of fabrication validity, surface alignment, and geometric fidelity, we physically fabricate eight joints using a standard 3-axis CNC machine, demonstrating that our results hold in real-world settings. Finally, we show that our method enables structured design exploration under milling constraints, significantly expanding the space of tightly coupled joint geometries that can be realized with modern CNC tools.

By integrating modern fabrication technologies with traditional joinery knowledge, our research contributes to reducing manual labor in production, expanding access to advanced joint design, and supporting the continued relevance of heritage woodworking techniques in contemporary manufacturing.

In summary, our contributions are:

1. MXG, a DSL for modeling shapes as the outcome of milling operations with flat-end tools, enabling both specification of artifact-free geometry under idealized conditions and systematic control over milling-induced artifacts.
2. A differentiable optimization framework for restoring tight coupling under fabrication constraints by maximizing surface proximity and milling-path alignment between joint part MXG programs.
3. A dataset of 30 traditional joint designs, modeled in MXG, serving as a benchmark for millability-aware joint generation.

Figure 6.3: **Overview:** Our method addresses two challenges: modeling milling-induced distortions and restoring tight coupling. Section 6.4 introduces MXG, a representation that models geometry as the outcome of milling operations, exposing rounding artifacts caused by milling. Section 6.5 presents an optimization scheme that adapts joint geometry to restore coupling despite these artifacts.

6.3 Task-Specific Positioning

MiGumi builds on a domain-specific literature in integral joints and milling-constrained fabrication. Prior work on integral joints includes systems for external connectors and integral joinery, including decorative joinery and CNC-oriented joint design [210, 87, 18, 115, 176]. Related work on interlocking assemblies studies global motion constraints in furniture and puzzle-like structures [195], but tight coupling in integral joints is a different requirement: the parts must maintain precise surface contact under fabrication artifacts.

The fabrication side is similarly specific. Much CNC research focuses on toolpath generation or approximating target geometry under machine constraints [106, 226, 10, 225, 159]. Other work incorporates accessibility or fabrication constraints into broader optimization pipelines [122]. MiGumi instead treats the symbolic representation, milling process, and coupling objective as a single acquisition problem: it optimizes a millable-by-construction program so that the fabricated geometry preserves the functional contact structure of the joint.

6.4 Modeling Millable Geometry

Milling-induced corner rounding artifacts break tight coupling between parts, introducing overlaps. Preserving coupling requires anticipating where artifacts occur and adapting the design accordingly. We address this need with MILLABLE EXTRUSION GEOMETRY (MXG), a representation that models geometry as the outcome of milling operations produced by flat-end, uniform-radius tools—a common setup in CNC woodworking.

Figure 6.4: (left) Morphological opening is the canonical way to derive geometry that can be safely removed by a milling tool. Given an implicitly defined input shape f_i and a structuring element B_r representing the tool shape, the operation first applies a Minkowski subtraction (erosion, middle column) and then restores the removed volume by a subsequent addition (dilation, right column). The resulting shape excludes regions that the tool cannot reach and serves as a conservative, millable approximation of the original geometry. (right) We construct a millable extrusion by defining a 2D SDF f_i using a symbolic CSG tree, applying morphological opening to obtain a millable base region C_i^r , and extruding this region along direction \mathbf{n}_i to produce the solid volume $\overline{\mathcal{E}}_i$.

6.4.1 Preliminaries

A millable solid $P \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is represented as:

$$P = M - \bigcup_i V_i, \quad (6.1)$$

where M is the material stock and each V_i is a volume removed by a milling operation. To ensure that V_i is physically realizable, it must be expressible as a Minkowski sum¹ with the tool's swept volume. The rotational sweep of a flat-end, uniform-radius drill bit yields a cylinder. Therefore, this can be written as:

$$V_i = X_i \oplus \text{Cyl}_i, \quad (6.2)$$

where X_i is an arbitrary shape and $\text{Cyl}_i \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is the rotational sweep of the drill bit for the i -th operation. To enforce accessibility, Cyl_i is modeled as a semi-infinite cylinder extending away from the milling direction, ensuring that each V_i is accessible from outside.

A constructive way to satisfy Eq. 6.2 is to define V_i as the extrusion of a 2D region $C_i \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, embedded in a plane orthogonal to the milling direction \mathbf{n}_i , over the semi-infinite interval $(-\infty, h_i)$. If C_i satisfies the **Minkowski condition**, i.e., $C_i = X_i \oplus B_r$ for some region X_i and disk B_r of radius r , then the resulting volume V_i is millable by a flat-end tool of radius r (see Appendix D for proof). MXG encodes this construction through a primitive called the *Millable Extrusion Field*. We now introduce this primitive and describe how it is composed to construct millable geometry by design.

¹Given two sets $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, their Minkowski sum is defined as $A \oplus B = \{a + b \mid a \in A, b \in B\}$.

6.4.2 MILLABLE EXTRUSION GEOMETRY (MXG)

We introduce MILLABLE EXTRUSION GEOMETRY (MXG), a representation for programmatically constructing millable geometry using explicitly parameterized subtractive primitives. The core construct in MXG is the *Millable Extrusion Field* (\mathcal{E}), which defines a single milling operation. Each \mathcal{E} generates a subtractive volume V_i that is guaranteed to be millable by a flat-end drill of radius r .

A millable extrusion field \mathcal{E}_i is parameterized by a 2D signed distance function $f_i : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, an embedding plane $p(\mathbf{o}_i, \mathbf{n}_i)$, an extrusion height h_i , and a drill radius r_i . It defines a volume $\overline{\mathcal{E}}_i$ by extruding the sublevel set $C_i = \{x \mid f_i(x) \leq 0\}$ from $-\infty$ to h_i along the direction \mathbf{n}_i , as shown in Figure 6.5.

To ensure millability, the base region C_i must satisfy the Minkowski condition with respect to a disk of radius r_i . We enforce this using morphological opening [160]: we erode f_i to obtain $g_i = f_i \ominus B_{r_i}$, then dilate the result to define the updated region

$$C_i^r = \{x \mid (g_i \oplus B_{r_i})(x) \leq 0\}.$$

This guarantees that the extruded volume is physically realizable with a drill of radius r_i . The full extrusion is then given by $\overline{\mathcal{E}}_i^e = \text{extrude}(C_i^r, \mathbf{n}_i, h_i)$. Figure 6.4 illustrates this process.

Figure 6.4 shows the full construction pipeline: a 2D profile defined using symbolic CSG is morphologically opened and extruded to produce a valid subtractive volume. f_i can be specified using an arbitrary constructive solid geometry (CSG) expression, allowing for rich and parameterized profiles.

Part Programs MXG defines complete part geometries as a sequence of millable subtractions. Each part is represented as a material stock M minus a set of millable extrusion volumes, i.e., $P = M - \bigcup_i \overline{\mathcal{E}}_i$, as given in Equation 6.1. This formulation ensures that the resulting geometry is physically millable by construction. Figure 6.6 illustrates the expressiveness of MXG through varied part geometries constructed by subtracting multiple different extrusions.

Modeling Milling-induced Artifacts A key feature of MXG is that it provides explicit control over milling artifacts through per-subtraction parameters: the drill direction \mathbf{n}_i and radius r . Figure 6.6 (a) illustrates how increasing the drill radius introduces progressively stronger corner rounding, while Figure 6.6 (b) shows how varying the milling direction alters the artifact—even when the underlying geometry remains

Figure 6.5: Extrusion with $r = 0$

Figure 6.6: (left) Examples of traditional integral joint parts modeled using MXG. Each example shows the resulting solid along with the milling directions and 2D contours of the subtractive extrusions used in its construction. These examples capture the original design but require a physically infeasible milling tool with radius $r = 0$. (right) Our MILLABLE EXTRUSION GEOMETRY (MXG) representation enables explicit control over milling-induced artifacts via the drill radius r and subtraction direction \mathbf{n}_i parameters. The left column shows the target part with an ideal tool radius ($r = 0$). (a) Increasing r amplifies corner rounding. (b) Varying \mathbf{n}_i shifts both the location and orientation of artifacts.

identical at zero radius.

Modeling MXG_0 programs To express clean, artifact-free geometry, we author joint designs under an idealized setting of a zero-radius mill bit $r = 0$, yielding what we refer to as MXG_0 programs. Although not directly fabricable, these programs capture the intended shape of traditional joints. As we increase the tool radius r , evaluating the same program yields geometry distorted by milling-induced artifacts. MXG thus provides a modeling framework that captures both idealized geometry and its distortion under fabrication constraints.

6.5 Restoring Tight Coupling

We now address the challenge of restoring tight coupling between parts in the presence of milling-induced artifacts. This requires reasoning about both the geometry of mating surfaces and the milling operations that generate them. We first formalize tight coupling using two complementary measures: one that evaluates surface contact between parts, and another that constrains the spacing between paired milling paths. These measures are differentiable and efficiently computable for MXG geometry, enabling their use as loss functions. We then describe an optimization process that takes MXG_0 programs as input and updates their parameters to maintain coupling under a target milling radius r .

Figure 6.7: (a) Our optimization pipeline exploits a structural property of the MXG representation to greatly reduce the problem complexity. Based on its definition as a composition of subtractive planar extrusions, we observe that tight coupling can be fully characterized in 1D slices that lie perpendicular to the extrusion directions. (b) Many of the slices exhibit identical behavior and can be further grouped into a few representative planar sets. (c) The optimization domain then reduces to 1D planar curves within these representative slice sets. The interface of Z_1 's slice with extrusions from other directions is shown as a dashed red line. Such boundaries are kept fixed. (d) We optimize this reduced space to compute tightly coupled geometry, and (e) reassemble the results into the final 3D MiGumi parts.

6.5.1 SURFACE GAP

Let a joint system be composed of parts $\mathbf{P} = \{P^1, \dots, P^n\}$. As tight coupling is typically expected only in the interior region of the joint system, we define the *coupling volume* $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ as the region within which all surfaces must be in tight contact. In our approach, we simply define Ω as the internal volume of the joint system excluding its exposed surfaces.

Let $\mathbf{P} = \{P^1, \dots, P^n\}$ be parts in \mathbb{R}^3 , and let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ be the coupling volume. The SURFACE GAP is defined as:

$$\mathcal{M}_S(\mathbf{P}; \Omega) = \sum_{a=1}^n \int_{\partial P^a \cap \Omega} \min_{b \neq a} \mathcal{D}(x, P^b) dA(x), \quad (6.3)$$

where ∂P is the surface/boundary of part P , x is the center of an infinitesimal surface patch $dA(x)$ on the surface ∂P^a , and $\mathcal{D}(x, P^b)$ is the Euclidean distance from point x to the surface of part P^b . We call a joint system \mathbf{P} *tightly coupled* within Ω if $\mathcal{M}_S(\mathbf{P}; \Omega) = 0$. That is, every point on a surface within the coupling volume must be in exact contact with the surface of another part.

6.5.2 SURFACE GAP for MXG Shapes

When each part P is constructed using an MXG program, a natural decomposition of its boundary surface emerges that allows us to reformulate the surface gap $\mathcal{M}_S(P; \Omega)$ into a significantly more tractable form.

Recall from Section 6.4.2 that a part P is expressed as $P = M - \bigcup_i \overline{\mathcal{E}_i}$, where each $\overline{\mathcal{E}_i}$ denotes the volume removed by extruding a planar region C_i along direction \mathbf{n}_i , starting from plane $p(\mathbf{o}_i, \mathbf{n}_i)$ and extending over the interval $(-\infty, h_i)$. As a result, the surface of part P is composed of three disjoint subsets (Figure 6.8): the

Figure 6.8: Our method incorporates a SURFACE GAP measure that promotes tightly coupled part interfaces. Its efficient evaluation relies on decomposing each part’s boundary into material surfaces (∂^M), cap surfaces (∂^C), and lateral surfaces (∂^L), illustrated here using a dovetail joint.

Figure 6.9: We optimize two complementary measures to ensure tight coupling: the SURFACE GAP evaluates the surface contact of adjacent part pairs, while the MILLING PATH DISTANCE constrains the spacing between their milling paths. Left: given an input joint design, we first convert it into tool paths (striped areas) with a nonzero tool radius. These initial paths do not yet yield tightly coupled geometry. Middle: the SURFACE GAP measures the proximity of opposing surfaces by numerically integrating the closest-point distances measured from a discrete sampling (red points) along the underlying plane curve within a representative slice (cf. Figure 6.7). Right: the MILLING PATH DISTANCE evaluates the distance between milling paths by inserting one path into the planar signed distance field (SDF) of the opposing part and smoothly penalizing values that deviate from the desired distance ($2 \cdot r$). We optimize both via gradient-based methods.

portion inherited from the material stock: $\partial^M = \partial P \cap \partial M$, the *lateral surfaces* formed by the sides of each extrusion, denoted by ∂_i^L , and the *cap surfaces* formed by the terminal flat ends of each extrusion, denoted by ∂_i^C . Using this decomposition, \mathcal{M}_S for a single part P can be rewritten as:

$$\mathcal{M}_S(P; \Omega) = \sum_i \left(\int_{\partial_i^L} \mathcal{T} + \int_{\partial_i^C} \mathcal{T} \right) + \int_{\partial^M} \mathcal{T}, \quad (6.4)$$

where $\mathcal{T} = \min_{P^b \neq P} \mathcal{D}(x, P^b) dA(x)$.

For clarity, we omit intersection with the coupling volume Ω , though all integrals are restricted to surface regions within it. Note that the surfaces ∂_i^L and ∂_i^C for an extrusion \mathcal{E}_i are formed only on regions where material exists (i.e., the part volume remaining after subtracting other extrusions).

We now focus on the lateral surface term ∂_i^L . Since this surface is generated by sweeping a 2D profile C_i along direction \mathbf{n}_i , we can partition it into infinitesimally thin slices orthogonal to \mathbf{n}_i , each corresponding to a planar curve. This allows us to express the 3D surface integral as a 1D integral over a family of planar contours:

$$\int_{\partial_i^L} \mathcal{T} = \int_{z=-\infty}^{h_i} \left(\int_{\partial C_i(z)} \min_{P^b \neq P} \mathcal{D}(x, P^b) ds(x) \right) dz, \quad (6.5)$$

where $\partial C_i(z) = \partial C_i \cap P(z)$ denotes the boundary of the 2D extrusion profile C_i that creates a surface on part P at depth z along the milling direction.

Now, rather than measuring the 3D distance from each surface point $x \in \partial C_i(z)$ to the full surface of P^b , we compute the 2D distance to its planar intersection at the same slice height z , denoted $P^b(z)$. Note that this yields a stronger criterion: the 2D clearance upper bounds the true 3D clearance, ensuring that any improvement under this measure also improves the true surface contact. Since each slice has infinitesimal thickness, this effectively measures the gap between projected part contours in 2D. A key observation now follows: for any two slicing planes z_1 and z_2 , the corresponding slice integrals are identical whenever (i) the domain of integration $\partial C_i(z)$ remains the same, and (ii) the set of projected contours $\{P^b(z)\}_{b \neq P}$ from other parts does not change. In such cases, the integral can be evaluated once on a representative slice and scaled by the size of the equivalent slice set.

This insight significantly reduces computational cost: surface gap for the lateral surfaces can be evaluated by identifying the set of equivalent slices, computing a single 2D contour integral for each, and summing their contributions:

$$\int_{\partial_i^L} \mathcal{T} \approx \sum_{k=1}^m w_k \cdot \left(\int_{\partial C_i(z_k)} \min_{P^b \neq P} \mathcal{D}(x, P^b(z_k)) ds(x) \right), \quad (6.6)$$

where w_k is the size of the k -th equivalence class, and z_k is any representative height from that class. Figure 6.7(a–c) illustrates our planar slice-based evaluation. (a) shows a two-part joint, (b) depicts the three planar equivalence slice sets for one part, and (c) highlights one representative slice from each set. Together, the contours $\partial C_i(z_k)$ on each representative slice span the lateral surface within the coupling volume Ω , and are used to efficiently estimate surface gap. This approach is especially effective for traditional integral joints, where large regions often satisfy the equivalence condition—allowing surface gap to be estimated efficiently from a small number of representative contours.

To keep the set of representative slices compact, slices are grouped along each extrusion direction after subtracting other extrusions whose directions are not parallel to the current one. Further, during optimization, we keep the contours along these inter-direction interfaces fixed, preventing shifts that would otherwise change their equivalence class. The red dashed lines in Figure 6.7(c-d) illustrate such a case.

Critically, evaluating surface gap on this compact set of planar slices not only improves efficiency but

also suffices to preserve global coupling. If the initial configuration is tightly coupled and only the extrusion profiles f_i are modified, then enforcing zero deviation on these slices ensures that the overall surface gap $\mathcal{M}_S(\mathbf{P}; \Omega)$ remains zero, i.e., contributions from cap surfaces and material surfaces also evaluate to zero.

6.5.3 MILLING PATH DISTANCE

Recall that each extruded region C_i is formed by dilating a base curve g_i by a disk of radius r_i , i.e., $C_i = g_i \oplus B_{r_i}$. We assume g_i is an exact signed distance function, and therefore the Minkowski sum can be performed using the dilation operator. The boundary ∂C_i defines the visible surface of the milled region, while the zero-level set of g_i can be interpreted as the tool path that generates ∂C_i . We refer to this zero contour $\partial g^i := \{x \mid g_i(x) = 0\}$ as the mill path associated with extrusion \mathcal{E}_i . Note that this is not the tool path used for fabrication.

While the SURFACE GAP measures deviation between mating surfaces, it operates solely on the extruded boundaries ∂C_i . These boundaries are produced by dilating the underlying mill paths g_i , which are parameterized and optimized to restore tight coupling. This introduces a mismatch: multiple different mill paths can produce nearly identical extruded contours. As a result, optimization can become unstable, with large changes in g_i producing negligible changes in ∂C_i . In practice, this leads to zero gradients from certain parameters of g_i and consequently poor convergence in certain configurations (Figure 6.10).

To address this issue, we impose an additional constraint on the mill paths. When a tightly coupled surface is generated by two extrusions $(\mathcal{E}_i^a, \mathcal{E}_j^b)$ with parallel normals, their mill paths—the zero-level sets ∂g_i^a and ∂g_j^b —must stay a fixed distance apart, equal to the sum of the cutter radii. Each milled surface is obtained by offsetting its mill path by the cutter radius. For the two surfaces to coincide without gaps or overlap, the underlying paths must be separated by $r_i + r_j$.

We formalize this using the MILLING PATH DISTANCE (\mathcal{M}_P), which penalizes deviation from the ideal path-to-path spacing:

$$\mathcal{M}_P(g_i^a, g_j^b) = \int_{x \in \partial g_i^a} \left(\mathcal{D}(x, g_j^b) - (r_i + r_j) \right)^2 ds(x), \quad (6.7)$$

where $ds(x)$ denotes arc-length measure along the contour ∂g_i^a , and $\mathcal{D}(x, g_j^b)$ gives the signed distance from x to the opposing mill path. In practice, this loss is applied only in planar slices where both contours arise from paired extrusions with collinear axes. A symmetric version of the loss, computed over ∂g_j^b , is also applied.

Figure 6.10: (a) We optimize the milling tool path (striped area) via the SURFACE GAP to keep the boundary of the subtracted volume (yellow) in tight contact with the opposing part. (b) A degeneracy can arise during this process, where the SURFACE GAP has zero gradient with respect to the concave regions of the tool path (dark blue vertices). We address the problem by introducing an additional MILLING PATH DISTANCE metric that keeps these vertices sufficiently close to the boundary.

6.5.4 Optimization

We now detail the optimization process that transforms an artifact-free MXG_0 program—defined under the idealized setting of zero-radius drill bits—into a physically realizable MXG_r program that preserves tight coupling under a target drill radius $r > 0$.

Our optimization strategy builds on the formulation in Section 6.5.2, where we showed that, for a single part, surface gap can be reduced to a small set of planar slice integrals, one per set of equivalent slices. To preserve tight coupling across the full joint system, we must now perform this optimization simultaneously across all parts. We sample a compact set of slices that span all lateral surfaces in the coupling volume and perform co-optimization of all intersecting paths within each slice. This strategy ensures that contact is restored across all interfaces while keeping the optimization tractable. To maintain compatibility across different directions, we treat interface contours between non-aligned extrusions as fixed. This allows each slice-aligned stage to proceed independently, while preserving both millability and global coupling. Figure 6.7(c-e) illustrates this process for a traditional joint: although optimization is performed on just three representative planar slices, the resulting design exhibits tight coupling across the full 3D assembly.

Per-Slice Optimization In each slice, we optimize the profile fields ∂g_i of all intersecting extrusions to minimize both surface gap (\mathcal{M}_S) and deviation from ideal milling path distance (\mathcal{M}_P). This requires computing losses that depend on distances between sampled points and neighboring geometry. Specifically, for each extrusion intersecting the slice, we sample points on its boundary contour ∂C_i and on its mill path ∂g_i , and evaluate their proximity to either other parts (for \mathcal{M}_S) or paired paths (for \mathcal{M}_P).

To evaluate the *Surface Gap* loss \mathcal{L}_S , a Monte Carlo approximation of \mathcal{M}_S (cf. equation 6.3), we construct a 2D slice-wise representation of each part by projecting its material and extrusion volumes onto the slicing plane. These are composed into a pseudo-signed distance field using Boolean operations. While not a true Euclidean SDF, it yields sufficiently accurate distance estimates near the contour ∂C_i , where optimization is

Figure 6.11: A selection of integral joints from our dataset of 30 traditional designs, modeled in MXG₀. Each example demonstrates a different functional or structural motif: (a) a case joint with hidden mating seams, (b) a joint using cylindrical stock, (c) a joint with diagonal subtraction, (d) a right-angled joint, (e) a joint with three parts, and (f) a straight connection joint. This dataset supports evaluation, benchmarking, and further research into CNC-fabricable joinery.

concentrated. At each sampled point on ∂C_i , we evaluate the minimum distance to projected boundaries of other parts in the slice. For the *Milling Path Distance* loss \mathcal{L}_P , a Monte Carlo estimate of \mathcal{M}_P (cf. equation 6.7), we use the exact SDFs of mill paths g_j . At each sampled point x on the zero contour ∂g_i , we evaluate $g_j(x)$ and penalize deviation from the target offset $r_i + r_j$. This directly constrains the alignment between opposing mill paths that form tightly coupled surfaces. Figure 6.9 illustrates how the two losses are computed: points are sampled on the surface curve to measure \mathcal{M}_S and on the mill paths to measure \mathcal{M}_P .

In addition to enforcing tight coupling, we encourage the optimized geometry to remain close to the original design by using an occupancy preservation loss \mathcal{L}_{occ} . This term penalizes deviations from the occupancy of each part across a uniform grid of samples on the planar slice. The occupancy field is computed as a smooth function of the part’s signed distance field, enabling gradient-based updates. The final optimization objective combines all three components:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \mathcal{L}_S + \lambda_P \cdot \mathcal{L}_P + \lambda_{occ} \cdot \mathcal{L}_{occ}, \quad (6.8)$$

where scalar weights λ_P and λ_{occ} control the relative influence of the auxiliary terms during optimization. Further implementation details, including point sampling routines and slice-projection of expressions, are provided in Appendix D.

6.6 Evaluation

We evaluate our approach on a curated dataset of traditional joint designs, focusing on the task of converting idealized, artifact-free programs into millable, tightly coupled assemblies. All experiments use a fixed drill radius of $r_d = 3.175$ mm (1/8 inch) and assume material stock with a 3×3 cm² cross-section unless otherwise noted. We begin by describing the dataset and methods compared. We then present quantitative results showing that our method ensures both tight coupling and millability. Finally, we show fabricated outputs and design variations.

6.6.1 A Dataset of Tightly Coupled Integral Joints

We construct a dataset of 30 traditional joint designs using the MXG₀ representation, based on a catalog of Japanese woodworking techniques [16]. The dataset captures a broad range of integral joinery structures used in practice. Interestingly, we found that approximately 80% of designs in the catalog could be faithfully modeled using flat subtractive extrusions. We believe this high coverage reflects an alignment between traditional fabrication and the MXG representation: in both settings, all material must be removed directionally from outside the stock. More importantly, manual fabrication techniques make it difficult to construct tightly coupled *curved* surfaces, resulting in a strong preference for planar features, precisely the type of geometry encoded by MXG’s flat extrusions.

The designs are authored using a custom visual programming tool that provides parametric control over extrusion profiles, milling directions, and depths. All parts are modeled under the zero-radius drill bit setting, yielding artifact-free geometry faithful to the source designs. Authoring the dataset required approximately 40 person-hours.

Figure 6.11 shows representative examples from the dataset. These include (a) case joints, (b) joints with cylindrical stock, (c) joints with diagonal cuts, (d) right-angled joints, (e) joints with three parts, and (f) straight joints. We believe this dataset provides a concrete foundation for research in joinery modeling, fabrication-aware geometry design, and CNC-compatible procedural representations.

6.6.2 Experimental Details

Comparison Methods. We compare our optimization-based method against two alternatives for converting artifact-free MXG₀ programs into millable, tightly coupled joint designs:

1. *Opening-Only (MO)*. Applies morphological opening to each part’s extruded region, producing millable geometry by construction. No attempt is made to preserve surface coupling.

Method	$\%M \uparrow$	$\%C_\tau \uparrow$
Opening-Only (MO)	100%	6.25%
Opening & Diff-Flip (ODF)	25%	96.87%
Ours	100%	90.62%

Table 6.1: Comparison of methods for converting joint designs into millable, tightly coupled geometry. We report *Millability* (\mathcal{M}) and *Coupling Success Rate* (C_τ). Only our optimization-based method is successful at generating designs that are both millable and tightly coupled.

2. *Opening & Diff-Flip (ODF)*. Begins with millable parts obtained via opening, then restores contact by applying the resulting shape differences to paired parts. That is, the volume of each part removed due to the opening operation (Diff) is directly added to the paired part (Flip). Although simple, this heuristic often yields invalid subtractions that break millability.

Evaluation Metrics. We report four metrics that collectively assess fabrication feasibility, contact quality, and geometric preservation.

Exact Millability ($\%M$) measures the percentage of designs for which all subtractions satisfy the Minkowski condition. Since morphological opening is idempotent, this is verified by checking whether each extrusion remains unchanged under opening. A design is counted as millable if every subtraction passes this test.

Coupling Success Rate (C_τ) quantifies how many designs retain tight surface contact after conversion. For each joint, we measure the volume of overlap between parts and the gap volume, i.e., space occupied by a part in the initial design that is no longer occupied by any part. This is done by voxelizing each part, with each voxel having side length $30/256 = 0.11$ mm, and counting voxels. A design is considered tightly coupled if the intersection volume is within a threshold $\tau = 135$ mm³ (i.e., 0.5% of the volume of a cube with 30 mm sides). Appendix D evaluates different threshold values.

To illustrate the difference between ablations of our method, we report the *Median Violation Volume* (\overline{V}), the median mismatch volume (gaps plus overlaps) across all joints. We also measure *Design Deviation* (\overline{D}), which quantifies how much the final part geometry differs from the original artifact-free design. We compute this by voxelizing each part before and after optimization and counting the number of non-matching voxels. The reported \overline{D} is the median of this value across all parts in the dataset.

6.6.3 Quantitative Evaluation

We evaluate all three methods on our dataset of 30 traditional joint designs. Table 6.1 summarizes the performance of each approach across millability and tight surface contact.

Figure 6.12: **CNC-Milled Physical Outputs.** Assembled and disassembled states of joints physically fabricated using a 3-axis CNC milling machine with a quarter-inch flat-end bit. The parts of joint (e) were positioned at a 45 degree angle during milling. The holes in joint (f) were fabricated after assembling the two main parts of the joint, ensuring high precision despite repositioning. The parts of joint (g) were repositioned twice to accommodate the multiple milling directions.

The *Opening-only* approach achieves perfect millability ($\mathcal{M} = 100\%$), as expected from its use of morphological opening. However, it entirely fails to preserve tight coupling: almost all the designs fail to meet the contact threshold ($C_\tau = 6.25\%$), and surface overlaps are visibly large. The *Opening & Diff-Flip* method improves contact, successfully achieving tight coupling for a notable majority ($C_\tau = 96.87\%$). However, 75% of the resulting designs contain one or more subtractions that are not valid under the Minkowski condition ($\mathcal{M} = 25\%$), limiting their fabricability. In contrast, our optimization-based approach satisfies both criteria across all designs: every joint remains fully millable by construction ($\mathcal{M} = 100\%$) while achieving tight contact on almost all mating surfaces ($C_\tau = 90.62\%$). This makes it the only method to guarantee both geometric and fabrication validity at once.

Figure 6.13 compares outputs from all three approaches across multiple joint designs. The *Opening-only* (MO) method consistently produces overlapping parts that prevent assembly, while the *Opening & Diff-Flip* (ODF) variant yields better alignment but often introduces subtractions that violate millability. In contrast, our optimization-based method produces geometries that are both tightly coupled and fabricable, with minimal deviation from the original designs.

	$\overline{\mathcal{V}}$ (mm ³) ↓	$\overline{\mathcal{D}}$ (mm ³) ↓
Ours	74.82	456.14
No \mathcal{L}_S	138.23	483.52
No \mathcal{L}_P	120.56	474.60
No \mathcal{L}_{occ}	83.16	543.27
No gradual r_d rollout	142.11	488.96
No ODF initialization	238.64	569.59

Table 6.2: Subtractive ablation of our optimization pipeline. Each row disables a single component, and we report *Median Violation Volume* ($\overline{\mathcal{V}}$) and *Design Deviation* ($\overline{\mathcal{D}}$). The full method yields the best performance across both metrics.

6.6.4 Ablation Study

To attribute the contribution of different components in our optimization pipeline, we conduct an ablation study by selectively removing loss terms and heuristics from our method. Table 6.2 reports the effect of each modification using two metrics: median violation volume ($\overline{\mathcal{V}}$) and design deviation ($\overline{\mathcal{D}}$).

We begin by ablating the loss functions introduced in Section 6.5. Removing the *Milling Path Distance* loss \mathcal{L}_P or the *Surface Gap* loss \mathcal{L}_S leads to notable increases in violation volume, highlighting the importance of using both to achieve tight coupling. Omitting the *Occupancy Preservation* loss \mathcal{L}_{occ} increases the average design deviation ($\overline{\mathcal{D}}$), indicating that it plays a key role in preserving geometric fidelity to the original design.

We also evaluate two implementation strategies that improve optimization quality and convergence. First, instead of optimizing directly at the target drill radius r_d , we adopt a gradual rollout schedule: starting from radius zero, we increase r in small increments, re-optimizing at each step. This improves stability, especially for large-radius artifacts. Second, we initialize the profile fields g_i using the output of an *Opening & Diff-Flip* (ODF) pass at radius $r_d/2$. This initialization expands the expressive range of g_i early on, enabling better adaptation during optimization. Without it, we observe stagnation due to insufficient parameter flexibility. While adaptive reparameterization is a possible alternative, ODF initialization provides a lightweight and effective solution. As shown in Table 6.2, removing any of these strategies results in a significant loss in performance, illustrating that they play a key role in ensuring that the optimization is successful.

Finally, we report that our optimization process takes roughly 5 minutes per planar slice. Most joints require 1 to 3 slices, depending on the number of parts and the orientation of milling directions. Full optimization typically completes within ~10 minutes.

Figure 6.13: Comparison of methods for converting joint designs into millable, tightly coupled geometry. *Opening-only* (MO) yields overlapping parts, while *Opening & Diff-Flip* (ODF) improves contact but violates millability. Our optimization-based method achieves both tight coupling and fabrication validity. Failure regions are highlighted with zoomed insets.

Figure 6.14: **Failure cases of our method** (a) Tight coupling is infeasible when three mill paths meet at a sharp corner, resulting in unavoidable gaps. (b) A joint that becomes unassemblable after optimization because our optimization does not consider assemblability as an additional requirement. (c) The Osaka-Jo Otomon Joint, which requires subtractions incompatible with flat-end milling and thus cannot be represented in MXG.

6.7 Fabrication and Design Outcomes

Physical Fabrication To validate that our optimized joint designs are physically realizable, we fabricated eight joints using a 3-axis CNC machine equipped with a quarter-inch flat-end bit. Each joint was generated from an MXG program and optimized using our method to ensure both millability and tight coupling under the target bit radius. All square parts were cut from 3 cm wooden stock, and the cylindrical part diameter was 4 cm. The joints were assembled without glue, nails, or fasteners. Appendix D provides further details.

Figure 6.12 shows the joints in assembled and disassembled states. Each achieves precise alignment and firm contact between mating surfaces, with no visible gaps or overlaps. Importantly, the observed milling artifacts (e.g., inner corner radii) match those modeled in the optimization process, confirming that our artifact-aware representation translates accurately to physical fabrication. Each joint required 18–25 minutes of machine time.

Enabling Design Exploration Beyond fabrication, MXG enables structured exploration of design alternatives. By explicitly modeling the parameters that induce milling artifacts—tool direction and drill radius—authors can evaluate how different configurations trade off aesthetic, structural, and fabrication considerations. Figure 6.15 shows two variants of the same functional joint, each implemented via a different MXG program. In (a), all extrusions are aligned along the joint’s sliding axis, hiding milling artifacts inside the joint; this improves exterior appearance but requires axis-parallel milling, which can be infeasible in some setups. In contrast, (b) performs all milling laterally, ensuring accessibility on typical 3-axis machines but revealing artifacts externally.

6.8 Limitations & Future Work

While our approach enables the fabrication of a broad class of traditional joints, several limitations remain, each pointing to promising future directions.

A key limitation of our approach arises when multiple concave subtractions are tightly coupled. When multiple extrusions intersect at sharp internal angles, it becomes geometrically infeasible to maintain perfect surface contact while satisfying millability constraints, resulting in small but unavoidable clearance gaps (Figure 6.14(a)). This issue also arises when two extrusions interface with a fixed boundary from non-aligned extrusions, as in the case of the joint in Figure 6.7. Addressing such cases may require hybrid fabrication strategies that go beyond 3-axis milling, such as introducing auxiliary planar cuts or incorporating secondary tools like chisels or saw blades. Such extensions would also be necessary to support the $\sim 20\%$ of joints in our source catalog [16] that cannot be modeled using flat-end extrusions alone. Figure 6.14(c) shows the Osaka-Jo Otomon Joint, a traditional design that includes subtractions which cannot be decomposed into externally accessible flat-end milling operations.

A second limitation is the need to manually author MXG₀ programs. While our visual programming tool streamlines this process, creating designs from scratch still requires expertise and time. Future work could explore automatic inference of subtractive extrusion programs from mesh-based geometry, allowing users to model joints in conventional CAD tools while benefiting from our representation. Additionally, improved authoring interfaces—such as motif libraries, sketch-based editing, or learning-based retrieval of common joint structures—could make MXG more accessible to novice users and support faster design iteration.

Third, our system does not currently account for assembly sequencing. Although the optimized joints are tightly coupled, they may become unassemblable due to the modified geometry. In our dataset, 1 of the 30 joints cannot be manually assembled after optimization. We show an example in Figure 6.14(b). Future work could incorporate directional blocking analysis directly into the optimization loop, or constrain

Figure 6.15: MXG enables controlled trade-offs between fabrication constraints and design aesthetics. Here, we show two variants of a joint that differ in milling direction. (a) Aligns all extrusions along the sliding axis, hiding artifacts internally but requiring axis-parallel milling. (b) Performs all milling laterally, improving accessibility but exposing artifacts externally.

extrusion paths to preserve known assembly sequences.

While our system enables the fabrication of integral joints via CNC milling, the full repertoire of techniques used by master carpenters remains beyond its scope. Traditional joints often incorporate subtle construction strategies, such as intentional minuscule misalignments or driven-in wedges, that enhance strength or aid assembly. Modeling these expert techniques and making them accessible through modern fabrication tools remains an open challenge. We view this chapter as a concrete step toward that broader goal.

6.9 Conclusions

MiGumi addresses a core failure mode of subtractive fabrication for integral joints: standard CNC milling with nonzero-radius tools rounds internal corners, and these milling-induced deviations break the tight surface coupling that traditional Kigumi designs rely on, leading to gaps, overlaps, or blocked assembly.

Our approach separates *representation* from *repair*. We introduce MILLABLE EXTRUSION GEOMETRY (MXG), a domain-appropriate symbolic representation in which each part is expressed as a sequence of subtractive milling operations parameterized by tool direction and drill radius. MXG makes the manufacturing process explicit and provides a structured parameterization over which coupling can be restored. To do so, we optimize MXG programs using two complementary objectives: SURFACE GAP, which penalizes separation between mating surfaces, and MILLING PATH DISTANCE, which constrains the toolpaths responsible for those surfaces. For MXG geometry, both objectives reduce to 1D contour integrals on planar slices, enabling tractable joint optimization of all extrusion profiles.

We evaluated our approach on a curated dataset of 30 traditional joints and fabricated eight assemblies

on a 3-axis CNC machine, verifying that the optimized designs remain millable while achieving substantially improved fit over baseline strategies. By making tightly coupled integral joint design directly millable with CNC machines, our approach makes such joints more widely accessible and lays the groundwork for a new class of joinery designs.

Within the larger arc of this thesis, MiGumi shows one form of annotation-free symbolic acquisition through direct optimization. The user authors an idealized milling program MXG_0 (an artifact-free target under a zero-radius tool), and the optimizer converts it into a realizable program MXG_r that respects the true tool radius while recovering tight coupling. The acquisition procedure works because the representation, losses, and optimization schedule are designed together: MXG exposes the fabrication variables, while the coupling objectives define what structure must be preserved.

At the same time, MiGumi remains semi-automatic. Its input is already a hand-authored idealized program, which gives the designer control over where milling artifacts arise but also leaves manual authoring as a limitation. The next chapter continues the direct-optimization thread in a less domain-authored setting: it asks how compact symbolic primitive assemblies can be acquired from raw or generated 3D shapes, where the input is an unstructured surface rather than an idealized fabrication program.

CHAPTER 7

ACQUISITION VIA DIRECT OPTIMIZATION: SUPERFIT

Residual Primitive Fitting of 3D Shapes with SuperFrusta

Figure 7.1: Primitive assemblies inferred by ResFit capture a wide range of shapes, including hollow forms, curved and toroidal parts, intricate geometry, and smooth organic shapes. The method shifts the reconstruction-parsimony frontier by achieving lower reconstruction error with fewer primitives than prior work.

7.1 Direct Optimization for Primitive Assemblies

This chapter returns to the dissertation’s central acquisition problem: recovering symbolic geometry without paired symbolic annotations. Here the input is measurement-centric 3D data: a raw mesh, a generated asset, or another unstructured shape whose surface can be sampled but whose parts, parameters, and construction logic are not named. The desired output is not just a more compact reconstruction, but a symbolic description that exposes editable structure.

The earlier acquisition chapters developed two other sources of signal. Chapter 3 used foundation-model priors to guide inference when direct symbolic labels were unavailable, while Chapters 4 and 5 used in-domain synthetic supervision to train systems from procedurally generated examples. The thesis then turns to a third route: direct optimization against the observed geometry itself. MiGumi, the first direct-optimization chapter, optimized a process-specific symbolic representation so that integral joints remained millable and tightly coupled. SuperFit is the second example of this route.

Figure 7.2: **SuperFrustum— An Expressive, Compact & Differentiable Primitive.** SuperFrustum is a unified analytic SDF primitive with only **8** parameters controlling dilation, taper, bulge, onion-like hollowing, profile roundness, and axial scaling. Its SDF is C^0 -continuous and fully differentiable (almost everywhere) with respect to all parameters, enabling robust inverse modeling and gradient-based optimization. As shown on the right, these parameters allow a single formulation to morph smoothly across common solids—cuboids, cylinders, cones, spheres, and toroidal variants—and to produce more complex shapes such as bent, hollow, or smoothly capped forms.

The acquisition target in this chapter is broader and more geometric: compact, editable assemblies of analytic primitives inferred from raw 3D shapes. Primitive assemblies are useful because they expose parts and continuous handles for editing, simulation, fabrication, and reuse. They are also difficult to acquire annotation-free: a method must explain detailed geometry while avoiding dense, redundant collections of overlapping primitives.

SuperFit shows that direct optimization is not merely an optimization trick applied after a representation has been fixed. It is a co-design problem between the symbolic representation and the acquisition procedure. The SuperFrustum primitive is designed to be expressive enough to cover curved, hollow, and tapered forms while remaining editable and differentiable. The Residual Primitive Fitting procedure is designed around that representation: it analyzes the unexplained residual, proposes primitives where the current assembly falls short, refines them by gradient-based fitting, and prunes redundant structure. The result is an annotation-free acquisition pipeline in which representation design and optimization strategy make each other work.

7.2 Introduction

Recent breakthroughs in 3D generation have enabled the creation of high-quality assets from simple prompts [100, 190]. However, while visually impressive, these outputs are often structurally unorganized, posing challenges for downstream applications like animation, rigging, and interactive editing. Primitive-based representations offer a compelling alternative by distilling complex geometry into a compact assembly of interpretable, analytic parts. This approach yields editable assets and aligns with cognitive findings that humans perceive objects as compositions of simpler forms [13], providing a structured understanding that

dense representations lack. The central challenge is converting these unstructured 3D assets into meaningful, primitive-based designs.

Inferring a primitive assembly from a raw 3D shape, however, presents a fundamental trade-off between reconstruction fidelity and program parsimony. Approaches that prioritize high fidelity often yield dense, redundant assemblies of overlapping primitives [140, 23, 6, 47, 179]. Conversely, methods that enforce parsimony may fail to capture fine geometric details or curved structures [194, 104, 139]. Achieving a representation that is simultaneously expressive, compact, and editable remains an open challenge.

This persistent trade-off can be attributed to two factors. First, commonly used primitive families such as cuboids, superquadrics, or ellipsoids [9] may require a large number of instances to model the rich shape variations in 3D assets. Second, the inference procedures themselves have distinct limitations. Methods that first commit to a complete segmentation of the input rely on a fixed partition that may not align with what the primitives can efficiently represent [181, 232, 197, 108]. This makes the process brittle, as any initial segmentation errors propagate directly to the final assembly. On the other hand, optimization-driven approaches that fit a large "soup" of primitives from scratch must navigate a highly non-convex loss landscape [143, 186, 23].

To address these limitations, we introduce a framework that marries a highly expressive primitive with a robust inference strategy. At the core of our approach is the **SUPERFRUSTUM**, an analytic primitive that fills a key gap in prior work: existing primitive families typically satisfy only one or two of the critical desiderata—*expressivity*, *editability*, and *optimizability*. In contrast, SuperFrustum (1) spans common solids such as cylinders, cones, spheres, and their tapered or bent variants; (2) is compactly parameterized with just 8 parameters; and (3) admits a signed-distance field that is differentiable with respect to all parameters, enabling smooth blending and effective inverse modeling. Intriguingly, its design builds on analytic functions uncovered by the Shadertoy and Demoscene communities in their pursuit of highly expressive analytic forms with minimal description length [136, 135, 137, 145]. We find that, when carefully adapted, these formulations are exceptionally well-suited for inverse modeling.

To achieve parsimonious assemblies, an expressive primitive must be paired with an equally effective inference algorithm. We propose **RESIDUAL PRIMITIVE FITTING (RESFIT)**, an unsupervised procedure that tightly interleaves global shape analysis with local primitive optimization to better navigate the highly non-convex reconstruction loss. Instead of optimizing a large set of primitives jointly from scratch, ResFit first analyzes the input geometry to propose initial structures based on global cues. These primitives are then refined via gradient descent to conform to the local geometry. The resulting assembly is subtracted from the target shape, and the process repeats on the unexplained residual. By alternating between proposing global structure and optimizing local parameters, ResFit allows these two signals to mutually inform each other,

producing assemblies that are both compact and high-fidelity.

Our approach sets a new state-of-the-art on diverse 3D benchmarks. It consistently produces higher-fidelity reconstructions—**improving IoU by over 9 points**—while using nearly half the primitives of prior work, demonstrating a fundamental shift in the fidelity-parsimony frontier. These results are enabled by our two primary contributions:

1. **The SuperFrustum:** A single compact analytic primitive that spans a wide range of canonical volumetric forms while remaining differentiable and suitable for gradient-based optimization.
2. **Residual Primitive Fitting (ResFit):** An unsupervised inference procedure that alternates between global shape analysis and local primitive optimization to produce compact and accurate assemblies.

Beyond reconstruction, we demonstrate how this framework enables downstream applications including the generation of editable assets, the inference of structured CSG programs, and the enrichment of semantic part segmentations.

7.3 Task-Specific Positioning

SuperFit belongs to the primitive-assembly branch of symbolic geometry acquisition. Existing methods can be grouped roughly into analysis-driven, optimization-driven, and learned approaches. Analysis-driven methods partition geometry using cues such as convexity, curvature, or thickness before fitting parts [181, 232, 197, 108, 194]. Optimization-driven methods fit primitive parameters directly to target geometry or rendered observations [143, 104, 127]. Learned methods predict primitive layouts or infer them through reconstruction objectives [212, 90, 68, 124, 47, 23, 140, 72].

The representation itself is equally important. Simple primitives such as cuboids and cylinders are interpretable but often require many parts; superquadrics and other analytic surfaces increase expressivity but can be hard to edit or fit robustly [9, 211]. Neural implicit parts can be expressive but are less transparent as symbolic structure [47, 140, 59]. SuperFit contributes to this line by co-designing an expressive analytic primitive with a residual fitting procedure, making the direct-optimization signal better aligned with the desired symbolic output.

7.4 Method

We define the primitive assembly inference task as follows: given a 3D shape x , our goal is to infer a primitive assembly z composed of analytic primitives whose execution $E(z)$ reconstructs the input shape. Each program z defines a sequence of primitives $\{f_{\theta_i}\}_{i=1}^{|z|}$ combined through compositional operators to

Figure 7.3: **ResFit** infers parsimonious assemblies by interleaving *shape analysis* and *primitive optimization*. Shape decomposition provides initial primitives, which are refined with decomposition-aware optimization. Residual unexplained volumes are then extracted and seeded with new primitives.

yield a closed surface $E(z)$. Following Occam’s razor, we seek programs that are both *accurate* and *compact*. Formally, we aim to maximize the following objective:

$$z^* = \arg \max_z O(x, z), \tag{7.1}$$

$$O(x, z) = \mathcal{R}(x, E(z)) - \alpha|z|, \tag{7.2}$$

where \mathcal{R} measures the reconstruction accuracy between the input shape x and the program execution $E(z)$, $|z|$ denotes the program complexity (or number of primitives in the program), and α controls the trade-off between accuracy and compactness. Maximizing O thus favors concise programs that explain the geometry with a small set of expressive parts.

We now summarize the components of our method. Section 7.4.1 introduces ResFit, our iterative fitting procedure. Section 7.4.2 defines SuperFrustum, the unified analytic primitive used in all assemblies. Section 7.4.3 describes our MSD-based initialization strategy, and Section 7.4.4 details the optimization process that balances geometric fidelity with parsimony.

7.4.1 ResFit : Residual Primitive Fitting

Purely optimization-based methods often produce entangled reconstructions, while analysis-based approaches partition shapes without considering the primitive family’s representational capacity. This creates a disconnect between the geometric analysis (top-down) and the primitive representation (bottom-up). Residual Primitive Fitting (ResFit) bridges this divide by interleaving shape analysis and assembly optimization,

Figure 7.4: Morphological Shape Decomposition (MSD) iteratively extracts connected regions of similar thickness. Top: successive MSD partitions of an input mesh. Bottom: MSD yields regions that form suitable initialization seeds for SuperFrusta —capturing non-convex structures such as bicycle tires (left), a cat’s curved tail (center), and bowl rims (right). In contrast, CoACD over-partitions these regions into many convex fragments, often using axis-aligned cuts that produce semantically misaligned parts.

Primitive	Expressive	Editable	Optimizable
S. quadrics [139]	✗	✓	✓
Alg. Surf [211]	✓	✗	✓
Multi-type [212]	✓	✓	✗
SuperFrusta	✓	✓	✓

Table 7.1: Comparison of primitive families across three key desiderata: expressivity, editability, and optimizability. SuperFrusta uniquely satisfies all three criteria.

allowing each phase to inform the other and yielding assemblies that are both compact and geometrically faithful.

Our procedure alternates between analysis and optimization (Fig. 7.3). The analysis stage decomposes the current residual volume into regions that seed new primitives. The optimization stage then adjusts parameters to maximize \mathcal{O} (Eq. 7.1), separating explained geometry from remaining residuals. This cycle repeats until \mathcal{O} saturates or a fixed iteration budget K is reached.

Several design choices let the iterative loop correct both excess and insufficient parameterization. To prevent excess parameterization, we seed few primitives per round and employ parsimony-aware optimization: a soft regularizer penalizes redundancy during fitting, while hard pruning removes parts that degrade \mathcal{O} . To address insufficient parameterization, primitives are optimized based on their local support, and the full assembly is re-optimized in each round. This enables self-correction as new parts are added, allowing the system to converge toward a compact and coherent structure.

7.4.2 Expressive, Editable & Optimizable Primitive

An ideal primitive for inverse graphics must be *expressive* enough for diverse forms, *editable* via intuitive controls, and robustly *optimizable*. As existing families often fall short, we introduce SuperFrusta, a unified analytic primitive designed to meet all three desiderata.

A SuperFrustum is the zero-level set of a signed distance function

$$SF(\mathbf{p}) = f(\mathbf{p}; \theta), \quad \theta = (\mathbf{s}, r, d, t, b, o), \quad (7.3)$$

with parameters $\theta = (\mathbf{s}, r, d, t, b, o)$. These 8 scalars intuitively control anisotropic scale (\mathbf{s}), profile rounding (r), dilation (d), taper (t), bulge (b), and onion/shell thickness (o), as shown in Fig. 7.2. Appendix E provides further implementation details and the reference code. Its continuous, piecewise- C^1 formulation spans a wide range of shapes including cuboids, cylinders, cones, and tori, and is differentiable almost everywhere, enabling stable gradient-based fitting.

The complete primitive assembly is formed by composing transformed SuperFrusta. Each instance i has a pose (R_i, t_i) and shape parameters θ_i , yielding a signed distance $g_i(\mathbf{p}) = f(R_i^\top(\mathbf{p} - t_i); \theta_i)$. The final implicit field \mathcal{F} is obtained by recursively applying a smooth union operator U :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_1(\mathbf{p}) &= g_1(\mathbf{p}), \\ \mathcal{F}_{k+1}(\mathbf{p}) &= U(\mathcal{F}_k(\mathbf{p}), g_{k+1}(\mathbf{p}); \beta_k), \end{aligned} \quad (7.4)$$

where β_k controls blend sharpness. The final surface is the zero level set of \mathcal{F} .

7.4.3 Shape Decomposition for SuperFrusta

ResFit initializes primitives from the volumetric regions produced by a shape decomposition method, and its performance improves when the chosen decomposition strategy aligns with the primitive family’s expressiveness. While recent work adapts Approximate Convex Decomposition (ACD) [194] for initializing primitives, we find that an adapted variant of Morphological Shape Decomposition (MSD) [143] is more suitable for initializing SuperFrusta.

MSD is an iterative “peel the thickest part first” technique. At each step, it finds the largest connected region of roughly uniform thickness, extracts it, removes it from the shape, and repeats on the residual. This process yields a thickness-ordered set of volumetric regions for primitive initialization, as shown in Figure 7.4.

Formally, given a signed distance field $f(\mathbf{p})$, each iteration k identifies the thickest interior region Γ_k by finding the connected component (cc) that survives erosion up to a radius $|\tau|$:

$$\Gamma_k \subseteq \{\mathbf{p} \in \Omega \mid f(\mathbf{p}) \leq \tau\}, \quad \Gamma_k \text{ is a cc.} \quad (7.5)$$

The threshold $\tau \leq 0$ is the minimum value such that $\text{Vol}(\Gamma_k)$ meets a volume fraction κ . To recover its full

spatial extent, we dilate Γ_k back by the same radius, $R_k = \Gamma_k \oplus B_{|\tau|}$. This part R_k is recorded and subtracted from the shape by updating the residual field:

$$f_{k+1}(\mathbf{p}) = f_k(\mathbf{p}) \setminus R_k, \quad f_1 \equiv f. \quad (7.6)$$

Repeating this process produces a sequence of candidate regions $\{R_k\}$ ordered by decreasing thickness.

MSD offers two key advantages over ACD [96, 197] for this task. First, ACD’s convexity constraint over-partitions non-convex structures that a single SuperFrustum can model, such as the bent and hollow forms shown in Figure 7.4 (bottom). Second, MSD is substantially more robust to the noisy surface artifacts present in the residual volumes generated during our iterative fitting loop, making it better suited for ResFit.

For each decomposed part volume, we instantiate a SuperFrustum. We initialize its parameters by using PCA on points sampled within the volume. The cylindricity score along each PCA axis is used to select a canonical direction. Pose (R, t) and scale are then inferred with respect to the canonical axis. Appendix E provides further details.

7.4.4 Decomposition-Aware Optimization

We optimize the assembly parameters to maximize the objective \mathcal{O} (Eq. 7.1) in two stages. First, a differentiable phase minimizes a corresponding loss via gradient descent. Second, a discrete pruning phase removes primitives that degrade \mathcal{O} . The differentiable loss comprises three components addressing reconstruction fidelity, program parsimony, and program quality.

Reconstruction. The reconstruction loss is a differentiable surrogate for \mathcal{R} in Eq. 7.2. We supervise the predicted occupancy field $\hat{o}(\mathbf{p}) = \sigma(-\beta \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{p}))$ of the current assembly against the ground-truth occupancy $o(\mathbf{p})$. Samples \mathbf{p} are drawn uniformly from the shape’s volume and densely near its surface. To better reconstruct thin, high-curvature structures, each point is weighted by the principal curvature $\kappa(\mathbf{p})$ of the target mesh. The loss is evaluated only within a spatial mask $\mathcal{M} = \{\mathbf{p} \mid \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{p}) < \tau\}$ to focus optimization on signals from the assembly’s vicinity.

$$w(\mathbf{p}) = 1 + \sigma(\kappa(\mathbf{p})), \quad (7.7)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{M}|} \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{M}} w(\mathbf{p}) (\hat{o}(\mathbf{p}) - o(\mathbf{p}))^2.$$

Parsimony. To encourage compact assemblies, each primitive i is assigned a stochastic existence variable $q_i \in (0, 1)$ sampled via a Gumbel-Softmax distribution. Its signed distance field is then modulated as $f_i^*(\mathbf{p}) = q_i f_i(\mathbf{p}) + (1 - q_i)$, which smoothly erodes primitives with low existence probability. The parsimony

Method	Reconstruction Quality				Program Quality			
	IOU (\uparrow)	BiSurfIOU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	EMD (\downarrow)	#Prims (\downarrow)	Overlap (\downarrow)	IntraPrim (\downarrow)	InterPrim (\uparrow)
3DGen-Prim Dataset								
PA [212]	34.62	30.56	7.588	0.119	19.81	0.402	0.359	0.238
PA (TTO)	53.73	37.90	0.742	0.131	64.87	0.493	0.244	0.156
MPS [104]	82.67	71.53	0.884	0.093	42.96	0.684	0.250	0.157
Ours	88.74	80.19	0.168	0.073	23.98	0.210	0.244	0.207
Toy4K Dataset								
PA [212]	36.76	31.63	5.771	0.142	19.14	0.341	0.322	0.255
PA (TTO)	49.08	37.78	1.220	0.146	44.78	0.408	0.237	0.179
MPS [104]	80.60	72.75	1.147	0.086	30.62	0.588	0.245	0.201
Ours	89.92	85.66	0.154	0.067	23.67	0.208	0.221	0.202

Table 7.2: Evaluation on 3DGen-Prim [224] and Toys4K [171] datasets. Our method achieves the best reconstruction and program quality scores simultaneously—improving IOU by 6–9 points while using roughly half as many primitives. Gold = best, Silver = second best.

loss penalizes the expected number of active primitives: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{count}} = \sum_i q_i$.

Quality. To improve editability and prevent geometrically entangled or overly blended assemblies, we add a structural regularizer that combines overlap and smooth-union consistency losses:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{qual}} = \underbrace{\max(1, \sum_i \hat{o}_i(\mathbf{p}))}_{\mathcal{L}_{\text{overlap}}} + \underbrace{\hat{o}(\mathbf{p}) - \min(\sum_i \hat{o}_i(\mathbf{p}), 1)}_{\mathcal{L}_{\text{union}}},$$

where \hat{o}_i is the occupancy of primitive i . The $\mathcal{L}_{\text{overlap}}$ term penalizes regions where multiple primitives are simultaneously active, discouraging redundant coverage. The $\mathcal{L}_{\text{union}}$ term penalizes regions that are occupied by the smooth union assembly but not by any of the independent primitives, discouraging excessive blending.

The total differentiable loss is the weighted sum of these components:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} + \lambda_{\text{count}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{count}} + \lambda_{\text{qual}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{qual}}. \quad (7.8)$$

Pruning. After the differentiable optimization converges, a discrete pruning step further simplifies the assembly. Primitives with negligible volume or contribution are tested for removal, and deletions are greedily accepted if they improve the primary objective \mathcal{O} .

7.5 Experiments

Datasets. We evaluate on two datasets capturing generated and real-world assets. As the *3DGen-Prim* dataset [194] is not public, we recreate it using 510 prompts from 3DGen-Bench [224] with the Hunyuan3D-

2.1 [178] generator. Our second dataset contains 500 geometrically diverse shapes from Toys4K [171], selected via farthest-point sampling.

Metrics. We evaluate *reconstruction accuracy* and *program quality*. For accuracy, we use standard metrics: voxel IoU (128^3), Chamfer Distance (CD), and Earth Mover’s Distance (EMD) over 2048 randomly sampled surface points. We also report a *Bidirectional Surface IoU (BiSurfIoU)* to better capture surface fidelity, computed as the mean of IoU scores from near-surface points sampled on both the target and reconstructed shapes, with the latter surface extracted via dual contouring of the SDF. For program quality, we introduce four metrics. Program length ($|z|$) and *Overlap Ratio* (the volumetric percentage of the shape covered by multiple primitives) measure parsimony and redundancy. To quantify semantic coherence, we use two metrics based on PartField features [102]. After associating surface points on the target mesh to their nearest primitive, we compute: *IntraPrim*, the mean feature variance within each primitive (lower is better), and *InterPrim*, the average nearest-neighbor distance between primitive feature centroids (higher is better). These scores are aggregated using a size-weighted average.

Baselines. We compare our method against two state-of-the-art approaches. *Primitive Anything (PA)*[212] is a learning-based method trained on a large dataset of manually annotated shapes to predict assemblies of cuboids, cylinders, and ellipsoids from point cloud inputs. Following the original work, we also report its test-time optimization variant, *PA (TTO)*, which refines its predictions using Chamfer Distance. *Marching Primitives (MPS)*[104] serves as a strong optimization-based baseline that directly optimizes a superquadric-based assembly from an SDF grid to achieve state-of-the-art reconstruction fidelity. We run MPS at 128 voxel resolution to match our input. We omit comparisons to methods outperformed by MPS [103, 38] or those without public code [194, 191].

Implementation Details. All experiments use a fixed set of hyperparameters unless stated otherwise. ResFit runs for a maximum of 10 fitting rounds or until convergence, with each round applying 7 iterations of MSD. The high-level objective O (Eq. 7.1) combines curvature-weighted surface IoU with a program-length penalty ($\alpha = 10^{-3}$). During optimization, the loss weights are set to $\lambda_{\text{count}} = 10^{-3}$ and $\lambda_{\text{qual}} = 10^{-2}$ (Eq. 7.8). Appendix E provides additional optimization details and ablations.

7.5.1 Parsimonious High-Fidelity Assemblies

Table 7.2 summarizes the reconstruction and program quality metrics on both datasets. Across all reconstruction measures, our method improves IoU scores by +6.1 points on 3DGen-Prim and +9.3 points on Toys4K over prior work. We attribute this performance to the expressivity of the SuperFrustum primitive and the iterative analysis-optimization loop of ResFit.

Figure 7.5: Our method reconstructs target shapes with high geometric fidelity and produces more interpretable assemblies, using compact, minimally-overlapping primitives. In contrast, Primitive Anything [212] (PA) and Marching Primitives [104] (MPS) often lose fine structure and generate assemblies with substantial primitive overlap.

These reconstruction gains are accompanied by improved program quality. Our assemblies use approximately half as many primitives as Marching Primitives while reducing volumetric overlap by over 3 \times . The inferred primitives also demonstrate high semantic coherence: our method achieves the lowest *IntraPrim* scores, indicating high semantic purity within primitives, and among the highest *InterPrim* scores, reflecting meaningful distinctions between parts. These results demonstrate that ResFit produces assemblies that are simultaneously more *accurate*, *compact*, and *semantically interpretable*.

Qualitative comparisons in Figure 7.5 corroborate these findings. Our assemblies exhibit higher geometric fidelity and are more interpretable, using a compact set of non-overlapping, semantically aligned primitives. In contrast, baseline reconstructions can show lower fidelity on complex structures and tend to produce assemblies with greater primitive overlap.

7.5.2 Ablative Analysis

Primitive Assembly Design. Table 7.3 compares different primitive families and composition operators. Our full SuperFrustum formulation achieves the highest reconstruction fidelity. Disabling smooth unions reduces accuracy and increases overlap, as continuous volumes must then be formed by intersecting primitives rather than by smooth blending. SuperPrimitive [135], a variant of our primitive without tapering or bending, also lowers accuracy, confirming that these degrees of freedom are important for capturing curved and non-uniform structures. Substituting our primitive with cuboids or superquadrics (SQs) further degrades performance. SQs are particularly susceptible to poor local minima when their axes misalign with the target geometry—an issue that methods like MPS mitigate via non-differentiable heuristics such as periodic

	S. Union	IOU	CD	#Prims	Overlap
Cuboid	✗	82.33	0.129	20.49	0.298
S Q	✗	76.50	0.523	18.17	0.286
S P	✗	86.66	0.134	21.36	0.291
S F	✗	87.15	0.173	18.68	0.257
S F	✓	88.37	0.147	21.46	0.199

Table 7.3: Primitive representation ablation: SuperFrustum delivers superior performance over Cuboids, Superquadrics (SQ), and SuperPrimitive (SP) (ref. Section 7.5.2). Combining SuperFrustum with smooth union further improves performance.

Step	Method	IOU	CD	#Prims	Overlap
Single	CoACD	86.56	0.368	26.67	0.226
Single	MSD	87.95	0.337	28.17	0.236
ResFit	CoACD	88.02	0.290	24.18	0.214
ResFit	MSD	89.86	0.157	23.46	0.207

Table 7.4: Fitting and decomposition ablation: ResFit, which interleaves analysis and optimization, outperforms a single-shot fitting approach (cf. Section 7.5.2). Moreover, pairing ResFit with MSD yields better results than using CoACD [197].

axis-flipping, which are excluded from our controlled comparison.

Decomposition and Fitting Strategy. Table 7.4 compares our iterative ResFit procedure against a single-shot fitting baseline, using both MSD and CoACD for initialization. The single-shot approach optimizes all primitives simultaneously after the initial decomposition. This makes it sensitive to the initial partition, as it has no mechanism to reallocate capacity to unexplained regions, resulting in less accurate and less compact assemblies.

In contrast, ResFit uses multiple refinement rounds to progressively reallocate primitives toward residual errors and prune where unnecessary. This iterative process achieves higher fidelity with fewer primitives and lower overlap. When comparing decomposition strategies, MSD consistently outperforms CoACD. MSD’s ability to produce non-convex partitions provides better initializations for our primitives, especially on the curved, hollow, and branching geometries as shown in Figure 7.4.

Timing. On the Toys4K test set, the full ten-round version of ResFit takes 652.6 s per shape on average. However, even a two-round variant offers a strong quality–time trade-off: it runs in 184.1 s while achieving 86.54 IOU with only 15.54 primitives. This matches—and slightly exceeds—the reconstruction accuracy of MPS at 256^3 resolution (86.30 IOU) while using *over* $5\times$ fewer primitives and a comparable runtime (194.6 s). PA (58.3 s) and MPS (37.9 s at 128^3) are faster but produce lower-quality assemblies. We note that ResFit is not yet optimized for speed; dedicated CUDA kernels for SuperFrustum may reduce runtime.

Figure 7.6: Optimizing per-primitive spherical 2D textures against a textured mesh yields *editable* and *deployable* assets.

Method	IOU	CD	#Prims	Overlap
CAPRI-Net [216]	84.46	0.100	23.0	N/A
Ours (Solid)	82.64	0.192	14.18	0.342
Ours	88.30	0.127	13.16	0.186

Table 7.5: CSG inference on the ABC dataset [80]: Our method achieves comparable reconstruction accuracy to CAPRI-Net [216] while using significantly fewer primitives.

7.6 Applications

Our representation enables several downstream uses that combine visual quality, editability, and analytic structure. We highlight four such applications; Appendix E provides implementation details.

Editable and Deployable Asset Generation. Our primitives are simultaneously compact, editable, and capable of high-fidelity reconstruction, allowing them to serve directly as deployable 3D assets. To produce textured assemblies, we associate each primitive with a local 2D spherical texture map and optimize it against the target textured mesh. The resulting textured assemblies can be deployed directly in real-time sphere-traced scenes while remaining editable (see Fig. 7.6).

Inferring Canonical CSG Programs. Although our framework is designed for smooth, soft-union assemblies, it can also infer discrete Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) programs composed of canonical solids. We achieve this by constraining the parameters of SuperFrustum to be a barycentric interpolation among canonical shapes—cuboid, cylinder, cone, and sphere—within the SuperFrustum formulation. Despite the lack of subtraction as a compositional operator, our primitive space natively contains “subtracted” shapes via the onion operator, which we include in the list of canonical shapes. Fitting under these constraints yields solid CSG programs that remain compact and interpretable. In Table 7.5, we compare this constrained version of our method, named “solid,” to CAPRI-Net [216] on a randomly sampled subset of the ABC dataset [80] containing 100 samples. Our approach achieves nearly the same CSG reconstruction accuracy as CAPRI-Net while using roughly two-thirds as many primitives. As shown in Fig. 7.7, our inferred programs produce

Figure 7.7: (left) Our method can infer CSG programs using canonical solids (e.g., cylinders, cuboids; cf. Sec. 7.6), producing far more parsable and structured trees than CAPRI-Net [216]. (right) ResFit enables finer, semantically consistent part segmentation. Row 1 shows the coarse semantic regions provided in Part-Objaverse. Row 2 shows the primitive assemblies inferred by ResFit. Intersecting each coarse region with its corresponding assembly (Row 3) yields meaningful sub-parts while remaining strictly within the original semantic boundaries.

Figure 7.8: Our method can infer primitive assemblies from images by leveraging text-to-3D models (Hunyuan3D-2.1 [178]).

cleaner, less entangled assemblies—owing to the analytic expressivity of our primitives and the structured refinement in ResFit.

Image-to-Primitive Assembly. Our method can be seamlessly combined with 3D generative models to produce primitive assemblies from images. In Figure 7.8, we use Hunyuan3D-2.1 [178] with ResFit on samples from the 3DGen-Bench suite [224].

Semantic Segmentation Enrichment. Manually annotating parts can be expensive, so datasets often provide only coarse-grained annotations. ResFit can help refine these annotations. In Figure 7.7, we intersect coarse semantic labels from the Part-Objaverse dataset [209] with our primitive assemblies to enhance segmentation granularity. As a result, we subdivide large parts into functionally meaningful subcomponents without drifting outside their semantic boundaries. This suggests a promising direction for integrating

analytic decomposition as a prior for open-world part segmentation tasks.

7.7 Conclusions

This chapter addressed annotation-free acquisition for a widely useful symbolic representation: *assemblies of analytic primitives*. Given raw or generated 3D geometry, the goal was to recover not only a faithful surface approximation, but a compact symbolic structure with editable parts and parameters. We introduced an end-to-end framework that converts raw 3D shapes into compact, editable, and high-fidelity assemblies, and showed that it shifts the reconstruction–parsimony Pareto frontier across benchmarks.

A central takeaway is the value of *co-designing* the representation and the acquisition procedure. SuperFrustum was designed not only for expressivity and editability, but for *inverse modeling*: a compact parameterization with an SDF that is differentiable with respect to parameters almost everywhere, enabling reliable gradient-based fitting. Conversely, the structure of Residual Primitive Fitting (ResFit) is tailored to what the primitive can represent: by combining global shape analysis with local optimization on residual geometry, it can propose and refine primitives in non-convex and curved regions, recovering parts such as tires, handles, and bent appendages that are difficult for purely local or purely convex fitting strategies. Together, these choices make it possible to recover assemblies that are simultaneously accurate, parsimonious, and directly editable. Alongside MiGumi, this chapter completes the dissertation’s direct-optimization thread: optimization becomes an acquisition strategy when the representation, initialization, and objective are designed together around the structure one wants to recover.

While our focus here is additive primitive assemblies, the SuperFrustum itself is compatible with richer symbolic formalisms, including CSG trees that mix additive and subtractive operations. Developing a corresponding acquisition pipeline for SuperFrustum within full CSG—including discrete structure search and robust handling of subtraction—is an important direction for future work.

Finally, acquisition alone does not solve every downstream problem. Even parsimonious assemblies can expose hundreds of continuous parameters, and directly editing them remains difficult for users unfamiliar with the representation. This challenge is not unique to primitive assemblies: similar complexity arises in material graphs, procedural asset models, and structured scene representations. The next chapter steps back from the individual systems to synthesize what these acquisition strategies suggest for future symbolic-geometry tools: how to move from unannotated measurements to useful structure, and how that structure can support controlled manipulation, fabrication, and design reuse.

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

8.1 Conclusions

This dissertation studied a gap between geometric data and geometric use. Meshes, point clouds, images, and neural fields describe where geometry is, but they usually do not expose the parts, operations, constraints, or design intent needed for editing, fabrication, synthesis, or reasoning. Symbolic geometry addresses this gap by representing geometry through such structure. The central question of this thesis has been how to acquire that structure when paired symbolic annotations are unavailable.

The thesis argues that this annotation scarcity is not incidental. New symbolic representations are often introduced precisely because existing data formats do not expose the structure a task requires. A representation for language-guided editing, programmatic pattern manipulation, millable joinery, or primitive assembly fitting is useful because it names structure that was previously implicit. Waiting for large corpora of expert-authored examples would therefore make many such representations impractical.

The chapters explore three strategies for annotation-free acquisition. PARSEL uses foundation-model priors, but grounds them with symbolic geometric reasoning. SIRI and Pattern Analogies use in-domain synthetic supervision, showing how rewrites, edits, executors, and invariants can become learning signal. MiGumi and SuperFit use direct optimization, showing that fitting becomes effective when the representation, objective, and initialization are designed together.

Together, these systems support a broader claim: symbolic representations should be designed not only for expression, but also for acquisition. A language that can be executed, rewritten, sampled, constrained, or optimized gives learning and search concrete footholds. This couples representation design with acquisition. Rather than choosing only symbolic forms that already have labeled datasets, we can design representations around the structure a domain needs, while also designing the mechanisms by which that structure can be recovered.

8.2 Limitations

Symbolic geometry does not remove the burden of choosing a representation; it makes that burden explicit. Different tasks require different symbolic vocabularies, and a poor choice of symbols can make acquisition brittle or force a system to explain geometry through the wrong handles. The inverse problem is also underdetermined: many symbolic descriptions can produce similar measurements, and the most accurate reconstruction is not necessarily the most editable, manufacturable, compact, or semantically meaningful one.

The acquisition strategies studied in this dissertation inherit their own failure modes. Foundation models can propose plausible but invalid structure. Synthetic supervision can reproduce the biases of the generator, sampler, or rewriter. Direct optimization can overfit the metric it is given, especially when the objective only partially captures the intended downstream use. These limitations suggest that symbolic acquisition systems should expose uncertainty rather than presenting a single recovered structure as definitive.

Evaluation remains another central limitation. Most acquisition systems can measure agreement between an observation and a generated artifact, but the purpose of symbolic geometry is usually downstream. An edit should preserve intent; a joint should fabricate and assemble; a primitive assembly should expose meaningful handles; a robot should be able to plan with the object model. These goals are harder to evaluate than reconstruction error. Progress therefore requires task-grounded metrics and executable checks that distinguish a merely accurate explanation from a useful one.

Finally, not every useful geometric detail is cleanly symbolic. Some domains will require hybrid representations in which symbolic structure coexists with dense residual geometry, learned priors, uncertainty estimates, or simulation-based validation. The goal is therefore not to replace all geometric data with symbols, but to recover the symbolic structure that is useful for a given task while preserving other forms of information where they are needed.

8.3 Future Work

The systems in this dissertation study three strategies for acquiring symbolic geometry when paired symbolic supervision is limited or unavailable: foundation-model priors, in-domain synthetic supervision, and direct optimization. A natural next step is to make these strategies interact more tightly. Foundation models can propose structure, optimization and execution can test it, and synthetic supervision can amortize what expensive search discovers. The central challenge is not merely to improve reconstruction, but to acquire symbolic structure that remains useful: editable by people, checkable by algorithms, and compatible with

the physical, functional, or aesthetic constraints of the domain.

8.3.1 Hybrid Acquisition Systems

The acquisition strategies studied in this dissertation are most powerful when combined. Foundation models provide top-down priors: they can suggest likely parts, symmetries, semantic roles, functional regions, object categories, or construction patterns from language, images, video, and partial geometry. Direct optimization provides bottom-up accountability: it can fit continuous parameters, enforce contact or alignment, and reject candidates that do not explain the observed shape. In-domain synthetic supervision can then amortize what expensive search discovers, turning fitted programs and corrected failures into training data for faster prediction.

Primitive fitting is a natural testbed for such a hybrid system. A foundation model could first propose a coarse partition of the object into meaningful regions, such as handles, cavities, supports, repeated limbs, or functional faces. A SuperFit-like optimizer could then recover the analytic primitives, attachments, and continuous parameters that best explain each region. Once this pipeline succeeds on a subset of shapes, its outputs could be rendered, perturbed, masked, and observed from many viewpoints to train an amortized predictor.

Such a system would use each strategy where it is strongest. Foundation-model priors would handle semantic ambiguity and top-down decomposition. Optimization would recover metric fidelity and enforce representation constraints. Synthetic data would expose the predictor to occlusion, partial scans, category variation, and rare geometries without requiring manual symbolic labels. The resulting loop would repeatedly propose, fit, evaluate, repair, and retrain.

A practical hybrid pipeline should also keep uncertainty alive through this process. Instead of committing immediately to one decomposition or one program, the system could maintain a small set of symbolic hypotheses with different semantic partitions, primitive choices, and constraint structures. Optimization would refine each hypothesis, evaluators would compare them under multiple criteria, and an amortized model would learn from both the winners and the near-misses. This would better match the ambiguity of real observations: a single partial scan may support several plausible constructions, but only some will remain useful after editing, fabrication, or interaction constraints are applied.

8.3.2 Symbolic Geometry for Robotics

Robots sit at an uncomfortable boundary between perception and proof. On one side, they receive images, depth maps, tactile readings, language instructions, object detections, and partial reconstructions. On the

other, they must commit to actions that obey preconditions, contact constraints, safety limits, and task goals. Symbolic geometry is compelling in this setting because it can turn high-bandwidth perceptual evidence into a compact model that a planner can query, check, and use to construct plans whose assumptions are explicit.

This setting makes representation design especially important. A representation for offline editing or reconstruction may expose parts, parameters, and symmetries; a representation for robotics must additionally expose what matters for action. The useful symbols may include contact surfaces, graspable handles, joint axes, motion limits, affordances, object state, and constraints between operations. The question is therefore not only how to acquire symbolic geometry, but which symbolic vocabulary makes perception useful for planning.

Articulated objects illustrate the gap. Links, joints, and limits are an important layer for manipulation, but they do not fully describe how everyday objects operate. A latch may release a hinge, a button may change an appliance state, and an interlock may block motion until a condition holds. Future symbolic asset representations should therefore connect geometry to operational structure: which actions are permitted, which states persist, which motions are coupled, and which shortcuts are invalid. The simulator can still handle contact, collision, and robot motion; the symbolic model can specify the object-level rules that make interaction meaningful. Such assets will be critical for training embodied agents that can interact with real-world objects such as coffee-machines and crank-operated windows.

If such models can be acquired from perception, then robotic understanding can be evaluated beyond visual fidelity. A useful reconstruction should support safe plans, reject invalid actions, remain stable as new observations arrive, and expose uncertainty when the scene admits multiple plausible interpretations. In this sense, robotics pushes symbolic geometry toward a broader goal: acquiring representations that are not only accurate descriptions of shape, but reliable substrates for action.

8.3.3 High-Detail Engineered Assets

At the other end of the spectrum from online robotic perception are high-detail engineered assets, where the difficulty is not only recovering visible shape but preserving the structure that makes a design function. Exterior surfaces, internal supports, fasteners, tolerances, assemblies, materials, manufacturing processes, electrical or mechanical interfaces, and performance requirements can all matter at once. A useful acquisition method for such assets cannot stop at surface reconstruction. It must recover enough design structure to support adaptation: changing an observed or generated geometry while preserving the constraints and functional relationships that make the object work.

CAD adaptation is a useful way to make the challenge concrete. Given a CAD model of an object such as

a computer mouse, can a system adapt it to a newly observed geometry? A surface-only answer would miss much of the design. The internal screw posts, button travel, wheel clearance, shell thickness, ergonomic constraints, and manufacturability requirements may all need to change coherently. In a related version, the target is not another observation but a set of requirements: reduce weight, preserve stiffness, alter thermal behavior, or satisfy a new mechanical constraint while keeping the parts of the design that should not move.

The computational object in this setting often looks less like a single program and more like a large codebase. An asset may be spread across part files, assembly constraints, sketches, parameters, manufacturing annotations, and simulation setups. Agentic code editing and generation methods are therefore a natural outer loop: inspect the project, decide which files and parameters matter, modify several linked artifacts, run checks, and iterate on failures. A foundation model can use semantic and design context to select which files, components, sketches, parameters, or constraints should be opened for change; direct optimization can then adjust those selected degrees of freedom while leaving the rest of the asset fixed.

Evaluation becomes central in this setting. Reconstruction error is not enough: the adapted asset must satisfy geometric constraints, assembly constraints, manufacturing constraints, and performance constraints. Yet full mechanical, thermal, or manufacturing analysis may be too expensive to call throughout search, and many early candidates will not justify that cost. One promising route is to learn in-domain score functions from synthetic data: generate design variants with an executor or simulator, evaluate them under task-relevant metrics, and train a surrogate that provides cheaper feedback during adaptation. Expensive simulation can then be reserved for validation, while learned evaluators guide early exploration.

Finally, Human designers will still need control over the process. They may want to lock interfaces, preserve a manufacturing process, expose only a few adaptation handles, or inspect why an internal feature changed. The symbolic form matters because it can make those decisions explicit. Viewed this way, high-detail engineered assets bring together the main themes of the dissertation: foundation-model priors to interpret semantics and intent, synthetic supervision to turn executable design spaces into learnable processes, direct optimization to satisfy geometry and performance constraints, and symbolic representations that remain inspectable by the people who must ultimately use the design.

APPENDIX A

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS FOR PARSEL

A.1 Introduction

In this appendix, we present additional details regarding our system. First, we provide a brief overview of the videos associated with the ParSEL materials. Next, we describe our editing system PARSEL in Section A.3, including the pre-processing and post-processing steps. Section A.4 provides additional details regarding ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION. Finally, Section A.5 presents details regarding the experiments presented in Chapter 3.

A.2 Qualitative Videos

The following videos accompany the ParSEL materials:

1. The set of videos used in our perceptual study, located in `./videos/perceptual_study`.
2. A video titled `real_time_shape_variations.mp4`, which demonstrates how our analytical editing programs enable real-time exploration of shape variations. This is contrasted with a prior approach that uses online edit propagation, resulting in a laggy user experience.
3. A video titled `live_proxydural_modeling.mp4`, which shows our system being used to create a high-quality procedural model of 3D assets.

We encourage readers to watch these videos to fully understand the capabilities and limitations of our system.

Relation	Instantiation	Constraint
REFLECTIONSYMMETRY	ref_sym(\mathbb{H} , origin= \mathbf{o} , normal= \mathbf{n})	$\ \mathbf{H}_j - \mathbf{H}_i - 2((\mathbf{H}_i - \mathbf{o}) \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n}\ _\infty < \delta \forall \mathbf{H}_i, \mathbf{H}_j \in \mathbb{H}$
ROTATIONSYMMETRY	rot_sym(\mathbb{H} , point= \mathbf{o} , rot_mat= \mathbf{R})	$\ \mathbf{H}_j - \mathbf{o} + \mathbf{R}^n(\mathbf{H}_i - \mathbf{o})\ _\infty < \delta \forall \mathbf{H}_i, \mathbf{H}_j \in \mathbb{H}, n = i - j$
TRANSLATIONSYMMETRY	trans_sym(\mathbb{H} , delta= \mathbf{d})	$\ \mathbf{H}_j - (\mathbf{H}_i + \mathbf{d})\ _\infty < \delta \forall \mathbf{H}_i, \mathbf{H}_j \in \mathbb{H}, n = i - j$
POINTATTACHMENT	point_attach(\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B})	$\ M_a \mathbf{H}_i - M_b \mathbf{H}_j\ _\infty < \delta \forall a_n \in \mathbb{A}, b_n \in \mathbb{B}$
LINEATTACHMENT	line_attach(\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B})	$\ M_{a_n} \mathbf{H}_i - M_{b_n} \mathbf{H}_j\ _\infty < \delta \forall a_n \in \mathbb{A}, b_n \in \mathbb{B}, \{n \in \mathbb{Z} \mid 1 \leq n \leq 2\}$
FACEATTACHMENT	face_attach(\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B})	$\ M_{a_n} \mathbf{H}_i - M_{b_n} \mathbf{H}_j\ _\infty < \delta \forall a_n \in \mathbb{A}, b_n \in \mathbb{B}, \{n \in \mathbb{Z} \mid 1 \leq n \leq 4\}$
VOLUMEATTACHMENT	vol_attach(\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{B})	$\ M_{a_n} \mathbf{H}_i - M_{b_n} \mathbf{H}_j\ _\infty < \delta \forall a_n \in \mathbb{A}, b_n \in \mathbb{B}, \{n \in \mathbb{Z} \mid 1 \leq n \leq 8\}$

Table A.1: **Inter-Part Relations:** We list the different inter-part relations supported in our structured shape representation. In the first column, we annotate the type of each relation. The second column depicts the pseudo-code used to initialize these relations, providing a reference for the relation parameters. Finally, the last column depicts the constraints that are enforced as a consequence of each relation. Note that for the Attachment relations, M_i denotes the harmonic coordinates [74] for the corresponding point i .

A.3 Parameterized Shape Editing Details

A.3.1 Shape Abstraction

Inter-part Relations

As discussed in Chapter 3, our system considers two types of inter-part relations, namely ATTACHMENT relations and SYMMETRY relations. We consider multiple sub-types for each of these relations, which are presented in Table A.1.

First, we use three types of SYMMETRY relations: REFLECTIONSYMMETRY, ROTATIONSYMMETRY, and TRANSLATIONSYMMETRY. Each of these relations introduces constraints between the parts based on the parameters of the relation, allowing us to detect when a relation is broken.

Secondly, we model 4 types of inter-part ATTACHMENT relations, namely POINTATTACHMENT, LINEATTACHMENT, FACEATTACHMENT, and VOLUMEATTACHMENT. These attachments constrain the relative movement between parts, with the constraints becoming more restrictive as we move from Point to Volume. LINEATTACHMENTS are typically useful for modeling attachment between parts that ‘widen’ together, such as a chair’s seat and its back. FACEATTACHMENTS are useful for modeling attachment between parts that *radially* scale together, such as a TV’s display and its frame. Finally, VOLUMEATTACHMENTS are suitable for modeling the attachment between parts that must always be edited in the same fashion (i.e. the only way to satisfy VOLUMEATTACHMENTS is by having the same edit on both parts). While these attachment relations behave in different ways, they are all modeled using only point attachments, with line attachment in practice converting into two attachments, face attachment into four co-planar point attachments, and volume attachment into eight attachment points. Note that technically face attachments and volume attachments could be modeled with just three and four point attachments respectively.

The most important detail is that all these relations, the symmetry relations as well as the attachment relations, are automatically derived, and this process is described in Section A.3.3.

Virtual Part Hierarchy

The parts we consider are often hierarchical in nature; parts such as ‘back’ can often be composed of multiple subparts such as ‘back-support-bars’ and ‘back-top-bar’. However, performing edit propagation while considering such hierarchy becomes increasingly complicated and can lead to undesirable edits, such as scaling a set of parts when translating some parts and scaling others is preferable. Prior methods [229] do offer some solutions. However, we avoid modeling hierarchy so that we can avert introducing additional complexity in the analytical edit propagation technique. This can be explored in future work.

Therefore, all our parts are only at a leaf level with no hierarchy. We only allow hierarchy in one case, namely in the presence of `ROTATIONSYMMETRY` or `TRANSLATIONSYMMETRY` relations. When such relations are present, we instantiate a *virtual* parent part containing all the instances. This allows us to edit symmetry relations with edit operations such as `CHANGECOUNT` and `CHANGEDELTA`. When we create such *virtual* parts, we also create `ATTACHMENT` relations between the virtual part and the other parts.

Specifically, when considering virtual parts, we allow edits on the virtual part; this allows modeling edits on all the instances together as well as relation edits (`CHANGECOUNT` and `CHANGEDELTA`). To edit parts within a symmetry relation, such as when scaling only the central back slat, we automatically turn off the virtual part (and its attachment), reducing the shape back to a hierarchy-less graph.

A.3.2 Parameterized Shape Editing DSL

As described in Chapter 3, our DSL provides atomic edit operators for performing parameterized edits on the parts as well as relations in the input 3D asset. We enumerate these operators in Table A.2. We also present the algebraic form induced on the `OPERAND` by these operators.

As shown in the table, our DSL includes two relation editing operations, namely `CHANGECOUNT` and `CHANGEDELTA`. These edits affect the number of instances or the spacing between them in `TRANSLATIONSYMMETRY` and `ROTATIONSYMMETRY` relations. We apply these operators in two modes: (i) a *Top-Down* mode, where the relation configurations, such as count and spacing, are derived from the parent part (i.e. a virtual part containing all the instances in the symmetry group). This allows edits where scaling the parent virtual part affects the count or spacing between the instances; and (ii) a *Bottom-Up* mode, where the parent virtual part’s shape is derived from the relation configuration. To achieve this functionality, we first over-parameterize the relations. For instance, *TranslationSymmetry* is represented by five variables:

Edit Operators	Instantiation	Algebraic Form
TRANSLATE	<code>translate(\mathbf{H}_i, dir=\mathbf{n}, amt=x)</code>	$\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{H}_i^0 + x \cdot \mathbf{n}$
ROTATE	<code>rotate(\mathbf{H}_i, orig=\mathbf{o}, axis=\mathbf{n}, amt=x)</code>	$\mathbf{R}(x) = \cos(x)\mathbf{I} + \sin(x)[\mathbf{n}]_{\times} + (1 - \cos(x))\mathbf{nn}^T$ $\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{o} + \mathbf{R}(x)(\mathbf{H}_i^0 - \mathbf{o})$
SCALE1D	<code>scale_1D(\mathbf{H}_i, orig=\mathbf{o}, dir=\mathbf{n}, amt=x)</code>	$\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{o} + x(\mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{H}_i^0 - \mathbf{o}))\mathbf{n} + (\mathbf{H}_i^0 - \mathbf{o})$
SCALE2D	<code>scale_2D(\mathbf{H}_i, orig=\mathbf{o}, normal=\mathbf{n}, amt=x)</code>	$\mathbf{H}_i^c = \mathbf{H}_i^0 - \mathbf{o}$ $\mathbf{H}_i^p = \mathbf{H}_i^c - (\mathbf{H}_i^c \cdot \mathbf{n})\mathbf{n}$ $\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{o} + (1 + x)\mathbf{H}_i^p + (\mathbf{H}_i^c \cdot \mathbf{n})\mathbf{n}$
SCALE3D	<code>scale_3D(\mathbf{H}_i, orig=\mathbf{o}, amt=x)</code>	$\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{o} + (1 + x)(\mathbf{H}_i^0 - \mathbf{o})$
SHEAR	<code>shear(\mathbf{H}_i, orig=\mathbf{o}, normal=\mathbf{n}, dir=\mathbf{d}, amt=x)</code>	$\mathbf{H}_i^c = \mathbf{H}_i^0 - \mathbf{o}$ $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{I} + x\mathbf{d} \otimes \mathbf{n}$ $\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{o} + \mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{H}_i^c$
CHANGECOUNT	<code>change_count($SymR_i$, amt=x)</code>	-
CHANGEDELTA	<code>change_delta($SymR_i$, amt=x)</code>	-
KEEPPFIXED	<code>keep_fixed(\mathbf{H}_i)</code>	$\mathbf{H}_i(x) = \mathbf{H}_i^0$

Table A.2: **DSL commands:** We list the parameterized editing operators provided in our DSL. Each command is parameterized by a variable x , which controls the edit magnitude. We omit the algebraic form of CHANGECOUNT and CHANGEDELTA, the two operators applied to symmetry relations, due to their complexity. Note that the initial 6 operators can also be applied only on part features such as a face, edge, or vertex, enabling non-affine transforms.

its *start-point*, *mid-point*, *end-point*, *count*, and *delta-vector*. This allows us to flexibly explore edits on any of these features, such as changing the count by introducing new edits next to the *edit-point*. Secondly, we replicate these points, marking them as points of the *virtual parent*, and create virtual ATTACHMENT relations between the points and their virtual parent counterparts. For instance, we create an ATTACHMENT relation between the *start-point* of the relation and the *start-point* in the virtual parent part. This allows us to *analytically* consider how the parent should be updated as the relation is updated, or vice-versa. Similarly, ROTATIONSYMMETRY relations are also over-parameterized by symbolic expressions for their *arc length*, *radius*, *count*, and *angle*, which are then used to communicate edits between the parent virtual part and the relation. Note that we currently only support editing of closed loop ROTATIONSYMMETRY groups.

A.3.3 Pre-Processing Input 3D Assets

Given a 3D mesh as input, we utilize prior work [193] to infer the reflection, translation, and rotation symmetries in the shape. This approach performs ICP between mesh parts with the same label to detect these relations. We alter the algorithm slightly to fit our needs. Specifically, we only allow translation and rotation when there are more than two parts, and only consider axis-aligned reflection symmetry relations. We also avoid considering hierarchies of such symmetry groups (for instance, translation symmetry of rotation symmetries) as such hierarchies tend to occur less frequently in the man-made objects we considered.

To create the attachment relations, we utilize the overlaps between parts. First, we ascertain whether two parts have an attachment relation by checking whether points sampled on one part are contained in the other part’s bounding box, and vice versa. Once an attachment is detected, we must decide the type of attachment between the parts. Attachments are classified as PointAttachment, LineAttachment, FaceAttachment, or VolumeAttachment based on the number of shared planes of intrinsic symmetry between the part and their intersection region.

This is computed by the following process:

1. First, we generate a point cloud of the intersection region by sampling points on one part’s surface and rejecting those that are outside the other part’s bounding box. This process is repeated for both parts.
2. Next, for each part, we calculate the *intersection-shared symmetry plane count*. We consider the number of intrinsic symmetry planes of its bounding box about which the intersection point cloud is symmetric as well.
3. The symmetry order of the attachment is assigned as the minimum of the *intersection-shared symmetry plane count* of both parts.

We permit one exception: we directly mark attachment between a part contained inside another part as having the highest symmetry order (i.e. 3). The attachment relations are then derived based on the symmetry order, with order 0 mapping to POINTATTACHMENT and 3 mapping to VOLUMEATTACHMENT.

Extending Part Labels

Additionally, we automatically enhance each part’s label with verbal directional phrases such as “front” and “back” to capture its relative positioning among other instances with the same label. These phrases help the LLM discern which instance to edit when the edit intent itself contains directional specifications (for instance, in ‘scale the *front* legs.’).

To perform this task, we first compute the relative placement vectors for each part within a shared label group, such as all parts containing the label ‘leg’. The relative placement vector is computed with respect to the center of all the parts. Then, based on the alignment of these vectors with the cardinal directions, we assign terms such as ‘front’ and ‘back-right’, which are then used to extend the labels.

When a group has more than two parts, we also separately identify whether they are approximately arranged in a rotational pattern or a straight line. This is done by calculating the angle created between the parts and the center. Based on this, different sets of directional phrases are used. For instance, four legs along a line going left to right are assigned the labels ‘left’, ‘left-center’, ‘right-center’, and ‘right’, whereas if they are approximately rotationally arranged, they are given the labels ‘left-back’, ‘left-front’, ‘right-back’,

Figure A.1: **Post-Processing**: Extreme deformation under our system can cause gaps to appear in the 3D mesh. With the post-processing we describe in Section A.3.4, which employs screened Poisson surface reconstruction (SPR) [77], these gaps can be fixed, though with a detrimental effect on the shape’s material.

and ‘right-front’. Groups with more than five labels, such as rungs in a bed’s ladder, are simply provided numeric indices as the directional phrase.

We found this approach provided correct labels for the majority of shapes considered, requiring minimal manual adjustment to the labels, particularly when parts are arranged in a non-trivial pattern. We emphasize that this is only implemented to help the LLMs and has no effect on our edit propagation algorithm. In future work, we expect this framework to be replaced with methods that leverage foundation models to consider inter-group part arrangements similar to PartSLIP [101].

A.3.4 Post-Processing Edited 3D Assets

3D assets are edited in PARSEL with part-level deformations and symmetry group modifications. Both of these operations can lead to the creation of holes in the 3D asset’s mesh, particularly when the user sets a high edit magnitude. In Figure A.1 (c) we show this in effect, where deforming the legs of a chair results in gaps between the chair legs and the seat. Therefore, after editing with the parametric editing programs, certain 3D assets require additional post-processing to improve edited asset quality.

Note that this artifact is also present in prior edit propagation methods. Prior approaches [229] employ an intricate approach, where a surface-based deformation approach [98] is used with virtual edges constructed between the points and the surface feature curves extracted using [132]. However, it does not resolve all mesh-related issues. We instead use a surface-reconstruction-based method to correct such artifacts. Given an edited 3D asset, we perform the following steps:

1. First, a dense point cloud is sampled on the deformed mesh (with 200000 points) using Poisson disk sampling.
2. We then employ screened Poisson surface reconstruction [77] to reconstruct a 3D mesh from the point cloud.
3. This mesh can often be dense, hence we perform mesh decimation using quadric-error-based edge

collapse.

4. Next, we partition this mesh into part-level mesh fragments. To perform this, first we extract all the vertices of the original deformed mesh, and simply transfer the label from these vertices to the reconstructed mesh vertices using a nearest neighbor lookup. The part labels are then used to partition the reconstructed mesh into fragments.
5. Finally, we transfer the material from the original part to the reconstructed part mesh. We transfer the vertex UV coordinates from the original (deformed) mesh to the reconstructed mesh using nearest neighbor lookup as well.

The results of this process are shown in Figure A.1 (d). We found this approach to be effective at filling small-to-medium gaps between the deformed parts while largely maintaining the 3D asset quality.

However, similar to prior approaches [229], we emphasize that this approach is only a stop-gap, and only serves as an additional utility function to demonstrate the effectiveness of the edit propagation mechanism. Fixing holes in edited meshes is an interesting research direction in itself, with many works [56] specifically targeting hole correction. In future work, we hope to leverage such approaches to improve the output from our method and maintain the quality of the 3D asset after deformation.

A.4 Analytical Edit Propagation Details

A.4.1 Pseudo-code for Analytical Edit Propagation

We present the pseudo-code for our system in Algo. 1, Algo. 2, and Algo. 3.

Algo. 1 provides the pseudo-code for the overall editing process. First, the LLM is prompted to return the *relation-validity*, *seed-edit*, and *type-hints*. Then our ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION technique is applied to the *seed-edit* with the *type-hints*.

Algo. 2 provides the pseudo-code for the edit propagation framework used in our system. Note that broken relations are gathered based on the broken constraints (\mathbb{C} , listed in A.1). The function `get_part_to_edit` returns a part that should be edited based on the broken relations. Following CSP literature, we use the Minimum Entropy Heuristic (MinE) and select the part with the most relations, since it is likely to have the fewest constraint-satisfying edits.

Finally, Algo. 3 provides the pseudo-code for the analytical edit solver. Here, the function `cas_solve` deploys a Computer Algebra System solver [117] to infer function assignments to the symbolic variable Y that satisfy the constraint equation eq.

Algorithm 1: PARSEL Overview

```
generate_program(shape, edit_request):  
    shape = set_sym_relations(shape, edit_request)  
    init_edit = get_init_edit(shape, edit_request)  
    edit_hints = get_edit_hints(shape, edit_request)  
    program = propagate(shape, init_edit, edit_hints)  
    return program
```

A.4.2 Analytical Edit Solver

In this step, we are tasked with introducing new parameterized edits that restore and preserve the broken relations across the input range. As discussed in Chapter 3, our strategy involves searching only over a subset of feasible PARAM assignments. The feasible PARAMS assignments are created using hexahedron features such as face centers, vertices, and local axis directions. To create these operators, we first collect a set of ‘feasible’ points (the center, face centers, corners, and edge centers), yielding 27 3D points, and a set of ‘feasible’ directions (the global cardinal directions as well as local cardinal directions). These feasible points and directions are then used to create the edit candidates. These edit candidates are then merged based on the equivalence between the edit expressions they create. We note that this simple sampling process creates an abundant quantity of edit operators to consider. However, since our analytical solving process is embarrassingly parallel, we are still able to search for edits in a reasonable duration.

nhbd-edits Parameterization

nhbd-edits address the fact that the PARAM required to edit a part may not always be derivable from one of its features. Therefore, when all the candidates in \mathbb{E}_R fail, we introduce additional candidates that contain PARAM assignments based on the features of other *edited* hexahedrons. We also introduce edit candidates with PARAM assignments based on the relative arrangement of the two parts, such as when one part is being scaled, moving the other part along the direction connecting the two parts is a potential translation edit candidate.

Edit Selection

For each candidate from the edit candidate set \mathbb{E}_R , our analytical edit solver infers plausible functional assignments to the AMOUNT parameter that create valid parameterized edits, i.e. edits that restore and preserve all the broken relations (for the part being edited). This results in a set of feasible edits, from which we must select the most suitable edit. We now introduce the criterion employed for this task.

At a high level, we select the edit that minimizes ARAP deformation energy [170], while maximally

Dataset	N. Shapes	N. Parts			N. Attachment Relations			N. Symmetry Relations		
		Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max
PartNet Lamp	7	5	11.57	30	4	7.00	12	0	1.71	4
PartNet Chair	15	7	16.40	31	2	18.93	42	1	5.60	11
PartNet Table	9	5	12.89	20	3	14.44	41	1	6.22	16
PartNet Storage Furniture	13	12	21.67	48	17	51.83	117	3	8.50	18
PartNet Bed	7	17	44.25	81	31	77.25	110	7	24.88	53
PartNet (<i>dev-set</i>)	51	5	19.5	81	2	31.82	117	0	7.96	42
CoMPaT3D++ (<i>test-set</i>)	50	3	12.5	23	1	19.54	72	0	4.8	14

Table A.3: **Dataset Statistics:** We provide statistics of the two datasets we use. We note that our *dev-set* explores a wider range of structural complexity, whereas our *test-set* explores a wider range of semantic variations (as it contains shapes from 21 different categories).

Algorithm 2: ANALYTICAL EDIT PROPAGATION

```

propagate(shape, init_edit):
    all_edits, finish = init_edit, false
    while !finish:
        propagate(all_edits)
        broken = gather_broken_relations(shape)
        if len(broken) > 0:
            part = get_part_to_edit(broken)
            edit, unfixed = solve(broken, part)
            reject_relations(unfixed)
            all_edits.add(edit)
        else:
            finish = true
            clean_up()
    return all_edits

```

preserving the edited part’s intrinsic symmetry planes. First, we remove all the edit candidates that result in a high ARAP energy. Next, each edit, based on its type and PARAM, is assigned the number of intrinsic symmetry planes of the hexahedron it retains. For instance, edits such as translation, rotation, and isotropic scaling do not affect any symmetry planes; the hexahedron is symmetric about axially aligned planes passing through its center even after being edited. On the other hand, edits such as Face Scaling disrupt this symmetry, and hence retain a lower number of intrinsic symmetry planes. From these edits, we select the set with the highest number of retained symmetry planes. Within this set, we simply select the edit that results in the least amount of ARAP energy.

We note that selecting directly based on ARAP energy works in most cases; however, considering symmetry planes helps in a few cases. This is mainly because when editing shapes, the user-desired edit may not necessarily match the minimum-ARAP-energy candidate. For example, most edits contain stretching, which, despite higher ARAP-energy cost, can actually be the preferred edit in many cases. The consideration of both ARAP energy and intrinsic symmetry planes results in a criterion closer to human preference.

Algorithm 3: ANALYTICAL EDIT SOLVER

```
solve(broken, part, edit_hints):
    Y = new_var()
    solution_set, scored_solutions = {}, {}
    candidates = get_candidates(part, edit_hints)
    constraints = get_constraints(part, broken)
    for edit in candidates:
        propagate(edit, amount=Y)
        for eq in constraints:
            solutions = cas_solve(eq, Y)
            solution_set.add(solutions)
    for sol in solution_set:
        score = count_satisfying(sol, constraints)
        unfixed = get_broken(sol, constraints)
        scored_solutions.add((score, unfixed))
    if len(solution_set) > 0:
        edit, unfixed = get_best(scored_solutions)
    else:
        edit, unfixed = None, broken
    return edit, unfixed
```

A.5 Experimental Details

A.5.1 Dataset

We construct our dataset by sourcing shapes from PartNet [126] and the CoMPaT3D++ [169] dataset. We provide more details of the dataset here.

First, we present the statistics of the parsed structured shape representation derived from the mesh models. Table A.3 reports these statistics. We note that our *dev-set*, containing shapes from PartNet, contains a wider array of shape sizes than the *test-set* created with CoMPaT3D++. Furthermore, since shapes in PartNet are often labeled at a finer level, more symmetry relations such as translation and rotation can be detected with them. In contrast, CoMPaT3D++ presents a wider array of shape categories. Finally, we observe that CoMPaT3D++ models are closer to real-world 3D assets, and as a result they (1) often have more intricate ATTACHMENT relations, and (2) tend to use closed-surface parts, which consequently helps us avoid the post-processing pipeline discussed in Section A.3.4.

The materials associated with Appendix A include all edit requests used for both datasets. Furthermore, the provided perceptual study videos also show shapes with their corresponding edit requests. As can be seen in the edit requests, the use of LLMs also allows us to support broader, more nuanced, and longer edit requests.

A.5.2 LLM Prompts

The materials associated with Appendix A provide the prompts we utilize for our system. In total, our system employs 4 prompts, one each for inferring the *seed-edit* and *type-hints*, and two for *relation validity*, one customized for REFLECTIONSYMMETRY and the other for ROTATIONSYMMETRY and TRANSLATIONSYMMETRY. We found that having these two separate prompts improved the LLM’s ability to correctly infer the *relation-validity*. We also employ two additional prompts, one for each extension.

We follow a common pattern for all the prompts, providing the following sequence of instructions: (i) the task overview, (ii) the output specification, (iii) examples, (iv) verbal shape description and edit request, (v) steps for performing the task, and (vi) guidelines. The last two details play a crucial role in improving the LLM’s ability to perform the tasks.

A.5.3 Program Quality Metrics

We introduce multiple metrics in Chapter 3 to analyze the different methods from various perspectives. First, we present the details of the metrics used for measuring the quality of inferred programs. These metrics compare the inferred programs against the ‘GT’ program annotated by a Human-Solver inference process. These metrics are used to measure quality across three criteria:

Programmatic ($\mathcal{J}(prog)$)

This metric assesses how closely the inferred programs match the GT programs. First, we convert each program statement (or edit operator) into a string signature consisting of only the type of edit operation, and its operand. Then, this metric is computed by measuring the Jaccard similarity between the set of edit signatures derived from the inferred program and the GT program.

Geometric ($\mathcal{D}(geo)$)

This metric measures the geometric distance between the shape edited with the inferred programs and the shape edited with the GT program. First, for both programs, we set the user-controlled parameter x to a fixed value (0.35). Then, for each part, we compute the L_2 distance between the hexahedron vertices deformed by the inferred program and the corresponding ones deformed by the GT program. This metric is computed by summing up these L_2 distances across the program.

Figure A.2: **Perceptual Study Interface:** We provide a screenshot of the questionnaire provided to the participants in our two-alternative forced-choice perceptual study. The videos used for this study are included in the materials associated with Appendix A.

Structural (%Rel)

This metric quantifies the percentage of inter-part relations whose state (broken vs. maintained) matches the relation’s state under the ground truth (GT) program. As all our relations can be represented as parameterized constraints as well, we simply check and annotate each relation’s state under the GT program and the inferred program. This metric is then computed by measuring the fraction of relations for which the annotations match. Note that we only consider relations that involve at least one edited part.

A.5.4 LLM Accuracy Metrics

Next, we elaborate on the metrics introduced for judging the quality of the LLM’s output.

Acc(SE)

This metric measures the seed edit accuracy. Similar to the process conducted for measuring $\mathcal{J}(prog)$, we derive the string edit signature of the seed edit inferred by the LLM. If this seed-edit signature is present in the GT program’s edit signature set, then we accept the seed edit to be an accurately predicted seed edit (i.e. $Acc(SE) = 1$).

	$\mathcal{J}(\text{Prog})(\uparrow)$	$\mathcal{D}(\text{Geo})(\downarrow)$	%REL(\uparrow)
<i>Ours</i>	1.0	0.0	100%
- <i>nhbd</i>	0.85	0.12	95.02%
- <i>breaking</i>	0.77	1.44	89.48%
<i>Naive</i>	0.76	4.32	87.9%

Table A.4: Quality of programs inferred by the solver: Removing *nhbd-edits* results in higher geometric distance ($\mathcal{D}(\text{Geo})$), while removing *breaking-edits* leads to more structural distance (%REL). The naive approach that removes both of these options is the least effective.

Acc(R)

This metric measures relation validity accuracy. During the Human-Solver inference process, we record the relations that the human user disables to enable the edit. $Acc(R)$ is then computed by comparing the LLM’s inference for each relation to the state set by the human user.

$\mathcal{J}(T)$

This metric measures the type hint accuracy. This metric is computed by computing the Jaccard similarity between the type hints set by the expert user during the Human-Solver inference process and the type hints set by the LLM. We find that expert users often set only a minimal set of required type-hints, i.e. the expert user elides type-hints for parts where the solver-inferred edit (without type-hints) will match the edit type specified by the edit request. In contrast, the LLM often tends to provide more type hints. We therefore discount the entries in the LLM-inferred type hints that, though not present in the expert user’s annotation, are not wrong, i.e. setting these type-hints does not change the solver’s output.

Match

This metric measures the fraction of input pairs where all LLM-inferred quantities match human annotations. *Match* is set as 1 if and only if all the other metrics $Acc(SE)$, $Acc(R)$ and $\mathcal{J}(T)$ are measured to be 1.

A.5.5 Perceptual Study Details

The two-alternative forced-choice perceptual study presented in Chapter 3 was conducted with 56 participants, collecting 1642 total judgments. These comparisons were conducted between the programs inferred by the different methods (*One Shot LLM*, *Ours Seed Only*, and *Ours*) on the 50 (shape, edit request) pairs in our *test-set*. We note that the program inferred by *Ours* matches those inferred by the *One Shot LLM* in 4 of the 50 pairs, and matches the program inferred by *Ours Seed Only* in 14 of the 50 pairs.

Note that *this is not a drawback of our method*. Certain edit requests only require a single *seed-edit*, for

Figure A.3: **Perceptual Study Analysis:** In a few cases, as shown above, users preferred *One Shot LLM* over *Ours*. We note that this preference is not caused by *Ours* failing to infer a valid program, but by a misalignment between the system interpretation (perform secondary adjustments) and the participant’s interpretation (do not perform any secondary adjustments).

instance ‘I want to increase the number of legs of this round table’, making the program inferred by the three methods match. Similarly, certain edits require no *type-hints* or *relation validity* settings, for instance ‘widen the chair’, making the program inferred by *Ours* and *Ours Seed Only* match. We remove these cases from our perceptual study to remove the noise that could potentially arise from including these comparisons.

Figure A.2 shows a screenshot of the visual interface provided to the participants. We further emphasize that all the comparison videos and the anonymized participant preferences are also included in the materials associated with Appendix A.

Additional Analysis

We analyze the (shape, edit-request) input pairs for which a majority of participants preferred *One Shot LLM* over *Ours*. This occurred in 5 of the 50 input pairs. We present two of them in Figure A.3. We note that this preference is not caused by any failure of *Ours* to infer a valid program, but rather due to a misalignment between the system interpretation (always perform secondary adjustments unless specifically asked not to) and the participant’s interpretation (do not perform any secondary adjustments unless *really* required).

A.5.6 AEP Solver Analysis with ‘GT’ Annotation

Chapter 3 reports an AEP solver ablation where the two features (use of *nhbd-edits* and *breaking-edits*) are removed to measure their effect on the solver’s performance. To emphasize the importance of these

two features, we also present this analysis with the expert user’s ‘GT’ annotations as input. We record the *seed-edit*, *type-hints*, and *relation-validity* set by the expert user, and infer the corresponding editing programs with the different variants of the solver. This result is presented in Table A.4. The metrics show that these features indeed play a crucial role in the success of the solver, and naively employing the solver can result in many failure cases.

APPENDIX B

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS FOR CODE REWRITING FAMILIES

In this appendix, we provide additional details and experimental results for *Sparse Intermittent Rewrite Injection*. It is divided into the following sections:

- **Additional Experiments:** We provide an additional comparison to CSG-Stump [148] in Section B.1.1. We report our experiments on advanced versions of CSG and ShapeAssembly in Section B.1.3, and Section B.1.4 reports additional analysis on SIRI.
- **Implementation Details:** In Section B.3, we elaborate on the different domain-specific languages (DSLs). Additionally, Sections B.4.1–B.4.3 provide implementation details for the three proposed rewriters.
- **Qualitative Results:** We present qualitative comparisons between CSG-Stump [148], PLAD [70], and our method in Section B.5.

B.1 Additional Experiments

B.1.1 Comparison to CSG-Stump

Program Complexity: In Figure B.1, we visualize the programs inferred by CSG-Stump 32 and SIRI as Geometry Node graphs in Blender [25], a popular tool for procedural modelling. We can see that CSG-Stump 32, despite being the smallest of the models (vs CSG-Stump 256), still produces highly complex graphs with a myriad of nodes and links. Editing such programs to create shape variations is arduous. Additionally, the program is hard to interpret due to its highly connected nature. Such complex program graphs lose a fundamental advantage of the programmatic representation: interpretability and editability.

Test-time rewriting with CSG-Stump: Our work proposes three rewriters that can improve bootstrapped learning and perform test-time rewriting (TTR). An important question is whether TTR can improve programs inferred by domain-specific networks such as CSG-Stump [148]. To answer this question, we

Figure B.1: We show the 3D CSG programs inferred by different methods as Geometry Node trees in Blender [25]. Programs inferred by even the smallest CSG-Stump [148] model (with 32 primitives and 32 intersection nodes) are highly complicated. In comparison, SIRI programs are parsimonious and easier to edit.

TTR	Model	IoU-32 (\uparrow)	IoU-64 (\uparrow)	mean CD (\downarrow)	med. CD (\downarrow)	Length (\downarrow)	Time (\downarrow)
\emptyset	CSG-Stump 32	49.88	39.83	1.88	1.58	98.94	0.05
3	CSG-Stump 32	73.83	54.34	2.56	1.03	63.58	133.88
\emptyset	SIRI	76.77	54.61	1.12	0.69	6.81	1.44
3	SIRI	90.59	60.60	0.83	0.51	15.96	14.60

Table B.1: We perform test-time rewriting on programs inferred by CSG-Stump 32 [148] with our proposed rewriters. While it improves reconstruction accuracy and decreases program length, it still underperforms SIRI. Additionally, applying TTR to CSG-Stump 32 inferred programs takes an order of magnitude more time than applying TTR to SIRI-inferred programs.

perform test-time rewriting with our rewriters on programs inferred by CSG-Stump. We report the results in Table B.1. To limit the optimization time, we apply our rewriters to the CSG-Stump 32 model, which has 32 primitives and 32 intersection nodes.

First, TTR improves the reconstruction quality (as measured by IoU and median CD) as well as the program length for CSG-Stump. However, mean CD increases due to some poorly optimized programs. Second, due to the large programs inferred by CSG-Stump (even for the smallest model), TTR takes an order of magnitude more time than it takes with SIRI-inferred programs. Both trends indicate that producing sparse programs from the start (via bootstrapped methods) may be preferable to producing over-parameterized programs (via domain-specific networks).

	IoU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	Length (\downarrow)
SIRI	78.63	1.13	6.81
No Sparse	77.94	1.28	6.98
Single Rewrite Queue	77.45	1.34	6.15
Single Queue	77.63	1.25	6.53
NRI	75.91	1.29	8.98

Table B.2: We compare variants of SIRI to validate its design. SIRI outperforms the baselines and shows that *sparse* rewrite usage, as well as *careful* rewrite injection (via source-separated queues), are essential for integrating rewriters into bootstrapped learning processes.

	IoU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	Length (\downarrow)
SIRI	78.63	1.13	6.81
no <i>PO</i>	77.80	1.27	6.10
no <i>CP</i>	77.31	1.21	6.18
no <i>CG</i>	76.21	1.27	5.58
PLAD	76.21	1.43	6.39

Table B.3: We report reconstruction accuracy as well as code quality on 3D CSG+ with each rewriter individually removed. Using all three rewriters (top row) yields the best reconstruction and code quality. Using no rewriters is equivalent to PLAD (bottom row).

B.1.2 Ablation

We now provide an ablative analysis of our method to verify the importance of each component. For consistency, we perform all ablations on the 3D CSG language and report metrics on the validation set.

SIRI ablation: We perform a subtractive analysis on SIRI by changing/removing individual components of the method. We compare SIRI to three alternatives:

1. **No Sparse:** Instead of applying rewriters to a subset of programs, they are applied to all programs.
2. **Single Rewrite Queue:** Instead of storing separate queues for each rewriter via the source mapping S_{PO}, S_{CP}, S_{CG} , we store a single queue S_R shared between all the rewriters.
3. **Single Queue:** We remove the separate sources $S_{NS}, S_{PO}, S_{CP}, S_{CG}$, and simply store the top-k ($k = 3$) programs for each input shape x .

We report the results in Table B.2. SIRI surpasses all the other ablations. At the same time, all the ablations surpass the naive rewriter integration NRI, albeit with a smaller margin. This shows that *sparse* rewrite usage, as well as *careful* rewrite injection (via source-separated queues), helps integrate the rewriters into bootstrapped learning processes.

Rewriter Ablation: Next, we test whether using all three proposed rewriters *PO*, *CP*, *CG* is essential.

	3D CSG+			ShapeAssembly+		
	IoU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	Length (\downarrow)	IoU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	Length (\downarrow)
PLAD	70.51	2.35	9.09	61.22	2.63	8.51
NRI	68.25	2.45	10.57	58.82	2.74	10.31
SIRI	71.48	2.17	9.99	63.91	2.41	9.24

Table B.4: We report test-set performance across advanced versions of 3D CSG (3D CSG+) and ShapeAssembly (ShapeAssembly+). As a result of their higher complexity, performance on advanced languages is lower than performance on simple languages. However, the trend observed in Chapter 4 is seen here as well: naively integrating the rewriters into PLAD (NRI) can deteriorate the model’s performance, and SIRI consistently outperforms both baselines.

TTR	3D CSG+			ShapeAssembly+		
	IoU	CD	Length	IoU	CD	Length
PLAD	78.5	1.68	15.9	71.82	2.17	11.35
SIRI	82.8	1.48	20.3	74.65	1.92	11.47

Table B.5: We apply test-time rewriting to models trained on the advanced languages. Consistent with the results in Chapter 4, using test-time rewrites with SIRI remains superior to using them with PLAD.

Table B.3 compares SIRI to models trained with one rewriter removed each. We see that using all three rewriters improves performance.

B.1.3 Advanced Languages

To take a step towards supporting languages closer to those used in real-world scenarios, we extend 3D CSG and ShapeAssembly to contain more complex features (described in detail in Section B.3), and perform additional experiments on these languages. Note that while the extensions are simple under our general framing, domain-specific networks such as CSG-Stump [148] and UCSG-Net [75] require non-trivial changes in their architecture to support such extensions.

Bootstrapped Learning: We train the unsupervised VPI network with PLAD, NRI and SIRI. We report the results in Table B.4. On both the advanced languages, SIRI outperforms the baselines. More importantly, a naive integration of the rewrites (i.e. NRI) is detrimental on both the languages. This experiment emphasizes the complexity of integrating rewrite mechanisms into learning frameworks. By using the rewriters sparsely and carefully injecting rewritten programs into the training data, SIRI is able to improve bootstrapped learning through the rewriters.

Test-Time Rewriting: We perform test-time rewriting (TTR) on both 3D CSG+ and ShapeAssembly+ domains with models trained with PLAD and SIRI. Our results are reported in Table B.5. Consistent with the results in Chapter 4, test-time rewriting is more effective on programs inferred by SIRI than by PLAD.

Figure B.2: We compare PLAD and SIRI for different values of α (X-axis), measuring the IoU (*left*), and program-length (*right*) on the validation set of the 3D CSG domain. SIRI consistently dominates PLAD, and setting $\alpha = 0$ harms both reconstruction accuracy and conciseness.

B.1.4 Other Experiments

Sensitivity to α : A key ingredient in the objective \mathcal{O} is the α factor balancing the weight between reconstruction accuracy and program length. In Figure B.2, we compare the validation-set performance of PLAD and SIRI on 3D CSG for different values of the alpha parameter. We note that across the different settings, SIRI consistently outperforms PLAD in reconstruction accuracy (IoU).

Understanding NRI failure: Why does NRI fail? To answer this question, we study additional training statistics, namely the trained network’s train-set performance, val-set performance, and quality (as measured by our objective \mathcal{O}) of the training data created via the *Search* and *Rewrite* phases. We show the corresponding graphs in Figure B.3.

One may assume that NRI performs poorly due to overfitting to the training data. However, we see that this is not the case: inference performance on both the training set and validation set for NRI is lower than SIRI. As PLAD fine-tuning performs early stopping, with weight reloading before the *Search* phase, it avoids overfitting to the training data. Another hypothesis may be that the programs found for the training shapes might be bad matches. However, we see that this is also not the case from the ‘Execution of train shapes’ plot. As NRI only trains on the “best programs” seen thus far, the training data quality, as measured by the objective \mathcal{O} , is significantly higher than SIRI. However, despite the higher reconstruction matches against their target shapes, the model trained with NRI does not generalize from these training programs and fails to perform well on the validation set, resulting in performance stagnation for NRI. In contrast, SIRI is able to perform well on the validation set, despite training on programs that have lower reconstruction matches versus their target shapes. This indicates that for bootstrapped learning, simply maximizing the reconstruction accuracy of training programs may not be sufficient: instead, it is necessary to find programs for shapes in the training set that both (i) produce good reconstructions, and (ii) help the inference network learn policies that generalize to held-out shapes from the same distribution (validation set). We find that the excessive use of rewriters in NRI violates assumption (ii), but we hope to explore this phenomenon more in future work.

Figure B.3: To understand why NRI fails, we analyze the training process for NRI-trained and SIRI trained models. We show (a) execution of train shapes, (b) inference on train shapes, and (c) inference on validation shapes. NRI does not overfit to the training data, and while its training data is of high quality (i.e. its execution yields a high value of objective O), its train and validation inference performance remain low (cf. Section B.1.4 for more details).

B.2 Evaluation details

To infer programs from the networks learned via bootstrapped learning processes (PLAD, NRI, SIRI), we perform neurally guided beam search with a beam size of 10. For each input shape, this search generates a candidate pool of programs, from which the objective-maximizing program is selected as the inferred program. This approach is the same as the one used in PLAD [70]. For CSG-Stump, a forward pass through the network produces a single probabilistic program. The inferred program is then generated by simply replacing each probabilistic parameter with the modal value of its distribution (for instance, the argmax of each categorical distribution).

Given a set of input shapes, we measure the quality of inferred programs along two axes: a) reconstruction accuracy, to measure how well the inferred program’s execution reconstructs the input shape, and b) program parsimony, to measure how concise the inferred programs are (motivated by Occam’s razor).

Reconstruction metrics: The execution of programs results in a \mathcal{R}^n grid of occupancy values (where $n = 2$ for 2D and $n = 3$ for 3D). As the input is also in the form of a \mathcal{R}^n grid of occupancy values, we can directly measure the Intersection over Union between the inferred occupancy and ground-truth occupancy by comparing them. For measuring Chamfer Distance, on 2D data we follow CSG-Net [161], and on 3D data we follow CSG-Stump [148].

Program Parsimony: Program length is measured as the number of statements/commands in a program. Note that this differs from the number of discrete tokens required to define a command/statement (for instance, a Cuboid command in 3D CSG requires 7 tokens, 1 to specify command type, 3 to specify the 3D position, and 3 to specify the 3D scale).

B.3 DSL Grammars

B.3.1 Simple DSLs

2D CSG: For 2D CSG, each primitive is instantiated with 5 parameters, specifying its 2D position, 2D scale and rotation. We specify the grammar as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S &\rightarrow E; \\ E &\rightarrow BEE \mid D(F, F, F, F, F); \\ B &\rightarrow \textit{intersect} \mid \textit{union} \mid \textit{subtract}; \\ D &\rightarrow \textit{rectangle} \mid \textit{ellipse}; \\ F &\rightarrow (-1, 1); \end{aligned}$$

In the $D(F, F, F, F, F)$ command, the first two real numbers F specify the translation, the next two specify scaling, and the last specifies rotation. F is mapped to different ranges for these different operations. For translation, F remains as is, for scaling F is linearly mapped from $(-1, 1)$ to $(0.01, 2.01)$, for rotation, we linearly map F from $(-1, 1)$ to $(-\pi, \pi)$.

3D CSG: 3D CSG matches the language used in PLAD [70]. For 3D CSG, each primitive is defined by 6 parameters, specifying its 3D position, and 3D scale (no rotation). The range mapping of real number language tokens F for the different operations followed for 2D CSG is applied here as well. We specify the grammar as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S &\rightarrow E; \\ E &\rightarrow BEE \mid D(F, F, F, F, F, F); \\ B &\rightarrow \textit{intersect} \mid \textit{union} \mid \textit{subtract}; \\ D &\rightarrow \textit{cuboid} \mid \textit{ellipsoid}; \\ F &\rightarrow [-1, 1]; \end{aligned}$$

ShapeAssembly: ShapeAssembly creates structures by instantiating cuboids, and attaching them to one another. We utilize the version of ShapeAssembly described in PLAD [69] with a slight modification. Specifically, in our version `attach` and `squeeze` commands are defined for 3D points rather than 2D surface points. This makes our version of ShapeAssembly closer to the original defined in ShapeAssembly [68]. Following PLAD, we restrict the bounding box to always have $l = 1, w = 1$, and remove the axis-alignment

flag from cuboid instantiation. Furthermore, for all sub-programs we restrict the bounding box to always have $h = 1$ as well. We specify the grammar for ShapeAssembly as the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \textit{Start} &\rightarrow \textit{BBlock}; \textit{CBlock}; \textit{ABlock}; \textit{SBlock}; \\
 \textit{BBlock} &\rightarrow \textit{bbox} = \textit{Cuboid}(l, h, w) \\
 \textit{CBlock} &\rightarrow c_n = \textit{Cuboid}(l, w, h); \textit{CBlock} \mid \textit{None} \\
 \textit{ABlock} &\rightarrow A; \textit{ABlock} \mid S; \textit{ABlock} \mid \textit{None} \\
 \textit{SBlock} &\rightarrow R; \textit{SBlock} \mid T; \textit{SBlock} \mid \textit{None} \\
 A &\rightarrow \textit{attach}(c_{n_1}, x_1, y_1, z_1, x_2, y_2, z_2) \\
 S &\rightarrow \textit{squeeze}(c_{n_1}, c_{n_2}, f, u, v) \\
 R &\rightarrow \textit{reflect}(\textit{axis}) \\
 T &\rightarrow \textit{translate}(\textit{axis}, m, d) \\
 f &\rightarrow \textit{right} \mid \textit{left} \mid \textit{top} \mid \textit{bot} \mid \textit{front} \mid \textit{back} \\
 \textit{axis} &\rightarrow X \mid Y \mid Z \\
 l, h, w &\in \mathbb{R}^+ \\
 x, y, z, u, v, d &\in [0, 1]^2 \\
 n, m &\in \mathbb{Z}^+
 \end{aligned}$$

B.3.2 Advanced DSLs

To ease learning, past approaches have used *simplified* versions of visual languages as described in the previous section. However, real world visual programs offer advanced operations, e.g. real world CSG programs contain hierarchical transformations (rather than primitive level transformations). As a step towards such languages, we also test our method on *advanced* 3D CSG (**3D CSG+**) and ShapeAssembly (**ShapeAssembly+**).

3D CSG+: We introduce two important classes of commands: *hierarchical transformations*, which can be applied to compound shapes, and *axis-aligned reflection*. Further, to reduce parameter redundancy, we instantiate primitives without any parameters, i.e., they are instantiated in a canonical form (origin-centered

and unit scale with no rotation). The grammar is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &\rightarrow E; \\
E &\rightarrow BEE \mid TE \mid D; \\
B &\rightarrow \textit{intersect} \mid \textit{union} \mid \textit{subtract}; \\
D &\rightarrow \textit{cuboid} \mid \textit{ellipsoid} \mid \textit{cylinder}; \\
T &\rightarrow \textit{translate}(F, F, F) \mid \textit{scale}(F, F, F) \mid \\
&\quad \textit{rotate}(F, F, F) \mid R; \\
R &\rightarrow \textit{reflect}(X) \mid \textit{reflect}(Y) \mid \textit{reflect}(Z); \\
F &\rightarrow [-1, 1];
\end{aligned}$$

ShapeAssembly+: We extend the simple ShapeAssembly described previously by allowing hierarchical composition of programs. Specifically, our version allows hierarchical programs, where cuboids in the root program can act as the bounding box for their own ShapeAssembly programs. ShapeAssembly+ follows the same grammar as ShapeAssembly with the following change:

$$\begin{aligned}
CBlock &\rightarrow c_n = \text{Cuboid}(l, w, h, \mathbf{sp}); CBlock \mid None \\
\mathbf{sp} &\in \mathbb{Z}^+
\end{aligned}$$

During cuboid instantiation, parameter \mathbf{sp} specifies whether the cuboid is empty ($sp = 0$) or contains the sp -th ShapeAssembly program (all the ShapeAssembly programs are decoded by the inference network).

B.4 Code Rewriters

Our rewriters are formulated to be generally applicable across visual programming languages. In this section, we outline the requirements to apply each rewriter, along with implementation details and a walkthrough example.

B.4.1 Parameter Optimization (PO)

The *Parameter Optimization (PO)* rewriter aims to improve the continuous parameters of a given program while keeping its discrete structural parameters fixed. Furthermore, it uses first-order gradient-based

Figure B.4: (left) We show the *PO* rewriter applied to 3D CSG programs. (right) We show the *CP* rewriter applied to 3D CSG programs. Note that in the second figure, *CP* identifies a sub-tree of the input program that obtains higher reconstruction accuracy w.r.t. the target shape.

optimization to update these parameters. Towards this end, *PO* requires that the programs derived from the language grammar must be continuous and piecewise differentiable with respect to ≥ 1 program parameters ϕ .

Additionally, as *PO* performs gradient-based optimization, it requires a *partially* differentiable executor for the language (differentiable w.r.t. ϕ at least). By chaining a differentiable reconstruction measure \mathcal{R} (such as L_2 -loss w.r.t. an occupancy grid) to the program’s differentiable execution, we can then optimize the program parameters ϕ to improve the reconstruction measure \mathcal{R} .

Most shape languages instantiate parameterized primitives and combine them with different combinators to create shapes. When languages can map the program parameters p to primitive parameters in a piecewise differentiable manner (as in ShapeAssembly [68], and CSG), we can yield a *partially* differentiable executor D for the language with the procedure outlined in Chapter 4 (Section 4.4.1). We revisit the procedure here with more details.

$D(z)$ maps the execution of a program to an equivalent implicit signed-distance function. Given a program z_ϕ , we use the program executor E to map program parameters ϕ to parameters (position, scale, rotation) of implicit functions representing simple geometric primitives (cuboids, spheres etc.). For CSG, the mapping is 1-to-1, but for other languages such as ShapeAssembly, these parameters are derived from the program’s execution. Then, we apply boolean combinators of the parameterized primitives to obtain the program’s *implicit equivalent*. Armed with the program’s implicit equivalent, we uniformly sample points $t \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and convert the signed distance at the points into “soft” occupancy values to yield a differentiable

Figure B.5: We show the two traversals of the *CP* rewriter on a manually created 2D CSG example. The top-down traversal identifies the objective \mathcal{O} maximizing root node, and the bottom-up traversal prunes extraneous nodes of the sub-tree starting from the objective-maximizing node. In this example, during the bottom-up traversal, because the top node matches its parent node, we remove its sibling node and simplify the expression.

execution of the program.

Optimization: From the program’s *implicit equivalent*, the soft-occupancy values $O(z)$ are derived as follows:

$$O(z) = \sigma(-\tanh(\text{sdf}(z) \times \alpha) \times \alpha), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where σ is the sigmoid function, and α is a scalar value. We run our optimization procedure for 250 steps with the Adam [79] optimizer (learning rate is set as 0.01), and we scale α logarithmically from $\log(3)$ to $\log(10)$. Finally, to ensure that the parameter values remain within range, we perform our optimization on $\theta = \tanh^{-1}(\phi/s)$, where s is the range of each parameter, instead of ϕ directly. Figure B.4 presents examples of the *PO* rewriting procedure in action.

B.4.2 Code Pruning (CP)

Given a shape x and program z , *CP* rewrites z s.t. $z^R \sim \arg \max_{\Omega^{CP}} O(x, z)$, where $\Omega^{CP}(z) = \{\tilde{z} | \tilde{z} \subseteq z\}$ represents the set of all valid sub-programs of z , i.e. *CP* aims to identify and remove program fragments that negatively contribute to our objective \mathcal{O} . In Figure B.4, we show examples of the *CP* rewriter in action, and in Algorithm 4 we present a high-level overview of *CP*. We first describe how to apply *CP* to a simply-typed lambda expression. We then describe how we map different languages, such as CSG and ShapeAssembly to such expressions.

Given a simply-typed lambda expression, we perform *CP* via two rewrite passes, namely a bottom-up and a top-down pass to approximate z^R . First, we create a directed acyclic expression tree comprising expression nodes and edges connecting them. Each expression node stores the execution of the sub-expression formed

Algorithm 4: Code Pruning

Input: Set of programs Z_x & Executor E .

Hyper-parameters: no. programs to rewrite n

Output: Rewritten programs Z_R

```
1: for  $z_x$  in random_sample( $Z_x, n$ ):
2:   # top down pass
3:    $z_r = z_x$ 
4:   for  $subtr\_node$  in extract_subtree_nodes( $z_x$ ):
5:     if  $O(z_{subtr\_node}, x) \geq O(z_r, x)$ :
6:        $z_r = z_{subtr\_node}$ 
7:   # bottom up pass
8:   for  $subtr\_node$  in extract_subtree_nodes( $z_r$ ):
9:     if removable( $z_r, subtr\_node$ ):
10:       $z_r = remove(z_r, subtr\_node)$ 
11:   if  $O(z_r, x) \geq O(z_x, x)$ :
12:      $Z_R.insert(z_r)$ 
```

with that node as the root. Our goal is to identify nodes that can be pruned from the graph. We perform a top-down traversal of the graph and evaluate the objective O w.r.t. the input shape x at each node. We identify the node with the highest score and mark it as the root node. Next, during the bottom-up traversal, we identify and prune nodes that are extraneous. For the CSG language, we detect such extraneous nodes by comparing them to their parent node: if the parent node’s execution exactly matches a child node’s execution, all sibling nodes are extraneous and can be removed. We also mark nodes as extraneous if the node’s execution is empty (i.e. the node’s sub-expression evaluates to null). For ShapeAssembly, nodes whose execution does not overlap with the target shape x are marked as extraneous (as ShapeAssembly is a purely additive language). We present an example of the two traversals in *CP* rewriting procedure in Figure B.5.

As stated earlier, to apply *CP*, we map the program to a simply typed lambda expression, which is then used to construct an expression tree. For CSG, the program itself is such an expression. For ShapeAssembly, we utilize the program’s implicit equivalent (as defined in Section B.4.1) to construct the expression. However, since ShapeAssembly is an imperative language, nodes can have dependencies that restrict their removal. Therefore, we additionally extract a partially ordered dependency graph from the program, and only remove nodes that are terminal in the dependency graph. Figure B.7 shows the expression tree and dependency graph for a ShapeAssembly program. Additionally, for ShapeAssembly we apply this procedure iteratively, since each pruning operation updates the dependency graph.

B.4.3 Code Grafting (CG)

The *CG* rewriter aims to replace sub-expressions of the given program with more suitable expressions from a cache of previously discovered sub-expressions. Algorithm 5 provides a high-level overview of *CG*, and

Figure B.6: We show the CG rewriter applied to 3D CSG programs.

Figure B.7: We show the mapping of a ShapeAssembly program to (a) its implicit equivalent expression tree and (b) its dependency graph. The CP rewriter prunes extraneous nodes from the expression tree while also ensuring pruned nodes have no incoming dependency. For the illustrated example, only the parts created by reflection operators are prunable, as they are the only leaves in the dependency graph.

Figure B.6 shows examples of applying this rewriter.

First, sub-expressions along with their executions (in the form of n -dimensional occupancy fields) are extracted from all inferred programs. All sub-expressions are then clustered by their execution using the FAISS [67] library (using INDEXBINARYIVF) and stored in a cache. We store only *unique* executions in the cache by identifying sub-expressions with approximately matching executions (Hamming distance < 100 for 3D, and < 10 for 2D) and retaining only the shortest ‘preferred’ sub-expression, while rejecting the rest.

This step provides our first rewrite. For each rejected sub-expression, we retrieve the programs from which it originated and insert the ‘preferred’ sub-expression into them. This rewrite results in programs that achieve similar reconstruction accuracy while having a shorter length. Lines 1-12 in Algorithm 5 correspond

Algorithm 5: Code Grafting

Input: Set of programs Z_x , sub-expression cache C & Executor E .

Hyper-parameters: $n, k = 10, \tau = 10$.

Output: Rewritten programs Z_R

```
1: # creating the subexpression cache
2: for  $z_x$  in  $Z_x$ :
3:   for  $subexpr$  in  $extract\_subexprs(z_x)$ :
4:      $match = retrieve(C, E(subexpr))$ 
5:     if  $match$ :
6:        $C.remove(match)$ 
7:        $shorter, longer = compare(subexpr, match)$ 
8:        $C.insert(shorter)$ 
9:        $z_r = replace(z_{longer}, shorter)$ 
10:       $Z_R.insert(z_r)$ 
11:    else:
12:       $C.insert(subexpr)$ 
13: # rewriting programs
14: for  $z_x$  in  $random\_sample(Z_x, n)$ :
15:    $num\_rewrites = 0$  &  $z_r = z_x$ 
16:   while( $num\_rewrites < \tau$ ):
17:      $candidates = []$ 
18:     for  $subexpr$  in  $extract\_subexprs(z_r)$ :
19:        $e^* = desired\_execution(subexpr, E(z_x))$ 
20:        $candidates.extend(C.get\_nn(e^*, k))$ 
21:        $z_{best} = get\_best(candidates)$ 
22:       if  $O(z_{best}, x) \geq O(z_r, x)$ :
23:          $z_r = z_{best}$ 
24:          $num\_rewrites += 1$ 
25:       if  $O(z_r, x) \geq O(z_x, x)$ :
26:          $Z_R.insert(z_r)$ 
27: return  $Z_R$ 
```

to these steps.

The second rewrite performed in *Code Grafting* aims to replace sub-expressions in a given program to improve its reconstruction accuracy.

We perform this rewrite in 3 steps:

1. We derive the *desired execution* for each sub-expression in the program by masked function inversion (described below). Note that for each sub-expression we only consider the *desired execution* within the bounding box of its execution (line 19).
2. For each sub-expression we retrieve the k -nearest neighbors of its desired execution from the cache as its replacement candidates (line 20).
3. We calculate the objective O achieved by each replacement, and perform the replacement that yields the highest reconstruction accuracy (lines 21-24).

Figure B.8: The CG rewriter derives *desired executions* (A^* and B^*) for each sub-expression (A and B), which can be used to search a cache for potential replacement candidates with respect to a target shape (T). The *desired execution* is derived via masked function inversion; here, we show the inversion for the three boolean combinators. For each desired execution, black indicates an area that should be occupied, white indicates an area that should not be occupied, and grey indicates invalid/masked regions.

This process (step 1 to 3) is repeated until none of the replacement candidates improve reconstruction accuracy, or until we perform a fixed number of replacements. Lines 14-24 in Algorithm 5 correspond to these steps.

Masked Function Inversion: Given a sub-expression A , we derive its *desired execution* A^* by masked function inversion. We assume the given expression executes to the given target T , and invert the expression S . The process can be described as follows:

$$T \sim S(A) \tag{B.2}$$

$$T \sim S_1(S_2(\dots S_n(A))) \tag{B.3}$$

$$A^* \sim S^{-1}(T) \tag{B.4}$$

$$A^* : \sim S_n^{-1}(S_{n-1}^{-1}(\dots S_1^{-1}(T))) \tag{B.5}$$

By defining atomic inversion operations for transforms and combinators, we can simply derive S^{-1} for a sub-expression A by applying the inversions of operators applied to it to the target T . As S can potentially be composed of non-invertible functions, we use a binary validity *mask* to identify input regions of space (\mathbb{R}^n) that cannot be inverted, and perform inversion only for invertible regions. For transforms such as translate, rotate, scale such masked inversions are trivial to define (e.g. $S_{\text{translate}}^{-1} = -S_{\text{translate}}$). For boolean

combinators $U(A, B)$ we define its inversions w.r.t. a child A as a $\{Target, Mask\}$ tuple as follows:

$$\text{Union}^{-1}(T, B) = \{T, \overline{\text{Intersect}(T, B)}\}, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\text{Intersect}^{-1}(T, B) = \{T, \text{Union}(T, B)\}, \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\text{Diff}^{-1}(T, B) = \{T, \text{Intersect}(T, \overline{B})\}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\text{Diff}^{-1}(T, A) = \{\tilde{T}, \text{Union}(T, A)\}, \quad (\text{B.9})$$

where \overline{X} stands for the complement of X , and the mask term indicates valid regions. We provide examples of the inversions in Figure B.8.

Canonical Execution: In the CSG domain, all sub-expression executions are used in *canonical* form: we prepend each sub-expression with a *translate* and *scale* command such that its execution is origin-centered and unit scale. Using the canonical form allows us to identify sub-expressions that are equivalent under translation/scale transformations. When the canonical sub-expressions are used for replacement, additional transform commands are prepended to make them fit the target expression’s position and scale. For the ShapeAssembly domain, all sub-programs are constructed in a unit-scale cuboid by construction (their bounding box is fixed to size $(1, 1, 1)$). We note that similar canonical forms have been previously used in [129] as well.

Empty Node: During each *CG* rewrite step, we optionally extend the input expression with a union and an empty node, i.e. $expr = \text{Union}(expr, empty)$. This allows us to additionally consider sub-expressions from the cache that, when attached to the input expression, improve the objective.

Cache size: We randomly sub-sample the cache as its size grows to curb the growth in memory requirements. We retain 35000 sub-expressions, each consisting of $32 \times 32 \times 32$ binary values, resulting in only ~ 1 GB of memory use. Note that the cache entries persist over multiple search-rewrite-train cycles, so that good sub-expressions are retained and propagated once they are discovered.

ShapeAssembly: We apply *CG* to ShapeAssembly+, as it allows hierarchical composition of ShapeAssembly programs. Since the simple ShapeAssembly used in Chapter 4 lacks hierarchical composition, we do not apply *CG* to it. First, we apply *CG* to strictly replace or introduce ShapeAssembly sub-programs (rather than just a set of statements). This allows us to treat each ShapeAssembly program’s implicit equivalent (as defined in Section B.4.1) as a simply typed (partially invertible) lambda expression. To derive the *desired executions*, we only need to invert simple CSG functions such as `translate` and `union`. Successful expression replacement acts as replacement (or introduction) of entire ShapeAssembly sub-programs, mapping edited implicit equivalents uniquely to a ShapeAssembly program.

Figure B.9: We show instances of programs that fail to fully reconstruct the input shape, despite test-time rewriting. A common failure mode is missing object parts. Changing the rewrite objective \mathcal{O} may help resolve this issue.

Figure B.10: We show examples of each rewriter applied one at a time, as well as their interleaved application on inferred programs during test-time rewriting. Each rewriter can iteratively improve the programs, and interleaved application improves them further.

Note that the preconditions on the languages for applying CG are fairly simple. It requires a mapping to a typed lambda calculus expression, which then allows us to perform type-matching replacements. Further, our masked inversion procedure requires the existence of masked inverse for each atomic operator.

B.5 Qualitative Results

We show qualitative comparisons between our method and prior approaches. Our method improves reconstruction accuracy over prior bootstrapping methods [70], and infers programs with higher conciseness than domain-specific architectures [148].

Failure Cases: While SIRI achieves better aggregate reconstruction performance compared with previous bootstrapped learning methods such as PLAD, and matches reconstruction performance of domain-specific architectures such as CSG-Stump, its outputs can still be further improved. One failure mode is that of

missing parts, even after test-time rewriting (see Figure B.9). We note SIRI is not the only method that falls victim to this failure mode. A careful tuning of the program length weighting parameter α in the objective O , along with a part-presence-sensitive reconstruction metric (instead of IoU), can help alleviate these challenges. In fact, SIRI’s use of rewriters might allow it to uniquely solve this problem, by making use of a new class of rewriters that identifies missing semantic parts of a target shape, and rewrites the program with a sub-expression that covers these missing parts.

Test-Time Rewriting: We visualize test-time rewriting in Figure B.10. As can be seen, each rewriter refines the program and their iterative application is beneficial.

Comparison to CSG-Stump: We compare SIRI + TTR with three variants of CSG-Stump in Figure B.11. We note that while the class-specific CSG-Stump model may surpass the reconstruction accuracy of SIRI + TTR, its output predictions are still overly complex and hard to reason over, as reflected in the renderings with colored primitives. Due to the high complexity of CSG-Stump programs, we color each intersection node instead of the primitives. Despite this, we observe that the programs are still greatly over-parameterized.

Figure B.11: We compare our approach (SIRI + test-time rewriting) to three variants of CSG-Stump [148]: (a) *CSG-Stump-32*, a model trained with 32 primitive intersection nodes, (b) *CSG-Stump-256*, a model trained with 256 primitive and intersection nodes, and (c) *CSG-Stump-256 (cs)*, where a model is trained for each class (we use the pretrained weights provided by the authors).

APPENDIX C

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS FOR PATTERN ANALOGIES

C.1 Introduction

In this appendix, we present additional details regarding our system. First, we provide a brief overview of the accompanying videos. Next, in Section C.3, we provide details of the proposed Domain-Specific Language (DSL), `SPLITWEAVE`, including the design of the two pattern-style-specific program samplers. Section C.5 provides additional details regarding *Analogical Quartet Sampling*, detailing the *programmatic* pattern edits employed. This is followed by details of our test dataset and the three applications enabled by our approach in Section C.6. Finally, Sections C.7, C.8, and C.9 present additional experiments and results, including qualitative examples and failure cases. The system code includes the DSL, program samplers, and model-training components.

C.2 Video Results

The accompanying materials include the following videos:

1. A video titled `editing.mp4` which demonstrates the use of `SPLITWEAVE` for editing real-world patterns with simple pattern analogies.
2. A video titled `pattern_animation.mp4` which presents our results for pattern animation transfer. Please refer to Section C.6.2 for more details on transferring pattern animations.

C.3 A language for visual patterns

In Chapter 5, we introduced `SPLITWEAVE`, a DSL designed for creating visual patterns. As described previously, we use `SPLITWEAVE` to (a) generate a large dataset of high-quality synthetic patterns for training an analogical editor and (b) define parametric analogy pairs (A, A') at test time to guide transformation in target pattern B .

*Work performed during an internship at Adobe Research

Figure C.1: **Program evaluation** We illustrate the evaluation of a SPLITWEAVE program. SPLITWEAVE is used to create directed acyclic graphs representing data flow between different operators. The *UV Grid Operators* are used to define UVExprs, which map spatial coordinates to UV grids. *Signal Operators* are used to define SExprs, which map UV grids to single- or multi-channel spatial maps (such as RGBA canvases). *Spatially Varying Operators* take inputs such as UV grids and fragment IDs to apply spatially varying transforms. Finally, *Utility Operators* perform tasks such as composing multiple RGBA canvases together.

We also constructed two custom SPLITWEAVE program samplers that support the sampling of high-quality synthetic patterns in two domains, namely *Motif Tiling Patterns* (MTP) and *Split-Filling Patterns* (SFP).

SPLITWEAVE is designed specifically for generating patterns that exhibit structured partitioning of a 2D canvas. Programs in SPLITWEAVE define a process to map each spatial location on the canvas to an RGBA value, resulting in a visual pattern. This process is achieved through two core mappings: (1) spatial locations (x, y) are first mapped to 2D UV coordinates and (2) UV coordinates are then mapped to outputs such as RGBA values or other signals. SPLITWEAVE provides operators to abstract and simplify these mappings.

C.3.1 UVExpr and SExpr

UVExpr and SExpr are the two key types of expressions used in SPLITWEAVE programs to define these mappings:

UVExpr A UVExpr defines a function

$$\text{UVExpr} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2,$$

which maps each spatial location (x, y) on the canvas to a corresponding UV coordinate (u, v) . This provides a spatial framework for pattern generation, enabling operations such as distortions, tiling, or structured partitioning (e.g., BrickSplit, HexagonalSplit). Evaluating a UVExpr generates a UV grid that serves

as the basis for further evaluating SExprs.

SExpr A SExpr defines a function

$$\text{SExpr} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N,$$

which maps each UV coordinate $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ to an N -dimensional output. The value of N depends on the type of output being generated. SExprs that evaluate to 4-channel outputs ($N = 4$) are typically used to generate RGBA canvases. Alternatively, SExprs that evaluate to single-channel outputs ($N = 1$) are used to generate single-channel buffers representing spatial masks, distortion fields, or other intermediate signals.

UVExprs are primarily used to generate structured partitions of the canvas through partitioning operators (e.g., *BrickSplit*). Evaluating these operators produces not only a corresponding UV grid, but also a **fragment ID buffer**, where each spatial location is assigned a fragment identifier corresponding to its partition. As operators are composed, the fragment ID buffers are updated and stacked, enabling hierarchical partitioning and fragment-aware transformations. This mechanism is critical for supporting *Spatially Varying Transformations*, used in *Motif Tiling Patterns* (MTP), where operations vary based on partitioning, and *Fragment Grouping*, essential for *Split-Filling Patterns* (SFP), where fragments are grouped together for applying color fills.

SExprs typically contain analytical functions defining SVG objects, such as 2D circles and Bezier curves, and texture-mapping operators, which map UV coordinates to samples on predefined 2D maps. Texture-mapping operators are primarily used for mapping RGBA tiles onto UV grids. Evaluating a SExpr on different UV grids results in different outputs. These outputs are used to generate RGBA canvases or auxiliary data buffers for generating the visual pattern image.

C.3.2 Operator Categories

SPLITWEAVE provides four broad categories of operators to support the construction of UVExprs, SExprs, and their transformations:

1. *~ 50 UV Grid Operators*: Used to define UVExprs.
2. *~ 70 Signal Operators*: Used to define SExprs.
3. *10 Spatially Varying Operators*: Used to define transformations in a partition-aware manner using fragment IDs (e.g., resizing alternate rows or applying per-fragment coloring).
4. *Utility Operators*: Used for remaining purposes such as combining multiple canvases (*SourceOver*) or generating auxiliary spatial signals used in fragment-aware operations.

In Figure C.1, we illustrate the evaluation of a SPLITWEAVE program used to create an MTP pattern.

Figure C.2: Our custom program samplers Φ generate attribute trees *AT*, a hierarchical data structure that encodes pattern-structure specifications. The attribute trees are then compiled into *SPLITWEAVE* programs. Finally, we generate visual patterns by evaluating each *SPLITWEAVE* program. The use of Φ and *AT* helps generate high-quality synthetic patterns.

This program uses all four types of operators, each associated with a separate color. To create the pattern, we separately create a background canvas and a foreground canvas. To create the foreground canvas, we first convert the pixel-space canvas to a UV Cartesian grid ($\in [-1, 1]^2$) using *Cartesian*. This grid is subsequently rotated using the *Rotate* operator. Next, by using the *BrickSplit* operator, we create two outputs: a transformed UV grid, which now consists of brick-style spatial partitions, and a 2D fragment-ID buffer containing integers that correspond to fragment IDs. Using the fragment-ID buffer, we apply spatially varying scaling to decrease the size of tiles in alternate columns. This is followed by a *ApplyTile* operator to create the foreground canvas. Internally, *ApplyTile* evaluates the *SExprs* corresponding to each tile on the transformed UV grid and merges alternate rows of the resulting two RGBA canvases using the fragment IDs from *BrickSplit*. A similar process is followed to obtain the background canvas. Finally, we combine the background and foreground with the *SourceOver* operator to obtain the final MTP pattern.

C.3.3 Implementation

SPLITWEAVE is implemented in Python, making it accessible to a wide range of users, including those with limited programming experience. This lowers the learning curve for novice users and facilitates integration with emerging tools, such as large language models (LLMs), for programmatic generation and manipulation of visual patterns. The core operators in *SPLITWEAVE* are implemented using PyTorch [141], which allows many of the operators to be automatically differentiable. This opens up exciting possibilities for future work in using automatic differentiation for visual program inference, enabling the recovery of programmatic structures directly from visual patterns.

We have also developed a front-end application using *Rete.js* [26] to support visual programming with *SPLITWEAVE*. This tool simplifies the creation and manipulation of *SPLITWEAVE* programs by providing an

intuitive, node-based interface. Manipulation of SPLITWEAVE programs using this interface is demonstrated in the accompanying videos. Currently implemented as a proof of concept, it is primarily intended for inspecting SPLITWEAVE programs and performing parametric analogical edits on real-world patterns. Future work will focus on refining the application to make it more user-friendly and suitable for broader usage. We hope that SPLITWEAVE serves as a stepping stone for further research in visual pattern generation and manipulation, inspiring new methodologies and applications in this domain.

C.4 Custom Program Samplers

As discussed in Chapter 5, random sampling of the SPLITWEAVE grammar often produces poor-quality patterns that are incoherent or irrelevant for training. To address this limitation, we construct custom program samplers designed to generate high-quality SPLITWEAVE programs through a structured, hierarchical process.

The custom program samplers work by generating an *attribute tree*, a hierarchical data structure that encodes the specification for a pattern. This attribute tree is then compiled into a valid SPLITWEAVE program, which, when executed, produces the final visual pattern. The pipeline can be formalized as:

$$\Phi \xrightarrow{\text{Sample}} AT \xrightarrow{\text{Compile}} P_{SW} \xrightarrow{\text{Execute}} \text{Pattern},$$

where Φ is a high-level process specification that defines the abstract structure of the pattern, AT is the attribute tree that instantiates this structure with specific parameters, and the resulting SPLITWEAVE program, represented as P_{SW} , defines the procedural steps to produce the pattern. Figure C.2 illustrates this workflow with an example, showing the attribute tree, its compilation into a SPLITWEAVE program, and the resulting visual pattern.

The attribute tree AT is constructed by first designing an abstract process specification Φ that represents the steps involved in creating a pattern. For example, in Motif Tiling Patterns (MTP), Φ includes stages such as sampling tiles, sampling layout parameters, and sampling effects like background elements. Each stage in Φ corresponds to a node or sub-tree in AT , where the nodes represent specific components, and the edges encode relationships or contextual parameters. To populate AT , we implement domain-specific random samplers for each node in the tree. These samplers generate valid and diverse configurations for their respective components. At the top level, a hierarchical sampler integrates these components to form a complete attribute tree. For instance, the MTP sampler samples specifications for canvas partitioning, tiles and their transformations, and spatially varying effects, combining them into a unified representation.

The hierarchical nature of the attribute tree allows modular control over each component, enabling

Figure C.3: We present synthetic samples generated by our custom program samplers for two pattern styles: Motif Tiling Patterns (MTP) and Split-Filling Patterns (SFP). The custom program samplers can still produce poor-quality patterns, as depicted in the rightmost two columns.

flexibility and extensibility. By sampling each node independently, the custom samplers ensure that the resulting patterns are both diverse and semantically meaningful, addressing the challenges of random grammar sampling. Once the attribute tree AT is constructed, it is compiled into a `SPLITWEAVE` program. This compilation step translates the hierarchical structure and parameters encoded in AT into valid `SPLITWEAVE` code, adhering to the syntax and semantics of the DSL. Executing the compiled `SPLITWEAVE` program produces the final visual pattern. This structured workflow provides a controlled and flexible framework for generating patterns. The combination of a process-driven attribute tree design and creation of pattern style-specific samplers ensures the generation of high-quality visual patterns.

In Figure C.3, we present synthetic samples of both MTP and SFP styles generated by this process. We also show failure cases in the two rightmost columns. The custom sampler for MTP patterns sometimes generates samples with a high amount of stretching, too much visual complexity, or sparse tiling. Similarly, the SFP pattern sampler can fail due to trivial grid partitioning, over-zooming, or poor random color selection.

To create the MTP patterns, we also generate a large dataset of 100,000 RGBA tiles. Earlier experiments with fewer tiles showed that having a diverse and large set of tiles is essential to generalize to ‘in-the-wild’ real-world patterns. To create tiles on a large variety of subjects, we first extract a subset of nouns from WordNet synsets [121]. We prune the nouns by type, avoiding types such as ‘event’ and ‘process’, followed by rejection based on keyword matches to avoid different forms of ‘bacteria’, ‘virus’, etc. Finally, we use SigLIP [220] text encodings of prompts in the form of “A photo of a/an \$item” to cluster the nouns and extract $\sim 10,000$ distinct nouns. These nouns are then used to create text prompts using a template of

Figure C.4: We generate tiles for MTP patterns using LayerDiffuse [221]. We present both good-quality tiles (top three rows) and poor-quality tiles (bottom row).

Figure C.5: We present analogical quartets created using our approach. While many analogical quartets are of good quality, our synthetic sampling process can also result in poor-quality quartets, as shown in the rightmost column.

the form “A minimal $\$style$ $\$second_term$ of a $\$noun$ $\$minimalism$ on a $\$color_scheme$ background. ”, where variables such as $\$style$ and $\$second_term$ are filled with random samples from a

Figure C.6: We present examples of editing synthetic patterns A with different edits to generate edited patterns A' .

list of keywords. We then generate RGBA images for each prompt using LayerDiffuse [221], which generates images with alpha maps. Finally, tiles are created by extracting a tight bounding box subset of the generated image, with simple thresholds to reject samples of too high or too low complexity, measured using JPEG [189] compression. Figure C.4 presents a few samples of tiles generated by this process. We note a few recurring failure cases: (a) extremely simple tiles, (b) tiles with multiple objects, (c) tiles with poor cropping, and (d) realistic rendering effects on tiles. Despite these flaws, most tiles appear useful, particularly for helping the model avoid overfitting to training tiles.

C.5 Sampling Analogical Quartets

In Chapter 5, we introduced analogical quartets (A, A', B, B') that are used to train our analogical editing model. These quartets are grounded in Structure Mapping Theory [48], which defines analogies as mappings of relational structure from a base to a target domain. The relationship R between program pairs $(z_A, z_{A'})$ and $(z_B, z_{B'})$ remains consistent:

$$R(z_A, z_{A'}) = R(z_B, z_{B'}). \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Here, we provide additional details on how edits are defined, sampled, and applied to construct these quartets, along with examples and a discussion of failure cases.

Edits in our framework operate directly on the attribute tree AT , rather than on SPLITWEAVE programs. This approach ensures semantic validity and allows for efficient resampling of components. Each edit targets

a node just below the root of the tree, corresponding to high-level components in the pattern creation process.

For Motif Tiling Patterns (MTP), the editable components include:

1. *Tiles*: Add, remove, or replace tiles in the pattern.
2. *Layout*: Replace the layout structure.
3. *Cell Effects*: Add or remove specific spatially varying effects applied to cells.
4. *Background and Border*: Replace background or border styles.

For Split-Filling Patterns (SFP), the editable components include:

1. *Foreground Layout and Background Layout*: Replace the layout for either foreground, background or both elements.
2. *Fill Specifications*: Replace the specifications for filling regions.

Edits are applied by resampling or modifying nodes in the attribute tree. To perform a *replace* edit, the target node is resampled to produce a new specification, such as a new layout or tile configuration, and this new specification is used to create both A' and B' . To perform an *add* edit, a new node is created and inserted into the appropriate list (e.g., adding a tile or effect). Finally, to perform a *remove* edit, a node is added, and the order of the quartet is flipped (e.g., swapping $A \leftrightarrow A'$ and $B \leftrightarrow B'$). Applying random edits to randomly sampled pattern sets (A, B) can generate invalid new patterns (A', B') . Therefore, we instead first sample an edit e and perform rejection sampling of (A, B) pairs to generate valid analogical quartets.

In Figure C.6, we present examples of pattern pairs generated by editing a pattern A to create A' in both MTP and SFP styles. Figure C.5 provides examples of generated analogical quartets, demonstrating consistent transformations between (A, A') and (B, B') . Despite its robustness, our approach can encounter failure cases. For instance, despite the pattern programs satisfying Equation C.1, a visually salient relation between (A, A') and (B, B') may not be analogical. Furthermore, the (A, A') pair may not always clearly demonstrate the desired change.

C.6 Additional Details

We now provide additional details regarding the real-world test set and the applications enabled by our method.

C.6.1 Test Set Creation

To evaluate our method, we created a test set by collecting 116 patterns from Adobe Stock. Based on visual inspection, we annotated desirable edits for 50 patterns in text. For each annotated edit, we manually

Figure C.7: Our model enables users to mix aspects of different patterns to create novel patterns. In this example, the layout of X is mixed with the tiles of Y to generate the pattern Y' .

Figure C.8: Our model can also be used to create wide canvases of non-stationary patterns by adapting MultiDiffusion [8] for spatially-conditioned generation. In these examples, we generate patterns of size 1536×1536 pixels and show a vertically centered crop.

constructed input analogies using SPLITWEAVE. These analogies were not always designed to be simple, as we aimed to test the model’s ability to interpret non-trivial analogies effectively. The test set, along with annotated edits, is included with this appendix.

C.6.2 Application: Pattern Mixing

The goal of pattern mixing is to transfer aspects of one real-world pattern X to another real-world pattern Y . This approach makes it easier to create novel variations of patterns and to transfer specific aspects of patterns that may not be present in our synthetic dataset. To achieve this, we construct an analogy pair (X, X') , which is used as input to edit Y . This sequential process, referred to as “chaining,” allows edits to build upon the outputs of previous steps.

Our model’s ability to use real-world patterns as analogy inputs enables chaining, which is critical for pattern mixing. This capability is attributed to the scale and diversity of the synthetic dataset used during training. Figure C.7 illustrates this process for a pair (X, Y) where we mix the layout of X with the tiles of Y .

C.6.3 Application: Pattern Animation

This application allows users to transfer animations created using a simple synthetic pattern A to real-world patterns B . Traditionally, such transfers require inferring the program for B and applying the animation to it. In contrast, with our method, users can automatically create analogy pairs from A 's animation sequence to generate corresponding variations in B . The user provides as input (A, \mathbf{A}') , where \mathbf{A}' represents the frames of the animation, and a real-world pattern B . We then employ TRIFUSER to generate variations of B that correspond to analogy pairs created for each frame as follows:

$$\mathbf{B}' = \{B' = M(A, A', B) | A' \in \mathbf{A}'\}. \tag{C.2}$$

To ensure temporal consistency, for each frame, we fix the initial latent noise, generate $n = 5$ samples, and select the one with the lowest PSNR relative to the preceding frame. This approach avoids program inference and enables automated animation transfer. A demonstration video is provided with this appendix. In the future, we hope to enforce stronger priors to improve temporal consistency.

C.6.4 Application: Wide Non-stationary Canvas

Visual patterns often need to adapt to varying resolutions, such as for use in presentations or posters. This is commonly achieved for stationary patterns by making the pattern image seamlessly tileable. In fact, images generated using convolution-based diffusion models can also be made seamlessly tileable by employing circular padding in the convolution layers. However, no such solution exists for non-stationary patterns. We provide a novel solution by adapting Multi-Diffusion [8] to our settings.

Multi-Diffusion solves the task of generating large images with diffusion models. This is achieved by first generating model predictions on tiled crops of the canvas and using the average predicted noise across overlapping image crops at each denoising step. Applying this naively to our method fails as our model strongly depends on the conditioning input (A, A', B) for generating B' , i.e., it depends strongly on the spatial orientation of the conditioning embeddings. To circumvent this issue, we adapt multi-diffusion for our model by performing consistent cropping across analogy inputs (A, A', B) and the latent code of B' during generation. This adaptation enables the generation of wide, non-stationary canvases. Figure C.8 illustrates three examples generated using this method, where we generated wide canvases that are 1536×1536 pixels in size.

Figure C.9: We compare our method, **TriFuser**, against the three baselines with four different metrics. The x-axis of each plot corresponds to the number of samples used for evaluation, demonstrating that **TriFuser** remains superior to the baselines across sample counts.

	Analogy data	DSIM (↓)	DISTS (↓)	LPIPS (↓)	SSIM (↑)
<i>LatentMod</i> CATEGORICAL	✗	0.242	0.320	0.613	0.502
<i>LatentMod</i> TOKENWISE	✗	0.307	0.333	0.581	0.500
<i>LatentMod</i> ANALOGICAL	✓	0.273	0.330	0.620	0.525

Table C.1: We compare different variations of the *LatentMod* baseline. None of the variations are suitable for performing precise *programmatic* edits, indicating that latent-arithmetic-based analogical editing is poorly suited to precise structure editing.

C.7 Quantitative Results

We now describe additional experiments conducted to further validate our system. First, we discuss quantitative evaluations in this section, followed by qualitative results in Section C.8.

C.7.1 *LatentMod* Ablation

An important baseline we considered is *LatentMod*, where first we train a model to learn a latent space for representing patterns, followed by deploying *latent-arithmetic* [180] to create analogical patterns. Specifically, we first train an Image Variation Latent Diffusion Model (LDM) on our pattern dataset (i.e., condition on tokens extracted from a pattern image to denoise the same pattern image). Then, during test time, given patterns (A, A', B) we infer the analogically edited pattern B' by using the LDM to denoise a Gaussian-initialized latent conditioned on the latent arithmetic tokens $(E(B) + E(A') - E(A))$. In this section, we

Figure C.10: We compare our model against the baselines on a per-edit type basis. We observe that our model obtains higher perceptual similarity to the ground truth target across the edit types.

Figure C.11: Training TriFuser with more analogical quartet samples improves its performance.

Figure C.12: Training TriFuser with a larger batch size improves its performance.

explore different variations of this model, demonstrating the superiority of the baseline used in Chapter 5 over its alternatives.

First, we consider two architectures for the Image Variation model. The first, referred to as CATEGORICAL, uses only a single pooled token (i.e., a 1×768 size embedding) as the conditioning input $E(A)$. The second,

referred to as `TOKENWISE`, uses all the 257 image tokens generated by the token extractor (i.e., a 257×768 size embedding) as the conditioning input $E(A)$. Finally, we also consider an alternative of `CATEGORICAL`, as introduced in `DeepVisualAnalogy` [147]. This variation, referred to as `ANALOGICAL`, has the same architecture as `CATEGORICAL`, but has an alternate loss formulation which resembles the test-time usage. Essentially, this model is trained to denoise B' while being conditioned on $E(B) + E(A') - E(A)$ explicitly. Note that `CATEGORICAL` and `TOKENWISE` only require a dataset of training patterns, whereas `ANALOGICAL` requires analogical quartets (A, A', B, B') during training as well (similar to conditional generative approaches like `ImageBrush` [174] and our approach, `TRIFUSER`).

Table C.1 compares these approaches on our synthetic validation set, reporting perceptual metrics—`DSim` [40], `DIST` [29] and `LPIPS` [222]—along with `SSIM` to capture pixel-level structural similarity. We first note that `TOKENWISE` shows worse results than `CATEGORICAL`. Since `TOKENWISE` is conditioned on a large embedding of size 257×768 , the latent embedding fails to aid analogical reasoning (i.e. compression is essential for learning a latent space capable of analogical latent arithmetic). Second, we notice a surprising result: `ANALOGICAL`, despite being trained explicitly for analogical editing, is in fact slightly weaker than `CATEGORICAL`. Visual inspection reveals that although `ANALOGICAL` and `CATEGORICAL` generate similar results, `CATEGORICAL` often tends to retain more aspects of the input pattern B compared to `ANALOGICAL`, which consequently sometimes results in a higher perceptual similarity to the target B' .

Finally, we remark that all these variations remain significantly weaker than the conditional analogical editors. This indicates that Latent Arithmetic is perhaps not suitable for *precise* editing, as there is an inherent tension between (a) representing sufficient details of patterns in the latent space to recreate them with high fidelity and (b) having sufficient compression of the latent space to achieve analogical reasoning via latent arithmetic. Consequently, most image-editing methods in the diffusion era have turned towards alternate strategies such as manipulation of attention maps [3] and latent noise inversion [58] for enabling *precise* editing.

C.7.2 `TRIFUSER` Ablations

As described in Chapter 5, analogies can have multiple valid interpretations, and even a single interpretation may yield several visually related variations. To account for this multiplicity, we generate k output patterns for each input set (A, A', B) and select the one that maximizes each metric. We first elucidate the relation between the number of generated samples k and the different metrics in Figure C.9. We show four plots, one for each metric. Each plot has the number of samples k as the x-axis, and the metric (e.g., `LPIPS`, `SSIM`) on the y-axis. These plots reveal that for perceptual similarity metrics, `TRIFUSER` triumphs over the baselines

Figure C.13: We show an example of a complex synthetic pattern B with a SPLITWEAVE program z_B containing 31 nodes. Inferring such programs automatically, i.e., VPI, is infeasible. Our approach, in contrast, allows users to construct a simple program z_A and create analogical patterns (A, A') to parametrically edit B , *without* inferring z_B . The task of constructing z_A is significantly easier; in this example, z_A contains 8 nodes, only $\sim 25\%$ of z_B 's size.

across all values of k . Furthermore, as we increase k , TRIFUSER significantly closes the gap between itself and *Inpainter* when measuring SSIM. More importantly, these plots reveal that using a smaller number of samples ($k = 5$ as used in Chapter 5) is sufficient, and performance does not drastically decrease as k is decreased from 16.

We also evaluate all the models separately for each type of edit in the synthetic validation set. We measure the average $(1 - LPIPS)$ with $k = 5$, so that a higher value indicates better performance, for each type of edit and visualize the results in a radar plot, as shown in Figure C.10. We observe that TRIFUSER surpasses all the baselines across the different types of edits. For more details regarding the edits, please refer to Section C.5.

C.7.3 TRIFUSER Scalability

Recent research has shown that scaling neural approaches, in terms of computational complexity and dataset size, is fundamental for achieving compelling results. Consequently, it is critical to investigate the *scalability* of novel models/methods. In this section, we study the scalability of TRIFUSER with respect to its training dataset size and its training compute budget.

First, we perform ablations to elicit the relation between training dataset size and TRIFUSER performance.

Figure C.14: (left) TRIFUSER generates multiple *equally valid* yet different edited images B' . (right) We present additional examples showing that TRIFUSER effectively edits patterns from novel pattern styles not present in the training dataset.

We train three variations of TRIFUSER with dataset sizes of 100,000 samples, 500,000 samples, and 1 million samples, respectively. The performance of these three methods is then compared on the held-out synthetic validation set. The resulting metrics are visualized as line plots in Figure C.11. Here, we provide four plots, one for each metric, similar to the format in Figure C.9. The x-axis corresponds to the number of samples (k), and the y-axis corresponds to the respective metrics. We notice a meaningful increase in performance across the different metrics as we increase the scale of the training dataset. This indicates that training the method in the future with larger datasets containing even more pattern styles may result in further improvements.

Similarly, we study the effect of training compute budget on model performance. All our models are typically trained on 8 A100-40GB GPUs with a batch size of 224. To explore the relation between training budget and model performance, we train a variation of TRIFUSER on 8 A100-80GB GPUs with a batch size of 448. We report a comparison between these two models in Figure C.12. As shown in this figure, increasing the batch size results in further improvements to the model, indicating a positive correlation with the training budget. In the future, training TRIFUSER with larger training budgets may lead to further improvements in the model's performance.

C.8 Qualitative Results

We now present qualitative results to emphasize the utility and impressive capabilities of our method. As discussed earlier, a primary motivator for our approach is that Visual Program Inference attempts to infer a program that fully replicates the input pattern, which is not only a hard task, but also results in a tedious editing experience as the user often has to adjust various parameters to ascertain *which* parts of the program must be edited to attain the desired edit. In contrast, with our approach, the user only has to construct the program for (A, A') , which demonstrates *which* property to edit and *how* to edit it. In particular, A does not even need to be similar to B , making the task of constructing the programs $(z_A, z_{A'})$ considerably simpler.

In Figure C.13, we compare the program of a complex target pattern B , marked as z_B , with the simple program z_A constructed to create an analogy pair (A, A') for editing the layout of B . While z_B contains 31 operator nodes, z_A contains only 8, which is $\sim 25\%$ of the size of z_B . We make the following notes: (a) the task users need to perform – that of creating z_A – is significantly easier than the task of inferring z_B , and (b) using the analogical editor induces parametric control over pattern B based on the program z_A . Consequently, to perform simple edits of pattern B , the user only needs to specify a simple program z_A .

As mentioned previously, analogies can have multiple valid interpretations, and even a single interpretation may yield several visually related variations. Consequently, an analogical editor must also be capable of producing multiple interpretations for any given input analogy pair. Having such a one-to-many mapping, as our model has, is more suitable for editing as the user can select the edited pattern that matches their edit intent from multiple generations. In contrast, restricting to a singular interpretation may more easily lead to scenarios where the system’s and user’s interpretation of the input analogy differ.

In Figure C.14, we present analogical edits performed on real-world patterns by our method, highlighting the generation of different *equally valid* analogy interpretations. The first row corresponds to an edit for removing a random coloring variation effect on the input pattern B . TRIFUSER produces two outcomes, both reasonable as pattern B does not make it clear what the tile’s original color is. The example presented in the second row corresponds to an edit to modify the background of the input pattern. However, it is unclear if the muted ellipses behind the lion tiles are part of the tile or part of the background. Consequently, some generations keep these ellipses, updating their color accordingly, while other generations eschew them to provide a uniform colored background as shown in A' . Finally, the third example corresponds to an edit on the layout of the input pattern. We show two equally reasonable outputs generated by our model as the underlying orientation of the bone tile is ambiguous.

Finally, in Figure C.14, we provide additional examples of our model reasonably editing patterns in styles unseen during training. Additionally, we present qualitative results comparing our method to the other

Figure C.15: We present examples from the test set where our method fails to produce a reasonable edit. Edits sometimes fail due to poor retention of tile details ((b) and (d)), imperfect application of the edit demonstrated with (A, A') ((c) and (e)), or failure to understand the input analogy pair, as shown in examples (a) and (f).

baselines in Figure C.16. Images comparing the four methods across the entire test set are also provided with this appendix.

C.9 Failure Cases

We present and discuss some recurring failure cases for our method. Figure C.15 provides 6 examples from our test set of real-world patterns where our method fails to generate a reasonable analogical edit. When editing the layout of patterns, our model still sometimes struggles to retain the fine details of the input pattern’s tile, particularly when they contain text — this is demonstrated in examples (b) and (d). Another mode of failure is when the edit does not *fully* perform the intended edit, as visible in examples (c) and (e). In (c), though the model adds a color change effect on B as intended, it produces color variations that do not match the color variations shown in (A, A') . This is due to the usage of *relative* color shifts (with respect to a hue wheel) in our synthetic patterns. Similarly, in (e), while the model correctly removes the tile scaling effect, it replaces the fish tile with the cat tile. Finally, a few failure cases also emerge due to the model failing to understand the input analogy pair, as shown in examples (a) and (f).

C.10 Limitations

While our method demonstrates robust performance and versatility, there are a few limitations that merit discussion.

Figure C.16: Qualitative comparison between patterns generated by our model, TriFuser, and the baselines. TriFuser generates higher quality patterns with greater fidelity to the input analogy.

The primary limitation lies in the reliance on a synthetic dataset of analogies. To extend this technique to other domains, users must construct a domain-specific language (DSL) and define editing functions.

Furthermore, real-world applicability of our method depends on the coverage of the DSL and the editing functions. Although we demonstrate generalization to related pattern styles, the current scale of the dataset limits the model’s ability to handle entirely novel pattern styles or edits. However, this limitation may be addressed by automatic construction of analogical data from multiple domains such as ShaderToy, which contains GLSL programs for creating patterns, and p5.js, which contains JavaScript-like code for creative computing. Such a dataset could enable pretraining on a broader variety of analogical variations before fine-tuning for specific domains. Additionally, various visual domains such as Zentangle patterns, materials, and LEGO already contain well-defined DSLs, making it easier to extend our framework to other structured visual data domains.

A second drawback is that analogies, while universal in their ability to represent arbitrary edits, are not always the most efficient modality for conveying edit intent. For example, simple edits such as color changes might be more easily performed through direct recoloring of the canvas. Furthermore, the inherent flexibility of analogies, which allows multiple interpretations, can sometimes make it tedious to sample and select a desired output. This issue could be mitigated by coupling analogies with text-based guidance or other constraints to make the process more directed and user-friendly.

Finally, using the system requires constructing analogy pairs, which depends on the user’s familiarity with SPLITWEAVE and node-based programming. While this could pose a barrier to some users, the increasing adoption of node-based tools in visual programming provides a promising path forward. Future research into improving user interaction for visual programming and analogical editing could further lower this barrier and make the system more accessible.

Despite these limitations, this chapter provides a flexible framework for analogical pattern editing and highlights several avenues for future research, including extending analogical datasets, improving edit specificity, and enhancing user interfaces.

APPENDIX D

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS FOR MIGUMI

D.1 Details: Modeling Millable Geometry

D.1.1 Cylinder Minkowski Sum Proposition

Our MXG representation leverages flat extrusions that satisfy the Minkowski condition to ensure that each subtraction V_i is millable. Here, we first provide the proposition and proof on which this representation is built.

We begin by characterizing the class of solids that can be constructed via subtractive milling¹. A solid $P \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is millable if it can be expressed as:

$$P = M - \bigcup_i V_i, \tag{D.1}$$

where M is the material stock and each V_i is a *millable* volume removed by the i -th milling operation. To be millable, each V_i must be a Minkowski sum² with respect to the milling tool’s rotational swept volume. The

¹We assume all solids are regular closed subsets of \mathbb{R}^3 , i.e., equal to the closure of their interior.

²Given two sets $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, their Minkowski sum is defined as $A \oplus B = \{a + b \mid a \in A, b \in B\}$.

Figure D.1: Our custom in-house node-based visual programming interface. On the left, we show a simple program that creates a shape. On the right, we show the program for a simple joint, “Ari Tsugi.” Notice the reuse of subgraphs for the 2D CSG expression between the two parts. We also record the assembly sequence using a state machine, and highlight the nodes that correspond to the assembly states in the top-left of the right image.

rotational sweep of a flat-end, uniform-radius drill bit yields a cylinder. Therefore, this can be written as:

$$V_i = X_i \oplus \text{Cyl}_i, \quad (\text{D.2})$$

where X_i is an arbitrary shape and $\text{Cyl}_i \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is the rotational sweep of the drill bit for the i -th operation. To enforce accessibility, Cyl_i is modeled as a semi-infinite cylinder extending away from the milling direction, ensuring that each V_i is accessible from outside. This formulation guarantees millability by construction: each subtraction aligns with tool geometry and access constraints, making the resulting solid P physically achievable through sequential milling.

The following proposition characterizes when a solid admits such a representation:

Proposition 1. *Let $V \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ be a solid, and let Cyl_r denote the semi-infinite cylinder of radius r along the z -axis. Then $V = X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$ for some solid $X \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ if and only if:*

1. (**Minkowski Condition**) *For every z , the horizontal slice*

$$C(z) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid (x, y, z) \in V\}$$

satisfies $C(z) = X(z) \oplus B_r$ for some $X(z) \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, where B_r is a circle of radius r .

2. (**Nesting Condition**) *For all $z_1 < z_2$, $C(z_1) \subseteq C(z_2)$.*

Intuitively, this proposition states that a solid is millable with a flat-end bit of radius r along a direction (e.g., the z -axis) if, when sliced perpendicular to that direction, each slice is a Minkowski sum of some base shape with a disk of radius r , and the slices nest monotonically, i.e., the volume forms a heightfield from the milling direction. Although stated here for the z -axis, the same conditions apply to any milling direction $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ after rotation.

Proof (if direction). (\Leftarrow) Suppose $V \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ satisfies the following conditions:

1. For each height z , the horizontal cross-section

$$C(z) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid (x, y, z) \in V\}$$

satisfies $C(z) = X(z) \oplus B_r$ for some planar shape $X(z) \subset \mathbb{R}^2$.

2. The slices are nested: for all $z_1 < z_2$, $C(z_1) \subseteq C(z_2)$.

We define the solid: $X = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid (x, y) \in X(z)\}$, and let $\text{Cyl}_r = B_r \times [0, \infty)$ denote the semi-infinite vertical cylinder of radius r .

We will show that $V = X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$.

(i) $V \subseteq X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$: Let $(x, y, z) \in V$. Then by definition, $(x, y) \in C(z) = X(z) \oplus B_r$. So there exist $(x', y') \in X(z)$, $(u, v) \in B_r$ such that $(x, y) = (x' + u, y' + v)$. Letting $w = 0$, we have:

$$(x, y, z) = (x', y', z) + (u, v, w),$$

where $(x', y', z) \in X$ and $(u, v, w) \in \text{Cyl}_r$. Thus, $(x, y, z) \in X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$.

(ii) $X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r \subseteq V$: Let $(x, y, z) \in X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$. Then there exist $(x', y', z') \in X$, $(u, v, w) \in \text{Cyl}_r$ such that:

$$(x, y, z) = (x' + u, y' + v, z' + w),$$

with $(x', y') \in X(z')$, $(u, v) \in B_r$, $w \geq 0$. By the nesting condition, $X(z') \subseteq X(z' + w)$. So $(x', y') \in X(z)$, and hence $(x, y) \in X(z) \oplus B_r = C(z)$. Thus, $(x, y, z) \in V$.

Conclusion: We have shown that $V \subseteq X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$ and $X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r \subseteq V$, hence:

$$V = X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r. \quad \square$$

□

Proof (only if direction). (\Rightarrow) Assume $V = X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$, where $\text{Cyl}_r = B_r \times [0, \infty)$ is a semi-infinite cylinder aligned with the z -axis.

We will show that the horizontal slices of V satisfy both the Minkowski and nesting conditions stated in the proposition.

(i) Minkowski Condition. Fix any height $z \in \mathbb{R}$, and define the horizontal slice of V at height z as

$$S(z) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid (x, y, z) \in V\}.$$

Since $V = X \oplus \text{Cyl}_r$, for any $(x, y, z) \in V$, there exists $(x', y', z') \in X$ and $(u, v, w) \in B_r \times [0, \infty)$ such that

$$(x, y, z) = (x', y', z') + (u, v, w).$$

This implies $z = z' + w$ with $w \geq 0$, so $z' \leq z$. Let us define

$$X(z) = \{(x', y') \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \exists z' \leq z \text{ such that } (x', y', z') \in X\}.$$

Figure D.2: Fixed interface constraints during slice-wise optimization. We show two example joints with the interfaces to non-aligned fixed extrusions highlighted in red. These fixed interfaces are preserved by enforcing a strong boundary loss, allowing the optimization to proceed on a compact set of slice-aligned contours without hampering tight coupling between non-aligned extrusions.

Then for any $(x, y) \in S(z)$, we have $(x, y) \in X(z) \oplus B_r$. Conversely, for any $(x', y') \in X(z)$ and $(u, v) \in B_r$, the point $(x' + u, y' + v, z) \in V$. Therefore,

$$S(z) = X(z) \oplus B_r.$$

(ii) Nesting Condition. Let $z_1 < z_2$. Then by construction, $X(z_1) \subseteq X(z_2)$, since $\{z' \leq z_1\} \subseteq \{z' \leq z_2\}$. Taking Minkowski sums with B_r , we get:

$$S(z_1) = X(z_1) \oplus B_r \subseteq X(z_2) \oplus B_r = S(z_2),$$

as required. □

A constructive way to satisfy these conditions is to extrude a 2D region $C_i \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, embedded in a plane orthogonal to the milling direction \mathbf{n}_i , over a semi-infinite interval $(-\infty, h_i)$. This ensures that the volume forms a heightfield along \mathbf{n}_i , satisfying the nesting condition. If C_i additionally satisfies the Minkowski condition (i.e., $C_i = X_i \oplus B_r$ for some $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$), then the resulting solid is millable with a flat drill bit of radius r . This leads naturally to our core primitive: the subtractive extrusion, which forms the foundation of the MXG representation.

D.1.2 Valid Dilation and Erosion Operations

As described in Chapter 6, each extrusion field \mathcal{E}_i is defined by a 2D signed distance function (SDF) f_i , constructed using symbolic expressions composed of primitives and Boolean operations such as union,

intersection, difference, and complement. While this representation offers high expressivity, the general protocol for evaluating such expressions using min/max functions yields only pseudo-SDFs: functions that preserve the sign of the distance but do not provide accurate Euclidean values [111].

This approximation is detrimental for morphological operations such as dilation and erosion, which rely on exact distance values to compute correct offsets. To address this, we convert each symbolic expression into a PolyCurve representation: a closed, non-intersecting polygonal chain composed of straight-line segments and circular arcs. We ensure that all Boolean operations (e.g., intersections or differences) are performed such that no two primitives have intersecting boundaries. This guarantees that min/max-based SDF evaluation produces exact SDFs.

Beyond improving accuracy for morphological operations, PolyCurve conversion also facilitates optimization. The original symbolic representation may lack sufficient degrees of freedom to reduce loss terms effectively. In contrast, PolyCurves provide direct, parameterized control over geometric elements, improving convergence during optimization.

D.1.3 Authoring Interface

We construct MXG₀ programs for each joint using a custom in-house node-based visual programming interface, shown in Figure D.1. The interface exposes symbolic construction of extrusion profiles via basic geometric primitives and 2D CSG operations. Though minimal in design, it supports parametric control and real-time feedback.

Internally, each expression is compiled into GLSL shader code and rendered using ray marching, enabling direct visualization without conversion to triangle meshes. Our renderer builds on Inigo Quilez’s ShaderToy pipeline, allowing fast previews of complex joint geometries.

While the current interface is targeted at expert users, we view it as a foundation for broader tooling. Making this system usable by non-experts remains important future work.

D.2 Details: Restoring Tight Coupling

D.2.1 Fixed Interface Constraint in Equivalence Slice Sets

Our optimization process operates slice-by-slice, but many slices are redundant in their contribution to the coupling loss. To reduce computational cost, we identify a compact set of representative slices that together cover the lateral surface of the joint. We refer to this set as the *equivalence slice set*. Each slice is selected from a set of planar extrusions that share tool direction and overlapping coupling regions.

However, not all interfaces are optimized simultaneously. Interfaces with extrusions from non-aligned directions, i.e., those not belonging to the current slicing direction, are treated as fixed. Figure D.2(a,b) shows examples of such non-aligned interfaces (highlighted with lines) that are held constant during a particular slice-aligned optimization stage.

To preserve surface continuity at these boundaries, we enforce a strong *boundary loss* that penalizes deviation from the current surface geometry. This effectively treats the extrusions from other directions as fixed walls, guiding the optimization toward solutions that remain compatible with them.

Algorithm 6: Optimization from MXG₀ Program to MXG_r Program

Require: MXG₀ Program \mathcal{P}_0 , target drill radius r

- 1: **for** each direction \mathbf{n} **do**
- 2: Identify extrusion fields aligned with \mathbf{n}
- 3: Sample slicing planes orthogonal to \mathbf{n}
- 4: Group extrusions into equivalence sets $\{\mathcal{S}_1, \dots, \mathcal{S}_K\}$
- 5: **for** each equivalence set \mathcal{S}_k **do**
- 6: Freeze misaligned boundary constraints
- 7: **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
- 8: Increase dilation rate $r_d \leftarrow \text{schedule}(t)$
- 9: Sample points on ∂g & ∂C_i on each slice
- 10: Compute total loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}}$
- 11: Update g_i parameters via gradient descent
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **end for**
- 15: **return** Final MXG_r Program \mathcal{P}_r

D.2.2 Optimization

Algorithm 6 summarizes the full pipeline used to optimize an MXG₀ program to its fabricable MXG_r form.

None of the algorithm’s steps require manual input. Extrusion fields aligned with a sampled direction \mathbf{n} are detected via their dot product with \mathbf{n} (step 2). Slices are then generated at regular intervals along this direction as intersections between the fields and planes at the sampled positions (step 3). Finally, to form equivalence sets, we assign each slice a signature based on the extrusions it intersects with (each slice’s signature is the set of signatures of the extrusions it intersects with) and group slices that share the same signature to form the equivalence sets (step 4).

Sampling Points on Part Contours ∂C_i : Let \mathcal{E}_i be an extrusion aligned with the slicing plane z_k , defined via a 2D signed distance function $g_i : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Its dilated contour ∂C_i is defined by the r -level set: $\partial C_i = \{x \mid f_i(x) = r\}$. Now, f_i is constructed from Boolean compositions over *PolyCurve* primitives, which are closed curves composed of line and arc segments. Therefore, we can sample points $x_\ell \in \partial C_i$ in a

differentiable way using a three-step approach:

1. **Offset curve primitives:** Sample points on each line and arc segment of the polycurve and offset them outward along the normal by distance r .
2. **Handle corners:** At each vertex v_i of the polycurve, generate a circular arc of radius r and sample along it.
3. **Contour filtering:** Reject any point x for which $f_i(x) \neq r$, ensuring that retained samples lie on the true offset contour.

This sampling strategy avoids constructing a closed-form expression for the offset curve and remains fully differentiable with respect to the parameters of f_i .

Per-part 2D Signed Distance Field Given a sample $x_\ell \in \partial C_i(z_k)$, we compute its signed distance from the 2D projection of another part P^b in the same slice plane. This part is represented as $P^b(z_k) = M(z_k) - \bigcup_j \overline{\mathcal{E}_j(z_k)}$. Since all components— $M(z_k)$ and $\overline{\mathcal{E}_j(z_k)}$ —are represented as signed distance functions (SDFs), we construct a pseudo-SDF for $P^b(z_k)$ using min/max composition. The distance from part $\partial P^b(z_k)$ can then be evaluated as: $\text{SDF}_{P^b}(x_\ell)$. Although this pseudo-SDF may deviate from the true Euclidean SDF away from the boundary, it matches closely near the zero-contour, where our optimization is concentrated. Additional discussion and analysis are provided in this appendix.

Occupancy Preservation Loss We define occupancy as a continuous field estimated using the signed distance function SDF_P for each part P . Let $O(x)$ be the binary occupancy of the original shape (pre-optimization), and let $\hat{O}_\theta(x)$ denote the soft occupancy field of the optimized part at point x , derived from its SDF using a sigmoid activation:

$$\hat{O}_\theta(x) = \sigma(-\alpha \cdot \mathcal{D}_P(x)), \quad (\text{D.3})$$

where α controls the sharpness of the transition. We then define the occupancy loss as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{occ}} = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{G}} \left(\hat{O}_\theta(x) - O(x) \right)^2, \quad (\text{D.4})$$

where \mathcal{G} is a uniform grid of sample points within the coupling volume. This loss encourages the optimized parts to remain close to their original geometry in both shape and extent, acting as a regularizer on the optimization.

Figure D.3: Threshold sensitivity analysis. Left: *Exact Millability* ($\% \mathcal{M}$) of the ODF method across varying distance thresholds. Trends remain consistent across a wide range, confirming that the results in Chapter 6 are not sensitive to specific parameter choices.

Figure D.4: For a given shape to be millable with a drill bit of radius r , constraining the boundary curvature to be less than $1/r$ is insufficient.

D.2.3 Alternate Approaches

We considered two alternate strategies for generating millable, tightly coupled geometries, but found them either insufficient or impractical in our setting.

Iterative ODF One possible approach is to alternate morphological opening with Diff-Flip updates, progressively restoring coupling after each step. However, in practice, this method encounters major hurdles. First, most 2D boolean libraries lack robust support for polycurve representations involving both lines and arcs, making repeated set operations error-prone. Even with rasterized occupancy grids and morphological operations, the procedure becomes unstable after just a few iterations. Moreover, convergence is not guaranteed, and thin features are often lost due to over-erosion. While simple in principle, this approach fails to yield consistent or controllable results.

Curvature Constraint. Another approach is to constrain the curvature of 2D contours used in subtractive profiles. Since flat-end tools cannot produce sharp turns, one might attempt to ensure that the curvature of

Figure D.5: Threshold sensitivity analysis. Right: *Coupling Success Rate* (C_τ) across the same thresholds. Trends remain consistent across a wide range, confirming that the results in Chapter 6 are not sensitive to specific parameter choices.

all profile paths remains below $1/r$, where r is the milling tool radius. When a contour is at the interface of two joints, we can then constrain the absolute curvature to be less than $1/r$. While this condition is necessary, it is not sufficient: a curve may have bounded curvature but still violate millability if opposing path segments come too close. Figure D.4 shows a counterexample where the curvature constraint holds, yet the tool cannot pass through due to local underclearance. Millability imposes global constraints on offset distance, not just local curvature bounds.

One might attempt to strengthen the curvature condition by also enforcing a minimum local thickness, requiring that opposing segments of a contour remain at least one tool diameter apart. However, implementing such a rule is non-trivial: it demands reliable detection of thin regions and careful reshaping to increase clearance without altering intended contact geometry. Moreover, for joints involving more than two parts, it is unclear how curvature and thickness bounds should be formulated across several interacting boundaries. These challenges limit the practicality of a curvature-plus-thickness strategy and motivate the global offset-distance formulation adopted in our method.

D.2.4 Optimization and Implementation Details

We implement our optimization pipeline in PyTorch, using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.003. Each slice-level optimization is run for 250 iterations, and we select the iteration with the lowest boundary loss as the final result. We ran all experiments on an Alienware workstation equipped with an Intel i9 11900K CPU, a GeForce RTX 3090 GPU, and 64 GB of DDR4 RAM.

Prior to optimization, we convert all input extrusion profiles to non-intersecting polycurve representa-

Figure D.6: The five different types of milling procedures used to fabricate the eight physical outputs in Figure 6.12 of Chapter 6.

tions. Due to occasional instability in boolean operations over polycurves (e.g., unresolved self-intersections or missing arcs), we manually corrected a small number of cases. These corrections apply only to the initial geometry and do not affect the optimization procedure. Additionally, for two joints in our dataset, we adjust the threshold used for detecting coupling boundaries due to noisy overlaps in the manually authored input geometry.

For joint assemblies involving three or more parts, we observe instability in the M_p gradient when a point on one milling path lies near multiple opposing paths. To mitigate this, we introduce a weighting scheme that downweights gradient contributions from such ambiguous regions. Specifically, we compute an entropy-based score over the top- k nearest opposing points and suppress gradients where the entropy exceeds a threshold, indicating poor localization of a unique coupled path. This improves convergence and avoids incorrect updates due to competing path associations.

D.3 Evaluation

Figure D.3 plots *Exact Millability* ($\%M$) for ODF as a function of the distance threshold used to verify the Minkowski condition. Figure D.5 shows the corresponding *Coupling Success Rate* (C_τ) across thresholds. Together, these plots demonstrate that the trends reported in Chapter 6 are robust and not the result of hand-tuned thresholds.

D.4 Dataset

Our dataset consists of 30 traditional integral joint designs, each modeled parametrically using our MXG_0 representation. These parametric programs allow for continuous variation in dimensions, proportions, and milling configurations—enabling the synthesis of a much larger family of design variants from each base joint.

We plan to expand the dataset to include additional designs from historical catalogs and contemporary applications. Figure D.8 provides an overview of all joint designs currently included in the dataset.

D.5 Details of the Physical Fabrication Process

We fabricated eight joints using a 3-axis CNC machine. The references (a)–(h) below refer to these physically fabricated joints, shown in Figure 6.12 of Chapter 6. Joints (a) *Koshikake Ari Tsugi* and (b) *Kime Kata Tsugi* were fabricated in the most straightforward manner, without repositioning and in flat orthogonal positions (figure D.6-I). For joints (c) *Kiguchi Ari* and (d) *Shimigiri Daimochi Tsugi*, one part from each joint was fabricated in a vertical orthogonal position (figure D.6-II). Joint (e) *Sumi Niho Kama Tsugi* was positioned at a 45 degree angle to achieve the diagonal cut. To reliably position the material at the 45 degree angle, we first milled out a jig, and then positioned the material in it before milling (figure D.6-III). Joint (f) *Okkake Daisen Tsugi* was repositioned to accommodate the milling of holes facing in a different direction from the main geometries (figure D.6-IV). For this joint, we first fabricated the two main parts. Then we assembled them, and cut out the holes for the plugs in the assembled state. In this way, there is no loss in fabrication precision in terms of the tightness of the coupling despite the repositioning: even if the repositioning is slightly inexact, the holes in the two different parts will still be perfectly aligned because they are cut together. Joint (g) *Kanawa Tsugi* requires a different type of repositioning, namely, milling from three directions per part (figure D.6-V). This process is more error-prone, so fabrication with a 4-or-more-axis CNC machine would have been preferable if we had access to such a machine. Nonetheless, we managed to fabricate a functional joint with our 3-axis machine setup by careful repositioning.

The CNC machine we used was a *ShopBot Desktop MAX with Aluminum T-Slot Deck*. The milling paths were created by importing meshes (*.stl files) of our system outputs into *VCarve*, and then generating roughing tool paths with clearance set to 0.0. To create a small tolerance for the joint, we set the milling bit size to slightly smaller (about 0.05 inches) than the actual mill bit size (1/4 inch). This results in a slight overcut, and the amount can be adjusted depending on the desired tightness of the joint.

Figure D.7: For certain joints, multi-directional milling is critical to ensure that tight coupling is feasible. While fabrication of individual parts with a single subtractive operation is feasible, it results in shapes that cannot be coupled, despite optimization. In contrast, with two oblique subtractions, we can generate a design that is millable and tightly coupled (after optimization).

D.6 Additional Results

Expanding the Design Space Our method accommodates complex joint configurations that lie outside the scope of prior systems. The use of general CSG-like 2D expressions enables us to cover a wider spread of designs. Furthermore, for certain joints, multi-directional milling is critical to ensure that tight coupling is feasible. Figure D.7 shows such a joint. While fabrication of individual parts with a single subtractive operation is feasible, it results in shapes that cannot be coupled, despite optimization. In contrast, with two oblique subtractions, we can generate a design that is millable and tightly coupled (after optimization).

D.7 Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

Several thoughtful questions were raised about our approach; we summarize them here for clarity.

Does the method require substantial manual modeling? Some manual input is needed because no dataset of CNC-adapted traditional joints exists, making data-driven automation infeasible. Moreover, joint design involves subjective choices—such as where to allow small milling artifacts—that benefit from designer control. Our interactive editor streamlines this process by enforcing millability while preserving flexibility. Future work will explore partial automation of common edits and a user-study evaluation.

Figure D.8: Our full dataset of 30 joints. This dataset supports evaluation, benchmarking, and further research into CNC-fabricable joinery.

Is the approach limited to simple geometry or assemblies? Traditional joinery was historically shaped with planar tools such as chisels and saws, and rarely involves free-form 3D surfaces or elaborate multi-stage assemblies. Our method targets this regime and does not attempt to cover joints requiring sculpted surfaces or complex assembly choreography.

In Figure 6.6(a), why are some joint boundaries rounded while others remain sharp? We apply a morphological opening with radius r to the subtraction region. This guarantees millability but differs from uniform filleting: only concave corners inside the removal region (yellow) are rounded, while other edges remain unchanged.

Is the method specific to 3-axis CNC milling? The geometry produced by our algorithm is compatible with 4- and 5-axis mills. We emphasize 3-axis setups because they are widely available in standard woodworking shops, while higher-axis machines can execute the same extrusions with fewer reorientations.

Why assume a single cutter radius? Could multiple tools improve efficiency? Our formulation adapts geometry for the smallest finishing radius, ensuring tight coupling and clearance. Standard practice, roughing with larger cutters and finishing with a small tool, is fully compatible with this geometry and supported by existing CAM software; our focus is on geometric correctness, not minimizing machining time.

Does the approach guarantee global accessibility for the cutter? Every subtraction is constructed as a semi-infinite extrusion along a fixed direction (Section D.1 of this appendix), which guarantees a straight-line tool path along that direction, assuming feasible fixturing.

How are 2D mill path contours represented? They are stored as a sequence of straight segments and circular arcs, using a vertex-bulge format. For implementation details, please refer to the released code.

APPENDIX E

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS FOR SUPERFIT

Appendix Overview

This appendix provides additional qualitative results, detailed technical explanations, and extended experiments supporting Chapter 7. For ease of navigation, we list the major sections below.

- 1. Qualitative Examples** (Sec. E.1)
Expanded visualizations of primitive assemblies on Toys4K, Part-Objaverse, and 3D GenPrim.
- 2. Understanding SuperFrusta** (Sec. E.2)
Expanded formulation, parameterization, and projection operators.
- 3. ResFit Details** (Sec. E.3)
High-level design, iterative loop structure, and full algorithmic flow.
- 4. Decomposition & Initialization** (Sec. E.4)
Detailed description of our volumetric partitioning method.
- 5. Optimization Details** (Sec. E.5)
Two-phase optimization, stochastic preconditioning, curvature weighting, and hyperparameters.
- 6. Applications** (Sec. E.6)
Textured primitive assemblies, canonical CSG inference, and semantic refinement.
- 7. Additional Experiments** (Sec. E.7)
Further evaluations, ablations, and extended comparisons.
- 8. Failure Cases** (Sec. E.8)
Representative scenarios where our method struggles and directions for improvement.

E.1 Qualitative Examples

Qualitative results on diverse 3D shapes. Figures E.1 and E.2 present qualitative reconstructions produced by our method on assets sourced from two datasets: Toys4K [171] and Part-Objaverse [209]. Across both collections, ResFit and SuperFrustum successfully model a broad range of object categories and geometric shapes. The inferred assemblies remain both *accurate* and *parsimonious*, capturing thin features and complex curvature while often partitioning the shape along semantically meaningful boundaries. These examples highlight the versatility of our primitive design: despite its compact parameterization, it adapts fluidly to highly heterogeneous shapes, producing coherent decompositions across diverse objects.

Comparison to prior work. We additionally compare our method against Primitive Anything [212] (PA) (with test-time optimization) and Marching Primitives [104] (MPS) (at 128 resolution) on representative meshes from the 3D GenPrim dataset [194]. As shown in Figures E.3, our method achieves noticeably higher reconstruction fidelity while using substantially fewer primitives. The performance gap is visually pronounced: prior methods tend to either over-fragment shapes or underfit curved and intricate structures, whereas our approach consistently yields clean, coherent assemblies that more closely match the target geometry.

Figure E.1: Qualitative results on the Toys4K dataset. Each example shows the input mesh (gray, bottom row) and the corresponding primitive assembly inferred by ResFit. These examples highlight our method’s ability to capture fine geometric detail and overall structure using compact, interpretable assemblies across a wide variety of toy categories.

Figure E.2: Primitive assemblies inferred on samples from Toys4K and Part-Objaverse. The top two rows show reconstructions on the diverse, real-world objects of Part-Objaverse, while the bottom rows show additional Toys4K results. Across both datasets, ResFit consistently produces compact assemblies that faithfully follow complex, varied geometries; gray rows show the corresponding input meshes.

Figure E.3: Comparison with PA (TTO) [212] and MPS [104] on examples from the 3D GenPrim dataset [194]. Our method achieves higher geometric fidelity while using far fewer primitives.

Figure E.4: RoundedRect2D. From left to right: level sets of the primitive; parameterization with size (s_x, s_y) and radius r ; SDF for each of the four regions of an origin-centered rectangle (by symmetry in x and y we reason in the top-right quadrant); morphological dilation to achieve a rounded rectangle with corner radius r , formed by shrinking to $\frac{1}{2}(s_x, s_y) - (r, r)$ and taking the r -level set. In all panels, the 0-level set is shown in red.

E.2 Understanding SuperFrusta

As discussed in Chapter 7, SuperFrusta is a convex primitive defined by an exact signed-distance function f with six interpretable controls: *size*, *dilation*, *roundness*, *taper*, *curvature*, and *onion* (shell thickness). We group them as $\theta = \{s_x, s_y, s_z, r, d, t, c, o\}$, where “size” counts as one control though it has three components.

$$\text{sdf}_{\mathbf{p}} = f(\mathbf{p}; \theta), \quad \theta = \{s_x, s_y, s_z, r, d, t, c, o\}.$$

Construction by composition. Let $\mathbf{p} = (x, y, z)$ and define the stages

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}^* &= \text{DomainCurve3D}(\mathbf{p}; s_z, c), \\ \mathbf{s}_{2D} &= \text{RoundedRect2D}(\mathbf{p}_{xy}^*; s_x, s_y, r), \\ s^* &= \text{Trapezoid2D}((\mathbf{s}_{2D}, \mathbf{p}_z^*); s_z, t, o), \end{aligned}$$

$$f(\mathbf{p}; \theta) = s^* - d.$$

We start by defining the 2D SDF primitives RoundedRect2D and Trapezoid2D, as well as their respective parameters. Second, we discuss how to compose these two 2D SDFs to form a 3D SDF, with Trapezoid2D $((\mathbf{s}_{2D}, \mathbf{p}_z^*); s_z, t, o)$. Third, we describe the curving function DomainCurve3D that produces the bulge effect. Last, we discuss the related work that informed this formulation.

E.2.1 RoundedRect2D

In this section, we describe the analytic formulation for RoundedRect2D, parameterized by s_x, s_y, r . See our Shadertoy example for an illustration, as well as panels (a)–(b) of Figure E.4 for a visualization of the level sets and the parameters.

Symmetry preamble. Consider an origin-centered, axis-aligned rectangle. The shape is invariant under the reflections $(x, y) \mapsto (\pm x, \pm y)$, and the oriented (inside-negative) distance to its boundary is unchanged by these reflections. It therefore suffices to derive the expression for the top-right quadrant $x \geq 0, y \geq 0$; the formulas for the other quadrants follow by replacing x, y with $|x|, |y|$. (This symmetry relies on the rectangle being centered and axis-aligned.)

We start by defining the SDF for a 2D rectangle, then generalize to RoundedRect2D.

Axis-aligned rectangle. Let $p_{xy} = (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. We consider a rectangle centered at the origin, with half-sizes $\mathbf{h} = (h_x, h_y) = (\frac{s_x}{2}, \frac{s_y}{2})$. Define $\mathbf{q} = (q_x, q_y) = (|x| - h_x, |y| - h_y)$. The signed distance to the rectangle (negative inside) is obtained by studying four cases (outside-corner, outside-near a vertical edge, outside-near a horizontal edge, inside); see panel (c) of Figure E.4:

$$d_{\square}(p_{xy}; \mathbf{h}) = \begin{cases} \|\mathbf{q}\|_2, & q_x > 0, q_y > 0, \\ q_x, & q_x > 0 \geq q_y, \\ q_y, & q_y > 0 \geq q_x, \\ \max(q_x, q_y), & q_x \leq 0, q_y \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

The above can be rewritten more compactly:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q} &= |\mathbf{p}_{xy}| - \mathbf{h}, \\ \text{sd}_{\square}(p_{xy}; \mathbf{h}) &= \|\max(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{0})\|_2 + \min(\max(q_x, q_y), 0). \end{aligned} \tag{E.1}$$

Rounded rectangle via dilation by radius r . To form a rounded rectangle, given a corner radius $r \geq 0$, we first shrink the half-extents, $\mathbf{h}' = \mathbf{h} - (r, r)$ (assume $r \leq \min(h_x, h_y)$), then take the r -level set (a morphological dilation / Minkowski sum with a disk of radius r). See panel (d) of Figure E.4. In signed-distance terms this is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sd}_{\text{rrect}}(\mathbf{p}_{xy}; s_x, s_y, r) &= \text{sd}_{\square}(p_{xy}; \mathbf{h}') - r, \\ \mathbf{h}' &= \frac{s_{xy}}{2} - (r, r), \end{aligned} \tag{E.2}$$

where sd_{rrect} is an abbreviation for the `ROUNDEDRECT2D` function. Expanding with the rectangle one-liner gives the standard shader form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q} &= |\mathbf{p}_{xy}| - (\mathbf{h} - (r, r)), \\ \text{sd}_{\text{rrect}}(\mathbf{p}_{xy}; s_x, s_y, r) &= \|\max(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{0})\|_2 \\ &\quad + \min(\max(q_x, q_y), 0) - r. \end{aligned} \tag{E.3}$$

E.2.2 Trapezoid2D

We now describe the analytic formulation for Trapezoid2D, parameterized by s_z , t , o (height, taper, and onion factor), visualized in Figure E.5 and Shadertoy.

Trapezoid geometry. Let $p = (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. We work with the intermediary parameters $H > 0$, $\text{inner} \geq 0$, and $x_3 \in \mathbb{R}$ (derived from t, s_x, s_y, s_z), and set $y_B = -H$, $y_T = +H$. The trapezoid is defined by its four vertices:

$$\begin{aligned} L_t &= (-\text{inner}, y_T), & R_t &= (x_3, y_T), \\ L_b &= (-\text{inner}, y_B), & R_b &= (x_3, y_B). \end{aligned} \tag{E.4}$$

Its four edges are: $[L_b, L_t]$ (left), $[R_b, R_t]$ (right), $[L_b, R_b]$ (bottom), $[L_t, R_t]$ (top). The right-edge direction is $e_S = (x_3, 2H)$; the left edge is vertical.

Here, the intermediary parameters are computed based on the parameters t and \mathbf{s} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{inner} &= \min(s_x, s_y) \times 0.5, \\ x_3 &= -(1 - t) \text{inner}, \\ H &= 0.5 \times s_z. \end{aligned} \tag{E.5}$$

The distance function is the minimum distance from p to the four edges:

$$\text{sd}_{\text{trap}}(p) = \pm \min\{d_{\text{left}}(p), d_{\text{right}}(p), d_{\text{bottom}}(p), d_{\text{top}}(p)\},$$

with negative sign inside the trapezoid and positive outside. We now detail the distance to one edge (the right slanted edge); the other edges follow analogously.

Distance to one segment via projection. Consider the segment $[A, B] = [R_b, R_t]$ with

$$\begin{aligned} A &= R_b = (0, -H), \\ B &= R_t = (x_3, +H), \\ e &= B - A = (x_3, 2H). \end{aligned} \tag{E.6}$$

Define the (unclamped) line-projection parameter

$$t_{\text{line}}^*(p) = \frac{\langle p - A, e \rangle}{\|e\|^2} \quad \text{with} \quad \|e\|^2 = x_3^2 + (2H)^2.$$

Figure E.5: Trapezoid2D. Level sets and parameterization: s_z controls the height, while t controls the amount of tapering (*i.e.*, how slanted the right edge is).

The *segment* projection clamps this to $[0, 1]$:

$$t^*(p) = \text{clamp}(t_{\text{line}}^*(p), 0, 1), \quad q(p) = A + t^*(p) e.$$

The exact Euclidean distance from p to the segment is

$$d_{\text{right}}(p) = \|p - q(p)\|.$$

Sign from an oriented half-edge. For an oriented edge $[A, B]$ with direction $e = B - A$, define

$$c_{A \rightarrow B}(p) = \det(p - A, e) = p_x e_y - p_y e_x.$$

Geometrically, $\frac{c_{A \rightarrow B}(p)}{\|e\|}$ is the *signed* distance from p to the *infinite line* through $[A, B]$, positive on the left side of the oriented edge and negative on the right. To make the polygon interior correspond to “non-positive”, we orient edges accordingly and, if needed, flip the sign (multiply by -1).

We collect the four signs; p is inside the trapezoid iff all four signs are non-positive.

Magnitude. We compute the four segment distances via projection:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\text{right}}(p) &= d(p, [R_b, R_t]), \\ d_{\text{left}}(p) &= d(p, [L_b, L_t]), \\ d_{\text{bottom}}(p) &= d(p, [L_b, R_b]), \\ d_{\text{top}}(p) &= d(p, [L_t, R_t]), \\ d_{\text{min}}(p) &= \min\{d_{\text{left}}, d_{\text{right}}, d_{\text{bottom}}, d_{\text{top}}\}. \end{aligned} \tag{E.7}$$

Figure E.6: **Composition of 2D SDFs to form a 3D SDF.** The 0-level sets of the two 2D primitives are shown as dashed curves: red for the *base XY* primitive, and green for the vertical *gate* primitive. For each z -slice, the vertical primitive defines a band on the red primitive (constant here for simplicity). The 0-level set of the resulting 3D primitive is drawn in solid red (line on slices; filled on top and bottom caps).

Sign. With the orientations/sign flips fixed above, set

$$\text{inside}(p) \iff C(p)$$

$$C(p) = \max\{c_L(p), c_S(p), c_B(p), c_T(p)\} \leq 0.$$

Final expression.

$$\text{sd}_{\text{trap}}(p) = \text{sign}(-C(p)) \cdot d_{\min}(p).$$

This yields the exact signed distance for the convex trapezoid (negative inside, positive outside). The same projection-and-half-space procedure applies *identically* to each edge.

E.2.3 Combining two 2D SDFs to define a 3D SDF

Remarkably, 2D signed-distance functions (SDFs) can be composed to form a 3D SDF, as in our parameterization:

$$\mathbf{s}_{2D} = \text{RoundedRect2D}\left(\mathbf{p}_{xy}^*; s_x, s_y, r\right),$$

$$s^* = \text{Trapezoid2D}\left((\mathbf{s}_{2D}, \mathbf{p}_z^*); s_z, t, o\right).$$

We now provide an intuitive visualization of how this composition operates.

A simple example with two 2D rectangles. We begin with a toy example to introduce the concept of composing two 2D SDFs. Define *two* rectangles: (i) a *base* rectangle in the (x, y) -plane that defines the 2D

signed distance (dashed red in Figure E.6):

$$s(x, y) = \text{sd}_{\square}((x, y); b_x, b_y), \quad \text{with half-sizes } (b_x, b_y),$$

and (ii) a *gate* rectangle in the (s, z) -plane, namely $[a, b] \times [-H, H]$, which selects a distance band $a \leq s \leq b$ and a vertical slab $|z| \leq H$ (dashed green in Figure E.6).

The 3D SDF for this volume is obtained by composing the two 2D SDFs:

$$\text{sd}(p) = \text{sd}_{\square}((s(x, y) - m, z); w, H),$$

$$m = \frac{a+b}{2}, \quad w = \frac{b-a}{2}.$$

One can verify that $\text{sd}(p) \leq 0$ iff $a \leq s(x, y) \leq b$ and $|z| \leq H$, with $\text{sd}(p) = 0$ on the faces $s = a$, $s = b$, and $z = \pm H$.

Composing a rounded rectangle with a trapezoid. We now generalize the rectangle–rectangle composition in two ways. First, the *base* SDF in the (x, y) -plane can be any 2D primitive; in SuperFrustra, we use a rounded rectangle because it is instrumental for modeling conic shapes:

$$s(x, y) = \text{sd}_{\text{rrect}}((x, y); \mathbf{b}, r), \quad \mathbf{b} = (w, h).$$

Second, the *gate* in the (s, z) -plane is no longer a constant band $[a, b] \times [-H, H]$, but a *trapezoid* whose horizontal bounds vary linearly with height z . Let $H > 0$ denote the vertical half-extent, $\text{inner} \geq 0$ the bottom-left extent in s -space, $x_3 \in \mathbb{R}$ the top-right offset, and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ the onion-thinning factor. With normalized height

$$t = \frac{z + H}{2H} \in [0, 1] \quad (t = 0 \text{ bottom, } t = 1 \text{ top}),$$

the z -dependent band becomes

$$\begin{cases} a(z) = L_{\gamma}(z) = -\text{inner} (1 - \gamma) + (\gamma x_3) t, \\ b(z) = R_{\gamma}(z) = x_3 t. \end{cases}$$

Each slice thus enforces

$$\text{inside} \iff a(z) \leq s(x, y) \leq b(z) \quad \text{and} \quad |z| \leq H,$$

with slice width $b(z) - a(z) = (1 - \gamma)(\text{inner} + x_3 t)$. The resulting 3D SDF is obtained by evaluating the exact trapezoid SDF in (s, z) :

$$\text{sd}(p) = \text{sd}_{\text{trap}}((s(x, y), z); \text{inner}, H, x_3, \gamma).$$

E.2.4 Onioning.

In signed-distance modeling, onioning extracts a finite-thickness shell by thresholding an SDF symmetrically about its zero set. Let $d : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an exact SDF for $\Gamma = \{x \mid d(x) = 0\}$ and let $o > 0$ be a half-thickness.

Define

$$d^{\text{on}}(x) = |d(x)| - o. \tag{E.8}$$

This operator assigns a negative SDF to points *between the two isosurfaces* $\{x \mid d(x) = \pm o\}$.

Topology under onioning. Shadertoy. Consider a disk of radius $R > 0$ with signed distance $d(x) = \|x\| - R$. For half-thickness $o > 0$, the onioned band is

$$B_o = \{x : |d(x)| \leq o\} = \{x : R - o \leq \|x\| \leq R + o\}.$$

There is a critical value $o^* = R$ at which the band changes topology. If $o \geq R$, the inner bound collapses and

$$B_o = \{x : \|x\| \leq R + o\},$$

i.e., a pure morphological dilation of the original disk (genus 0). If $0 < o < R$, then B_o is an annulus with inner radius $R - o$ and outer radius $R + o$ (a hole appears, genus 1). This illustrates that onioning can change the topology of a base shape, controlled continuously by o —a convenient parameterization that is harder to achieve with explicit primitives.

A naive approach to achieve the onion effect is to simply apply the onion computation on the 2D rounded rectangle SDF value, i.e.

$$\text{sd}_{\text{rect}}^{\text{on}} = |\text{sd}_{\text{rect}}(\mathbf{p}_{xy}; s_x, s_y, r)| - o \tag{E.9}$$

Since this 2D SDF function is used together with the trapezoid function to create a 3D surface, the resulting SDF after this onion operation is very inaccurate – to the extent that sphere tracing with such a primitive definition produces incorrect renders. Furthermore, this design of the onion operator couples the inner "hole" creation with the outer rounding operation. That is, the inner hole boundary ($-d(x) + o = 0$)

Figure E.7: DomainCurve3D. **(a) Source domain.** The sector is parameterized around the circle center C , with polar angle $\varphi \in [-\theta, \theta]$. Inside the sector, iso-offset curves (colored) are circular arcs about C ; at the boundaries $\varphi = \pm\theta$ they meet the tangent frames with unit directions $\mathbf{t}_T = (\sin \theta, \cos \theta)$ and normals \mathbf{n}_T . **(b) Target domain.** Under $\mathbf{q} = \text{mapArcBulge}(\mathbf{p})$, concentric arcs map to vertical lines inside the strip $x' \in [-U, U]$, $y' \in [-\frac{z}{2}, \frac{z}{2}]$, while the tangent continuations remain straight outside the strip. Colors are preserved to track corresponding curves across panels. The red iso-surface of the bulged rectangle on the left maps to the rectangle on the right.

exists in tandem with a dilation of the outer surface ($d(x) + o = 0$). Therefore, we instead use a formulation where (a) the onion effect is achieved by modifying the trapezoid parameterization, and (b) it is performed only for inner-hole creation without affecting the positive SDF outside:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_L &= -\text{inner}(1 - o), \\
 x_{TL} &= -\text{inner} + (x_3 + \text{inner})o, \\
 y_B &= -h, & y_T &= h, \\
 L_b &= (x_L, y_B), & L_t &= (x_{TL}, y_T), \\
 R_b &= (0, y_B), & R_t &= (x_3, y_T).
 \end{aligned} \tag{E.10}$$

E.2.5 Adding curvature

We now explain the last parameter, the curvature c , used to bend primitives with DomainCurve3D. The function is parameterized by the primitive height s_z and by the bulging intensity c .

The goal of the `mapArcBulge` transformation is to construct a smooth bijection between a *rectangular chart* in canonical coordinates (x', y') and a *bulged cap* region in the original domain (x, y) . Intuitively, the mapping unwraps a circular arc into a straight vertical strip. Concentric circles around the arc's center correspond to vertical iso- x' lines, while the angular coordinate φ along the arc maps linearly to the vertical coordinate y' . Outside the sector delimited by the arc, the mapping transitions continuously to tangent-plane coordinates, ensuring differentiability across the boundary. In practice, the shader implements the *inverse transformation*: given a point $\mathbf{p} = (x, y)$ in the bulged domain, it computes its corresponding chart-space

coordinate $\mathbf{p}' = (x', y')$.

Construction of the reference arc. Let $h = z/2$ be half the height and define the endpoints $E_{\top} = (0, +h)$ and $E_{\perp} = (0, -h)$. The circular arc through these points has center $C = (x_c, 0)$ on the x -axis and radius $R = \sqrt{x_c^2 + h^2}$. We set the half-opening angle

$$\theta = \max\left(c \times \frac{\pi}{2}, \varepsilon\right),$$

where $c \in [0, 1]$ controls curvature: $c = 0$ yields a flat cap ($\theta \rightarrow 0$), while $c = 1$ produces a semicircular cap ($\theta = \pi/2$). By trigonometry,

$$x_c = \frac{h}{\tan \theta}.$$

The circular sector bounded by $\varphi = \pm\theta$ is the interior of the bulged region.

Inside-sector mapping. For points whose polar angle around C satisfies $|\varphi| \leq \theta$,

$$y' = \frac{h}{\theta} \operatorname{clamp}\left(\frac{\varphi}{\theta}, -1, 1\right),$$

$$x' = \|\mathbf{p} - C\| - R.$$

The first line linearly reparameterizes angle into vertical coordinate (clamped to $y' = \pm h$ at the endpoints), and the second converts radial offset to x' , so the reference arc maps to $x' = 0$. Hence concentric arcs map to vertical iso- x' lines.

Outside-sector mapping. For $\varphi > \theta$ or $\varphi < -\theta$, we switch to a local tangent frame anchored at the top or bottom endpoint. At the top, with unit tangent and normal

$$t_{\top} = (\sin \theta, \cos \theta), \quad n_{\top} = (-\cos \theta, \sin \theta),$$

(and analogously $t_{\perp} = (-\sin \theta, \cos \theta)$ at the bottom), we project

$$\text{along} = \langle \mathbf{p} - E, t \rangle, \quad \text{perp} = \langle \mathbf{p} - E, n \rangle,$$

and define

$$(x', y') = \begin{cases} (\text{perp}, +h + \text{along}), & \varphi > \theta, \\ (\text{perp}, -h + \text{along}), & \varphi < -\theta. \end{cases}$$

This continues the mapping outside the arc by following tangent rays: horizontal displacements measure perpendicular offsets to the tangent, while the vertical coordinate advances along the tangent direction.

E.2.6 Our Contributions

Prior “super primitives” have appeared in the demoscene and Shadertoy community [145, 135, 136, 137], where the central goal is to achieve a large variety of analytic shapes using compact expressions suitable for real-time rendering. This work shows that these formulations are not only expressive under this original objective, but—crucially—can also serve as *differentiably optimizable* primitives. We demonstrate that, with appropriate reformulation, this family of primitives becomes highly effective for inverse modeling, enabling stable gradient-based fitting while retaining compactness and editability.

Size-relative parameterization. A key contribution of our work is the introduction of *size-relative* parameterization for the taper, rounding, and onion factors. In prior formulations, these parameters are specified in absolute units; while this is acceptable for manual authoring, gradient descent during inverse modeling can drive the parameters toward values where the SDF becomes inaccurate or even ill-defined, causing optimization instability. Our relative formulation guarantees geometric validity across all optimization iterates, ensuring that the solid remains well-behaved and sphere-traceable for all parameter updates. This modification is critical for reliable differentiable fitting.

Arc-based bending via domain reparameterization. We introduce an analytic bending operation based on an *arc-based domain reparameterization* (Section E.2.5). To our knowledge, no prior Shadertoy super primitive incorporates this arc-based mapping. This bending operation substantially expands the shape family expressible by a single primitive—enabling smooth axial curvature without sacrificing differentiability.

Lower-error onion operator. We also introduce a revised formulation of the onion (shell) operator that preserves the *accuracy* of the signed distance field (Section E.2.4). Conventional onioning introduces SDF distortions that lead to rendering artifacts, incorrect gradients, and inconsistencies in the constructed surface—issues that become critical during inverse modeling. Our alternative formulation maintains correct distance values across the entire shell region, ensuring stable gradient flow and producing reliable geometry under subsequent constructive operations such as onioning and dilation.

On SDF accuracy and exact formulations. Our super primitive yields an accurate but not mathematically exact signed distance field. In practice, this leads to only mild rendering artifacts, and these can be further suppressed by restricting the parameter ranges to regions where the SDF approximation remains most reliable.

For completeness, we explored an exact formulation in which the SDF is computed as the minimum

Figure E.8: ResFit reconstruction sequences for a couch and a dog toy. Each row corresponds to a single round of ResFit. Each initialization phase introduces primitives required for the residual region, and each optimization phase jointly re-optimizes *all* existing primitives. This full-assembly refinement enables ResFit to correct early under-fitting errors, progressively improving fidelity while carefully increasing the number of primitives. This process consequently converges to an accurate yet compact assembly.

distance to analytically partitioned surface patches. However, the tapered–rounded corner regions form canal surfaces whose exact distance queries require solving a quartic equation, making the method significantly more expensive. Moreover, this exact variant does not naturally accommodate onioning or bending. Given these limitations, we adopt the approximate—but efficient and stable—formulation presented in Chapter 7.

E.3 Residual Primitive Fitting (ResFit) Details

High-level overview. ResFit addresses the gap between top–down geometric analysis and bottom–up primitive optimization. Purely optimization-based methods tend to produce entangled assemblies, while analysis-only methods partition shapes without regard to the expressive limits of the primitive family. ResFit bridges these extremes by alternating between residual-based shape analysis and joint primitive optimization: each analysis step extracts regions from the unexplained residual, and each optimization step fits the growing assembly to maximize \mathcal{O} . By allowing these two phases to inform each other, the method produces assemblies that remain both compact and geometrically faithful, correcting over- and under-parameterization as the reconstruction progresses.

Algorithm 7: Residual Primitive Fitting (ResFit): Interleaved Decomposition and Optimization

Input: Target SDF grid T ; max iterations K ; MSD thresholds (v_{\min}, e_{\min}) ; parsimony weight λ
Output: Final primitive assembly P
 $P \leftarrow \emptyset$;
 $R \leftarrow T$;
 $O_{\text{prev}} \leftarrow -\infty$;
for $k \leftarrow 1$ to K do
 $C \leftarrow \text{MSDDECOMPOSE}(R, v_{\min}, e_{\min})$;
 if $C = \emptyset$ then
 return P ;
 $P \leftarrow P \cup \text{INITPRIMITIVES}(C)$;
 $P \leftarrow \text{OPTIMIZEPROGRAM}(P, T, \lambda)$;
 $P \leftarrow \text{PRUNE}(P, T, \lambda)$;
 $O \leftarrow \text{OBJECTIVE}(P, T, \lambda)$;
 if $O \leq O_{\text{prev}}$ then
 return P ;
 $O_{\text{prev}} \leftarrow O$;
 $R \leftarrow \text{RESIDUAL}(P, T)$;
return P ;

Procedure. At iteration k , the current residual volume is decomposed into regions using morphological shape decomposition (MSD). Each region seeds a new primitive, and the resulting primitives are merged with the existing assembly. All primitives are then optimized together to maximize O , with each primitive influenced by its local support. A pruning step then removes redundant primitives whose presence lowers O . Finally, the pruned assembly defines a new residual, and the cycle repeats until the objective saturates or no further valid partitions can be extracted. This interleaved process enables the system to refine earlier primitives as new ones are added, yielding a coherent and compact final assembly.

Figure E.8 visualizes ResFit sequences. The iterative loop progressively improves reconstruction quality while keeping the assembly compact: each round refines the residual, introduces new primitives only where needed, and re-optimizes the entire assembly. Importantly, the sequence does *not* form a hierarchy—primitives introduced early are re-adjusted whenever new primitives are added. This continual re-optimization enables the method to self-correct and converge toward a coherent, parsimonious assembly.

E.4 Decomposition & Initialization

E.4.1 Morphological Shape Decomposition (MSD)

MSD identifies thickness-homogeneous regions by analyzing progressively less-eroded level sets of the target SDF. Let $m = \min(T)$ denote the most negative SDF value, and let $\ell_1 < \ell_2 < \dots < \ell_L$ be a linear sequence from m to 0. For each erosion level ℓ_j , we form the eroded mask $M_{\ell_j} = \{x : R(x) \leq \ell_j\}$ and extract

Algorithm 8: MSDDecompose: Morphological Shape Decomposition

```
Input: Target SDF  $T$ ;  
number of erosion levels  $L$ ; max iterations  $K$ ;  
min eroded size  $S_{\text{erode}}$ ; min part size  $S_{\text{part}}$ .  
Output: Set of MSD parts  $\mathcal{P}$   
 $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;  
 $R \leftarrow T$ ;  
 $m \leftarrow \min(T)$ ;  
 $\{\ell_j\}_{j=1}^L \leftarrow \text{linspace}(m, 0, L)$ ;  
for  $k \leftarrow 1$  to  $K$  do  
   $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;  
  for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $L$  do  
     $M_{\ell_j} \leftarrow \{x : R(x) \leq \ell_j\}$ ;  
     $\{C_i\} \leftarrow \text{connected components of } M_{\ell_j}$ ;  
    // Eroded size condition  
     $\{C_i\} \leftarrow \{C_i : |C_i| \geq S_{\text{erode}}\}$ ;  
    if  $\{C_i\} \neq \emptyset$  then  
      // Dilate parts  
       $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \text{dilations of } \{C_i\} \text{ toward } R$ ;  
      // Part size condition  
       $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \{D_i \in \mathcal{D} : |D_i| \geq S_{\text{part}}\}$ ;  
      if  $\mathcal{D} \neq \emptyset$  then  
         $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \mathcal{P} \cup \mathcal{D}$ ;  
        break  
  if  $\mathcal{D} = \emptyset$  then  
    return  $\mathcal{P}$ ;  
  // Residual update  
   $R \leftarrow \text{SUBTRACTPARTS}(T, \mathcal{P})$ ;  
   $R \leftarrow \text{RENORMALIZEFASTSWEEP}(R)$ ;  
   $R \leftarrow \text{CLEANUPMORPHOPEN}(R)$ ;  
return  $\mathcal{P}$ ;
```

its connected components $\{C_i\}$. Components whose eroded support satisfies $|C_i| \geq S_{\text{erode}}$ are then dilated back toward the zero level of R to obtain morphological–opening candidates D_i ; components meeting the post–dilation size requirement $|D_i| \geq S_{\text{part}}$ are retained as MSD parts. Once such a batch is obtained, these parts are subtracted from the current target, the SDF is redistanced using a fast–sweep [187] to restore SDF consistency, and finally a small morphological opening removes residual artifacts. This procedure, detailed in Algorithm 8, is repeated until no further valid parts can be extracted, yielding a compact set of coherent regions that serve as initialization seeds for primitive fitting.

E.4.2 Initializing SuperFrusta

Once MSD yields volumetric partitions $\{V_i\}$, we initialize one SuperFrustum per partition as part of the INITPRIMITIVES(C) step in Algorithm 7. For each V_i , we first sample points from its interior and compute

a centroid-aligned PCA frame. Each candidate direction (in both orientations) is evaluated as a potential primitive axis.

For a selected axis direction Z , we project all points onto Z to obtain axial coordinates t , and slice the point set along this axis. For each slice, we compute the 2D covariance of the points in the plane orthogonal to Z , whose eigenvalues (σ_u^2, σ_v^2) represent cross-sectional variances along two orthogonal in-plane directions. These statistics yield three scalar measures: (1) *stability* (S_{stab}), capturing how consistent the cross-sections are along Z ; (2) *circularity* (S_{circ}), capturing how similar the in-plane variances are (i.e., how round the section is); and (3) *elongation* (S_{elong}), capturing the normalized length of the region along Z . Given slice-averaged variances σ_u^2, σ_v^2 and axial range t_{\min}, t_{\max} , the cylindricity score for axis Z is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{\text{stab}} &= 1 - \frac{\text{std}(\sigma_u^2, \sigma_v^2)}{\text{mean}(\sigma_u^2, \sigma_v^2) + \varepsilon}, \\
 S_{\text{circ}} &= 1 - \frac{|\sigma_u^2 - \sigma_v^2|}{\sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2 + \varepsilon}, \\
 S_{\text{elong}} &= \frac{t_{\max} - t_{\min}}{\sqrt{\sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2 + \varepsilon}}, \\
 S &= S_{\text{stab}} + S_{\text{circ}} + 0.1 S_{\text{elong}}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{E.11}$$

The axis with the highest score is chosen as the principal axis of the initialized SuperFrustum.

Once the principal axis is selected, the primitive’s translation, rotation, and in-plane size parameters are obtained directly from the centroid and PCA frame of the partition’s point cloud. We additionally estimate the remaining shape parameters using simple statistics computed in the local (u, v, t) coordinate system aligned with the chosen axis. *Roundness* is initialized from the uniformity of in-plane radii across cross-sections, giving higher values when the region is consistently circular. *Taper* is inferred from the relative change in in-plane extent between the lower and upper portions of the volume, capturing whether the shape widens or narrows along the axis. Finally, the *Onion* parameter is estimated from the ratio between inner and outer radii measured in narrow bands around the coordinate axes, providing an initial guess for how much the shape contains an inner “core” structure. Other parameters such as *Bulge*, *Dilation*, and smooth union amount are initialized with a fixed value. We emphasize that all parameters are continuously adjusted using gradient descent during optimization. Implementation details are available in the accompanying code.

E.4.3 Additional Remarks

We highlight two details that clarify how MSD interacts with the fitting loop.

MSD can yield multiple seeds per round. Each MSD iteration extracts all connected components that satisfy the thickness criteria for the current erosion level. Consequently, a single round may produce several volumetric partitions if multiple regions share similar thickness in the residual. Thus running N rounds of MSD does *not* imply obtaining exactly N primitives; the method can expand the seed set adaptively when the residual contains many similarly thick, disconnected regions. This behavior is essential for modeling complex shapes: even with as few as 5–10 rounds, ResFit can introduce dozens of primitives when needed (see the grapes example in Fig. E.1), allowing reconstruction quality to scale with shape complexity without requiring many outer-loop iterations.

Relation to Marching Primitives [104] The initialization strategy used in Marching Primitives (MPS) can be interpreted as a restricted, single-iteration instance of MSD. At each round, MPS selects the deepest erosion level whose eroded region exceeds a minimum volume and directly initializes primitives from that eroded component. In MSD terms, this corresponds to taking a single erosion threshold, extracting the qualifying eroded region, and *not* performing the dilation step that restores the component’s full morphological extent. Because MPS does not decompose the shape into multiple connected components at that erosion level, it behaves more like an optimization-based method driven by residual depth. Nonetheless, its seeding process aligns with a simplified form of MSD.

E.5 Optimization Details

We provide additional clarification on the components of our decomposition-aware optimization strategy.

Two-phase stochastic dropout. Our optimization proceeds in two phases distinguished by the temperature parameter of the Gumbel–Softmax existence distribution. During the first phase, the temperature is held at 1.0, yielding a smooth relaxation that allows primitives to remain active while the assembly adjusts globally. Once progress saturates, we enter a second phase in which the temperature is gradually annealed toward 0.1, sharpening the distribution and forcing the optimizer to make discrete keep-or-delete decisions for each primitive.

Stochastic preconditioning. At the beginning of each phase, we apply stochastic preconditioning [97]. For the first third of the iterations of that phase, we add diminishing Gaussian noise to the input sample points, reducing it linearly to zero by the one-third mark. This strategy improves convergence by smoothing the loss landscape early on and reducing local trapping, particularly in the presence of complex residual geometry.

Periodic surface resampling. To ensure fresh and accurate near-surface supervision, we resample both surface points and surface-adjacent perturbed points every $k = 100$ iterations. Occupancy queries for these points are computed using a BVH-accelerated signed-distance evaluation [163], providing robust ground-truth supervision throughout the optimization trajectory.

In total our loss for reconstruction can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}_R = \mathcal{L}_{\text{vol}} + \mathbf{w} * \mathcal{L}_{\text{surf}} + \mathbf{w} * \mathcal{L}_{\text{adj}}, \quad (\text{E.12})$$

where \mathcal{L}_{vol} is an occupancy loss on points sampled uniformly in \mathbb{R}^3 (typically on a 64^3 grid over $[-1, 1]^3$), $\mathcal{L}_{\text{surf}}$ is a loss on target-mesh surface points that drives the signed distance value to 0, and \mathcal{L}_{adj} is an occupancy loss on points sampled around the mesh surface. The vector \mathbf{w} contains the mesh-curvature-based weights.

Curvature-aware reconstruction weighting. To emphasize thin and high-curvature structures during optimization, each surface sample \mathbf{p} is assigned a curvature weight $w(\mathbf{p})$ derived from the principal curvatures of the target mesh. We first estimate a multiscale curvedness value $C(\mathbf{p})$ by smoothing the raw per-vertex curvedness through heat diffusion at several scales and averaging the results. This produces a stable curvature estimate that suppresses spurious high-frequency spikes. To bound the influence of curvature and avoid extreme weights, we map $C(\mathbf{p})$ through a sigmoid function:

$$w(\mathbf{p}) = 1 + \sigma(\alpha (C(\mathbf{p}) - C_0)),$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the logistic sigmoid, α controls the sharpness of the transition, and C_0 sets the curvature threshold at which weighting begins to increase. Thus $w(\mathbf{p}) \in [1, 2]$, providing a modest but reliable emphasis on geometrically salient regions. The same weighting is used both in the reconstruction loss and in the reconstruction component of the overall objective \mathcal{O} .

Bound-preserving reparameterization. Rather than optimizing primitive parameters directly, we optimize unconstrained variables and map them to valid parameter ranges via a smooth reparameterization. For a parameter with bounds $[p_{\text{low}}, p_{\text{high}}]$, we write

$$p = \tanh(x) R + C,$$

where $R = \frac{1}{2}(p_{\text{high}} - p_{\text{low}})$ and $C = \frac{1}{2}(p_{\text{high}} + p_{\text{low}})$. This guarantees that parameters remain within their prescribed domain throughout optimization and improves numerical stability.

Further details. The accompanying code contains complete implementation details.

E.5.1 Hyperparameters

For all experiments, we use a consistent set of hyperparameters governing optimization, sampling, and temperature scheduling. We optimize with a learning rate of 0.01 and run a maximum of 1600 iterations, with a base budget of 400 iterations and a saturation patience of 100 iterations for both triggering the second (temperature-decay) phase and finishing optimization. The Gumbel–Softmax temperature is fixed at $\tau_{\text{max}} = 1.0$ during Phase 1 and annealed toward $\tau_{\text{min}} = 0.1$ during Phase 2. To stabilize occupancy predictions, we apply a scale-factor schedule increasing smoothly from 10 to 15 over the course of optimization. To keep the losses local, we use loss banding; that is, the loss is evaluated only on points x where $\mathcal{F} < 0.05$.

Stochastic preconditioning uses an initial noise magnitude of $\sqrt{3} \times 0.02$, linearly reduced to zero over the first third of each phase. Every 100 iterations we resample 10^5 surface points and corresponding perturbed surface-adjacent points from the target mesh. Volumetric supervision is provided by uniformly sampling the SDF on a 128^3 grid.

All results reported in Chapter 7 and this appendix use these settings without per-shape or per-category tuning.

E.5.2 Pruning Routine

Our pruning strategy follows the general variant-sampling approach used in [42, 99]. After differentiable optimization converges, we generate candidate program variants and select the one that maximizes the objective \mathcal{O} .

Sampling via stochastic existence variables. Because each primitive has an associated Gumbel–Softmax existence variable, we can sample discrete program variants by adding fresh Gumbel noise to the optimized existence logits and converting the resulting probabilities into one-hot indicators (primitive kept or removed). We draw $K = 100$ such samples, evaluate \mathcal{O} for each resulting assembly, and retain the best-scoring variant. This captures stochastic uncertainty from the optimization phase and can remove primitives that are only marginally supported.

Deterministic leave-one-out pruning. When the existence distributions have already sharpened, stochastic sampling alone is often insufficient. We therefore complement it with a deterministic leave-one-out procedure: for each primitive, we evaluate O on the assembly formed by removing that primitive. If any removal improves O , we accept the corresponding reduced assembly. This process is applied recursively—each accepted deletion triggers a new pass over the remaining primitives—until no further improvement is possible.

Final selection. The highest-scoring assembly identified by either stochastic sampling or recursive leave-one-out pruning is returned as the final pruned program.

E.6 Applications

E.6.1 Inferring Canonical CSG Programs

We describe how the inferred primitive assembly can be adapted to recover programs composed only of canonical solids such as cuboids, cylinders, cones, and spheres. Directly constraining each primitive to one of these forms would disrupt the continuous optimization process that is central to our representation. Instead, we introduce a *Solid Super-Primitive*: a variant of SuperFrustum augmented with four additional logits that define a distribution over the canonical forms. During optimization, the primitive behaves as a probabilistic mixture of these canonical shapes, and gradually collapses to one of them when the temperature is annealed.

Canonical parameterizations. SuperFrustum has 8 parameters:

$$\theta = \{s_x, s_y, s_z, r, d, t, c, o\}.$$

Each canonical solid is expressed as a special case of SuperFrustum by fixing or tying its parameters appropriately:

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{cube}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{p}; (s_x, s_y, s_z, 0, 0, 1, 0, o)),$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{cone}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{p}; (s_x, s_y, s_z, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0)),$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{cyl}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{p}; (s_x, s_y, s_z, 1, 0, 1, 0, o)),$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\text{sphere}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{p}; (0, 0, 0, r, d, 1, 0, 0)).$$

Notably, allowing nonzero onion amounts for cubes and cylinders enables axis-aligned subtractive effects, which commonly arise in mechanical designs.

Solid Super-Primitive. Let $p_{\text{cube}}, p_{\text{sphere}}, p_{\text{cyl}}, p_{\text{cone}}$ be soft selection weights (from a Gumbel-Softmax distribution) over the four canonical solids, and let $\mathbf{s} = (s_x, s_y, s_z)$, r , d , t , c , and o denote the base size, roundness, dilation, tapering, bulge ratio, and onion ratio parameters of SuperFrustum. Instead of evaluating all four SDFs and mixing them in execution space, we construct a single *super-primitive* by blending these parameters in parameter space.

We first form a cylindrical size profile by averaging the in-plane extents,

$$s_{xy} = \frac{1}{2}(s_x + s_y), \quad \mathbf{s}_{\text{cyl}} = (s_{xy}, s_{xy}, s_z),$$

and then define the blended parameters

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}' &= p_{\text{cube}} \mathbf{s} + (p_{\text{cyl}} + p_{\text{cone}}) \mathbf{s}_{\text{cyl}}, \\ r' &= p_{\text{cyl}} + p_{\text{cone}}, \\ d' &= p_{\text{sphere}} d, \\ t' &= p_{\text{cube}} + p_{\text{sphere}} + p_{\text{cyl}}, \\ c' &= 0, \\ o' &= (p_{\text{cube}} + p_{\text{cyl}} + p_{\text{cone}}) o. \end{aligned} \tag{E.13}$$

The Solid Super-Primitive is then evaluated as a single instance of SuperFrustum using these blended parameters. This parameter-space blending approximates a mixture-of-SDF formulation $p_{\text{cube}} \mathcal{F}_{\text{cube}} + p_{\text{sphere}} \mathcal{F}_{\text{sphere}} + p_{\text{cyl}} \mathcal{F}_{\text{cyl}} + p_{\text{cone}} \mathcal{F}_{\text{cone}}$, but avoids the $4\times$ cost of evaluating all four SDFs separately, making canonical-program inference computationally practical.

Temperature coupling and canonical collapse. The soft-selection distribution is governed by a temperature variable that we tie to the per-primitive existence temperature used in our two-phase optimization. During Phase 1, this temperature is held at 1.0, allowing the super-primitive to explore continuous interpolations among the canonical families. During Phase 2, it is annealed toward 0.1, forcing the mixture to collapse to a single canonical solid. Consequently, the final assembly contains only the four target canonical shapes, even though the underlying primitive family is far more expressive.

Limitations and subtractive structures. Because our assembly does not include explicit subtraction, the inferred canonical programs cannot express full CSG trees with complex Boolean structure. As shown in Fig. E.9, parts with true subtractive operations may therefore be approximated but not reproduced exactly. Extending our framework to handle subtractive compositions is an exciting direction for future work.

Figure E.9: Failure cases arising from the lack of explicit subtractive operations in our assembly. Certain shapes—such as parts with cavities, through-holes, or cutouts—require true CSG subtraction to be represented exactly. As illustrated, ResFit approximates these structures using positive volumes only, which can reproduce the outer form but cannot capture internal voids or Boolean detail.

E.6.2 Editable & Deployable Assets

Each inferred primitive serves not only as a geometric element but can also serve as a texturable, editable primitive. To this end, every primitive \mathcal{F}_i is assigned a *single 2D texture map* T_i defined in spherical coordinates. During sphere tracing, when a surface point \mathbf{p} is hit on primitive i , we convert its local coordinates $\mathbf{p}_{\text{local}}$ into spherical angles and perform a texture lookup:

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{local}}\|, & \mathbf{d} &= \frac{\mathbf{p}_{\text{local}}}{r}, \\
 \theta &= \text{atan2}(d_z, d_x), & \phi &= \arccos(d_y), \\
 \mathbf{u} &= \left(\frac{\theta}{2\pi} + \frac{1}{2}, \frac{\phi}{\pi} \right), & \text{albedo} &= T_i(\mathbf{u}).
 \end{aligned}$$

This yields a stable, distortion-minimal parameterization for arbitrary primitive shapes, enabling consistent texture authoring and editing.

Materials under smooth union. While the geometry of two primitives is blended with a smooth-union operator, we do *not* blend their textures. Given two primitives with SDF outputs $f_1(\mathbf{p})$ and $f_2(\mathbf{p})$, the smooth union computes a blended SDF

$$f_{\text{su}}(\mathbf{p}) = \text{SmoothUnion}(f_1, f_2, \beta),$$

but the material is taken from whichever primitive attains the smaller SDF value:

$$\text{material}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{cases} \text{mat}_1(\mathbf{p}) & \text{if } f_1(\mathbf{p}) < f_2(\mathbf{p}), \\ \text{mat}_2(\mathbf{p}) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This choice avoids texture mixing across primitives, producing cleaner, more interpretable textures while retaining smooth geometric transitions.

Together, these mechanisms allow the inferred primitive assemblies to act as lightweight, editable, and visually rich assets that can be deployed directly in real-time sphere-traced renderers. Next, we describe how these per-primitive texture maps are *inferred* by optimization to match a target textured mesh.

Texture inversion for deployable assets. Given a textured input mesh, we first run ResFit to obtain a geometric primitive assembly. We then equip each primitive with a learnable $128 \times 128 \times 3$ texture map. To supervise these textures, we mesh the primitive assembly via dual contouring on its SDF and uniformly sample points on the reconstructed surface. For each sampled point on primitive i , we find the closest point on the original textured mesh and assign its color as the target albedo for that location.

During optimization, the primitive geometry remains fixed; only the per-primitive textures are updated. Each surface point \mathbf{p}_j is evaluated through the textured assembly, producing a predicted color $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_j$ via spherical texture lookup (Sec. E.6.2). Let \mathbf{c}_j denote the ground-truth color transferred from the mesh. Both are converted to Oklab using a fixed mapping $g(\cdot)$, and we minimize an ℓ_2 color loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{tex}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \|g(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_j) - g(\mathbf{c}_j)\|_2^2.$$

To encourage spatial coherence and suppress high-frequency artifacts, we apply a standard total-variation penalty $\text{TV}(T)$ on the texture maps, yielding the final objective

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{mat}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{tex}} + \lambda_{\text{tv}} \text{TV}(T).$$

We optimize the texture parameters using the same stochastic-preconditioning framework as in primitive fitting, but with all geometric parameters frozen. This produces a textured primitive assembly that matches the appearance of the original asset while remaining compact, sphere-traceable, and fully editable.

E.7 Additional Experiments

E.7.1 Primitive Design Ablation

In Chapter 7 we evaluated several alternative primitive families without smooth union. Here we extend this study by repeating the ablation with smooth union enabled for all families (Table E.1). This isolates the geometric expressiveness of each primitive class from the benefits provided by smooth blending. The

	S. Union	IOU	CD	#Prims	Overlap
Cuboid	X	82.81	0.208	24.26	0.333
S Q	X	76.61	0.954	18.79	0.293
S P	X	86.30	0.214	23.93	0.340
S F	X	87.69	0.206	20.55	0.299
Cuboid	✓	84.46	0.128	23.88	0.340
S Q	✓	78.94	0.601	17.96	0.171
S P	✓	89.06	0.152	22.59	0.192
S F	✓	89.97	0.144	24.01	0.214

Table E.1: We compare our full SuperFrustum against Cuboids, Superquadrics (SQ), and variants of the SuperPrimitive (SP). **SP** corresponds to SuperFrustum with tapering and bending disabled. Results are shown both with and without smooth union. Across all settings, SuperFrustum achieves the best reconstruction fidelity, while smooth union consistently improves performance for every primitive family.

MSD Steps	Reconstruction Quality				Program Quality			
	Per Round	IOU (↑)	BiSurfIOU (↑)	CD (↓)	EMD (↓)	#Prims (↓)	Overlap (↓)	IntraPrim (↓)
2	86.59	79.85	0.246	0.072	17.49	0.155	0.248	0.278
5	87.82	81.32	0.244	0.069	19.83	0.175	0.233	0.235
7	90.26	85.87	0.148	0.066	24.09	0.214	0.219	0.200
10	88.77	82.55	0.262	0.066	22.63	0.220	0.220	0.203
20	88.38	86.24	0.185	0.068	21.91	0.216	0.215	0.197
∞	88.46	82.41	0.318	0.073	28.49	0.242	0.211	0.184

Table E.2: Ablation on the number of MSD-seeded primitives per round. Seeding too few primitives (e.g., 2 or 5) yields compact programs but can prematurely terminate the fitting loop, reducing reconstruction quality. Seeding too many (e.g., ∞) improves some reconstruction metrics but substantially worsens program quality due to over-parameterization. Moderate seeding (7 to 20) provides the best balance, achieving high fidelity while maintaining compact, low-overlap assemblies.

results confirm two trends observed earlier: (1) smooth union improves reconstruction fidelity and reduces overlap across *all* primitive families, and (2) even under this more favorable setting, SuperFrustum remains the strongest representation, achieving the highest reconstruction accuracy with competitive parsimony and low overlap.

E.7.2 ResFit Ablation

We now perform ablations to verify design decisions. We evaluate the variations in this subsection on a subset of 250 shapes from the Toys4K dataset. As discussed in Chapter 7, several design choices ensure that the iterative loop in ResFit can correct both over-parameterization, that is, having more primitives than required, and under-parameterization, that is, having fewer primitives than required.

Table E.3 isolates the impact of these design choices in ResFit. To avoid *underparameterization*, two components are essential. First, *local optimization* ensures that newly inserted primitives focus on the region that seeded them, leaving clean, fillable residuals for subsequent iterations. Removing this (“No re-opt”)

	IOU	#P	Overlap	IntraPrim	InterPrim
No re-opt	84.18	23.66	0.220	0.231	0.207
Global Opt	87.82	19.16	0.165	0.229	0.222
No Prune	91.13	29.02	0.213	0.211	0.182
Ours	89.92	23.98	0.213	0.220	0.201

Table E.3: Ablation of the key components of ResFit. Local optimization and global re-optimization are both crucial for preventing underparameterization and achieving strong reconstruction. Conversely, removing decomposition-aware pruning (“No prune”) increases IoU but at the cost of substantially more primitives, indicating overparameterization. Our full method provides the best balance of accuracy and parsimony.

substantially lowers reconstruction due to primitives competing for the same geometry. Second, *global re-optimization* refines all existing primitives at every iteration instead of freezing earlier ones; omitting this step (“No freeze”, shown as “Global Opt” versus the baseline) limits the system’s ability to correct early mistakes and reduces overall fidelity.

To avoid *overparameterization*, we use a decomposition-aware objective that balances reconstruction with redundancy penalties. If we maximize reconstruction alone (“No prune”), the system indeed attains the highest IoU, but only by introducing nearly 30% more primitives—yielding assemblies that are far less compact. Our full method strikes the intended middle ground: high reconstruction quality while maintaining strong parsimony.

Effect of the number of MSD-seeded primitives per round. A key mechanism preventing overparameterization in ResFit is that each MSD round contributes only a small number of new primitives rather than instantiating all detected volumetric parts at once. Table E.2 evaluates this design by varying the number of primitives seeded per round. The results reveal a clear trade-off: seeding too *few* primitives (e.g., MSD-2 or MSD-5) produces more compact programs but can prematurely halt the fitting loop, leading to underfitting and lower reconstruction quality. Conversely, seeding too *many* primitives (e.g., MSD-40) improves reconstruction in some cases but yields substantially worse program quality—especially larger primitive counts and higher overlap—indicating over-parameterization. Moderate seeding levels (MSD-7 to MSD-20) strike the best balance, achieving strong reconstruction while maintaining compact and well-behaved assemblies.

MSD vs. CoACD Initialization. We compare our morphological shape decomposition (MSD) seeding strategy with CoACD—a widely used convex decomposition method—under matched budgets of decomposition steps (Table E.4). Across all settings, both approaches yield broadly similar reconstruction fidelity; however, MSD consistently produces *significantly more parsimonious* assemblies. At 5, 10, and 20 decomposi-

	N Steps	IOU	CD	#Prims	Overlap
MSD	5	87.55	0.249	19.67	0.174
CoACD	5	88.47	0.307	21.32	0.224
MSD	10	88.45	0.260	22.35	0.218
CoACD	10	88.24	0.243	25.11	0.229
MSD	20	89.37	0.182	21.94	0.215
CoACD	20	89.95	0.216	25.14	0.231
MSD	∞	88.46	0.318	28.49	0.242
CoACD	∞	89.61	0.242	30.83	0.273

Table E.4: Comparison of MSD and CoACD as decomposition-based initializers under matched step counts. Both methods achieve similar reconstruction accuracy, but MSD consistently produces more compact assemblies with fewer primitives and lower overlap. This supports MSD as a more structurally appropriate prior for primitive-based reconstruction.

Method	Reconstruction Quality				Program Quality			
	IOU (\uparrow)	BiSurfIOU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	EMD (\downarrow)	#Prims (\downarrow)	Overlap (\downarrow)	IntraPrim (\downarrow)	InterPrim (\uparrow)
- \mathcal{L}_Q	89.63	85.00	0.145	0.066	20.45	0.248	0.226	0.208
- \mathcal{L}_P	91.13	87.51	0.143	0.064	29.05	0.213	0.211	0.182
- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{surf}}$	83.03	76.07	0.212	0.073	23.640	0.161	0.232	0.210
$w(p) = 1$	87.81	81.34	0.295	0.068	20.01	0.189	0.228	0.222
+ $\mathcal{L}_{\text{Tversky}}$	87.97	81.93	0.322	0.067	23.48	0.221	0.221	0.196
- Prune	89.73	85.16	0.151	0.066	22.74	0.194	0.223	0.219
Ours	89.92	85.66	0.154	0.067	23.67	0.208	0.221	0.202

Table E.5: Ablation of our loss components. Removing program-length or program-quality losses dramatically alters the parsimony and coherence of the inferred assemblies (top block). Ablations of the reconstruction losses (middle block) show the importance of surface supervision, curvature weighting, and balanced inner/outer penalties. Removing hard pruning (bottom block) causes early saturation and weaker reconstructions. Overall, the full loss design achieves the best balance between fidelity and program quality.

tion steps, MSD achieves comparable or superior Chamfer distance and markedly lower overlap while using 10–20% fewer primitives. These results highlight that MSD is a better structural prior for primitive-based reconstruction: it extracts coherent, thickness-homogeneous regions that align naturally with our primitives, whereas CoACD tends to over-fragment the shape. Overall, MSD offers a more compact, semantically aligned initialization without sacrificing reconstruction accuracy.

E.7.3 Optimization Loss Ablation

Losses on Program Length and Program Quality. We first ablate the two decomposition-aware terms that discourage over-parameterization: the program-length loss \mathcal{L}_P and the primitive-quality loss \mathcal{L}_Q . Removing \mathcal{L}_P yields the highest reconstruction accuracy in the table, but does so by inflating the primitive count by nearly 30%, confirming that this term is essential for maintaining parsimony. Conversely, removing \mathcal{L}_Q produces assemblies with significantly higher primitive overlap and weaker geometric coherence, even

	IOU	#P	Overlap	IntraPrim	InterPrim
No	89.49	28.56	0.294	0.219	0.187
Low	89.36	28.09	0.278	0.219	0.194
Med	89.93	24.00	0.213	0.219	0.201
High	83.97	16.80	0.094	0.240	0.258

Table E.6: Ablation of jointly scaling the program-length and program-quality loss weights. Excessively small weights reduce program quality, while excessively large weights severely hurt reconstruction by over-regularizing the assembly. The medium setting (our default) provides the best balance between fidelity and structural compactness.

Method	Reconstruction Quality				Program Quality			
	IOU (\uparrow)	BiSurfIOU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	EMD (\downarrow)	#Prims (\downarrow)	Overlap (\downarrow)	IntraPrim (\downarrow)	InterPrim (\uparrow)
Run 1	88.10	81.70	0.243	0.067	21.18	0.193	0.227	0.215
Run 2	88.03	81.67	0.248	0.067	20.98	0.186	0.227	0.223
Run 3	87.91	81.62	0.250	0.068	20.98	0.195	0.227	0.217
Avg	88.01	81.66	0.247	0.067	21.05	0.191	0.227	0.218
Std	0.078	0.032	0.003	0.000	0.094	0.004	0.0	0.003

Table E.7: Statistical significance of evaluation metrics. We report reconstruction and program-quality scores across three independent runs, along with their mean and standard deviation. The extremely small variance across all metrics confirms that the quantitative results presented in Chapter 7 are statistically reliable and not sensitive to run-to-run randomness.

though the primitive count remains low. Together, these losses jointly regulate the structure of the inferred program, trading a small amount of reconstruction fidelity for a substantially cleaner and more compact assembly.

Losses Governing Reconstruction. We next ablate components of the reconstruction loss. Eliminating the surface-point loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{surf}}$ leads to a sharp drop in both IOU and BiSurfIOU, showing that explicit surface supervision is critical for convergence. Replacing curvature-aware sample weights $w(p)$ with a constant $w(p) = 1$ also hurts performance—especially surface IOU—demonstrating that curvature weighting effectively guides optimization toward challenging geometric regions. We additionally evaluate a Tversky-style outer-vs.-inner reweighting (heavier penalties for false positives), similar to LightSQ, but find that it degrades performance: overly emphasizing exterior errors can prematurely shrink primitives before they have adapted to their local neighborhoods.

Pruning. Finally, we ablate the hard-pruning step used after optimization. Removing pruning does not degrade parsimony in the way one might expect; instead, it leads to *lower* reconstruction accuracy with slightly fewer primitives. This occurs because without pruning the objective saturates sooner, causing ResFit to terminate earlier and reducing the number of refinement rounds. Thus, pruning acts as a stabilizer that

Method	Reconstruction Quality			Program Quality				Timing
	IOU (\uparrow)	BiSurfIOU (\uparrow)	CD (\downarrow)	#Prims (\downarrow)	Overlap (\downarrow)	IntraPrim (\downarrow)	InterPrim (\uparrow)	
MPS 64	71.46	51.68	2.207	9.338	0.472	0.355	0.332	7.9
MPS 128	80.60	72.75	1.147	30.62	0.588	0.245	0.201	37.9
MPS 256	86.30	79.93	0.740	85.76	0.738	0.196	0.103	194.6
Ours 1	81.13	73.83	0.798	9.354	0.113	0.288	0.326	84.8
Ours 2	86.55	80.62	0.231	15.54	0.145	0.241	0.248	184.1
Ours 3	88.28	83.08	0.167	19.19	0.168	0.230	0.223	290.6
Ours 5	89.67	85.25	0.149	23.01	0.203	0.222	0.204	551.2
Ours 10	89.91	85.68	0.147	23.93	0.213	0.220	0.201	692.6

Table E.8: Comparison with Marching Primitives (MPS) across voxel resolutions (64, 128, 256). ResFit achieves a substantially better reconstruction–parsimony tradeoff: even with only two refinement iterations, our method attains reconstruction quality comparable to MPS–256 while requiring 5–6 \times fewer primitives and similar runtime. With additional iterations, ResFit surpasses all MPS variants across all reconstruction metrics while maintaining compact assemblies.

prolongs meaningful improvement and contributes to the overall reconstruction–quality–vs.–parsimony balance achieved by our full method.

Joint Scaling of Program–Length and Program–Quality Losses. We jointly vary the loss weights for program length (λ_{count}) and program quality (λ_{qual}), where λ_{qual} controls both the overlap and unoverlap terms. In Chapter 7 we report $\lambda_{\text{count}} = 10^{-3}$ and $\lambda_{\text{qual}} = 10^{-2}$; the actual coefficients used during optimization are twice these values due to symmetric penalties applied to inside–outside consistency. Here, we sweep four regimes: *No* ($\lambda_{\text{count}} = \lambda_{\text{qual}} = 0$), *Low*, *Med* (our default), and *High*, corresponding to weight configurations ranging from 0 up to 2×10^{-2} and 2×10^{-1} for λ_{count} and λ_{qual} , respectively. This experiment evaluates how the relative strength of these two regularizers shapes the reconstruction–parsimony tradeoff.

Increasing these weights too aggressively (*High*) yields extremely compact assemblies with very low overlap, but at the cost of a large drop in reconstruction quality. At the opposite extreme, eliminating both terms (*No*) surprisingly does not improve reconstruction, while significantly degrading program quality—indicating that a moderate amount of structure regularization is beneficial for fitting. Our default *Med* setting achieves the best overall balance: strong reconstruction accuracy, reasonable primitive counts, and clean low–overlap assemblies.

E.7.4 Additional Comparisons

Statistical significance of reported metrics. Because our fitting procedure includes stochastic components—sampling of Gumbel variables, point–resampling, and stochastic preconditioning—it is important to verify that the evaluation metrics reported in Chapter 7 are statistically meaningful rather than artifacts of a single run. To assess this, we execute the full pipeline three times on the same inputs and report the per-run

Figure E.10: Comparison of our default fitting schedule (*Ours*) against the accelerated configuration (*Cheap*) across ResFit iterations. Left: IOU steadily improves under both settings, with our configuration achieving higher accuracy. Middle: Primitive count grows more aggressively under the full schedule, supporting higher reconstruction fidelity. Right: The accelerated regime reduces runtime substantially while maintaining competitive quality.

scores together with their mean and standard deviation (Table E.7). To lower the computational cost of this experiment, we conduct volumetric point sampling at 64^3 resolution rather than the 128^3 resolution used for other experiments; consequently, all three runs have slightly lower reconstruction accuracy. Across all reconstruction metrics (IoU, BiSurfIoU, CD, EMD) and program-quality measures (#Prims, Overlap, IntraPrim, InterPrim), the variance is extremely small, indicating that the differences we observe across methods and ablations in Chapter 7 are well above the noise floor. Thus, the metrics used throughout our comparisons can be interpreted as statistically stable and representative of the method’s true performance.

Comparison to Marching Primitives Across Resolutions. Table E.8 compares our method to Marching Primitives (MPS) evaluated at three voxel resolutions (64, 128, 256). As the MPS resolution increases, reconstruction improves but at the cost of substantially more primitives and rapidly growing runtime. In contrast, our ResFit iterations trace out a significantly better Pareto frontier: for a comparable number of primitives, our reconstructions exhibit markedly higher IOU, lower Chamfer distance, and stronger surface consistency. Notably, our 2-iteration setting (*Ours 2*) nearly matches or exceeds the reconstruction quality of MPS at 256 resolution while using 5–6× fewer primitives and similar runtime. Our full 10-iteration model further pushes reconstruction quality well beyond MPS at any tested resolution. This highlights the efficiency and effectiveness of decomposition-aware fitting: high fidelity does not require ever-increasing voxel grids, but instead a sequence of informed primitive refinements.

Cheaper optimization regime. We also investigate whether the fitting procedure can be accelerated by relaxing several optimization hyperparameters. Specifically, we reduce the number of optimization iterations (from 400 to 250), lower the maximum iteration cap (from 1600 to 1200), increase the learning rate (from 0.01 to 0.015), and perform volumetric sampling at 32^3 resolution instead of 64^3 . As shown in Table E.9, these modifications reduce runtime by more than 1.6× while preserving most of the reconstruction fidelity and

Method	Reconstruction Quality			Program Quality				Timing (↓)
	IOU (↑)	BiSurfIOU (↑)	CD (↓)	#Prims (↓)	Overlap (↓)	IntraPrim (↓)	InterPrim (↑)	
Cheap	89.05	84.14	0.160	19.71	0.222	0.227	0.221	417.2
Ours	90.02	85.74	0.146	23.87	0.214	0.220	0.199	692.6

Table E.9: Effect of a cheaper optimization configuration. Reducing the number of iterations, increasing the learning rate, and using lower-resolution volumetric sampling significantly decreases runtime (from 692 s to 417 s) while maintaining comparable reconstruction and program-quality metrics. This shows that meaningful speed–accuracy trade-offs are achievable without major degradation in assembly quality.

Figure E.11: Reconstruction IOU versus total parameter count for Primitive Anything (PA), Marching Primitives (MPS), and our method. Despite using a more complex primitive, our approach yields the best accuracy for a given parameter budget, resetting the accuracy–parsimony Pareto frontier.

structural quality of the inferred assemblies. Although the “Cheap” configuration yields slightly weaker performance than the full model, the gap remains small across all metrics, indicating that substantially faster fitting is possible with modest trade-offs. Exploring more principled acceleration strategies—such as adaptive schedules, coarse-to-fine decomposition, or learned initialization—presents a promising direction for future work.

To better understand how the accelerated configuration behaves over the course of the ResFit loop, Fig. E.10 plots the evolution of IOU, primitive count, and runtime across iterations. Both schedules follow the same qualitative trajectory, but the cheaper regime progresses more quickly and saturates earlier, yielding slightly lower reconstruction accuracy and fewer primitives. Importantly, ResFit does not force a fixed number of refinement rounds: the loop continues only while the objective improves, and we merely raise the *maximum* iteration limit rather than enforcing all iterations. This highlights the trade-off—our full schedule achieves higher accuracy, while the accelerated variant offers a controlled speed–quality compromise for use cases where runtime matters.

Figure E.12: **Common Failure Cases** (a) Shell-like or hollow shapes (e.g., helmets, shoes) cannot be represented without explicit negative operations, leading to many primitives. (b) Multi-turn curved structures (e.g., LED filaments) fragment due to the single-arc primitive design. (c) Some complex shapes (e.g., chairs) require overlapping primitives when local geometry exceeds the primitive’s expressiveness. (d) Extremely thin curved surfaces yield weak gradients and underfit geometry. (e) Irregular thickness can cause MSD to decompose hollow containers into thin slats, rather than a hollow cylinder. (f) In rare cases, primitives spill across semantic boundaries when needed to maintain fidelity.

Accuracy–Parameter Tradeoff. In Chapter 7 we compare reconstruction accuracy against primitive count, but different primitive families vary substantially in the number of parameters they require: Marching Primitives (MPS) uses superquadrics with 5 parameters each, PA uses 2–3 parameters depending on type, and our SuperFrustum uses 8. To provide a fair cross-method comparison, Fig. E.11 plots IOU against the *total parameter count* of each inferred program. Even here, our method establishes a new Pareto frontier: for any given parameter budget, SuperFrustum assemblies achieve higher fidelity than both MPS and PA, highlighting that our primitive is not only expressive but also parameter-efficient.

E.8 Failure Cases

While ResFit performs reliably across a broad range of shapes, we observe several characteristic failure modes (Fig. E.12).

(a) Non-uniform hollow or shell-like structures. Our primitive family cannot represent arbitrary hollow surfaces. Shapes such as helmets, hats, and shoes contain thin shells enclosing large voids; without

explicit negative-space operations, ResFit approximates these with many primitives, producing assemblies that are geometrically valid but semantically unsatisfying. Richer support for subtractive geometry would address many of these cases, though deformable materials (e.g., cloth) may remain difficult regardless.

(b) Multi-arc or winding structures. Because each primitive contains only a single bending arc, it cannot capture long, continuously curved trajectories. In shapes such as LED filament spirals, the desired geometry has a multi-turn curve, but MSD splits it into multiple short thickness-consistent segments; the optimizer faithfully fits each, yielding many fragmented primitives. A multi-arc or curve-swept primitive family would resolve this limitation.

(c) Overlapping assemblies in complex but common categories. Even in standard categories such as chairs, we occasionally observe assemblies that achieve reasonable reconstruction but require a large number of overlapping primitives. This arises when local curvature cannot be matched well by the current primitive’s shape space, suggesting the need for a more expressive base primitive.

(d) Extremely flat curved surfaces. When a part is both highly curved and extremely thin, the gradients associated with roundness, scale, or taper parameters become very small, leading to weak updates. As a result, thin bent panels such as the wings of the dragon may be improperly fit. Sampling points directly from a dual-contoured reconstruction of the target mesh would provide higher-quality supervision in such cases.

(e) Irregular thickness in hollow containers. We observe that for some hollow shapes, the ground truth contains inconsistent wall thickness. In such cases, MSD decomposes the shape into thin slats instead of recovering a coherent onioned cylinder. This occurs because thickness irregularity perturbs the morphological openings. Increasing MSD’s robustness to noisy or highly variable thickness fields is an important future improvement.

(f) Semantic spillover across part boundaries. In a few cases, achieving high fidelity requires primitives whose spatial support crosses semantic boundaries—for example, a primitive intended for the cheek region may extend into the eye area. These issues could be mitigated by incorporating segmentation cues from multi-view renderings during optimization, nudging primitives to remain consistent with part structure.

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